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**TEACHERS' LANGUAGE IDEOLOGIES
AND EARLY READING INSTRUCTION PRACTICES
IN PHILIPPINE MULTILINGUAL CLASSROOMS**

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02 September 2023

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Acceptance Page

This paper prepared by **JACKSON G. ORLANDA** with the title: “**Teachers’ Language Ideologies and Early Reading Instruction Practices in Philippine Multilingual Classrooms**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Education, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the Master of Arts in Language and Literacy Education.

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Maraming salamat, UP. Hanggang sa muli.

-JACKSON G. ORLANDA

Dedication

To my *mamang*, my first reading teacher

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Abstract

Philippine linguistic diversity is recognized in the Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) policy. MTB-MLE is one of the salient features of the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013. The mother tongue is the primary mode of instruction (MOI) from kindergarten to the third grade of elementary education. From first to third grade, Mother Tongue, Filipino (the national language), and English are taught as separate subjects. Filipino and English, the country's official languages, are gradually introduced as MOI from fourth to sixth grade. Beginning reading is first taught in the mother tongue. Through a solid foundation in the mother tongue, stronger literacy abilities are developed, which are expected to transfer across languages. However, recent studies have shown that only one-third of schools are implementing MTB-MLE, due to factors like resistance in using the mother tongue for academic purposes and opposition thrown against it because of misconceptions favoring the dominant official languages. Against this backdrop, the present study aimed to answer the following questions: (1) What are the teachers' language ideologies on the use of the local language alongside Filipino and English as the language of instruction in early reading classes?; (2) What are the teachers' early reading instruction practices in the local language, Filipino, and English?; and (3) Are the teachers' language ideologies reflected in their use of language/s in early reading instruction?

This qualitative study involved 13 public school early grades teachers in a linguistically diverse province in Northern Philippines where the local languages Bolinao, Iloko, and Pangasinan are used in MTB-MLE. Semi-structured interviews were first conducted, recorded, and transcribed. The transcriptions were manually coded first, then uploaded to Atlas.ti, a qualitative data analysis software, to further review and finalize the codes. The research themes were extracted from these codes.

Data triangulation was conducted through classroom observations of early reading classes, review of relevant documents, and focus group discussions.

The extracted themes from the findings revealed four teachers' hegemonic language ideologies: (1) English as a highly valued language; (2) Filipino as preferred language; (3) challenges in MTB-MLE implementation; and (4) use of translations. The teacher participants believed that English and Filipino held a dominant role in early reading instruction due to their perceived benefits (e.g., social, academic, and economic). Teachers' adherence to the concept of standardized languages posed challenges to the diversity and variations found in languages, which they perceived as confusing and complex. Teachers' resistance towards MTB-MLE, especially concerning the use of the mother tongue, could be attributed to their belief that the inclusion of the mother tongue in early reading instruction was a hindrance to learning the official languages. Language hierarchy also marginalized the local languages. Utilizing translations as a component of translanguaging served as a bridge between the languages used in early reading instruction; however, this mostly benefitted a dominant language. On the other hand, one theme showed teachers' counter-hegemonic language ideology: language preservation and fostering identity. The use of the mother tongue was believed to foster and safeguard the community language and history. In teachers' early reading instruction practices in the local language, Filipino, and English, five themes emerged: (1) big six of reading with a focus on phonics instruction; (2) learners' experiences; (3) medium of instruction and/or learning area; (4) translanguaging; and (5) learning environment and resources. The use of phonics-based instruction was utilized as the starting point in beginning reading. The utilization of learners' experiences in early reading instruction promoted engagement and comprehension. Different language patterns involving the three

languages used in early reading instruction were strategically and purposefully used by the teachers. Translanguaging was also used in teaching learners to read in multiple languages. The availability and unavailability of print-rich classrooms and the use of technology defined and contributed to learning environment and resources. The findings also showed how teachers' language ideologies were reflected in their use of language/s in early reading instruction. All the teachers' language ideologies were clearly manifested in the teachers' use of language/s in early reading instruction.

If MTB-MLE is to be implemented successfully in the wake of questions on its significance and legitimacy, teachers' language ideologies which shape how early reading is taught in a multilingual setting should not only be revisited but also thoroughly examined. If local languages continue to be marginalized in early reading instruction, building and strengthening the learners' reading skills in other languages would be affected, and language discrimination will persist, instead of the policy fostering cultural identity and heritage among learners.

Keywords: language ideologies, early reading instruction, translanguaging, teaching practices, language policy

Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

The Philippines, with 183 living languages, is one of the most linguistically and culturally diverse countries in the world (Koyfman, 2019). This is not an impossibility because the Philippines is composed of 7,641 islands, making it an archipelago (Lasco, 2017). Hence, the language used in economic activities, commerce, and education is always central to language-in-education policy decision-making process and the issues surrounding it (Gonzales, 1998).

In 2009, the Philippine Department of Education through Order No. 74 institutionalized the “Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education” (MTB-MLE) policy in formal basic education for children to start their formal education in the language they know best (Philippines Department of Education [DepEd], 2009). This program has four goals: improve learners’ cultural development, language development, cognitive development, and academic development (DepEd, 2012). From just merely promoting the utilization of learners’ home language as the medium of instruction (MOI), materials and assessments were further required to be in the learners’ first language (L1) when President Benigno S. Aquino III signed into law the “Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013” or Republic Act 10533. RA 10533 stipulates the use of the mother tongue as the primary MOI from kindergarten up to the third grade of elementary education. Before the use of the local languages in Philippine elementary classrooms was enacted, the bilingual education policy which promoted English and the Tagalog-based Filipino elevated the Filipino language as a symbol of unity and national identity (DepEd, 1987). According to the Philippine Constitution (1987) Article XIV Section 7, Filipino and English serve as the official languages. The former is used

as the lingua franca and the latter as the national working language (Metila et al., 2016). Parba (2018) argued that placing Filipino and English as official languages led to the construction, circulation, and reproduction of language ideologies, and it also resulted in the displacement of the local languages.

The use of the learners' mother tongue in schools continues to receive criticisms and oppositions due to misconceptions (Parba, 2018). Tupas (2015) postulated that "MTB-MLE continues to face structural and ideological challenges to its successful implementation" (p. 113) such as the hegemonic belief that the use of learners' L1 in instruction dumbs down learners and teachers alike (Tupas, 2017). Structures of linguistic imperialism, globalization's English-only policy, unequal structures of learning English, and colonially induced hatred towards the mother tongues are some of the challenges facing multilingualism in the Philippines (Tupas, 2015). Tupas (2015) further argued that teacher education programs must also revolve around teacher ideology and not only on teaching methodology.

Numerous research studies have been done about MTB-MLE in the Philippines, proving the support available, showing its importance, and outlining its benefits (see, e.g., Balacano, 2020; Fillmore, 2014; Medilo, Jr., 2016). However, these studies are also a testament of the need to evaluate the language-in-education policy in line with its implementation and guided by the challenges faced by those at the grassroots level.

In August of 2023, DepEd launched the new MATATAG¹ curriculum which aims to decongest the current curriculum. The number of subjects in Grades 1 and 2 that are being taught has been reduced from seven to five. Mother Tongue was also

¹ MATATAG is DepEd's newest battle cry, which means "MAke the curriculum relevant to produce competent and job-ready, active, and responsible citizens; TAke steps to accelerate delivery of basic education facilities and services; TAke good care of learners by promoting learner well-being, inclusive education, and a positive learning environment; and Give support to teachers to teach better" (DepEd, 2023a)

removed as a subject, but not as medium of instruction. MATATAG will be implemented in phases, starting in school year 2024-2025; by school year 2027-2028, it will have been fully implemented (DepEd, 2023b). However, MTB-MLE is one of the provisions of RA 10533. The removal of the Mother Tongue subject seems to run counter to what is specified in the standards and principles in the process of formulating an improved foundational educational curriculum: “The curriculum shall adhere to the principles and framework of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE)” (Section 5, para. 9).

The language used in the teaching and learning process is truly an important factor in literacy and/or reading instruction, especially in associating verbal and written symbols with the spoken language (Chang et al., 2020). Even UNESCO (2018) highlighted the importance of the language of instruction in advocating for effective and practical teaching and learning. UNESCO (2018) reported that 40 percent of the children around the world have no educational access in a language they speak and understand. Language matters for the reading improvement and formal literacy development of learners (Pflepsen, 2019), so it is imperative to consider contextual factors and other important areas of the educational system in advocating for and implementing a language to be used in classrooms. When it comes to bilingualism and/or multilingualism, Schiefner (n.d.) asserted the possibility and the pride that come with learning how to read and write in different languages.

However, there is a lack of research studies on teachers’ language ideologies and their early reading instruction practices in a multilingual setting, particularly in the Philippines. The teachers’ role in reading instruction, especially their use of language/s in a multilingual classroom, is crucial to and should not be undermined in the success of the learners when it comes to reading. The language used in reading also plays an

important role in reading instruction. One of the goals of this study, then, was to fill that literature gap and find out the teachers' prevailing language ideologies regarding the use of the local language alongside English and Filipino in multilingual classrooms. It also investigated teachers' early reading instruction practices, and how the teachers' use of language/s in early reading instruction was being influenced by their language ideologies.

Research Questions

This study aimed to investigate primary grades teachers' language ideologies and early reading instruction practices in multilingual classrooms. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the teachers' language ideologies on the use of the local language alongside Filipino and English as the language of instruction in early reading classes?
2. What are the teachers' early reading instruction practices in the local language, Filipino, and English?
3. Are the teachers' language ideologies reflected in their use of language/s in early reading instruction?

Significance of the Study

This study was conducted to revisit RA 10533, especially its provision on MTB-MLE language-in-education policy. The results of this study will help administrators and other stakeholders of the educational system in making informed decisions and/or policy modifications regarding the use of the local language in a multilingual education setting, taking into consideration not only the teachers' language ideologies and early reading instruction practices but also the implementation of the new MATATAG

curriculum which highlights the removal of the Mother Tongue subject. This will also support the development and implementation of MTB-MLE as a coherent and relevant language-in-education policy for multilingual classrooms.

This study will also provide fresh perspectives on how the local language alongside other languages is used in multilingual classrooms. Likewise, this will determine the trends in reading instruction, especially in terms of teachers' use of language/s in lower elementary multilingual classrooms. This study will also support Tupas's (2015) proposition that there is a need to recalibrate the training and education of preservice teachers to probe into teacher ideology and not only focus on teaching methodology.

Since teachers' language ideologies and teachers' current practices in teaching beginning reading are least researched topics, this study will add to the very few related studies that have been conducted in the country. Moreover, this study is the first to investigate whether the teachers' language ideologies are reflected in their use of language/s in early reading instruction in Philippine multilingual classrooms.

Lastly, this study could serve as a springboard for further research on the influence of teachers' language ideologies on their use of language/s in early reading instruction.

Scope and Delimitations

This qualitative descriptive study focused on the hegemonic and counter-hegemonic language ideologies and early reading instruction practices of 13 lower elementary teachers (five Grade 1 teachers, four Grade 2 teachers, and four Grade 3 teachers) who teach using the local language alongside Filipino and English in a multilingual classroom. Although the research context was located only in one province in the Philippines, three local languages – Iloko, Pangasinan, and Bolinao – that are

being used in multilingual classrooms in line with MTB-MLE were featured in this study. The participants came from different public schools in the province of Pangasinan, to represent each of the three local languages included in this study. They were interviewed, their reading classes were directly observed/video recorded during the first three months of the school year (covering 30% of the total number of school days), and they participated in focus group discussions (FGDs). Relevant documents on teachers' early reading instruction practices (e.g., lesson plans, instructional materials) were also reviewed and analyzed. Factors like highest educational attainment, years in service, and teaching position of the teacher-participants may have influenced the results of this study, but these were not the focus of the research.

Chapter II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The studies and works included in this review are divided into two sections: teachers' language ideologies and early reading instruction.

The first section talks about teachers' language ideologies. Because reading is a language-based process, teachers' language ideologies can influence reading instruction (and consequently, learners' reading acquisition and development). In this section, different theoretical models of reading that show teachers' language ideologies as a factor or consideration in reading pedagogy are discussed. Furthermore, concepts on how languages are viewed and empirical studies about teachers' language ideologies are also discussed.

The second section talks about early reading instruction. This includes teaching practices in early reading instruction in general and in multilingual contexts. Empirical studies on teachers' early reading instruction practices are also included. Teachers' use of language/s in class, translanguaging, and the Philippine MTB-MLE implementation and the national languages curricula are also discussed.

Teachers' Language Ideologies

Language works its way in various facets of society. It is now considered more than a social practice; it has become central to issues concerning economy, politics, and national policies (Cavanaugh, 2019). Sociolinguistics focuses on how language variations are viewed and how languages are seen in real social contexts. It is also linked to discovering the comparative differences of various languages for educational planning, decision making, and studying language attitudes, values, and beliefs (Shuy, 1974). In a critical sociolinguistic perspective, language teaching – including reading

instruction – is considered an ideological and social practice and entrenched in and fashioned by society and history (Daugaard, 2020). To understand what language and reading teachers think, know, believe, and do, teacher cognition explains the mental constructs underlying the teacher's actions in the teaching-learning process (Borg, 2003).

In early reading instruction where language/s play/s an important role, theory and practice are inseparable and enjoy a cyclical relationship (Ocampo, 1997). Because reading is an active process (Sheridan, 1981), there are various models that discuss the nature of processes that occur during this activity, such as the traditional (bottom-up), cognitive (top-down), interactive, and transactional models of reading. In the traditional model of reading, teachers lead the learners in the decoding and comprehending of texts (Phajane, 2014). The traditional model consists of bottom-up models such as Gough's (1972), where learning to read starts from sounding out letters before forming them into words and sentences (Hamilton, 2017). The cognitive theories of reading are the top-down models of reading such as Goodman's (1976) where the whole text is approached first before individual letters, in contrast to the traditional models (Hamilton, 2017). Rumelhart (1977) formed the interactive reading process model, a hybrid of the top-down and bottom-up models, where reading demonstrates the significance of tapping on one's prior knowledge and the simultaneous interaction of information from both internal and external sources. The transactional model of Rosenblatt (1969) features the continuous transaction of the reader and the text, and teachers must demonstrate to the readers how to use what they read and how to understand what they read as they make meanings (Raudenbush, n.d.).

Some reading models recognize how teachers' beliefs play a fundamental role in shaping how reading is taught and learned in the classroom. Teachers' knowledge and beliefs are an important consideration in these models. In the sociolinguistic perspective in reading, the learner, the reading material, and the teacher are the fundamental categories of language learning (Dillingofski, 1979). On the other hand, in the sociocognitive model of meaning-construction, the learner, the reading teacher, the text, and the learning environment are the main factors that are considered in interactive meaning-making (Ruddell et al., 2019). In this model, the reader's and teacher's prior beliefs and knowledge in both affective (e.g., motivation) and cognitive conditions (e.g., knowledge and strategies) are underscored while the meaning-construction process transpires in the text and classroom context as the learning environment. These affective and cognitive conditions are highly dependent on each other. Reading cultivates in readers several outcomes involving text representation. The teacher is expected to have the necessary skills and knowledge (including content) in teaching reading effectively. The teacher's beliefs also affect their instructional decision-making process. Sociocultural meanings and classroom discourses are included in the text and classroom context. Figure 1 below encapsulates the model.

Figure 1

Reading as a Meaning-Construction Process: The Reader, the Text, and the Teacher (Ruddell et al., 2019)

The earlier version (Ruddell & Unrau, 2013) of the sociocognitive model of meaning-construction (Ruddell et al., 2019) is based on several fundamental assumptions such as:

Language and reading performance are directly related to the reader's sociocultural environment... Readers construct meanings not only of printed manuscripts but also of events, speech, and behaviors as they "read" gestures, images, symbols, signs, and signals that are embedded in a social and cultural environment... The role of the teacher is critical in negotiating and facilitating meaning construction in the text and social context of the classroom (Ruddell & Unrau, 2013, p. 1016).

The reader, as one of the model's components, has prior beliefs and knowledge, both cognitive and affective. These two factors (cognitive and affective) affect how a reader constructs meaning. The affective conditions have a direct impact on the reader's choice to engage in reading. The reader's affective conditions for learning are significantly influenced by their sociocultural values and beliefs. Moreover, reading is intricately embedded within complex sociocultural systems that shape and foster the development of reading skills in children. Literacy events consist of the cultural realm in which the texts are situated. In addition, literacy and languages only hold meaning within their specific cultural context. The cognitive conditions of the reader, which include the knowledge used in the meaning-construction process, also significantly impact the process of reading (Ruddell et al., 2019).

The teacher is another component of the sociocognitive model of meaning-making. The teacher's prior knowledge and beliefs (which are also affective and cognitive conditions) encompass emotional and cognitive factors that are influenced by and formed through a diverse array of their life experiences. Affective conditions

involve instructional beliefs and philosophy, including elements such as instructional orientation that aligns with their individual sociocultural values and beliefs. The beliefs held by teachers directly influence the affective conditions that shape and impact their purpose, planning, and construction of instructional strategies. For instance, teaching reading comprehension is facilitated by possessing the knowledge and skills to utilize a variety of strategies. The sociocultural values and beliefs of teachers affect the way they interact with their learners, the decisions they make regarding instruction, and their interpretation of texts. Moreover, if learners' sociocultural values and beliefs do not align with those of the teacher, or if the teacher does not acknowledge cultural differences, it can lead to communication breakdowns for the learners. By fostering relationships, engaging in reflection, and promoting self-exploration, teachers can enhance their responsiveness to learners' sociocultural backgrounds. This enables them to design classroom instruction that considers diverse perspectives and experiences. In addition, the cognitive conditions of teachers are specific sets of knowledge that are stored, such as their knowledge of the reader's meaning-construction process, literature and content areas, teaching strategies, metacognitive strategies, and personal and world knowledge. Having knowledge of teaching strategies is crucial for teachers when making instructional decisions and effectively implementing their chosen instructional purpose. In a constructivist perspective, the creation of meaning as an active comprehension process must consider the reader's existing knowledge and beliefs, especially in the classroom social context of meaning construction. Utilizing learners' prior experiences in the process of teaching them how to read aids both the teacher and learners in establishing connections between the learners' existing knowledge and the new knowledge they need to acquire. As part of their metacognitive strategies, teachers should also possess an understanding of

potential communication breakdowns and strategies to clarify meaning. This awareness enables them to adapt instructional strategies and enhance the process of negotiating meaning (Ruddell et al., 2019).

The text and classroom context represents the third component of the sociocognitive model of meaning-making, which is the learning environment. The learning environment exerts a significant impact on learners' motivation to participate in the learning process. The reader's active involvement in reading, interaction with the teacher and peers, and active participation in the process of negotiating meaning can be anticipated. This is supported by the reader's motivation to read and learn, activation of their prior beliefs and knowledge, personal relevance of tasks given to them, and facilitation of active meaning construction. Texts may not only mean books but also events, behaviors, and other symbolic processes (Ruddell et al., 2019).

In this paper, the sociocognitive model of meaning-construction (Ruddell et al., 2019) was adopted as the primary underpinning theory. Negotiation between the reader and the reading teacher happens in the sociocognitive model of reading through the interaction of factors that influence the construction of meaning involving the text and the classroom context.

Regarding teachers' literacy background which is clearly aligned with the sociocognitive model of meaning-making, McGlynn-Stewart (2012) conducted a study on the influence of lower grades teachers' literacy history on their literacy identity and practice. Six beginning teachers participated in the qualitative case study. Interviews, observations, and document analysis were conducted to gather data. The findings revealed that teachers used strategies that they believed worked for them before. They also assumed that these would also be suitable to their learners. How teachers saw themselves shaped the way they taught, as shaped by their early literacy experiences.

Because the teachers believed their early literacy experiences worked for them, they also utilized their learners' prior experiences to address their literacy needs. Teachers valued the literacy experiences, skills, and knowledge of their learners in reading instruction.

There are other established facts about how language is viewed, learned, shaped, and addressed in the teaching-learning process, such as the language indexical theory of style (Jaff, 2009) where “the social meaning of linguistic forms is most fundamentally a matter not of social categories such as gender, ethnicity, age, or region but rather of subtler and more fleeting interactional moves through which speakers take stances, create alignments, and construct personas” (p. 2). Languages, or even a specific language, shape people's culture (Shashkevich, 2019) and the way they view their world (Yu, 2014). Language is part of the “ideas, beliefs, and opinions about things and of people in the world” (Tupas, 2009, p. 314). One concept about language is linguistic imperialism. It is both structural (i.e., more materials and resources are allotted to the dominant language) and ideological (i.e., beliefs that glorify the dominant language) (Phillipson, 1992, 2013). Tupas (2009) pointed out how this is implicated in teaching and learning other languages, and called it “linguistic discrimination” (Tupas, 2015, p. 118). As a subgroup of cultural imperialism and educational imperialism, this issue clarifies how the domination of a colonial language may endanger the local languages in a multilingual setting (Pervaiz et al., 2019). Also, linguistic equality as a language concept argues that no language is inferior to another whether linguistically or cognitively (Boisvert & Thiede, 2020). However, for practical goals, defining linguistic equality is problematic to a certain extent and sometimes neglected (Tonkin, 2015). The language used in the society and particularly in the classroom also covers political issues. In the Philippine context, Parba (2018)

described this using Tollefson's (1991) argument on the politics of language: "what language(s) should be used in education has a crucial impact upon access to economic resources, to policy-making institutions, and to political power" (p. 28). Tollefson (1991) further stipulated that there is a relationship among language, social class, and power.

One more concept that continues to permeate how languages are used and taught is language ideologies. Woolard (2021) stressed that "language ideologies occur not only as mental constructs and in verbalizations but also in embodied practices and dispositions and in material phenomena" (p. 2). Silverstein's (1979) language ideologies as "sets of beliefs about language articulated by users as a rationalization or justification of perceived language structure and use" (p. 193) is also one of the prevailing definitions of language ideologies. This pertains to the shared beliefs of a group of people about a language and its role in the society. Burton (2013) described the term "language beliefs" as specific from one person to another and argued that there is usually a leading ideology within a social group. Hence, the term "language ideologies" is used in this paper instead of "language beliefs." Cavanaugh (2019) discussed how language ideologies shape how collective language users form both meaningful and powerful connections between languages. Fine et al. (2019) highly believed that the way teachers put meanings to languages inadvertently influences their classroom practices. It is important how teachers must undergo reflection on how these linguistic assumptions impact the people around them (in this case, the language learners).

Moreover, differing language ideologies in a language classroom only create frustration and conflict as consequences (Trentman, 2018). Various language ideologies subscriptions lead to different interpretations on how languages are viewed,

used, and learned. Language ideologies are present in the sociolinguistic reality of how languages are used in education. In Farr and Song's (2011) research study on the relationship of language ideologies and policies in multilingualism and education, they claimed that the concept of multilingualism challenges monolingualism and the standardization of languages. They further maintained that the assumptions about languages have significant and sometimes overpowering effect on the teaching-learning process. It is important how teachers interpret and implement language policies in instruction (Farr & Song, 2011). Some of the common concerns about the presence of language ideologies in multilingual classrooms include discourses strategies, power relations, and the creation or strengthening of learners' identities (Fuller, 2009).

Linguistic diversity is and should be present in multilingual classrooms. Abelian (2022) believes that languages are inherently vulnerable due to the marginalized and dominant groups of language speakers, thereby threatening linguistic diversity or the rope that binds people to their cultural and historical heritage and identities. Having linguistic rights (or the expression of oneself in the language of one's choice) is an international human right, enshrined in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UNESCO, n.d.). In one of its press releases, DepEd (2022) has also called for an increased recognition of the need for preservation of languages, as this promotes multiliteracy, multilingualism, and multiculturalism among Filipino learners. However, language use is often met by resistance and challenges. Language hegemony, for instance, is one of the barriers to linguistic diversity. Wiley (2000) defined language hegemony as how a dominant group of individuals would like to think that other languages are inadequate or less powerful compared to what they use and speak. Suarez (2002) provided an in-depth situation where language hegemony becomes a

context where "linguistic minorities will believe in and participate in the subjugation of the minority language to the dominant, to the point where just the dominant language remains" (p. 514). There are overlapping factors embedded in language hegemony. These include the politics of power, weaponizing languages, and the legitimacy and influence of languages (Awonusi, 2004). Arguing against the hegemony in the linguistic landscape is counter-hegemony, which is the resistance built against the language hegemony. Counter-hegemony supports language diversity and linguistic justice. It also counters how hegemonic language ideologies resulted in oppression, discrimination, and economic exploitation, among others (Achugar, 2008).

Ideologies are located at the heart of critical literacy approaches (Luke, 2019). In the critical pedagogy of language teaching, Fleischer (2009) indicated that counter-hegemony in teaching advances a more democratic learning environment. In critical literacy, Cushman (1999) stressed the significance of language practices that show discourses incorporated in the political world where meanings are derived from power relations. This is manifested in social change targeting the marginalized social groups or language speakers. Vasquez's (2019) definition of critical literacy points to its academic use relating to learners' rich cultural knowledge and contextualized learning, social issues, and social practices. Luke (2019) explained that "critical pedagogy raises the very practical pedagogical and curriculum question of the relationship between representation and truth, objectivity, reality, facticity, and lived experience" (p. 355). Hence, it is related to social, cultural, and political theories. The critical approach to literacy instruction allows for the representation of one's identity through language, among others, for self-determination, and one that amplifies the voices of the marginalized (Luke, 2019). Through the critical literacy approaches, language is used for representation and transformation. Luke (2019) also unpacked this into "how

language, text, discourse, and information make a difference” (p. 351) and for whom this difference is. It is one of the realities of language use and its effects on everyday people.

The different concepts of language and approaches related to language ideologies support the primary underpinning of this study, the sociocognitive model of meaning-making (Ruddell et al., 2019).

Empirical Studies on Teachers’ Language Ideologies

Studies have been conducted to investigate teachers’ language ideologies or how teachers perceive languages used in their classroom. Five recent studies investigating teachers’ language ideologies published from 2013 to 2021 were included in this review; four were foreign studies, and one was a local research.

A study conducted by Phyak (2013) analyzed the ideologies and practices in the local languages as the medium-of-instruction policy in a multilingual and multigrade school in the socio-politically stratified country of Nepal. This critical ethnography of a language policy also examined the ideological and implementational challenges of the said language policy. Phyak (2013) employed various methods during four years of data gathering to glean into how teachers, parents, and learners accepted the language policy. The researcher conducted field visits and focus group discussions (FGDs), interviewed the stakeholders of the school in the Nepali language, observed teaching and learning processes in the classroom, took photographs, and analyzed relevant documents. The data showed that the marginalized ethnolinguistic groups in Nepal seemed to be attracted to the idea of sending their children to the recently opened English-medium private schools in their area although these groups predominantly used their mother tongue. This proved that the English language is considered the dominant language in this country. Majority of

non-Rajbanshi and Santhali (RS)² teachers and parents were reluctant to embrace the importance of minority languages, which contrasted with RS teachers and parents who were in favor of the policy in teaching the learners their culture and identity. Phyak (2013) argued that these ideological issues in Nepal concerning multilingual education policy were the result of the history of linguistic oppression and socio-economic stratification. It was also found that there was a dearth of teachers who could teach in the local languages. Although teachers developed textbook manuscripts in the local languages, the language ideology of English-for-a-better-life still engaged them. The researcher acknowledged how social class plays a vital role in the language policy decision-making process, and that social elites' opinions give more weight to how languages are perceived.

Ganuzza and Hedman (2015) conducted an ethnographic study in Sweden for one year covering 67 lessons, to highlight the mother tongue teachers' pedagogical beliefs, literacy practices, and ideological assumptions. Although mother tongue instruction is supported legally, debates regarding its legitimacy continue to persist. The researchers employed classroom observations involving grades 1-5, and even higher grades, and in-depth interviews. There were 15 teachers who worked with mother tongue instruction who participated in the study. Nine of them taught Somali, and six of them taught Bosnian/Croatian/Serbian (BCS); Somali and BCS are among the largest new local languages and the two most common in Sweden. Issues concerning the teachers' background, their pedagogical views, the role of the mother tongue in instruction, and their literacy beliefs and practices in reading instruction were tackled in semi-structured interviews. Qualitative Data Analysis (QDA) software,

² The Rajbanshi and Santhali are considered marginalized people in Nepal (Phyak, 2013). The Rajbanshi and Santhali (RS) communities represent the two prominent ethnolinguistic groups in the locality surrounding Phyak's (2013) research context.

specifically Nvivo Software, was utilized to analyze thematically the field notes, transcripts of the interviews, and the photos and copies of teaching materials. The struggles concerning the legitimacy of mother tongue instruction and the legitimacy of mother tongue teachers as 'real' teachers were the major themes found in the interviews. There was no formal teachers' program for mother tongue teachers, which led to anti-mother tongue protests claiming there were no qualified teachers to teach in the minority languages. Mother tongue instruction in Sweden is non-mandatory and receives less time allotment compared to the second languages Swedish and English. Learners also varied in age and their level of proficiency in the use of the mother tongue. Regarding the teachers' literacy pedagogical beliefs and practices, it was found that teachers' discussions among themselves often circled around practical issues rather than pedagogical matters. Their practices were geared towards the development of basic language skills such as oral proficiency, writing, and reading. Reading practices revolved around pronunciation, spelling, word knowledge, and reading comprehension. Teaching reading was often interrupted to explain individual words. Writing activities were often just about copying notes from the whiteboard to the learners' notebooks. Skills worktexts were also used, and literacy practices were guided by textbooks. There were also limited peer-to-peer interactions, and teachers dominated initiation-response-evaluation³. Regarding mother tongue teachers' ideological assumptions, Ganuza and Hedman (2015) discovered that teachers held positive views towards the use of two languages, or more, and even emphasized its benefits in acquiring other languages. Language separation was practiced in the classroom however, and the use of the second languages such as Swedish was

³ Initiation-response-evaluation (IRE) is a form of classroom discourse where the teacher asks a question to a student, who responds, and then the teacher evaluates the answer (Adler, 2019).

encouraged for pragmatic and sometimes specific purposes only, like translations and comprehension-related tasks. Translanguaging was also practiced in the mother tongue classrooms to support task completion. It was concluded that the monoglossic ideology (i.e., languages are static and distinct) contributes to the teachers' teaching practices, which leads to a "focus on norms and normative language use" (p. 136), teacher domination, and less learners' initiative and collaboration. However, the need for flexible pedagogical practices is possible in the future for as long as teachers remain committed in their work, despite the difficult working conditions.

A study conducted by Daugaard (2020) explored how mother tongue was taught, as supported by both language ideologies and practices, in a specific primary school in Denmark. Using linguistic ethnography, the researcher gathered fieldwork data for 17 months through classroom observations of a particular group of learners and interviews with teachers, school management, and learners. The interviews were audio and video recorded, then transcribed. In the group of learners, 24 of 25 children's families had roots in different parts of the world. Although all the learners were born and raised in Denmark, they spoke other languages at home other than Danish. On a weekly basis, 18 of the 25 learners attended mother tongue teaching in Arabic, Dari, Pashto, or Somali. Teaching Danish and English is mandated by the Danish national education curriculum. Due to the European Union (EU) regulations, two sides of mother tongue teaching were formed: mother tongue instruction in official EU languages and mother tongue instruction in other languages. In the research locale, mother tongue teaching (although an elective subject) is mandatory. It takes into consideration the language suitable to the learners and when parents opt to enroll their children in the mother tongue subject. Daugaard (2020) focused the study on the cases of three teachers – Emal, Hawra, and Ildle (pseudonyms) –and described these

teachers' positions on their language ideologies and orientations. All three of them had different personal and educational backgrounds and working conditions. Emal taught Dari and Pashto, one lesson a week in each language. He subscribed to the separation ideology when he differentiated learners with Afghan background into Dari and Pashto teaching. This perspective resonates with the linguistic tension in Afghanistan where Dari and Pashto are considered the official languages, reflecting the Pashtuns as a powerful minority, and Dari, traditionally, being the language of education and commerce. However, Emal himself considered Pashto more complex than Dari. The variations of 'old Pashto' and 'modern Pashto' challenged Emal as well. He thought of the latter as "problematic... highly linguistically complex and it complicates intergenerational understanding" (p. 12). Emal tried to blur the distinction between these two Pashto variants. In Hawra's case, she practiced the Arabic-only language policy and took pride in it. She taught Arabic as mother tongue. For first time learners in her class, she generally and informally assessed their language proficiency in Arabic, focusing on linguistic competencies and prior knowledge of the language. Learners who could not speak the language were not welcome in class and considered time thieves⁴. The case of Ildle was somewhat similar to the sociolinguistic variation observed in Emal's. Ildle taught Somali and had problems in motivating and committing the Somali children to learn the language. However, he acknowledged the children's knowledge of the varied dialects of Somali (e.g., Northern Somali, Southern Somali, and national Somali). The experiential data gathered from Emal's, Hawra's, and Ildle's cases proved that mother tongue instruction is a complex and tension-filled language ideological practice. Mother tongue teachers also "waver between different

⁴ These are learners who disturb and challenge the teaching, thereby stealing time from the teacher and other learners (Staunæs, 2004).

linguistic norm centers and language ideologies as an integral part of their teaching practice” (p. 15). The three teachers argued that teaching the mother tongue along with the Danish language supports the learners’ language development, intergenerational understanding, building of sustainable relations, and safeguarding of peace and stability in the transnational world.

In the qualitative study conducted by Maseko (2021), teachers’ language ideologies, conflicting language policy and practices in Zimbabwe (a multilingual country in Africa), was investigated. Twelve (12) teachers from three primary schools participated in the study. Semi-structured interviews were utilized to gather data. Specifically, the study sought to identify the teachers’ language ideologies in relation to the Zimbabwean language-in-education policy and how these language ideologies on indigenous African languages and the colonially inherited English were related to their language practices in multilingual classrooms. It was found that teachers are aware of the language-in-education policy of the country with the provision to promote African languages, but still preferred English as the language of instruction. The indigenous languages were considered important only when the need for explaining complex concepts arose but considered them difficult when used as languages of instruction. Translanguaging was used in negotiating multilingual classroom encounters such as using any language in class to help learners understand better what was taught to them.

Locally, the ethnographic study done by Parba (2018) investigated how elementary school teachers understand the Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) policy and how this language policy affected or changed their language ideologies and classroom practices. The researcher purposefully chose the context and participants primarily because he wanted to know whether English was

also dominant in rural public schools as it was in highly urbanized places; the research context was in a rural area. Likewise, he also wanted to know how the teachers and learners practiced the negotiation process of the language-in-education policy. He investigated the challenges that teachers faced in teaching MTB-MLE. Parba (2018) conducted the study in 14 weeks in a public elementary school in Bukidnon, Philippines. The data were gathered through interviews where the Cebuano language was used, classroom observations using rubrics, ethnographic notes, and continuous communication through online platforms such as Messenger and Skype. Two kindergarten teachers, seven primary grades teachers, and the school principal participated in the study. The politics of language in the Philippines (Tollefson, 1991) was used by Parba (2018) to elucidate the idea of using a specific language in education, relating it to activities concerning mass media, politics, commerce, and government. The impact of this language in education has a significant role upon people's access to economic resources, policy-making institutions, and political power. The researcher found how teachers' language ideologies on MTB-MLE shifted from resistance to acceptance. At first, teachers had a resistant attitude towards the language policy, until it gradually changed to supporting it when they realized the policy's practicality and pedagogical effectiveness in the learning of their students. Parba (2018) also discussed how some parents wanted their children to be taught in the English language, thereby devaluing their local language. It was mentioned in the study that the English language remains at the top of the linguistic hierarchy in the Philippines, followed by the Filipino language, and this endangers the minority languages in the Philippines. The parents also seemed to be attracted to the idea of the need to teach their children in the English language because of the perceived economic benefits and how the language will help their children become skilled

workers in the future. One of the classroom practices noted by the researcher was translanguaging. This was done by both the learners and the teachers, as a manifestation of heteroglossic approach⁵ to language policy and use. This practice helped the teachers acknowledge the language policy and language use by accepting learners' dynamic language use (e.g., answering their teacher in mixed languages) as authentic. The lack of materials and the confusion in the textbooks brought by the diversity of the Cebuano language variations were some of the challenges found regarding how MTB-MLE was taught. The researcher implied the need for continuous conversations about teachers' language ideologies, which could help in the decision-making process and in the modifications of language policies put into place.

Four of the five research studies discussed above were ethnographic studies. Ethnographic studies are a type of qualitative research where the researcher immerses themselves, interacts with, and observes the research participants in their own environment and usually for a long period of time (Spotless, n.d.). The shortest time allocated for an ethnographic study – 14 weeks – was in Parba's research (2018). On the other hand, Phyak (2013) allotted two years to complete the data gathering. Various methods were used by the researchers. These included interviews, classroom observations, and ethnographic notes (Daugaard, 2020; Ganuza & Hedman, 2015; Maseko, 2021; Parba, 2018; Phyak, 2013). Interviews were recorded, and the recordings were transcribed. Some of the researchers also analyzed related documents on teaching using the local language (Daugaard, 2020; Phyak, 2013).

⁵ Heteroglossic approach refers to the juxtaposition and relations of multiple languages, which is in contrast to a monolingual approach (Holloway & Kneale, 2009).

Summary and Insights

All the empirical studies on teachers' language ideologies remarked that teachers' language ideologies are inherently part of teachers' teaching pedagogies and practices (Daugaard, 2020; Ganuza & Hedman, 2015; Maseko, 2021; Parba, 2018; Phyak, 2013). Phyak (2013) contended how the English-only policy remains a pervasive language ideology in Nepal, and even teachers were engaged by this. Although there was a resistance at first with regard to the use of the local language in Philippine multilingual classrooms, Parba (2018) noted how teachers' initial language ideologies transformed to supporting the said language-in-education policy when they found out that it was practical and pedagogically effective. Similar to Phyak's (2013) findings, Maseko (2021) and Parba (2018) also acknowledged the language hierarchy and its effects on the local languages in their research context. Ganuza and Hedman (2015) found that teachers held positive views on using two or more languages, but they still practiced language separation, like one of the cases in Daugaard's (2020) study. Aside from language separation, the prevailing ideologies discovered by Daugaard (2020) included a specific language only policy and sociolinguistic sensitivity. While Daugaard (2020) observed how mother tongue teachers teach the basic literacy competencies focusing on reading, translanguaging was among the teaching practices in teaching the local language that were observed by Ganuza and Hedman (2015) and Parba (2018). All the research studies claimed that there are other social and political factors such as parent's opinion and social class that affect how teachers teach in the local language in linguistically diverse contexts.

Expectations in a language classroom must be informed by the teachers' language ideologies (Trentman, 2018). However, these language ideologies often result in marginalization and exclusion of the local languages in classrooms where

some languages are considered dominant (Siegel, 2006), and these language ideologies even promote colonizing language practices (Disbray et al., 2020). If teachers' language ideologies are considered important in classroom reading assessments for multilingual learners (Ascenzi-Moreno, 2021), then it could be argued that it is equally important to consider these teachers' language ideologies in early reading instruction in a multilingual learning space, especially in terms of how the teachers utilize a language/s in teaching early graders how to read. Hence, it is imperative to determine how the teachers' language ideologies are reflected in their use of language/s in a language classroom, particularly during early reading instruction in classrooms where multiple languages are used by the teacher and learned by the learners. Therefore, this research is needed and warranted.

Early Reading Instruction

Teaching reading to children at an early age forms the foundation for enhancing educational outcomes. Children who fail to acquire reading abilities in the initial stages encounter difficulties in cultivating higher-level skills, which are frequently learned through the act of reading (Asian Development Bank, 2014). Achieving proficiency in early reading is a fundamental requirement for achieving success in reading during the subsequent years (Slavin et al., 2009).

Kreamer et al. (2020) outlined four components of successful reading instruction in the primary grades to make it more creative and individualized: 1) learners having authentic choices; 2) encouraging learner agency and ownership; 3) meaningful peer interactions; and 4) collecting and using formative data. Balanced instruction in teaching early literacy where communication, reading, and writing are interrelated with each other is being promoted by the Ministry of Education in Ontario, Canada (Ontario – Ministry of Education, 2003). This is done to prevent reading

difficulties among their young learners. In reading instruction, different activities on reading (from guided reading to independent reading) are supported, giving learners opportunities for plenty of practice. Choosing interesting texts to be read in class, building learners' prior experiences, and teachers helping readers to make connections are also important practices in teaching beginning reading (Levy, n.d.). As mentioned in the theoretical underpinnings of this study, the text used in reading instruction plays a pivotal role in the construction of meaning. Careful selection of texts in teaching beginning reading is also necessary (Hiebert, 1999). Moreover, the learners' prior experiences help bridge the gap in reading instruction. Crosby (1959) believed that experiences guide early readers in meaning-making.

Reading instruction practices in the early grades are often guided by the learners' needs for their growth as readers (Mokhtari et al., 2010). Individual differences of the learners include their interests, characteristics, and attitudes. Wawire (2020) postulated that good reading instruction helps in mitigating early literacy problems.

Teaching Practices in Reading Instruction (General)

Fab Five, Big Six, and the Importance of Oral language

The National Reading Panel (NRP) (2000) identified five essential domains (Fab Five) in teaching beginning reading, namely: phonemic awareness, phonics, vocabulary, fluency, and comprehension. NRP (2000) argued that teaching children how to manipulate phonemes within words proved to be extremely effective across all aspects of literacy. Moreover, phonemic awareness instruction yielded favorable impacts on both word reading and pseudoword reading, suggesting its support in decoding new words and retaining the ability to read familiar words. Phonics instruction defines the crucial aspect of the initial stages that entail how beginning

readers acquire knowledge of the alphabetic system, the relationships between letters and sounds, as well as patterns in spelling. NRP (2000) also argued that systematic phonics instruction plays a role in reading words through multiple ways, as it educates readers about the utilization of the alphabetic system; familiarity with the alphabet as essential for decoding words, recalling sight words, and employing sight word memory for word recognition through analogy. NRP's (2000) report further stated that fluency frequently receives insufficient attention in reading instruction. The report also defined skilled readers as "readers [who] read words accurately, rapidly, and efficiently. Children who do not develop reading fluency, no matter how bright they are, will continue to read slowly and with great effort" (p. 191). Vocabulary also holds a significant role in the process of acquiring reading skills. When a learner initiates reading, the vocabulary present in the text(s) gets connected with the spoken vocabulary that the learner already possesses. NRP (2000) implied that acquiring knowledge within immersive and rich environments is beneficial for expanding one's vocabulary, and vocabulary should also be taught both implicitly and explicitly, as relying solely on a singular method of vocabulary instruction will not lead to the most effective learning outcomes. The last element of the NRP's (2000) Fab Five is comprehension. Reading comprehension was conceptualized as an active process rather than a passive, receptive one, involving the active engagement of the reader.

Pressley (2002) argued for the expansion of the NRP report on effective practices in teaching beginning reading. He also argued that effective beginning reading instruction includes the importance of instruction or reading at home to demonstrate parent-learner interaction over literacy tasks. He also mentioned that making use of technology such as television is also an effective component of beginning reading instruction; when captions are used in televisions, reading

readiness, word recognition, and vocabulary increase. Community resources provide opportunities for reading as well. Pressley (2002) also argued that whole language promotes literacy in young learners and increases engagement and academic curiosity through literature and skills-learning. He also claimed that the language of instruction should be thought of and considered, to support an effective beginning reading instruction.

Konza (2014) made a case for the inclusion of oral language in the National Reading Panel (2000) report to complete the “Big Six” in reading. Oral language has also been found to be an integral factor in developing independent and critical readers, as supported by the science of reading.⁶ Brown (n.d.) stated that oral language is found at the very heart of reading. Konza (2014) provided a description of each of the six components of reading. Oral language allows beginning readers to use their language through their early literacy experiences to develop more their growing vocabulary, unconsciously building the grammar and pragmatics of their language/s. Sounds are learned in the phonological awareness component, where readers learn the rhythm, intonation, and sounds of the language they hear around them. Letter-sound knowledge is the phonics component; this is the component where readers learn the connection of letters to their sounds, and its goal is word recognition. In the vocabulary component, readers make sense of the meaning of words, and it is best learned through exposure to various sources. Confidence and effort in reading are shown in the fluency component – its subcomponents are accuracy or the reading of words correctly, rate or the number of words read in a certain time frame (e.g., per minute), and prosody or reading with proper expression (i.e., right phrasing, stress,

⁶ The science of reading encompasses research studies from different fields including education, cognitive psychology, developmental psychology, and neuroscience, which explain how individuals learn to read, as well as the best teaching practices in reading (Gentry & Ouellette, 2019).

and pitch). The reading comprehension component, the ultimate goal of reading (Hermosa, 2002), is where the reader actively engages with the text and finds meaning in reading. Konza (2014) summarized that the NRP's (2000) five domains in teaching early reading have "led to new understandings and new classroom practices that have increased the effectiveness of teachers to meet the needs of all students" (p. 164). If the contribution of oral language to reading is acknowledged, more opportunities in teaching beginning reading are not just boosted but also created (Konza, 2014).

Research spanning various domains of oral language consistently validates the significance of oral language as a predictor for future achievement in reading (Hill, 2009). In their study, Chang et al. (2020) developed a set of computational reading models to explore how diverse training approaches impact the process of learning how to read. They aimed to assess the impact of varying levels of pre-existing oral language skills on the efficacy of these training methods. Their simulation-based investigation illustrates the essential role of oral language proficiency as a fundamental basis for reading, and it indicates that the effectiveness of reading instruction might be influenced by this literacy domain. The findings of their study propose that a rich foundation in oral language, combined with teaching the relationships between spelling and sounds, enables the process of acquiring reading skills to make use of the connections between written, spoken, and semantic representations of words in alphabetical structures.

According to Shanahan and Lonigan (2013), there are strong predictive associations between oral language and reading comprehension as well as decoding skills (with correlations of .70 and .58, respectively). This indicates that learners possessing proficient oral language abilities are more likely to showcase enhanced decoding and comprehension capabilities. Learners who start their schooling with

proficient phonological, semantic, and grammatical understanding tend to acquire reading skills more effectively compared to their peers who start school with lower levels of oral language proficiency (Byrnes & Wasik, 2019). The development of oral language initiates at an early stage and holds paramount importance in attaining the literacy skills essential for achieving success in both educational settings and later career readiness:

Oral language is multifaceted and includes the development of a variety of skills that establish the foundation for full language expression and use. In classrooms, educators should incorporate oral language development in early elementary grades and should provide ample structured and unstructured opportunities for students to interact with peers and adults in developing and utilizing oral communication skills. Specifically, processing and expressing sound, learning, and using new vocabulary while expressing ideas using rich, complex language structures can help students both academically and socially (Carter & Hopkins, 2022, p. 10).

Skills-based/Phonics Instruction

Reading instruction is often divided into extremes: phonics-based instruction versus whole language approach (Armstrong, 2019). Phonics-based instruction makes use of breaking down words into parts while the whole language approach considers the relationship of words with each other (Armstrong, 2019).

Skills-based approach is also used in teaching beginning reading. It is often associated with the basal curriculum (Davis, 2010). Skills-based reading tasks/activities include: (1) explicit teaching of phonics and skills-based literacy in decoding, grammar, vocabulary, and comprehension; (2) instruction aimed at essential reading concepts; (3) teachers' identified goals and modeling of the desired skills; and

(4) teacher-directed literacy tasks (Davis, 2010). The NRP (2000) stated that beginning reading can be a daunting task for young readers, because many cognitive processes are needed for them to read fluently and accurately. Part of beginning reading is the need to learn the alphabetic system (letters-sound relationship and spelling patterns). Hence, teaching phonics must be done systematically and explicitly, because doing so provides a bigger contribution to learners' awareness, understanding, and use of the alphabetic code (NRP, 2000). The traditional approach in teaching beginning reading, however, was frequently relied upon excessively to strengthen learners' phonics abilities, overlooking other elements of reading and failing to address the unique needs of diverse children (Phajane, 2014).

In the Philippine context, teaching beginning reading in Filipino is usually related to using the Marungko approach as a teaching practice (Boltron & Ramos, 2021). The Marungko approach aims to enhance learners' reading abilities by employing the modern Filipino alphabet. Instead of following the conventional letter arrangement, the letters are organized according to their respective sounds (Save the Children Philippines, n.d.) The Marungko approach, developed by Nooraihan Ali and Josefina Urbano, was initially implemented in a public elementary school located in Marungko, Angat, Bulacan, hence the name of the approach (Oli, 2022). This approach is 'phono-syllabic' because words are formed by a combination of sound-units in syllables (Ali & Urbano, 1967). The letter sounds are taught to align with the phonemic level, and there are designated common and recognizable letter patterns that are taught (Boltron & Ramos, 2021). It also focuses on teaching 'accurate' individual sounds and combining them to form syllables then words. It is emphasized that acquiring proficiency in letter sounds holds a significant importance in this

approach (Oli, 2022). Several studies featuring this approach have been conducted in the country.

For instance, Vales (2019) utilized the Marungko approach in teaching beginning reading in Filipino in a first grade class in Cavite, Philippines. Using a pretest-posttest design, the researcher found that the respondents' performance in word recognition significantly improved. She then recommended the use of the approach in teaching beginning reading in Filipino.

Boltron and Ramos (2021) also conducted a quasi-experimental study to test the effectiveness of the Marungko approach in teaching beginning reading in Filipino to Grade one learners in Cebu, Philippines. The finding of their study showed a significant difference in the initial and final assessments of beginning reading competencies (identifying letter names, identifying letter sounds, identifying initial sounds, reading familiar words, and reading oral passages). It was concluded that Marungko approach is an effective approach in enhancing learners' proficiency in the initial reading stage.

Santos and De Vera (2020) conducted a study to determine the level of reading performance of Grade 1 learners in Filipino using Marungko approach in a public school in the province of Tarlac. The quantitative data gathered through questionnaire and reading performance evaluations showed that a large portion of Grade 1 learners demonstrated a very satisfactory level of proficiency in Filipino in terms of phonemic awareness, reading in isolation, and reading in context. This means that their ability to read effectively relied on their understanding of oral processes, which include comprehending word order and usage of words within a given context. A considerable number of learners also achieved a highly satisfactory level of proficiency when it comes to vocabulary and reading comprehension. This means that most of them were

familiar with and retained the meanings of the words introduced to them during the four-week Marungko teaching sessions and could comprehend what they read. Thus, the researchers recommended the use of the Marungko approach in Filipino early reading instruction.

Using video lessons employing the Marungko approach, Laurente (2021) determined the effectiveness of this approach in improving the reading performance of the learners. Quasi-experimental method was employed, and the quantitative data or the results of the study indicate that employing the Marungko approach in early reading instruction has the potential to improve learners' performance in reading. This is because the approach incorporates video lessons that enable learners to observe how to sound out letters and words correctly. By aligning the instruction with the most essential learning competencies⁷, the approach is believed to improve learners' reading skills.

Aside from the Marungko approach, Claveria technique is also used in teaching Filipino beginning reading in the Philippines. Formulated by Erlinda S. Claveria, the Claveria technique, a phonovisual method, exemplifies a text-marking strategy, comprising of relatable pictures aimed at learners. Each picture represents both the symbol and sound of the syllable (Quiambao & Maguyon, 2021).

Manzalay (2019) conducted a descriptive quantitative study aimed at determining the effectiveness of the Claveria technique on non-readers and struggling readers in Filipino. Results showed that the Grade one students' reading levels improved. Following a three-month period of implementing a structured reading intervention with the participants, gradual progress was observed. With the help of the

⁷ DepEd offices (i.e., central office, regional offices, and schools division offices) and teachers themselves have referred to these competencies for the development of activity sheets, self-learning modules, and video lessons. These competencies have been used by public schools in the Philippines since school year 2020-2021 up to the present.

pananda [text-marks], learners were able to acquaint themselves with syllables, enabling them to effectively read words, phrases, sentences, and short stories.

Using the Claveria technique as a reading remediation tool for Grade one learners, Bautista (2022) conducted a pretest-posttest design study to determine how the technique would improve learners' performance in reading. Assessments used included completing a word by filling in the blank with the missing syllable, connecting a line from a picture to its name, and comprehension items by marking each item with a check or x mark. Based on the comparative analysis of the pretest and posttest scores, a significant difference was noted, suggesting the improvement of the respondents' reading performance.

Furthermore, the Fuller approach that targets the teaching of beginning reading in English is one of the many approaches used to teach the sequence of sounds to be learned by beginning readers (Ocampo, 1997). This approach integrates letter recognition, phonics instruction, and whole word methods to effectively teach word recognition in the English language. Learners' proficiency in both the names and shapes of the alphabet letters is essential for this approach, and the words to be read should start with a single consonant (DepEd Teachers' Club, 2020). During the initial twenty-one lessons, a column is arranged with a set of three-letter words, followed by four-letter words, all having consistent sound endings, and "the rhyme facilitates the learning" (Ocampo, 1997, p. 207).

To determine the effectiveness of the Fuller approach in enhancing the English reading skills of struggling grade two learners, Lubuguin (2019) employed pretest and posttest assessments and interviews to gather data. The findings of this study indicate that the Fuller approach has a moderate impact on improving a child's reading

proficiency. So, Lubuguin (2019) looked into other factors that may hinder learners' reading progress such as parents' cooperation.

Using different Fuller materials as an intervention, Goyja (2023) employed an experimental research design to determine the effectiveness of Fuller approach in teaching English reading among Grade 3 pupils. An improvement in learners' reading abilities, in line with the English learning competencies related to reading which were set by DepEd, was noted, hence supporting the effectiveness of the Fuller approach. Goyja (2023) also recommended the implementation of the Fuller approach to develop learners' reading skills which could contribute to their meaningful experiences in school.

Learning Environment and Materials

A conducive learning setting promotes educational engagement through playful interaction with a diverse array of resources and learning prospects. This kind of environment is also adaptive, incorporating elements that stimulate all five senses, inspire thinking, and stir creativity (Roy, 2015). Moreover, books and other literacy resources such as authentic reading materials (Kung, 2017) also have significant roles in teaching second language reading (Dong, 2019). Kung (2017) believed that the use of authentic materials also increases motivation in reading. Printed materials and online reading have become deeply ingrained in the daily lives of learners. eBooks and digital technology have the potential to captivate readers who may otherwise be hesitant or unenthusiastic (Alcott, 2021). The utilization of these materials complements and reinforces conventional print resources in reading, fostering multimodal learning. Samat and Aziz (2020) found that the incorporation of multimedia learning in teaching reading comprehension was beneficial. The integration of various media elements supported and enhanced the process of comprehension.

Furthermore, the Tata Institute of Social Sciences, Hyderabad (2019) stated that a print-rich environment refers to a setting where young children have numerous opportunities to engage with various types of printed materials. To truly qualify as print-rich, a classroom must effectively integrate print into teaching and learning activities. This involves exploring print within meaningful contexts and observing adults using print. Such exposure is crucial for children's literacy development. It demonstrates that print holds meaning, and that reading and writing serve practical, everyday functions. Rehman (2019) argued that a print-rich environment underscores the significance of oral communication, reading, and writing in the education of every learner. This entails curating materials that support language and literacy development. Ibrahim et al. (2022) investigated the effect of print-rich classrooms on the reading development of primary graders in Nigeria, Africa. They found that a classroom environment that is abundant in print proved highly effective in aiding and inspiring learners to enhance their literacy skills. To nurture and promote literacy, they implied that early-grade teachers are responsible for crafting, showcasing, and utilizing meaningful charts. They could also incorporate co-created print, functional print, labels, and other materials to make the learning environment engaging, welcoming, and interactive. They also recommended that teachers must be equipped with knowledge and awareness regarding the importance of a print-rich classroom environment in their teaching practices and on how to create purposeful materials to facilitate children's literacy development.

The Education Hub (2019) stated that digital devices and technology are often presented as a means to generate greater learner engagement with the educational content they encounter in school. Education is experiencing continuous growth. The integration of technology in lessons serves as a potent tool to capture the attention of

learners, particularly in the domain of reading. Incorporating multimedia learning into reading instruction proves beneficial, as the amalgamation of various media elements facilitates the scaffolding of the comprehension process. When Castillo (2017) investigated the impact of computer-based early grade reading intervention on reading instruction in rural South Africa, he found that guided and contextualized technology aids in teaching early reading and is used in cross-lingual transfer of skills. Once learners had reached a certain level of proficiency in decoding skills in their mother tongue, they experienced improved support for the transfer of those skills to the English language. Arendain (2019) conducted an analysis of the effectiveness of print and non-print reading resources in improving reading comprehension. She utilized a quasi-experimental pre-test post-test design. The experimental group was engaged in electronic learning through a web-based portal, whereas the control group was assigned paper-based reading activities through face-to-face content delivery. The findings indicated that, prior to the intervention, the cognitive learning in reading comprehension was comparable between the experimental and control groups. However, following the intervention, the pupils exposed to non-print format demonstrated a gradual improvement, while those using print format showed a significant increase in their reading comprehension scores. This suggests that both web-based reading portals and paper-based delivery methods can effectively enhance reading comprehension skills.

Summary and Insights

Teaching young children to read early on lays the groundwork for better educational achievements. Those who struggle with reading in the beginning often face challenges in developing more advanced skills that are typically acquired through reading. Proficiency in early reading is essential for continued success in reading

throughout later years. The Fab Five of the NRP (2000) namely, phonemic awareness, phonics, fluency, vocabulary, and comprehension underscore foundational abilities that all learners must possess to become proficient readers. Understanding these five elements or distinct aspects of reading and their interconnectedness is important, especially for early grades teachers. The inclusion of oral language (Konza, 2014) shows that it serves as the basis for all other elements of reading. Oral language bridges the gap between spoken and written language, enabling children to decode, understand, and engage with written texts effectively.

Reading debates always involve the “battle” between phonics and whole-language approach. This debate also shows that traditional methods of early reading instruction often placed excessive emphasis on reinforcing learners' phonics skills, while neglecting other essential domains of reading and not adequately catering to the distinct characteristics of diverse learners (Phajane, 2014). In the Philippines, Marungko, Claveria, and Fuller are some of the skills-based approaches used in teaching beginning reading. All of the quantitative studies on the Marungko approach mentioned in this paper remarked that using this approach in Filipino early reading instruction improves learners' reading skills, particularly their beginning reading competencies (Boltron & Ramos, 2021; Laurente, 2021; Santos & De Vera, 2020; Vales, 2019). The two studies on the Claveria technique (Bautista, 2022; Manzalay, 2019) mentioned earlier showed the effectiveness of this technique in Filipino early reading instruction. The two cited studies on the Fuller approach (Goyja, 2023; Lubuguin, 2019) support the effectiveness of the approach in teaching beginning reading in English. However, reading is not only about decoding, as discussed in the Fab Five (NRP, 2000) and Big Six of Reading (Konza, 2014). Reading is a multifaceted skill that encompasses not only decoding but also comprehension, vocabulary

development, fluency, and critical thinking. The traditional method, by disproportionately prioritizing phonics, tended to overlook these other essential components. Aside from these components, oral language also plays an important role in the development of learners' literacy skills, especially as it provides the foundation for reading.

The learning environment and available resources also complement the teaching practices in reading instruction. Resources such as authentic materials (Kung, 2017) and online and multimedia materials (Alcott 2021; Samat & Aziz, 2020) enhance the delivery of reading instruction. Moreover, literacy-rich environments provide opportunities and allow positive learner engagement with various resources (Ibrahim et al., 2022; Rehman, 2019; Tata Institute of Social Sciences, Hyderabad; 2019). Technology-assisted instruction also support reading instruction, especially in engaging learners (Education Hub, 2019), cross-lingual transfer of skills (Castillo, 2017), and using a variety of reading materials and platforms (Arendain, 2019). Print-rich environments, rich reading materials, and thoughtful and effective technology integration contribute to learners' literacy development, cognitive growth, and overall educational success. Teachers, as part of interactive meaning-making, need to understand that these elements outline a holistic learning environment that embraces different learning styles, interests, and abilities while promoting lifelong learning habits.

Teaching Practices in Reading Instruction (Multilingual)

In connection to teaching beginning reading in multilingual contexts, Green (2017) validated the use of mother tongue in teaching early reading. This was discussed in the article "Learning to read in their mother tongue helps to accelerate children's learning." The article features the multilingual country of Mozambique. However, it presents a problem when the language used in teaching reading is

different from the one the learners speak upon entering school. In line with reading instruction in the learners' L1, children who are taught in their mother tongue are expected to perform better in their second language learning (World Vision, 2016). Louge (2016) outlined practices in teaching reading in a multilingual context, and these include sensitivities around language of instruction, especially the mother tongue, and the development of rich reading materials. In the multilingual country of Burundi in Africa, Nsengiyumva et al. (2021) found that language-in-education policy makers (including language curriculum designers and implementors) are encouraged to utilize the interactions that happen in the different languages in the classroom to improve individual learners' language proficiency.

Recognizing the importance of the mother tongue in early reading instruction, Prosper and Nomlomo (2016) investigated how reading stories in the learners' mother tongue was used in the classroom. They also investigated the limitations of storytelling with regard to the learners' biliteracy development. The qualitative study involved one teacher with a teaching assistant and her whole grade one class. The teacher possessed bilingual proficiency in both English and Afrikaans, whereas her assistant demonstrated bilingual competence in English and isiXhosa. Using interviews and class observations, it was discovered that utilizing multilingual reading resources had its benefits and pedagogical limitations for literacy development in three languages (Afrikaans, English, and isiXhosa). The pedagogical approaches used by the teacher appeared to restrict learners from utilizing other languages in both reading and writing activities, as all literacy tasks were exclusively conducted in English. The learners' mother tongue was beneficial as a cognitive resource, because it aided them in improving their understanding of stories written in English. However, the teacher and her assistant were not able to teach literacy across languages due to their poor

preparation (improper planning, lack of teacher training and teacher support) in these languages, which affected how literacy instruction was delivered. Although stories were read to learners in the three languages, these were explained to them using English only. Also, their instructional methods appeared to promote a focus on English (L2) literacy exclusively, thereby reinforcing a subtractive bilingualism (acquisition of a second language leading to the deterioration of the home language) or monolingual approach rather than cultivating biliteracy or proficiency in multiple literacies.

In teaching reading in a second language (L2), Mikulecky (2009) suggested teaching reading skills one at a time. Teaching reading in the learners' L2 also presents a handful of challenges that teachers must learn how to face, especially in using the learners' linguistic experiences from their L1 as they bring these in reading instruction; reading in a second language requires the simultaneous utilization of various cognitive and linguistic abilities (Ahmed, 2015). Ahmed (2015) further argued that reading teachers also face the challenge of teaching L2 reading beyond mere text comprehension, and that they should focus on enhancing the learners' overall reading ability.

Cross-Language Transfer of Reading Skills

Cross-linguistic transfer is also a topic on multilingual reading research. Piper and Miksic (2011) argued that the transfer of literacy skills across languages is easier facilitated in multilingual contexts. Cross-linguistic transfer happens when learners use their L1 experiences and resources in learning another language or languages (Cárdenas-Hagan et al., 2007).

Two studies on cross-linguistic transfer in the Philippines were conducted by Melendez (2010) and Danieleles-Cortez (2021). Melendez (2010) found that the literacy skills of the learners in their L1 (Cebuano) and L2 (English) were transferred to their

L3 (Filipino). Melendez (2010) administered six measures per language to 123 children ages six to eight years old to come up with the data. Danieles-Cortez (2021), on the other hand, investigated cross-lingual transfer of literacy skills among Grade 1 pupils speaking same and different home and school languages. She found that vocabulary knowledge and listening comprehension could be transferred across languages. Learners with the same home and school languages also performed better than learners with different home and school languages.

Yang et al. (2017) conducted a systematic review of literature of cross-linguistic transfer between Chinese (L1) and English (L2), covering 33 research studies. They found that there were significant correlations between the L1 and L2 in phonological awareness, decoding, vocabulary, and morphological awareness.

Mother tongue has a great influence on how learners process words in the target languages, especially on word processing (relating to word features and morphology). Mother tongue also has potential in L2 syntactic processing or analyzing the grammatical structure of a sentence to understand its meaning (Lago et al., 2020).

Translanguaging/Use of Multiple Languages

Still in line with early reading instruction in multilingual contexts, strategic approaches on the use of languages in multilingual classrooms are expected to guide teachers in instruction. Teachers employ language practices to facilitate learners' comprehension in classrooms where multiple languages are used (and read) (Lartec et al., 2014). Common language practices in multilingual classrooms involve translation, code-switching, and translanguaging (De Los Reyes & Bagona, 2022). These language practices can be differentiated from one another.

Translanguaging allows the use of more than one language especially in multilingual contexts, making language practices more fluid (España & Herrera, n.d.).

Translanguaging in the classroom is closely associated with the historical construct of code-switching. There is also a significant degree of overlap between the latter and the former. Code-switching practices involve the concept of separating languages, whereas translanguaging emphasizes the simultaneous use of both languages without separation (Lewis et al., 2012). In classrooms where there are considered dominant languages, a teacher may engage in translation from one language to another to ensure that children comprehend the content in their more proficient language. While translanguaging involves the simultaneous use of two (or more) languages, translations focus more on language separation, providing support, and primarily operating in the stronger language. These two practices are oftentimes employed concurrently (Lewis et al., 2012).

However, despite the differences among code-switching, translations, and translanguaging, De Los Reyes (2018) subsumed code-switching and translations under translanguaging when he investigated the third grade teachers' and learners' language practices in the teaching of English as a second language in Mindanao, Philippines. De Los Reyes (2018) expanded the scope of translanguaging by incorporating additional language practices such as code-switching and translations. Code-switching and translations are found to be inherent among multilingual individuals, and their inclusion enhances the definition of translanguaging.

Kumar et al. (2021) investigated the effectiveness of code-switching in primary grade language classrooms by utilizing the perspectives of second language teachers in India. Although code-switching is viewed negatively, the results suggest that code-switching is primarily utilized in classrooms for interpreting intricate concepts, translating questions, seeking confirmation, checking of learners' understanding, as well as fostering solidarity. Moreover, code-switching is particularly prevalent in

primary education. This language practice aids in meeting the needs of language learners.

In a research paper written by Zhang (2023), he argued that code-switching frequently happens in kindergarten and primary grade levels in China. It is used as a strategy to teach English in English as a foreign language (EFL) classrooms. Many young English learners in China possess proficiency in their first language. However, they have limited opportunities to learn English outside of the classroom context. Code-switching is argued to assist teachers in providing clearer explanations and minimizing the need for repeated explanation due to learners' misunderstandings. From English, the teacher could code-switch to Chinese (L1), in order to provide clarification, enhance student learning, and foster learners' interest in the subject matter.

Given the challenges posed by multilingualism and globalization, it is crucial to recognize the importance of translations in nation-building and identity formation, because translations democratize knowledge and provide equal access to information (Cruz et al., 2020). In a study conducted by Besinga (2019) investigating the strategies employed by lower grades teachers in implementing MTB-MLE, it was found that due to the absence of mother tongue books or materials written in the mother tongue, teachers resort to translations. Translations of the target language to the mother tongue, according to the respondents, is the best response to the aforementioned issue regarding the availability of MT materials. Sukirmiyadi (2018) translated popular Indonesian kid songs to English and used these translated materials to teach English to Kindergarten, Grade 1, and Grade 2 learners. Singing is a popular technique that is used by teachers. The use of the translated songs appeared to be highly effective and efficient, particularly for young learners.

Cenoz and Gorter (2017) studied minority languages and sustainable translanguaging as a protection of the former. The researchers analyzed translanguaging and how it protected minority languages. They argued that classroom translanguaging is called pedagogical translanguaging primarily because it includes instructional strategies involving two or more languages. On the other hand, spontaneous translanguaging happens inside and outside the classroom, showing the shifting boundaries between languages and is initiated by learners. Both pedagogical and spontaneous translanguaging can be used to comprehend how translanguaging occurs in classrooms with multiple languages. Translanguaging is also used to increase learners' comprehension of where the mother tongue is needed: literacy levels increase when learners are allowed to use their first language to analyze texts that are in other language/s. It was also found that there have been concerns about minority languages losing their pure selves when mixed with other languages (e.g., Basque mixing with Spanish). The politics of languages is also a challenge to translanguaging because of the status and perceived influence of the major languages. The researchers further argued that translanguaging could sustain the minority languages for as long as appropriate principles are put in place.

Makalela (2019) investigated data from African classrooms on how translanguaging contributed to deepening comprehension and developing oneself. Fifteen (15) in-service literacy teachers who came from three provinces of South Africa participated in the study through a translanguaging induction program. After the program, the researcher conducted on-site visits and class observations, and audio recorded classroom discourse was also analyzed. The results revealed that the teachers utilized intentional translanguaging to elicit a variety of languages, creating opportunities for wider multilingual language use. The strategic use of translanguaging

also led to deeper comprehension among learners. Hence, translanguaging supported multilingual learning.

Wawire and Barnes-Story (2023) studied translanguaging for multiliteracy development. They discussed that the use of pedagogical strategies, especially ones that promote literacy in more than one language, is important in teaching multilingual learners. These strategies that reflect the identities of the multilingual learners promote social and linguistic justice and inclusive learning. The strategies include legitimizing use of translanguaging in the classroom, modeling translanguaging, creating an accepting multilingual environment, development of multilingual language learning objectives, implementing collaborative working environments, creating multilingual listening centers, providing multilingual learning materials, and using of a backward curriculum design.

Language and education are associated with each other. Language is the vehicle used in classroom interactions, and teachers try to inject their influence into these interactions (Knors, 2016). The power that each language holds should bring forth awareness to teachers and on how they use these languages in the classroom (Brevik & Rindal, 2020). Teachers are used to utilizing classroom language while learners are used to hearing it (Bilash, 2011). Although student-centered language learning has arisen in recent history, there are still teachers who monopolize language learning, with learners being restricted in the speaking aspect of language (Loyola, 2016). Brown (2014) argued that early reading instruction heavily relies on languages due to their crucial contributions to various aspects of learning. These include fostering phonological awareness and vocabulary development, serving as a form of communication, and facilitating social interactions. She further argued that by actively participating in the reading process, children acquire the ability to apply their

expanding knowledge and skills in a flexible manner, integrating them across all areas of development.

One study about teachers' use of languages in class was conducted by Crichton (2009), where five teachers were observed and audio-recorded to determine their ways of teaching languages. The study also aimed to see how learners responded to inputs of the teachers in the target language while mother tongue was occasionally inserted or used. It was found that the teachers' way of teaching the language was crucial in the general learning of the learners. The teachers' interactions with the learners using the target language while considering the learners' level of understanding was also pivotal in ensuring that learning is happening:

The pupils may not use the language they hear a great deal in class without prompting, but, if the teacher actively involves them in listening, through questioning and checking for comprehension, they are drawn into the language because they have to be able to demonstrate understanding at the very least. (Crichton, 2009, p. 32)

Through an action research project in Indonesian schools, Kartika-Ningsih and Rose (2018) analyzed the structures and functions of language use in multilingual classrooms through multilingual interactions between the teacher and the learners. Data were gathered through recorded classroom observations. Four patterns were discovered in multilingual classrooms: (1) the use of the mother tongue only; (2) the use of the second language only; (3) combination of MT and L2; and (4) combination of L1, L2, and L3. Structures of language shift were specific according to role (speakers take up roles such as services or information) and within the roles (between and within moves). This language shift, especially in line with pedagogy, may serve to

present the sources of meanings, scaffold the teaching-learning process, or enact the teacher-learner relations.

Sometimes, learners bring a language that is patterned differently from the one used in schools, and teachers challenge the validity of this discourse pattern. It is important that teachers' use of languages in class reflects the different backgrounds of the learners, considering the society in general and their culture and language in particular (Fillmore & Snow, 2000). Teachers may dominate the language the learners use, but they should also encourage and accept the use of the language learners are comfortable using instead of just merely tolerating it or worse banning it (Kemsley, 2015).

Djorbua et al. (2021) studied the role of English as the mode of instruction in lower primary schools in Ghana, a multilingual country in Africa. Fourteen (14) teachers and 39 pupils participated in the study. Data from class observations and interviews were utilized in the data analysis. The findings showed that when teachers and learners could not speak in the expected mother tongue in the classroom, they resorted to using another L1 along with English to let the learners understand what was being taught to them. The English language was also a dominant instructional language. The teachers used English as the common ground of the languages of instruction. Despite the standing language policy, the teachers still determined the medium of instruction to be used in class, supported by their rationale that language serves as the shared foundation for all learners.

A mixed-method study by Norro (2022) looked into the language practices of Namibian primary grades teachers. The results showed that teachers preferred teaching using the English language than the learners' mother tongue. According to them, using English simplified the process of explaining to learners from diverse

backgrounds. Other reasons included practical concerns like the scarcity of materials or suitable vocabulary in local languages, as well as the presence of linguistically diverse groups. Teachers faced the challenge of not knowing all the learners' languages and felt that if they opted to use only one of the local languages, it might result in unequal treatment among the learners. Code-switching was utilized in both content teaching and in activities related to classroom management, like giving out instructions or addressing disciplinary matters. There was also a hierarchical relationship between English and the local languages, with English being positioned at the top and the local languages considered subordinate. The hierarchical language ideology was reinforced by assessments conducted exclusively in English. However, teachers may use their agency to implement multilingual practices, even during exams, as a way to mediate this situation.

Challenges in Multilingual Classrooms

Despite the benefits of multilingualism, multilingual classrooms are not without a challenge. UNESCO (2023) stated that a number of countries and governments or local administrations have previously shown hesitation and opposition in supporting multilingual education. In Nepal for example, a complete generation of indigenous individuals were deprived of the chance to receive education in their native languages. Languages of the indigenous communities face the dominance of international languages such as English. The perceived economic advantages of learning a global language are considered to be more significant than those of acquiring local languages, especially when English is a fundamental component of the national curriculum (UNESCO, 2023).

In Bangladesh, every language-related policy and educational strategy has been centered around fostering and advancing the Bangla language and culture. This

led to the disregard for the diverse multilingual composition of the nation and consequently marginalized indigenous communities (Rahman, 2010). Several challenges face the implementation of a multilingual language-in-education policy in Bangladesh: (1) disputes regarding the demographic, settlement, and linguistic aspects of indigenous communities; (2) standardizing and choosing languages spoken by minority groups; (3) hierarchical and centralized educational framework; and (4) economic hardship and environmental catastrophes. Controversies related to population, habitation, and languages of indigenous people create a significant barrier to the execution of a multilingual language-in-education strategy in Bangladesh. Without a mutual agreement on the precise count of indigenous communities and their members, the challenge of selecting and standardizing indigenous languages as medium of instruction for children's education will persist. Most indigenous languages in Bangladesh are spoken, lack written forms (orthographies), and are often employed within households and community contexts. Many indigenous individuals, similar to the broader population of Bangladesh, are fluent in Bangla. Some formally educated indigenous individuals can both speak and write Bangla, setting them apart from their illiterate counterparts. These indigenous people utilize their native languages as home languages. Controversies also exist over prioritizing either Bangla or English language acquisition over the use of mother tongue as language of instruction. The dichotomy between those who have an easy access to an English-medium education and the larger population limited only to Bangla-medium instruction, is present due to the absence of a balanced English language education policy in the country (Rahman, 2010).

In Switzerland, primary school learners acquire proficiency in two foreign languages (one of the Swiss national languages and English); hence, multilingual

pedagogy is used in their classrooms. The inclusion of the learners' home language also faces challenges in classrooms. While promoting interactions in learners' mother tongues can increase their prominence within the classroom, such activities might not substantially impact children's perspectives on linguistic and cultural diversity. In fact, these endeavors often appear meaningless. Possibly, time limitations could be a factor, or it might be due to teachers having limited understanding and/or familiarity in effectively incorporating the mother tongue (Peyer et al., 2020).

Discussion on the challenges in Philippine mother tongue-based multilingual classrooms is included under the heading "Philippine context."

Empirical Studies on Teachers' Early Reading Instruction Practices

Studies concerning early reading instruction practices have also been done. Six studies on teachers' early reading instruction practices from 2012 to 2021 are included in this review.

Dubeck et al. (2012) conducted a qualitative descriptive research study about the early primary literacy instruction in the Coast Province in Kenya, where the districts were considered one of the poorest in the country. The study aimed to determine how Kenyan children were taught to read in English and Swahili (Kenya's national language). It also aimed to see how the literacy instruction aligned with the current views of research on reading instruction and the factors relating to these reading instruction practices. The researchers stated that the literacy levels of schoolchildren in sub-Saharan Africa were low, and the issues of health, poverty, and lack of reading materials contributed to this fact. They also argued that a balanced approach in reading instruction (where phonics instruction is included) that gave emphasis to meaning, language, and connected text was the most effective practice. In Kenya, the foundation skills in literacy are taught in the early grades. Mother tongue instruction in

Swahili is used from Grades 1 to 3. In the succeeding grades, learners begin to be taught in English. Forty (40) Grade 1 and Grade 2 public school teachers from 24 schools with varied profiles participated in the study. They were interviewed using open-ended questions, and their classes were observed. The interviews were recorded and transcribed. In total, there were 24 observations that were done. Post-observation conversations were also conducted. Different data gathering methods (interviews, class observations, and post-observation conversations) were used to triangulate the findings and validate them. The researchers utilized the NVivo 8 software in the data analysis. Dubeck et al. (2012) found that the development of oral language focusing on whole words was prioritized in reading instruction, and teaching sound-and-letter relationship was only given minimal time because of the lack of materials. Teachers also followed the Swahili and English subjects' curricula. However, the teachers also acknowledged the importance of the letter-sound relationship in teaching reading in Swahili and English. Also, class sizes that ranged from 40 to 120 learners were a factor, too, in grouping learners according to their literacy abilities. The researchers also noted that Swahili instruction was done explicitly. The teachers listed three constraints to reading acquisition: 1) learner absenteeism; 2) lack of parental support; 3) and multilingualism. They also favored English as a dominant language among other languages. Their English-only policies were put in place to make learners succeed in the school's internal exams which were written in English. The researchers concluded that the teachers' reading instruction practices could be improved by utilizing other methods.

In a qualitative case study, Dlamini and Sheik (2019) explored two urban public primary schools' teachers' practices in teaching reading using the English language to Grade 1 in Eswatini or Swaziland. The results of the semi-structured interviews,

observations, and focus group discussions, which were analyzed thematically, revealed that teachers had the theoretical background on the instructional practices to teach reading. However, the result of the observations contradicted this when it was observed that learner-centered approaches were not always used in their classrooms. Analysis of relevant documents used by the teachers in reading instruction was also conducted. Teachers considered several aspects in teaching reading such as subject matter knowledge and pedagogy, beliefs about teaching reading and/or literacy, training of teachers, learners' educational needs, curriculum standards, and learning environment, among others. These factors served as the rationale for their instructional practices. It was also revealed that the teachers' lack of opportunities to be coached or mentored and the lack of learning resources made teaching literacy difficult and challenging. Moreover, these difficulties were being overcome by teachers by having their own initiatives in teaching literacy such as having a positive approach to work, giving additional literacy materials that the learners can use, organizing school-based trainings and activities with other teachers, and using reading remediation and intervention.

A qualitative descriptive research study conducted by Desta (2020) analyzed the reading instruction practices of 112 primary teachers in Gojjam Zone, Ethiopia. Using semi-structured interviews, questionnaires, and observations, the researcher found that teachers did not have the necessary background to teach early reading, resulting in their failure to teach reading effectively. One of the reasons for the poor practices of the teachers was the lack of supplementary materials or other resources needed to teach reading. The large size of classes also affected the delivery of reading instruction. The teachers also favored the traditional approaches in teaching reading (i.e., teaching sounds and letters in isolation, then words and sentences, to longer

texts). However, they created an atmosphere where learners were encouraged to be active and critical thinkers. It was concluded that the teachers did not focus on teaching reading skills and strategies in reading instruction.

Lewis-Fokum and Thomas (2018) explored how teachers teach literacy in grade one classrooms in Jamaica. A qualitative case study design was utilized for the two-year collection of data for this study. There were six teacher-participants, purposively chosen, for this study. The researchers found that teachers used psychomotor activities, mostly teacher-directed activities, through songs, games, and a variety of movements to engage learners. The use of praises was fairly evident in the teachers' classrooms where the learners were applauded for correct responses, and others were also encouraged to congratulate the learners whose answers were correct. Classroom instruction was phonics in orientation, revealing that teachers favored the skills-based approach in teaching reading. Teachers also used translation strategies in teaching reading. For example, Jamaican Creole statements were translated to the standard English language.

Suarez et al. (2020) conducted a mixed-method study in Spain to analyze the relationship of six kindergarten and primary grades teachers' beliefs about reading instruction, their instructional practices in reading, and reading discourses. Qualitative and quantitative information sourced from observations (Suarez et al., 2018) were mixed, and interviews and questionnaires were transcribed and coded for analysis. They found that giving out feedback (e.g., praising or correcting a learner and direct instruction such as individual and group reading – silent or oral) and functional knowledge of reading including comprehension activities were the dominant teaching reading practices that the teachers usually did in their class. On the other hand, they seldom used literacy activities and reinforcement. The researchers, however,

concluded that despite the noticeable differences among the teacher-participants in the study, they all maintained an eclectic approach⁸ in teaching reading.

Using the teacher inquiry approach, Wagner (2021) discussed the teacher language practices in multilingual contexts where learners speak and use more than one language and how these practices were developed, implemented, and refined. The study was participated in by five multilingual teachers teaching early childhood with different language backgrounds, program orientation and contexts, and professional experiences. He found that modelling multilingual language practices was effective in teaching reading. This was also connected to how teachers, considering the culture of the learners, went beyond the content and used the learning environment to foster deeper learning. Teachers also provided the learners opportunities to learn the languages, inspiring curiosity about other languages. Teachers also used the home languages of the learners to support their learning. The diversity of the language practices, it was revealed, supported multilingual learners' language development.

Summary and Insights

Mother tongue is considered an important factor in multilingual education, especially in connection with literacy instruction (Green, 2017). Children who are taught in their home language are anticipated to excel in acquiring their second language skills (World Vision, 2016). Teacher preparation and proper utilization of the languages in a literacy classroom greatly affect how reading instruction is delivered (Prosper & Nomlomo, 2016). In multilingual settings, the transfer of literacy skills between languages is more easily facilitated (Piper & Miksic, 2011). In the two studies on cross-linguistic transfer conducted in the Philippines, it was found that literacy skills

⁸ With an eclectic approach, reading teachers can incorporate the most effective elements of all widely used strategies and use them where they are most appropriate (Alsayad, 2019).

of the learners from their first language transferred across languages used in school (Danieles-Cortez, 2021; Melendez, 2010). This finding is similar to the finding of Yang et al.'s (2017) study where significant correlations between the L1 and L2 in phonological awareness, decoding, vocabulary, and morphological awareness were found. However, despite the availability of research studies supporting cross-linguistic transfer (Pang et al., n.d.), a number of learners learn how to read in other languages without learning how to read using their mother tongue, even though it is supposed to be part of their everyday life. This is because the language used in school is different from their home language.

Typical language practices identified within multilingual classrooms include translation, code-switching, and translanguaging (De Los Reyes & Bagona, 2022). The current study acknowledges the merits of code-switching, translations, and translanguaging as legitimate language practices in multilingual classrooms. However, this study adopts De Los Reyes' (2018) assertion that code-switching and translations are subsumed under translanguaging for the same reasons: (1) These are practices which are natural among multilinguals.; (2) These three are understood better using the perspective of multilingualism; and (3) The given conceptualization expands the scope of translanguaging. The current study, which covers translanguaging as an early reading instruction practice, also adds to the limited translanguaging studies conducted in the Philippines (De Los Reyes & Bagona, 2022). There is a dearth of research studies about translanguaging and teachers' use of language/s in early reading instruction. Hence, this study covering how teachers use language/s in early reading instruction in a multilingual classroom is also needed and warranted.

When it comes to challenges in multilingual classrooms, UNESCO (2023) identified reluctance and resistance towards multilingual education and prominence of

dominant languages in multilingual classrooms as some of these challenges. Using an indigenous language as the language of instruction in Bangladesh is also controversial (Rahman, 2010). In Switzerland, using the mother tongue in class often appears to be superficial, and this could possibly be related to either time constraint or teacher difficulty in utilizing the mother tongues (Peyer et al., 2020). These are just some of the challenges facing multilingualism in classrooms. The challenges faced in a multilingual classroom provide valuable insights into the importance of language diversity and the need for tailored teaching approaches and effective teaching practices.

Studies on teachers' early instruction practices in contexts where more than one language was used by the learners showed that teachers have different ways of teaching early reading. Many factors such as the learner, the teacher, and the environment contributed to the successful teaching of early reading (Desta, 2020; Dlamini & Sheik, 2019; Dubeck et al., 2012; Lewis-Fokum & Thomas, 2018; Suarez et al., 2020; Wagner, 2021). The various studies on teachers' early reading instruction practices employed various research designs, but the majority of them were designed descriptively. Dubeck et al. (2012) reported that teachers considered English as the dominant language among other languages. Desta (2020) and Lewis-Fokum and Thomas (2018) found that teachers favored the teaching of skills more than the whole language approach, and majority of the activities were teacher-directed. Dlamini and Sheik (2019) discovered that teachers used their experiences to support their lack of pedagogical knowledge in teaching reading. Teachers also used an eclectic approach in teaching reading (Suarez et al., 2020). Wagner (2021) revealed that modeling multilingual language practices supported multilingual learners. All of these studies utilized varied data gathering methods such as classroom observations, interviews,

and analysis of documents related to the teaching-learning process. There is also a dearth of recent studies on the topic teachers' early reading instruction practices in the Philippines. Hence, this study will help fill that gap in the literature.

The Philippine Context

National Languages Curricula

Different countries have educational curricula formulated at various levels (national or school level), which outline the subjects and content that learners are expected to learn. These curricula establish clear guidelines and expectations for learners, specifying the knowledge, skills, and attitudes they should gain through their formal education (Mullis & Martin, 2019). The key components of the curriculum and governing policies that are especially important for developing reading skills include the set standards or benchmarks for reading proficiency. An organized sequence of teaching and strategies for improving reading skills involves a shift in focus from decoding to comprehension techniques. It also involves providing learners with diverse reading materials and implementing reasonable strategies to cater to both advanced readers and those who face difficulties (Mullis & Martin, 2019).

Gabe (2012) argued that the primary objective of reading instruction is to integrate essential skills and knowledge into a well-structured reading curriculum. The key components of a well-structured reading curriculum include the following: (1) development of skills related to recognizing and understanding words; (2) extensive vocabulary development; (3) practicing comprehension skills and/or strategies; (4) building awareness of discourse structure; (5) promoting strategic reading; (6) practicing reading fluency; (7) practicing extensive reading; (8) development of reading motivation; and (9) integration of content-reading/learning. Furthermore, Gabe (2012) stated that reading instruction and curriculum have important implications not just for

L1 reading instruction but also for L2 reading instruction. A content and reading curriculum should incorporate numerous reading skills. These skills are reflected in reading tasks and activities that students can regularly practice, utilizing information from various texts to acquire meaningful and new content. The curriculum should include integrated academic language tasks that are aligned with the specific language and literacy instruction that learners have received, preparing them for the real-world academic language demands.

The integrated language arts (Mother Tongue, Filipino, and English) curriculum in the Philippines was conceptualized to provide more in-depth information and elaboration on the areas of knowledge and skills that children need to learn and teachers need to teach (DepEd, 2012b). There are 14 language and literacy domains in the curriculum that are aligned with the five sub-strands of the language arts and multi-literacies curriculum (LAMC)⁹. These 14 domains are:

Oral language, phonological awareness, book and print knowledge, alphabet knowledge, phonics and word recognition, fluency, spelling, writing and composition, grammar awareness and structure, vocabulary development, reading comprehension (schema and prior knowledge, strategies, narrative texts, and informational texts), listening comprehension, attitudes towards language, literacy, and literature, [and] study strategies (DepEd, 2012b, p. 2).

All of these domains are funneled across kindergarten up to the third grade of elementary education. DepEd (2012b) also believed that the Integrated Language Arts Curriculum for Kindergarten to Grade 3 employs an iterative approach to teach the skills, ensuring that the domains and skills are revisited and built upon across grade

⁹ The language arts and multi-literacies curriculum (LAMC) features the interrelated five sub-strands (listening, speaking, reading, writing, and viewing) that act as the foundational elements for the creation of meaning and effective communication across various learning areas (DepEd, 2016a).

levels and different languages (i.e., spiral across grade levels and across languages). This aims to cultivate strong linguistic abilities that will lay a solid groundwork for acquiring more advanced and academic language skills in future learning. The domains of the integrated language and literacy curriculum expect learners to demonstrate learning standards¹⁰ and learning competencies¹¹.

As previously mentioned, there are more than 180 languages in the Philippines (Koyfman, 2019). DepEd, however, only covers 19 languages for MTB-MLE: “Tagalog, Kapampangan, Pangasinan, Iloko, Bikol, Ybanag, Sinugbuanong Binisaya, Hiligaynon, Waray, Bahasa Sug, Maguindanaoan, Maranao, Chavacano, Ivatan, Sambal, Akianon, Kinaray-a, Yakan, and Sinurigaonon” (DepEd, 2016d, para. 3). Monje et al. (2021) found that other languages (e.g., Bolinao) are actually being used by schools as medium of instruction aside from the 19 languages mentioned. DepEd (2016d) also mentioned that MTB-MLE is “implemented in two modules: 1) as a learning/subject area and 2) as medium of instruction” (para. 3). Hence, these local languages are both the subject (Mother Tongue) and the medium of instruction (mother tongue). However, the language in the Mother Tongue subject in school is not necessarily a child's first language (L1) or ‘mother tongue.’

DepEd (2016c) emphasized the importance of a strong mother tongue foundation in children, as it contributes to the development of more proficient literacy skills in the language of instruction at school. These literacy skills are expected to

¹⁰ These are the content standards and performance standards which are expected in all learning areas. Content standards are core content in terms of knowledge or skill that a learner should learn and understand. Performance standards, which are under the content standards, are the works that a learner is expected to be able to do. These also include the achievement, acquisition, and application of the knowledge or skill required by the content standard (DepEd, n.d.)

¹¹ Learning competencies, which are under the performance standards, are the more specific applied knowledge, skills, and values that indicate or validate learning consistent with the broader content and performance standards (DepEd, n.d.)

transfer across other languages. Figure 2 shows the basic elements, concepts, and processes of the MTB-MLE Curriculum Framework.

Figure 2

MTB-MLE Curriculum Framework (DepEd, 2012c)

The DepEd (2016c) MTB-MLE curriculum promotes L1 literacy for cross-lingual transfer. It engages learners in discussion using the language already familiar to them and utilizing their prior experiences. It aims to develop higher order thinking skills and/or critical thinking. It acts as a strong bridge in building confidence and fluency in the other languages used in the classroom. It supports learning when the L2 is not adequately developed to be used independently. It is used for teaching meaning and accuracy in the context of meaningful learning. Two tracks are used for MTB-MLE: the story track (focus on meaning) and primer track (focus on accuracy). In the story track of the sub-strand reading, learners are expected to: “read with understanding to apply,

analyze, evaluate, and to create new knowledge” (p. 5), while in the primer track, learners are expected to: “decode by recognizing parts of words, sentences” (p. 5).

MTB-MLE promotes literacy. Acquiring reading skills in the first language (L1) cultivates abilities that can be transferred to reading in any other language. The use of learners’ prior knowledge is also given space. Promoting active learner participation in discussions revolving around their familiar home language and culture enhances the learning of the curriculum by integrating and applying that knowledge into their existing cognitive frameworks (DepEd, 2016c).

There are eight guiding principles for teaching and learning in MTB-MLE (DepEd, 2016c): “known to the unknown, language and academic development, cognitive development, discovery learning, active learning, meaning and accuracy, language learning and language transfer, [and] affective component: valuing the home language and culture” (pp. 6-9). ‘Known to the unknown’ promotes starting where the children are. ‘Language and academic development’ shows how learners possessing proficient skills in their first language have a higher likelihood of acquiring additional language/s with greater ease and proficiency, thus benefiting their academic performance. ‘Cognitive development’ promotes comprehension that motivates learners to apply, analyze, and evaluate their knowledge, thus generating new knowledge. ‘Discovery learning’ allows learners to use new ideas meaningfully. ‘Active learning’ includes peer interaction, second language learning, and purposeful talk. ‘Meaning and accuracy’ refers to the story track and primer track, respectively. ‘Language learning and language transfer’ acknowledges the time and effort needed to learn another language. ‘Affective component: Valuing the home language and culture’ encourages the use of the learners’ mother tongue (DepEd, 2016c).

The Filipino language curriculum, on the other hand, aims to develop communicative competence, critical and/or reflective analysis, and appreciation of literature through reading materials and technology for national identity, cultural literacy, and continuous learning (DepEd, 2016b). The teaching of Filipino to Grade 1 learners starts at the second quarter of every school year. Figure 3 shows the basic elements, concepts, and processes of the Filipino curriculum framework.

Figure 3

Batayang Konseptuwal na Balangkas sa Pagtuturo ng Filipino [Basic Conceptual Framework in Teaching Filipino] (DepEd, 2016b)

Note. Here are the translations of the phrases/statements in the framework: at the upper left corner, *Mga Batayang Pilosopikal, Legal, at Teoryang Pang-Edukasyon* [Philosophical and Legal Foundations and Educational Theories]; at the upper right corner, *Mga Teorya sa Kalikasan ng Wika, Mga Teorya/Simulain sa Pagsusuring Literari, sa Pagkatuto/Pagtuturo ng Wika (L1, L2, L3), at mga Dulog sa Pagtuturo ng mga Tekstong Palahad at Panitikan* [Theories on the Nature of Language, Theories/Principles in Literary Analysis, Language Learning/Teaching Theories (L1, L2, L3), and Approaches in Teaching Expository Texts and Literature]; at the lower left

corner, *Pangangailangang Panlipunan at Global na Pamayanan* [Social Needs and Global Community]; at the lower right corner, *Kalikasan at Pangangailangan ng Mag-aaral* [Nature and Needs of Learners]; inside the blue box positioned at the right side of the framework, *Buo at Ganap na Filipino na May Kapaki-pakinabang na Literasi* [Complete and Proficient Filipino with Useful Literacy]; outside the three circles, *Suporta ng Lipunan, Pribado, Pampubliko, Midya* [Support from Society, Private, Public, Media], *Suporta ng Tahanan, Pamahalaang Lokal, Administratibo* [Support from Home, Local Government, Administrative], and *Suporta sa Komunidad, Guro, Kagamitang Pangpagtuturo* [Support for the Community, Teachers, Instructional Materials]; in the green circle, *Nakaagapay sa Mabilis na Pagbabagong Nagaganap sa Daigdig* [Adapting to Rapid Changes Occurring in the World]; in the red circle, *Kultural na Literasi* [Cultural Literacy], *Patuloy na Pagkatuto Gamit ang Teknolohiya* [Continuous Learning Using Technology], and *Pambansang Pagkakakilanlan* [National Identity]; in the yellow circle, *Pagpapahalagang Pampanitikan* [Literary Appreciation], *Mapanuri/Replektibong Pagsusuri* [Critical/Reflective Analysis], *Kakayahang Komunikatibo* [Communicative Competence], *Pakikinig* [Listening], *Pagbabasa* [Reading], *Panonood* [Viewing], *Pagsasalita* [Speaking], *Pagsusulat* [Writing]

Since the American colonial period, English has held official status in the Philippines, exerting a profound influence on the nation's history and culture (Martin, 2008). As part of the integrated language arts curriculum, the English curriculum (DepEd, 2016a) shows in its philosophy and rationale how a language serves as the foundation for all forms of communication. It is also the primary tool for thinking and expressing ideas. Also, a language forms the fundamental basis for establishing and nurturing connections between individuals.

There are six guiding principles in the English curriculum (DepEd, 2016a):

- (1) All languages are interrelated and interconnected. Facility in the first language (L1) strengthens and supports the learning of other languages (L2)...
- (2) Language acquisition and learning is an active process that begins at birth and continues throughout life... Students enhance their language abilities by using what they know in new and more complex contexts and with increasing sophistication (spiral progression)...
- (3) Learning requires meaning. Start with what the students know; use that to introduce new concepts. They use

language to examine new experiences and knowledge in relation to their prior knowledge, experiences, and beliefs. (4) Learners learn about language and how to use it effectively through their engagement with and study of texts. The term 'text' refers to any form of written (reading and writing), oral (listening and speaking) and visual communication involving language... (5) Successful language learning involves viewing, listening, speaking, reading and writing activities... [and] (6) Language learning involves recognizing, accepting, valuing, and building on students' existing language competence, including the use of non-standard forms of the language, and extending the range of language available to students. (DepEd, 2016a, pp. 3-4).

Figure 4 shows the different components of the English curriculum.

Figure 4

English Curriculum Framework (DepEd, 2016a)

The English language curriculum has four components (DepEd, 2016a). Component 1, *Learning Processes*, shows the impact of the acquisition and learning of a language. It provides insights into the methods and mechanisms of language learning, thus serving as guiding principles for language teaching. The principle of contextualization ensures that learners acquire the language in genuine and meaningful situations of application through the carefully crafted learning tasks and activities. Lessons are organized based on learning outcomes, thematic elements, or specific types of text to enable learners to effectively utilize relevant language skills, grammatical structures, and vocabulary in both spoken and written forms, while considering the purpose, audience, context, and cultural aspects. Component 2, *Effective Language Use*, describes the necessary knowledge and skill domains, including cultural understanding, language comprehension, and strategic language processes. These competencies are cultivated through the macro-skills of language arts. Component 3, *Make Meaning Through Language*, demonstrates the cultivation of thinking skills and the interconnectedness and mutual influence among the macro-skills of language. Component 4, *Holistic Assessment*, shows the comprehensive assessment approach of the Language Arts and Literacy Curriculum. This assessment serves as feedback to evaluate its efficacy for learners, teachers, school administrators, and curriculum developers. Moreover, the teaching of English to Grade 1 learners only starts at the third quarter of every school year.

When the COVID-19 global health crisis prompted the closure of schools around the world, the learning competencies in the original integrated language arts Mother Tongue, Filipino, and English curricula (DepEd, 2016a; DepEd, 2016b; DepEd, 2016c) were streamlined to most essential learning competencies or MELCs (DepEd, 2020a). These were originally intended to be used for only one school year (2020-

2021). However, the MELCs have been used by schools since then. The original aim was to prioritize instruction using the critical and indispensable competencies that learners need to acquire, considering the potential challenges (e.g., limitations caused by COVID-19) in delivering effective learning. Furthermore, they were intended to alleviate the task of transforming classroom-based learning resources into materials suitable for distance learning (e.g., modular distance learning, blended learning, online learning). Part of the selection process of MELCs from the original curriculum was deciding whether a learning competency should be retained, merged, dropped, or rephrased. Learning competencies were retained when they fulfilled the requirement of 'endurance' (which significantly contributes to lifelong learning and serves as a prerequisite skill for the subsequent grade level). When two or more learning competencies shared the same objective or learning intention, they were merged or clustered together into one comprehensive learning competency. Learning competencies were either dropped or removed when they exhibited a high level of specificity and their phrasing resembled that of a learning objective, and when they were repetitive or recurrent in nature, among other reasons. Some competencies were restated or reworded to be more concise. Teachers were advised to consult the 2016 Curriculum Guides (e.g., DepEd, 2016a; DepEd, 2016b; DepEd, 2016c) as a resource in the unpacking¹² of the MELCs. Teachers were granted flexibility to create learning objectives that they consider essential for their students' cognitive development, as long as they complied with the curriculum standards set by the Department of Education (DepEd, 2020a).

¹² MELCs are expected to be unpacked into learning objectives/competencies based on the 2016 Curriculum, so teachers can organize learning activities systematically and address the diverse needs of learners, effectively tackling the challenges associated with instructional delivery (DepEd, 2020c).

Acquiring the content knowledge in other learning areas was considered in choosing the MELCs in the MT, Filipino, and English subjects to maintain the curricular quality of integration (DepEd, 2020c). The number of learning competencies in the curriculum (DepEd, 2016a; DepEd, 2016b; DepEd, 2016c) had been substantially reduced in the MELCs due to learning competencies' recurrence and their ability to be clustered together (DepEd, 2020a).

MTB-MLE Implementation in the Philippines

As mentioned in this paper's background of the study, the Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) in the Philippines has been implemented for a decade already. It is being implemented in all public schools across the country with its goal to help develop readers and writers by the first grade (DepEd, 2012). MTB-MLE requires utilizing the language that learners are accustomed to (their first language or mother tongue) as the medium of instruction to enable learners to better understand basic concepts with ease. The mother tongue is the language learners are expected to understand best (DepEd, 2016d).

In 2005, the Basic Education Reform Agenda (BESRA), a package of policy reforms aimed to enhanced quality results in education and sustain better performance, was introduced to attain the Education for All (EFA) by 2015 (DepEd, 2005). One of the language and literacy reforms introduced by Ocampo (2006) and her team of researchers from the University of the Philippines under the key result thrust (KRT) 3 'Increase social support for the attainment of desired learning outcomes' is to "implement a developmentally and culturally sound programming of language and literacy development in schools" (p. 48).

The core idea behind this KRT is that individuals who come from various social backgrounds even without specialized training and/or background in professional

education, can both improve the education learners receive in schools and even bolster the support for the teachers and schools, whose job is to facilitate inclusive learning opportunities for everybody (Ocampo, 2006). The critical reforms to support KRT 3 were a product of agreement among different groups of individuals/stakeholders such as public thinkers, teachers, community members, and experts, among others, who considered the Philippines' multilingual context vis-à-vis desired educational aims/outcomes through a series of consultative workshops. Executing an approach to language and literacy development in schools that is both aligned with developmental stages and cultural appropriateness is one of the strategies under the National Language and Literacy Reform. It acknowledges the importance of the learners' experiences, especially in relation to the development of their oral language, acquired through their environment. The language that the learners bring to school should be harnessed to support them when they first enter school:

By beginning the child's informal and formal learning experiences in the language which the child speaks, the school/learning environment respects the child and provides him with all the opportunities to build on what he already knows as he learns new concepts and other languages... The variety of languages in the Philippines must also be reflected in the programming of languages in school so that the society can sustain and maintain its diverse and rich cultures and protect cultural identities. In addition to the mother tongue/local languages and the target languages of learning, Arabic is an important language for Moslem children to learn. It is an additional language to nearly all Moslem children, in the same way that Filipino and English are additional languages to most Filipino children. Programming language

development must begin with the use of the child's language as medium of learning. This gives children all the chances to participate and partake of all social, cognitive, and linguistic experiences from the very beginning of child education (Ocampo, 2006, p. 48).

The recommendations of BESRA confirm the advantages of multilingual education (DepEd, 2009). Hence, in 2009, the Philippine MTB-MLE was institutionalized. Since then, various research studies have been conducted on MTB-MLE.

The United States Agency for International Development (USAID), for example, spearheaded a cross-language MTB-MLE study called the 2014 Philippines EGRA (Early Grade Reading Assessment) study or PhilEd Data II, focusing on teachers' pedagogy, teaching and learning materials, and instructional practices (Pouezevara et al., 2014). The study was conducted in four regions in the country. It was found that teachers needed more training when it comes to mother tongue instruction. There was also a dearth of important literacy materials in the mother tongue. Moreover, a large chunk of time used in teaching learners how to read was allotted for reading practice such as reading chorus. Although most of the sampled learners' home language matched the language of instruction, some of the learners' home language was different from the one used in schools. One of the notable findings showed the strong relationship of MTB-MLE to teaching learners how to read, as evidenced by their reading performance.

The study of Cabansag (2016) showed that stakeholders working closely with MTB-MLE implementation support this language-in-education policy because it is believed to boost better expression of oneself using the language learners know best. It also supports confidence and retention among learners. However, multilingualism

was also believed to be a challenge in MTB-MLE implementation. Teachers then resorted to using Filipino as a common language among the multilingual learners, especially if the teachers themselves had inadequate knowledge in utilizing the first language of the learners. The dominance of the English language also affected the program's implementation because of the stakeholders' concern that arose from the belief that the policy would actually hinder the development of English proficiency among learners. Because learners could have different mother tongues, Llaneta (2018) argued that teachers are encouraged to allot a special time to learners whose first language is different from the one used in class and to collaborate with their parents on creating practices that foster better learning in a multilingual classroom.

Teachers also shared their experiences in teaching MTB-MLE in a study conducted by Medilo, Jr. (2016). They shared that they understood the need to implement this component of the curriculum and further emphasized its importance in building the literacy skills of the learners. However, they also acknowledged the widespread influence of the English language. The teachers favored English as the language and representation of intellectual and material superiority. They also tended to undermine learners who are unable to speak and/or communicate in English, which is an inappropriate mindset for the successful implementation of MTB-MLE.

Monje et al. (2021) conducted a process evaluation of the MTB-MLE program implementation. The study dug into the program theory, service delivery and utilization, and program organization of the language policy. Eighteen (18) randomly selected schools around the country participated in the study. Data were gathered through interviews with key stakeholders, focus group discussions with teachers and parents, and use of online survey. Observations were also conducted. The results specified that the challenges of MTB-MLE implementation range from conceptual to

implementational. Four basic activities are expected for a successful implementation of MTB-MLE: (1) writing of big books; (2) developing the orthography; (3) writing the grammar; and (4) writing the dictionary of the language. Results showed that less than 10 percent of schools were found to be implementing the program in line with the activities that are expected to guide MTB-MLE implementation. In 2017-2018, only one-third of the schools in the country were implementing the program. Reasons for this included lack of teaching materials, no dictionary of the language, lack of learners' textbooks, teachers' inadequacy in the language, and parents, teachers, and school officials not supporting the school's chosen MOI. Other challenges identified were the linguistic diversity in the classroom and funding issues in the procurement and development of learning materials. Although teachers believed that MTB-MLE connects learners to their roots, they believed that the English language is superior to other local languages because of both academic and economic reasons. Teachers believed that since the majority of academic content is presented in English, it is logical and reasonable to acquire knowledge in that language. They mentioned that English is used in competitions, not the mother tongue. They also thought that being skilled in English leads to higher earnings. They also suggested that intense focus on learning the mother tongue and less time intended for English learning impair learners' opportunity to benefit from the economic advantages offered by English. It was also observed that translanguaging happened all the time in the classroom.

Tupas and Lorente (2014) revealed that the old bilingual education policy of the Philippines, where Filipino and English were specifically used, contributed to the promotion of Filipino and not just of English:

Tagalog-based Filipino through bilingual education increasingly became widespread across the archipelago and took root in the lives of many Filipinos

especially through the media and popular culture. The same national language has served as lingua franca among Filipino workers scattered all over the world. Although still resisted along ethnolinguistic lines, research has shown that majority of Filipinos have come to accept the Filipino language as the country's national language (Tupas & Lorente, 2014, p. 174).

Tupas (2015) contended that, despite the mandated implementation of MTB-MLE, the policy faces substantial obstacles that include both ideological and structural dimensions:

It is not automatic that teaching the mother tongues or using them as languages of instruction reflects positive attitudes towards them; MTB-MLE in this sense is ultimately about transforming social and educational infrastructures which tolerate and breed harmful language attitudes and ideologies. The point is this: if we teach with and through the mother tongues with the belief that our pupils or students learn best through them, but nevertheless underestimate or disregard the realities of inequalities of multilingualism which embed our own teaching and learning, then MTB-MLE will not go too far. While MTB-MLE is meant for the classroom, the real battleground is bigger than the classroom where speakers of languages are distributed across unequal social spaces and relations through which they espouse ideologies which either help them wield power over others or keep them firmly entrenched in conditions of unfreedom (Tupas, 2015, p. 121).

Tupas and Martin (2017) further argued that the use of mother tongues in schools is continued to be challenged. In the context of the old bilingual education policy there was a need to present the use of mother tongues as a more attractive proposition to all those involved in education. They also presented that one of the

prevailing challenges to the language-in-education policy is the attitude towards the English language. The English language remains widely embraced by a significant majority of Filipinos as the sole means by which they acquire scientific knowledge and achieve economic stability. When it comes to the dominance of the Filipino language, it is further argued:

The implications of the privileging of the educational argument over the cultural one have been politically and discursively massive. Filipino is not the mother tongue of a majority of Filipinos so it cannot be that it is the language most familiar to most Filipino pupils. Consequently, the issue of Filipino as the national language has been decoupled from the issue of Filipino as MOI. As mentioned earlier, several studies have shown that resistance to Filipino as the national language has waned, although this cannot be said about Filipino as MOI. What this means is that a national language does not automatically make it the most viable and appropriate MOI. What this also means is that nation-building is not the exclusive dominion of Filipino; the imagining of the nation is also possible through the mother tongues (Tupas & Martin, 2017, p. 7).

Summary and Insights

The Philippines' integrated language arts curriculum (Mother Tongue, Filipino, and English) was designed to offer comprehensive knowledge and skills in languages, aligning with language arts and multi-literacies curriculum (LAMC) sub-strands. This curriculum involves 14 language and literacy domains, ranging from oral language to study strategies. These domains follow an iterative approach across grade levels and languages. The language arts curriculum aims to establish a strong linguistic foundation, especially for the acquisition of other languages. It underscores the significance of a rich mother tongue foundation in developing proficient literacy skills,

with the expectation of skill transfer to other languages (DepEd, 2012b; DepEd, 2016a; DepEd, 2016b; DepEd, 2016c). Amid the global COVID-19 crisis, schools worldwide were closed. The learning competencies in the original K-12 curriculum guides were streamlined into the most essential learning competencies (MELCs), initially intended for a single academic year (2020-2021) (DepEd, 2020a). However, schools continued to use the MELCs beyond that timeframe. This adjustment aimed to prioritize critical competencies.

The recommendations of BESRA supported the institutionalization of MTB-MLE in the Philippines. Although the benefits of MTB-MLE have been identified, different challenges continue to confront its implementation. Problems such as teachers' lack of training (Monje et al., 2021; Pouezevara et al., 2014), lack of learning materials (Monje et al., 2021; Pouezevara et al., 2014), dominance of official languages (Cabansag, 2016; Medilo, Jr., 2016; Monje et al., 2021; Pouezevara et al., 2014; Tupas, 2015; Tupas & Laurente, 2014; Tupas & Martin, 2017), resistance towards the mother tongue (Monje et al., 2021; Tupas, 2015), and linguistic diversity (Cabansag, 2016; Monje, et al., 2021; Pouezevara et al., 2014), among others, hound MTB-MLE. Despite being supported by bodies of research, the legitimacy of MTB-MLE continues to be questioned. This would aggravate the questionable implementation of this language-in-education policy. This could also result in educational, cultural, and linguistic consequences that may hinder learners' holistic development, access to quality education, and the preservation of linguistic and cultural diversity in communities. In this paper (especially in the results section), the capitalized 'Mother Tongue' was used to refer to how DepEd defines it in the MTB-MLE policy and curriculum (i.e., learning area). Although the lower-case 'mother tongue' is

synonymous to first language, it was also used primarily in this paper to refer to the local language as first language and as medium of instruction.

Conceptual Framework

The figure below illustrates the relationship of teachers' language ideologies to their early reading instruction practices in the early grades multilingual classroom.

Figure 5

The Relationship Between Teachers' Language Ideologies and their Use of Language/s in Early Reading Instruction in the Early Grades Multilingual Classroom

In the context of primary grades multilingual classrooms, a part of the interaction in the reading process between the teacher and the learners is specified as the teachers' early reading instruction practices in the local language and the

languages Filipino and English, as shown in Figure 1. Teachers' use of language/s is part of early reading instruction. The arrow pointing to it refers to how the teachers' language ideologies, both hegemonic and counter-hegemonic views in using the local language alongside English and Filipino, are reflected in their use of language/s in early reading instruction.

Definition of Terms

Counter-hegemonic views. These are the teachers' language assumptions that support language diversity and language equality, which were primarily determined through the teacher interviews.

Early reading instruction practices. These refer to the teachers' practices involving the conduct of the teaching of reading in multilingual classrooms, as primarily determined through teacher interviews, and validated by class observations, review of relevant documents (e.g., teachers' lesson plans and instructional materials), and focus group discussions.

Hegemonic views. These are the teachers' language assumptions that negate language diversity and language equality, which were primarily determined through the teacher interviews.

Language ideologies. These are the teachers' perceptions about the use of the local language, Filipino, and English in multilingual reading classes, as primarily determined through the teacher interviews, and validated by class observations, review of relevant documents (e.g., teachers' lesson plans and instructional materials), and focus group discussions.

Local language. This refers to the language used predominantly by the speakers in the research context. This refers to Bolinao, Iloko, or Pangasinan. This also refers to

the language used as the mother tongue in early grades multilingual classrooms. It was identified by conducting the background questionnaire.

Multilingual classroom. This is the lower elementary classroom of Grades 1-3 levels where the local language Iloko or Pangasinan or Bolinao alongside Filipino and English is used in the teaching-learning process.

Multilingual learners. These refer to the Grades 1-3 learners who are taught to read in three languages: local language, Filipino, and English.

Reading teachers. These refer to the participants of the study who teach in an early grade (Grade 1, 2, or 3) multilingual classroom using the local language alongside Filipino and English.

Use of languages. This refers to how the teacher utilizes (a) language/s in early reading instruction, as determined through the teacher interviews, class observations, and focus group discussions.

Chapter III

METHODOLOGY

This chapter discusses the research design, participants and research locale, research instruments, data gathering procedure (including ethical considerations), and data analysis procedure.

Research Design

This study employed a qualitative descriptive research design (e.g., Desta, 2020; Dubeck et al., 2012). The ethnographic studies of Daugaard (2020), Ganuza and Hedman (2015), Parba (2018), and Phyak (2013) were also qualitative descriptive in nature. Qualitative descriptive research describes the participants and their situation, and it answers the research questions what, when, where, and how (McCombes, 2019). Semi-structured interviews, class observations, documents review, and focus group discussions (FGDs) were conducted to gather data on how the teachers view the use of the local language with other languages and what their early reading instruction practices in their multilingual classrooms look like. The transcriptions of the recordings of the interviews and focus group discussions and the information from class observations and documents related to early reading instruction were qualitatively examined. Through this data analysis, the trends and themes in the teachers' language ideologies and early reading instruction practices were identified and thoroughly examined.

Participants and Research Locale

This study used purposive sampling, which is widely used in qualitative research (Patton, 2002) (e.g., Lewis-Fokum & Thomas, 2018; Parba, 2018). Purposive sampling is a method where the researcher selects samples for the purpose of the

research (McCombes, 2021). The characteristics of the intended participants were used in the selection of the research sample. For the current study, potential participants needed to be teaching the Mother Tongue subject, Filipino subject, and English subject. This was determined by pre-interviewing the possible teacher-participants. The participants of the study were public elementary school teachers (e.g., Dlamini & Sheik, 2019; Parba, 2018) who taught early grades (Grades 1-3) in the province of Pangasinan, Philippines.

The current literature on average supports nine participants for teachers' language ideologies; hence, for this research study, nine (9) were initially tapped to participate; at least three teachers were considered for each of the primary grade levels. However, 13 teachers were able to participate. There were five teacher-participants who were Grade 1 teachers, four who were Grade 2 teachers, and another four who were Grade 3 teachers. The three languages used in mother tongue instruction were represented in every grade level. Kindergarten teachers were not included/selected as participants because kindergartens only use the mother tongue in their subject Language, Literacy, and Communication. They don't have Filipino and English subjects yet (DepEd, 2016e).

Public school teachers were tapped to participate in this research because they use the local language in mother tongue instruction, unlike several private schools in the province (especially in urban areas) that use Filipino and English in their mother tongue instruction.

In Table 1, the participants are listed according to the order of the interviews conducted. The table provides a brief overview of the participants. The letters of the alphabet were used as pseudonyms, thus protecting the participants' privacy. Six of the participants belonged to the Iloko group, three to the Bolinao group, and four to

the Pangasinan group. The average age of the participants was 36, the average years teaching in the current grade level was eight years, and the average years in service was 11 years. All the participants were female. Only one of them held a master teacher position, while most of them are level III teachers (77%).

The majority of the participants' first language is the language of the community, with the exception of Participants B and D. All of the participants' second language is Filipino, and their third is English. Almost half of them have already earned their master's degree in education while the other half of the participants have completed the academic requirements (CAR) for their master's. Those who were able to pursue higher education beyond their bachelor's degree in elementary education majored in either educational administration or educational management. Most of them (77%) spent only eight hours on MTB-MLE training, 15% spent 24 hours on MTB-MLE training, and 8% did not have any MTB-MLE training at all. In addition, most of them (62%) did not have training on literacy.

Table 1*Demographic Information of the Participants*

Participants	Mother Tongue Group	Age	Gender	Years Teaching in the Current Grade Level	Years in Service	First Language	Second Language	Third Language	Highest Educational Attainment	MTB-MLE Training ¹³ in Hours	Literacy Training ¹⁴ in Hours
A	Iloko	34	F ¹⁵	6	10	Iloko	Filipino	English	Bachelor's	8	0
B	Iloko	23	F	3	3	Filipino	Iloko	English	MA Units	8	0
C	Iloko	58	F	25	33	Iloko	Filipino	English	MAEd CAR	24	16
D	Iloko	47	F	10	13	Filipino	Iloko	English	MAEd CAR	8	16
E	Bolinao	31	F	4	4	Bolinao	Filipino	English	MAEd CAR	0	0
F	Bolinao	28	F	4	4	Bolinao	Filipino	English	MAEd	8	0
G	Bolinao	41	F	10	19	Bolinao	Filipino	English	MAEd	24	0
H	Iloko	46	F	10	15	Iloko	Filipino	English	MAEd CAR	8	0
I	Iloko	26	F	4	4	Iloko	Filipino	English	MAEd CAR	8	0
J	Pangasinan	29	F	5	7	Pangasinan	Filipino	English	PhD	8	24
K	Pangasinan	27	F	4	4	Pangasinan	Filipino	English	MEd ¹⁶	8	0
L	Pangasinan	39	F	12	14	Pangasinan	Filipino	English	MEd	8	8
M	Pangasinan	35	F	8	10	Pangasinan	Filipino	English	MAEd ¹⁷	8	8

¹³ Curriculum-related (e.g., competencies)

¹⁴ Approaches, methods, strategies in literacy instruction

¹⁵ Female

¹⁶ Master of Education

¹⁷ Master of Arts in Education

Based on the language data of the learners involved in this study encoded in DepEd's Learner Information System (LIS) for school year 2022-2023, the first language of 86% of the learners in the Bolinao group is the Bolinao language, the first language of 87% of the learners in the Iloko group is the Iloko language, and the first language of 71% of the learners in the Pangasinan group is the Pangasinan language. Learners who do not belong to the percentages mentioned have a different first language or are transferees.

Languages of Instruction in the Research Locale

The chosen research locale, Pangasinan, has three different languages for mother tongue instruction in public schools: Pangasinan, Iloko, and Bolinao, making it an interesting research context. Nineteen (19) major languages across the country are being used in MTB-MLE, and these include Pangasinan and Iloko (DepEd, 2016d). Other mediums of instruction are also being used in Philippine schools (Monje et al., 2021). The Bolinao language is used in some island schools in Bolinao, Pangasinan because it is the language of the community (R. Caalaman, personal communication, April 14, 2022). The Province of Pangasinan (n.d.) also claims that:

English and Filipino are widely spoken and are the mediums of instruction in all schools. Ilocano¹⁸ is the major dialect [*sic*] spoken by a greater portion of the population in the western and eastern areas. There is some fear that the Pangasinan dialect [*sic*], spoken predominantly in the central areas, is losing its hold on the local tongue. Bolinao, at the northernmost tip of western Pangasinan has a unique language of its own, also called Bolinao.

¹⁸ Ilocano is just a variation of the Iloko language. Other variations of the name of this language include Ilokano and Iloco (Gorlinski, n.d.). However, in the official list of the 19 languages used in MTB-MLE, DepEd uses Iloko (DepEd, 2016d).

It is also important to note that “Filipino and other Philippine languages have transparent orthography” (Alonzo, 2015, p. 4).

Bolinao Language

Bolinao is an endangered native language of the Philippines (Ethnologue, n.d.a). It is spoken in the northwestern region of the town of the same name, Bolinao, and also in the town of Anda, the only island town of Pangasinan. Bolinao is also used by the local residents on the island of Santiago, which they refer to as ‘Isla,’ a word that translates to *island* in their language (Del Corro, 2015). The writing system follows the Latin alphabet.

The Bolinao language, also known as Binobolinao, belongs to the Zambali language group and exhibits a strong linguistic affinity with the Sambali¹⁹ language. Bolinao is part of the Austronesian²⁰ language family. Despite the impact of Pilipino (now Filipino) taught in the schools, the Bolinao language has also experienced significant modification due to the dominant impact of Iloko language. While it was previously influenced by Pangasinan, its main linguistic influences come from the two aforementioned languages (Persons, 1978).

Historically, Bolinao possessed a total of 20 phonemes, consisting of five vowels and 15 consonants. The following vowels are pronounced as follows: *a* as /a/; *e* as /ə/; *i* as /i/; *o* as /o/; and *u* as /u/. Vowels, when in sequence, are pronounced individually. The consonants *b, k, d, g, h, l, m, n, ng, p, r, s, t, w,* and *y* are pronounced

¹⁹Also belonging to the Malayo-Polynesian family, Zambal/Sambal is primarily spoken in the Province of Zambales, located in Central Luzon, Philippines.

²⁰ The Austronesian languages, previously known as Malayo-Polynesian languages, constitute a language family spoken across a vast region, including the majority of the Indonesian archipelago, the entire Philippines, Madagascar, and the island groups in the Central and South Pacific (excluding Australia and significant portions of New Guinea). Additionally, they are spoken in extensive areas of Malaysia, as well as in scattered regions of Vietnam, Cambodia, Laos, and Taiwan. Due to the sheer number of languages, it covers and its extensive geographic distribution, the Austronesian language family ranks among the world's largest language families (Blust, 2023).

with a short *ä* vowel. There are five diphthongs in Bolinao, involving a vowel and either of the consonant *w* or *y*. These diphthongs are pronounced as follows: *ay* as /ī/; *aw* or *ao* as /aü/; *ey* as /əy/; *iw* as /ēw/; *oy* as /òi/; and *uy* as /üy/ (Binubolinao, n.d.). Syllables have two basic patterns: consonant-vowel (CV) and consonant-vowel-consonant (CVC) (Persons, 1978). Bolinao language follows a simple orthography:

The Bolinao orthography is simple that it only employs the existing symbols used in Tagalog orthography. It consists of 28 letters: *a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i, j, k, l, m, n, ñ, ng, o, p, q, r, s, t, u, v, w, x, y, z*. The use of *f, v,* and *z* can be seen in borrowed words or proper names such as *Villareal, Zaragosa, fiesta,* and *del Fierro*. The letters *ñ* and *x* are included in the Bolinao orthography, but no examples were given for each letter. The letter *c* formerly represents [k] in the old orthography and is retained in Bolinao proper names and words: *picocobuan* ‘place where one rides the boat going to the islands’ and *Catawan* ‘God’. The glottal stop is represented by the apostrophe (‘) in the initial, medial and final positions: *‘ampi’ikap* ‘living/playing’, *ke’en* ‘will go to’, *ba’yo* ‘new’, *tekre’* ‘sit’, and *bale’* ‘but’ (Villareal, 2020, p. 31).

Iloko Language

Iloko language also belongs to the Austronesian language family (Ethnologue, n.d.b). It has five vowels (*a, e, i, o, u*) and 17 consonants (*b, d, f, g, h, k, l, m, n, ng, p, r, s, t, w, y*) (Constantino, 1971). The Komisyon sa Wikang Filipino (2019), however, acknowledges the 26 letters of the Filipino alphabet as the same letters for the Iloko language. In Iloko, it is possible for two consonants to come together and form a cluster at the start of a syllable, particularly when the cluster appears at the beginning of a word. The majority of these initial consonant clusters in Ilokano are observed in words that have been borrowed from other languages. Iloko has several rising diphthongs,

namely *ay*, *aw*, *uy*, *oy*, *ey*, and *iw*. Moreover, it includes all falling diphthongs except for *wu* and *wo*. The language follows a basic orthography: the letters are represented by symbols of the phonemes; an accent mark is used to indicate stress; question marks (?) are used for questions, and period (.) for declarative statements; capitalization is used for the first letter of the sentence and for proper nouns (Constantino, 1971).

Pangasinan Language

Pangasinan exhibits close linguistic connections with just four small languages from the Southern Cordilleran group. These languages include Ibaloy, Karaw, Kalanguya, and Ilongo. Pangasinan stands out from other Philippine languages due to its distinct lexicon. While it shares a similar number of loanwords from Sanskrit, Malay, Arabic, Spanish, and English with other major Philippine languages, what sets it apart is the higher influx of loanwords from Chinese (predominantly Fujian). This increased borrowing from Chinese is a result of a long-standing and profound Chinese influence in the area (Anderson & Anderson, 2007).

Pangasinan follows the Roman alphabet²¹. The standard five vowel letters are employed to represent four or five (and potentially even six for certain speakers) distinct vowel sounds. Letter *e* is pronounced in two ways (/e/ and /ə/). Letters *o* and *u* sometimes use only one significant phoneme. If a vowel is followed by the same vowel (e.g., *a* is followed by *a*), they can be merged to create a single long vowel. Likewise, stressed vowels can be prolonged, and a vowel at the end of a sentence or phrase, before a significant pause, is always extended (Benton, 1971). There are 28 letters in the Pangasinan alphabet, with five vowels (*a*, *e*, *i*, *o*, *u*) and 23 consonants

²¹ Also known as Latin alphabet

(*b, c, d, f, g, h, j, k, l, m, n, ñ, ng, p, q, r, s, t, v, w, x, y, and z*). The alphabet is pronounced using the English phonetic system, with the exception of the Spanish *ñ* (Pangasinan Historical and Cultural Commission, 2016). In Pangasinan, a syllable comprises a vowel, either in isolation or surrounded by a limited number of consonants, and is characterized by a single stress. Every word in Pangasinan is composed of a central element or root word. This root can function independently as a standalone word, or it can be combined with one or more affixes to create a complete word (Benton, 1971).

Filipino Language

There are 28 letters in the modern Filipino alphabet (five vowels and 23 consonants). Each of the letters represents a sound and follows the English phonemic system, with the exception of *ñ* (Spanish). The vowels need the consonant to form a syllable. A syllable can be formed by using one vowel. However, there is only one vowel in every syllable, but there could be more than one consonant in every syllable (e.g., *bi-be* [duckling]; *tsart* [chart]) (Komisyon sa Wikang Filipino, 2013).

English Language

Although the English language contains only 26 letters, it encompasses around 44 distinct sounds, referred to as phonemes. There are 20 vowel sounds, and 24 consonant sounds (The Reading Well, n.d.). In contrast to the Philippine languages, the English orthography is marked by significant irregularities and inconsistencies in how letters and sounds are related. This includes numerous cases where a single letter represents multiple sounds, instances where single sounds correspond to multiple different letters, and combinations of letters representing single sounds (Miller, 2019).

Data Sources

Demographic Questionnaire

This instrument was initially used to gather information regarding the participants' demographic profile. The questionnaire covers the participant's name, school where the participant teaches, age, gender, years in service, teaching position, grade level being taught, years teaching in the current grade level, subjects being taught, highest educational attainment and major of study, and number of days/hours trainings related to MTB-MLE and literacy instruction. It also includes the language/s (i.e., first language, second language, and third language) spoken by the participant. See Appendix A for the Demographic Questionnaire.

Semi-structured Interviews

Two sets of semi-structured interviews (e.g., Daugaard, 2020; Dlamini & Sheik, 2019; Parba, 2018) were prepared, one for the first research question and another set for the second research question. The participants spent at least an hour for these two sets of interviews.

A semi-structured interview method that allows changing of direction, asking other questions, and expanding one's answers (Doyle, 2020) was used with each of the participants. A semi-structured interview format specifically allows more open-ended questions and discussions (Cotien & Manion, 1994).

The language the participants were comfortable using was utilized. The semi-structured interview questions were developed based on the related literature, and to determine their content validity and functionality, they were reviewed by three experts and pilot tested on three teachers. Revisions were made after the experts' review and pilot testing. The interview questions were also guided by the Interview Protocol

Refinement Framework (Castillo-Montoya, 2016). For environmental familiarity, the interviews were conducted in the teaching context of the participants.

The first set of semi-structured interviews covered the teachers' language ideologies. These interviews focused on language exclusion and inclusion, opinions on the languages used in MTB-MLE and on MTB-MLE in general, and language hierarchies. The second set of semi-structured interviews covered the teachers' early reading instruction practices. These interviews focused on the effective practices in teaching beginning reading based on the review of related literature, the "Big Six" of reading and how these are included in early reading instruction (Konza, 2014), and the use of languages in teaching beginning reading. They were audio recorded and transcribed for analysis. A research assistant helped the researcher in the transcription of the interview data. The research assistant was also required to take a course on research ethics [Tri-Council Policy Statement: Ethical Conduct for Research Involving Humans (TCPS 2)]. See Appendix B for the Interview Schedule for Teachers' Language Ideologies. See Appendix C for the Interview Schedule for Teachers' Early Reading Instruction Practices.

Class Observations

Announced class observation method was also utilized. The observations (e.g., Dubeck et al., 2012) were a combination of face-to-face observations and video-recorded observations. Observation is the procedure of collecting data needed for research by focusing on specific participants (Gall et al., 2003), considering more of what they do instead of what they say. Naturalistic observation techniques allow the researcher to study spontaneous behaviors of the participants (McLeod, 2015).

Class observations were conducted to collect information to see first-hand the teachers' use of language/s and early reading instruction practices. Each of the

teacher-participants was observed at least three times in each language she taught. There was a total of 76 class observations in all, covering the local languages (Iloko and Pangasinan), Filipino, and English. Twelve (12) class observations covered Pangasinan reading lessons (six in Grade 1, three in Grade 2, and three in Grade 3). Eighteen (18) class observations were spent for Iloko reading lessons (six in Grade 1, six in Grade 2, and six in Grade 3). Twenty-seven (27) class observations covered the Filipino reading lessons (eight in Grade 1, ten in Grade 2, and nine in Grade 3). Nineteen (19) reading lessons in English were also observed (ten in Grade 2 and nine in Grade 3). The observations were scheduled one month apart. Dubeck et al. (2012) conducted only 24 observations in their study on Kenyan teachers' reading instruction practices.

The Iloko group of teachers chose to video record their reading lessons. The Pangasinan group of teachers initially wanted to teach their MT reading lessons using the Filipino language. The school principal was in favor of this idea, but the district supervisor opposed it and emphasized the use of the mandated medium of instruction which was the Pangasinan language. For the first two weeks of the school year 2022-2023, the Bolinao group of teachers were still using the Bolinao language as the language of instruction. However, after the first two weeks, the MOI became Filipino. It was a sudden change, because the Bolinao language had been used by some of the schools in Bolinao, Pangasinan since the start of MTB-MLE implementation (as part of localizing the language-in-education policy).

During the observation process, the researcher took notes and used these notes in the data analysis process to answer the research questions. The reading instruction observables were parallel to the questions in the second set of semi-

structured interviews to establish consistency and trustworthiness in the study. See Appendix D for the Classroom Observation Protocol.

Documents Review

Review and analysis of the school curriculum (MT curriculum, Filipino curriculum, and English curriculum), teachers' lesson plans in subjects where reading was taught, and the learners' materials (i.e., textbooks/instructional materials) were conducted to validate the data from the interviews and class observations (e.g., Dlamini & Sheik, 2019). Data revealed through the observation process were compared to the lesson plans that were gathered to see if the participant delivered the lessons consistently with the lesson plan; this allowed the researcher to determine the consistency of the data, especially on teachers' use of languages and their early reading instruction practices. These documents were read and studied thoroughly. The researcher collected at least three lesson plans in each of the languages taught, per participant. Moreover, the researcher also took photographs of the teaching materials in reading.

Focus Group Discussions

Focus group discussions were also used to triangulate the data from the first two research questions; these were used to primarily support the third research question. FGD guide questions were based on the results of the interviews, class observations, and documents review. The FGD questions were developed according to the guidelines specified by Douglass et al. (2022) and Krueger (2002). These guidelines include using open-ended questions, avoiding dichotomous questions, rarely using why questions, and using 'think back' questions, among others. Douglass et al. (2022) and Krueger (2002) also provided examples of generic questions that the

researcher used as pattern. In FGDs, the researcher moderates and facilitates the group discussion on a specific issue (Nyumba et al., 2018), such as how teachers' reading instruction practices (especially their use of languages) are influenced by/reflected in how they view the languages used in their classroom. The FGDs were also audio recorded and transcribed.

There were three FGDs conducted (one for the Iloko group, one for the Bolinao group, and one for the Pangasinan group). The classification of participants based on their school's selected MOI was crucial in ensuring their ease and comfort during the discussions. Each of the FGDs was allocated a minimum of one hour. The FGDs were also held in the participants' workplace to create a sense of familiarity.

The results of the first two research questions were revealed to the participants through the FGDs. The teacher-participants were asked about their opinions regarding the data. For instance, if a teacher's language ideologies were hegemonic or counter-hegemonic and these were reflected in their use of language/s in their early reading instruction practices, they were asked to support or negate this by allowing them to further explain the connection of their language ideologies and their use of language/s in teaching beginning reading. The FGDs were also used for clarifications. For instance, if a teacher's language ideologies were hegemonic, and their use of language/s in early reading instruction was actually counter-hegemonic (or vice versa), they were asked to support or negate this by allowing them to explain further the connection of their language ideologies and their use of language/s in early reading instruction. See Appendix E for the Focus Group Discussion Guide Questions.

Data Collection Procedure

When the research proposal had been evaluated by the designated University of the Philippines Open University – Master of Arts in Language and Literacy

Education Program Faculty and granted the approval needed to conduct the study, the first step in the data collection process was to obtain permission and recommendation to conduct the study from the schools division superintendent (see Appendix F and Appendix G) and public schools district supervisors of the districts where the schools in this study were located (see Appendix H). The researcher visited different schools districts. Once permission and recommendation had been granted to the researcher, the purpose of the research was discussed to the school heads; information about the school was also gathered through them (see Appendix I and Appendix J). The chosen MOI and the school heads' willingness to have their schools and/or teachers be included in this study were primary factors in the initial selection of schools. Then, it was discussed with the teachers. Before data gathering was conducted, consent from the teacher-participants was obtained after they had been assured of data confidentiality and anonymity (see Appendix K). The aim of the study, the risks and benefits, and the participants' role were also explained to them through the study information and consent sheet adapted from Burton (2013). Consent from the learners' parents/guardians and learners' assent were obtained before the conduct of class observation. The letter given to the parents included a confirmation slip indicating their permission to have their child observed (see Appendix M). The learners were asked to write their name on the assent form to indicate their permission to be included in the observations (see Appendix L). The FGDs were conducted using prepared guide questions, after the data from the first two research questions had been obtained. See Table 2 for the Timeline of the Research Data Collection.

Table 2*Timeline of the Research Data Collection*

Component	Activity	Time Frame	Date
Invitation to Participate in the Research	Secure recommendation from DepEd division superintendent, district supervisors, and school heads	2 Weeks	May 16 - June 10, 2022
	Secure consent from possible teacher-participants	2 Weeks	June 1 - 20, 2022
	Secure learners' assent and their parents' consent	2 Weeks	August 22 - September 2, 2022
Interviews	Conduct interview of teachers on their language ideologies and early reading instruction practices	1 Month	July - August 2022
Class Observations	Conduct announced class observations of reading instruction	3 Months	September - December 2022
Documents Review	Conduct review of relevant documents such as the curriculum and lesson plans used in reading instruction	3 Months	September – January 2022
Focus Group Discussions	Conduct focus group discussions to validate the data	1 Week	May 22-24, 2023

Data Analysis Procedure

Table 3 outlines the summary of data sources for each of the research questions. It also shows how these data were analyzed.

Table 3*Summary of Data Sources and Analyses*

Research Questions	Data Sources	Analysis
What are the teachers' language ideologies on the use of the local language alongside Filipino and English as the language of instruction in early reading classes?	Semi-structured interviews	Content/Thematic
	Class observations, documents review, focus group discussions	Used for validation
What are the teachers' early reading instruction practices in the local language, Filipino, and English?	Semi-structured interviews	Content/Thematic
	Class observations, documents review, focus group discussions	Used for validation
Are the teachers' language ideologies reflected in their use of language/s in early reading instruction?	Results of the first and second research question	Content/Thematic
	Focus group discussions	Used for validation

The aim of the data analysis was to identify the teachers' language ideologies and early reading instruction practices, and to understand whether these language ideologies are reflected in the teachers' use of language/s in early reading instruction. The process of data analysis was both emergent and continuous, constructed gradually and systematically from the very beginning up to writing the final version of this study. After the completion of the interview transcripts, the researcher proceeded to organize and prepare the data for analysis. The researcher personally transcribed the semi-structured interviews (as the primary sources of the codes), with the assistance of a research assistant in the transcription process. Once the data had

been transcribed, the researcher engaged in a thorough process of familiarization by repeatedly reading and reviewing the data. The researcher thoroughly immersed himself in the data to obtain a comprehensive understanding of the findings, allowing him to grasp the larger context and patterns within them. Then, the transcripts were uploaded to Atlas.ti, a QDA software, after the manual coding. The uploaded transcripts were reviewed for accuracy. See Appendix N for the complete list of RQ1 codes and sample data excerpts. See Appendix O for the complete list of RQ2 codes and sample data excerpts.

The codes from which the themes were extracted were initially collected from the semi-structured interview transcripts, as the semi-structured interviews were the primary sources of data. Thematic analysis was applied using King and Horrocks' (2010) basic thematic analysis system and Wong's (2008), which is seen in Figure 6, qualitative analysis flowchart.

Figure 6

Qualitative Analysis Flowchart (Adapted from Wong, 2008)

Generating Initial Codes

After gaining familiarity with the data, the researcher proceeded to generate initial codes from the data by identifying similarities in meanings, characteristics, or patterns. The aim was to identify as many codes as possible that could contribute to the research. During the first step which was descriptive coding, the segments of the

semi-structured interview transcripts that aligned more closely with the research questions were identified. This enabled the researcher to gain a comprehensive understanding of the semi-structured interviews prior to analyzing them in smaller sections. In the second stage, known as interpretive coding, the coding process assumed a more focused role in identifying data that could be categorized into distinct groups based on their thematic similarities. The researcher iteratively repeated this process until no new codes emerged or until saturation was achieved. This involved continually analyzing the data, generating codes, and reviewing their relevance and comprehensiveness, ensuring that all significant aspects were captured within the coding framework. Simultaneous coding or double coding was also utilized to an excerpt of data when a single code was insufficient to accurately represent it. This was also done to show the interrelationship among codes. Table 4 shows examples of the generated codes.

Table 4*Generating Codes – Example*

Text	Code
<p>May mga halimbawa d’yan. Halimbawa, Sir, ‘agburburek.’ ‘Agburburek adia’y danum.’ Hindi na maintindihan ng bata ‘yan, Sir. Eh di i-translate mo na naman sa Filipino ‘yan para maintindihan. [There are examples of that. For example, Sir, ‘agburburek’ (‘boiling’). ‘Agburburek adia’y danum.’ [‘The water is boiling.’] Learners can no longer understand that, Sir. So, you have to translate it into Filipino for them to understand it.]</p>	<p>Language Difficulty, Translation</p>
<p>“Sa sounds po talaga magsisimula. Basic po ‘yun.” [“It really starts with sounds. That’s the basic idea.”].</p>	<p>Sounds</p>
<p>Ang kagandahan po ng isang print-rich na classroom ay kahit saan ka lumingon ay marami kang babasahin. Then ‘yong mga babasahin ay hindi po siya mahihirap lang. Ang kagandahan po ng ganu’n ay ‘yong bata syempre ay susubukan niya pantigin ‘yong mga words o ‘yong words na nakikita niya. [The beauty of a print-rich classroom is that wherever you look, there are many things to read. And the reading materials are not just difficult ones. The good thing about it is that children naturally try to syllabicate the words they see.]</p>	<p>Learning Environment</p>

Searching for Themes

Once the initial codes were established, the researcher consolidated them based on their similarities and meanings, leading to the creation of second-level codes or categories. Subsequently, the researcher assigned names to the categories based on their grouping into similar themes. This led to the establishment of overarching themes. These broader themes were of a more abstract nature and drew upon the study's theoretical framework and general research questions. There are no rigid or universally defined rules regarding what constitutes a theme. The process of identifying themes is subjective and relies on the researcher's interpretation and

understanding of the data (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The codes that were deemed less relevant to the research study underwent an additional review. If these codes did not share similar characteristics with other codes or could not be merged into another category, they were subsequently discarded. This process ensured that only the most pertinent and meaningful codes were retained, contributing to the overall coherence and clarity of the analysis. Table 5 shows examples of generated themes.

Table 5

Generating Themes – Example

Codes	Possible Themes
Language Difficulty	Proficiency in the languages
Learning Environment	Multilingual learning environment
Sounds	Teaching approaches
Translation	Language practices

Reviewing Themes

According to Merriam (2009), new categories should fulfill several criteria when creating categories and themes during the process of data analysis. These criteria include: (1) the themes should be aligned with the research objective and purpose, ensuring that they are directly relevant to the overarching research questions; (2) the themes should be comprehensive and inclusive, ensuring that they can cover all relevant data within a main category or subcategory; (3) the themes should be sensitizing, indicating that they should be highly sensitive and accurate representations of the actual data they cover; and (4) the themes should be conceptually congruent, implying that all categories should possess a similar level of abstraction. In other words, a set of categories or subcategories should logically align with one another and exhibit conceptual interrelatedness.

The researcher critically assessed the potential themes that emerged from the analysis. Themes that were deemed unimportant or irrelevant to the research study underwent a reevaluation process. This involved considering whether these themes required renaming or if they lacked relevance to the research study altogether. If the irrelevant themes were determined to have no meaningful contribution to the study, they were promptly discarded.

Additionally, the researcher engaged in the process of identifying the essence of each theme and determining what specific aspect of the data each theme captured. The researcher proceeded to organize the themes into a cohesive and internally consistent account, accompanied by a narrative that provided context, examples, and explanation. In some cases, the researcher also identified sub-themes under certain themes. Once this organization was completed, the researcher interpreted the themes in relation to how they reflected the original research questions. See Appendix P and Appendix Q, respectively, for research questions one and two groupings of codes leading to the final research themes. Table 6 also provides the list of the final research themes.

Table 6*Final Research Themes*

Research Questions	Themes
What are the teachers' language ideologies on the use of the local language alongside Filipino and English as the language of instruction in early reading classes?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • English as a highly valued language • Filipino as preferred language • Challenges in MTB-MLE implementation • Use of translations • Language preservation and fostering identity
What are the teachers' early reading instruction practices in the local language, Filipino, and English?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Big six of reading with a focus on phonics instruction • Learners' experiences • Medium of instruction and/or learning area • Translanguaging • Learning environment and resources
Are the teachers' language ideologies reflected in their use of language/s in early reading instruction?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • English as a highly valued language • Filipino as preferred language • Challenges in MTB-MLE implementation • Use of translations • Language preservation and fostering identity

The logical narrative of the themes describes the data and presents arguments that relate to the research questions. The themes were compared and/or contrasted with other data sources (class observations, documents review, and focus group discussions) and existing empirical research to provide validation and support for the findings derived from the data analysis. By comparing and/or contrasting the identified themes with other data sources and previous research, the researcher sought to establish connections, highlight similarities or differences, and strengthen the credibility of the conclusions drawn from the data analysis process. Also, Braun and Clarke (2006) argued that thorough and rigorous thematic analysis can yield findings

that are both trustworthy and insightful. Moreover, similarities and differences that represented the research participants were also checked. Pie graphs were used to visually represent the codes. A thematic framework for each of the research questions, and for some of the research themes, was also created for more readability.

Teachers' language ideologies were considered hegemonic (Awonusi, 2004; Suarez, 2002; Wiley, 2000) when the teachers considered the local language less dominant and less useful compared to Filipino and English, thus contributing to linguistic discrimination and negating linguistic diversity. On the other hand, teachers' language ideologies were considered counter-hegemonic (Achugar, 2008) when the teachers believed that the local language is equal to and as complex as other languages such as Filipino and English, has a place in education, and challenges the perceived dominant languages. Counter-hegemonic language ideologies support language diversity, language equality, and the linguistic rights of the learners. How teachers utilized a language in teaching beginning reading and their personal biases for certain languages were a guide in determining if the teachers' existing language ideologies were reflected in their use of language/s in early reading instruction. The way the teachers allowed or restricted the learners in using other language/s aside from the one being taught (i.e., translanguaging) and how the teacher-initiated discourses transpired in early reading instruction were also utilized to answer the third research question. The teachers' personal reasons, their linguistic hierarchy, and preferences regarding the need to use a particular language in early reading instruction because of its perceived importance in the educational setting and in the bigger world outside of it were also included in the analysis of data. Instances of manifesting these were noted for analysis. For instance, if the teacher believed that languages are equal to each other and that the mother tongue is important in serving

as the foundation for learning other languages, it would be reflected in the teacher's use of language/s in early reading instruction when the teacher allowed the learners to use their mother tongue or the teacher used the learners' mother tongue to facilitate learning/comprehension, even though there was a different target language. On the other hand, if the teacher believed in language hierarchy and there was a dominant language and that learners' mother tongue hindered their academic development, it would be reflected in the teacher's use of language/s in early reading instruction when the teacher restricted the learners in using their first language in a subject where the target language is different, or the teacher used only one language. The last stage of the analysis involved summarizing the data and drawing conclusions.

To summarize, qualitative analysis "is not a technical exercise as in quantitative methods, but more of a dynamic, intuitive and creative process of inductive reasoning, thinking, and theorizing" (Wong, 2008, *Analyzing Qualitative Data* section, para. 1). The cited related studies' data concerning the teachers' language ideologies and early reading instruction practices were also qualitatively examined. The theoretical underpinnings of this study, especially the sociocognitive model of meaning construction (Ruddell et al., 2019), supported the explanation of the observed behaviors and guided the analysis of data. The researcher analyzed the interviews (supported by class observations, relevant documents, and FGDs data transcripts) and looked for codes, patterns, and relationships. This was done through the use of manual coding and Atlas.ti, a qualitative data analysis (QDA) software (e.g., Dubeck et al., 2012; Ganuza & Hedman, 2015), to identify the trends and common themes in teachers' language ideologies and early reading instruction practices.

Qualitative analysis includes reading and studying the data over and over and dividing the data into different meaningful categories. Moreover, the analysis primarily

centered on the collective group rather than individual members within it (Krueger, 1994). To a great extent, the themes that emerged were largely a result of the group's collaboration and did not exactly represent individual viewpoints (Smithson, 2000).

Qualitative Validity and Trustworthiness

Qualitative researchers place emphasis on comprehending the underlying structures of knowledge that arise from engaging in personal interactions with participants and delving deep into their experiences (Creswell, 2013). The researcher implemented various measures to ensure the highest level of trustworthiness in conducting the study. The trustworthiness and credibility of the data in this study were reinforced through data triangulation, which involved gathering and analyzing information from multiple sources (semi-structured interviews, class observations, documents analysis, and focus group discussions). Triangulation in qualitative research involves the process of corroborating evidence from multiple sources to gain a comprehensive understanding of a particular theme or perspective (Creswell, 2013). Member checking was done through the focus group discussions to seek the views and perspectives of participants regarding the credibility of interpretations and findings. In most qualitative studies, the process of member checking typically involves returning the data, analyses, interpretations, and conclusions back to the participants. This allows them to review and assess the accuracy and credibility of the researcher's account (Creswell, 2013). By sharing the findings with participants, researchers provide an opportunity for them to offer insights, corrections, or additional perspectives that can validate or challenge the interpretations.

To facilitate transferability, the researcher provided a detailed description of the research context, methodology, and findings. Transferability in qualitative research refers to the extent to which the findings of a study can be applicable or useful to others

in similar situations or contexts (Marshall & Rossman, 2016). It involves considering how the research findings, interpretations, and conclusions can be relevant and meaningful beyond the specific study sample or setting.

For research question one, to ensure reliability and validity, data were cross-checked in semi-structured interviews for research question two, class observations, and analysis of relevant documents. Data from the semi-structured interviews for research question one was compared to and validated by the said data sources. The similarities, differences, and consistency of teachers' language ideologies across data sources were reported, discussed, and analyzed.

Similarly, for research question two, the teachers' instructional practices especially their use of language/s in early reading instruction were checked across data sources, and the similarities, differences, and consistency of these practices (e.g., teachers' use of languages) were also reported, discussed, and analyzed. Likewise, the data from the semi-structured interviews for research question two were compared and validated across the other data sources mentioned.

The data from the first two research questions were analyzed until saturation to determine the relationship between the teachers' language ideologies and their use of language/s in early reading instruction. Focus group discussions (FGDs) were employed to supplement, further verify, triangulate, and/or fill in the gap in the data. The final step of the analysis involved identifying relevant quotes.

Chapter IV

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This chapter contains a detailed presentation and discussion of the results of this study. It is organized around the research questions, and the findings pertaining to each question are presented in a separate section with their own distinct themes. The findings are discussed primarily in narrative form. They are presented under the following major headings: Research Question 1: What are the teachers' language ideologies on the use of the local language alongside Filipino and English as the language of instruction in early reading classes?; Research Question 2: What are the teachers' early reading instruction practices in the local language, Filipino, and English?; Research Question 3: Are the teachers' language ideologies reflected in their use of language/s in early reading instruction?

Research Question 1:

What are the teachers' language ideologies on the use of the local language alongside Filipino and English as the language of instruction in early reading classes?

The analysis of the data primarily from the interviews and supported by other data sources such as the semi-structured interviews intended for the second research question, class observations, documents analysis, and focus group discussions provided a rich insight into the teachers' beliefs about the languages used in early reading instruction. Out of the 274 codes (i.e., frequency of codes including the co-occurrence), five relevant major themes emerged from the data. Figure 7, the extracted themes from RQ1 codes, graphically presents the dominant extracted themes.

Figure 7

Extracted Themes from RQ1 Codes

Figure 7 shows that *Dominance of English* (20%), *Dominance of Filipino* (18%) and *Multilingualism and Language Varieties* (14%) cover half of the data. A little over a quarter of the data are covered by *Language and Identity* (14%) and *Resistance towards MTB-MLE* (14%). The rest of the data occupy the last quarter of the graph: *Language Hierarchy* (8%), *Use of Translations* (6%) and *Others* (6%).

When further summarized, five major themes emerged from the data. Four of these are linked to hegemonic language ideologies: *English as a Highly Valued Language*, *Filipino as Preferred Language*, *Challenges in MTB-MLE Implementation*, and *Use of Translations*. The remaining theme, *Language Preservation and Fostering Identity*, is associated with counter-hegemonic language ideologies.

One of the key assumptions of the sociocognitive model of meaning-construction specifies that proficiency in language and reading skills is significantly influenced by an individual's socio-economic environment. In this socio-cultural

context, the teacher plays a pivotal role in fostering meaningful interactions within the social dynamics of the classroom, assuming a significant responsibility in the meaning-negotiation process (Ruddell et al., 2019). Moreover, Ruddell et al. (2019) argued that the teacher's prior beliefs and knowledge shape their understanding of affective and cognitive conditions, drawing upon their life experiences. Affective conditions include instructional beliefs and philosophy, encompassing elements such as instructional orientation that mirrors their personal sociocultural values and beliefs. The findings of this study are aligned with the assertions of the sociocognitive model of meaning-construction as teachers shared their linguistic beliefs on the use of the local language alongside Filipino and English as the language of instruction in early reading classes. These language ideologies are discussed below and are summarized in Figure 8, the thematic diagram of teachers' language ideologies.

Figure 8

Thematic Diagram of Teachers' Language Ideologies

Hegemonic Language Ideologies

English as a Highly Valued Language

The dominance of the official languages is one of the most prominent patterns in the data analysis. All the teachers in this study perceived that English and Filipino as official languages of the country are dominant languages because of their use inside and beyond the school. Participant E, for example, believed that many children have stopped speaking or using the required mother tongue, and these children opt to use the more known languages. She said, “Mayroon po talagang mga pagkakataon na mapapansin mong hindi na ginagamit ng mga bata ang *mother tongue* ng *school* at ginagamit na po nila ang mga wikang mas kilala tulad ng sa [*sic*] Filipino. Minsan nag-ta-try din po silang mag-*English*.” [“There are times that you would notice that the children are no longer using the mother tongue used in school, and they are already using more known languages such as Filipino. Sometimes they are trying to speak in English, too.”] In another example, Participant L mentioned that she herself did not become proficient in the local language Pangasinan because she got used to people prioritizing the use of the major languages. She shared, “Parang hindi na rin po ako natutong mag-Pangasinan masyado kasi mas nasanay na po akong mas nabibigyan ng pansin ng iba ang Filipino at tsaka [*sic*] *English*.” [“It seems like I personally did not become proficient in the Pangasinan language because I got used to the fact that there seems to be a focus on Filipino and English.”] Notably, the teachers related the use of English for a variety of purposes mostly for economic, social, and academic reasons. Figure 9 shows the thematic diagram of the reasons behind the theme *English as a highly valued language*.

Figure 9

Behind English as a Highly Valued Language

Jobs and Internationalization

Economic reasons on the use and benefits of the English language have been underscored. Participant D described that when applying for a job, the interviewer usually asks the applicant in English, relating her personal experience when she entered the public school system:

Halimbawa na lang po sa pag-a-*apply* natin sa trabaho. ‘Di ba po nung *first* tayong ma-*in*, in-*interview* tayo hindi naman po ginamit ‘yong Iloko na salita, kun’di ang priority po is *English*? Ang masasabi ko po ‘yong *English* po kahit saan ka man pumunta na mag-*apply* ng trabaho ‘yon naman ‘yong i-na-*adopt* nilang salita; hindi naman po puwedeng halimbawa in-*interview* ka, ang salita mo is Ilokano²², ‘di ba po hindi naman po pare-parehas ‘yong salita natin, kaya ang ginagamit po natin is *English*. [An example of this is when we apply for a job. When we applied in public schools and were interviewed, English was used, not Iloko. What I can say is wherever you go to apply for a job, Ilokano is not used; you can’t use it during interviews. Since we have different languages, we use English.]

²² Ilokano is just a variation of the Iloko language. Other variations of the name of this language include Ilocano and Iloco. However, in the official list of the 19 languages used in MTB-MLE, DepEd uses Iloko.

Participant I echoed that English, the language of internationalization, should be prioritized. She also emphasized that DepEd's goal is to produce globally competitive learners. Therefore, the globally used language, English, should be given importance. Accordingly, as one of the most used languages in the world, utilizing the English language is for practical reasons: "Lahat naiintindihan naman 'yan. Nagpapadala ang bansa natin ng mga tao *abroad* kasi nga kulang ang puwedeng pasukan at maayos na trabaho dito." ["Everyone understands it. The Philippines sends human resources abroad due to lack of available and decent jobs in the country."]

Academic Competitions and Social Integration

The English language is used as well for social and academic purposes. Participant E and Participant I for instance, believed that English should be a priority in the K to 12 curriculum, because when learners join competitions such as mathematics contests, English is used in the construction of the questions. Learners are expected to understand these questions when reading them. Participant K described the use of English in competitions in the following way, implying that learners who are taught in their mother tongue instead of English find it difficult to read and understand the questions and win in the said competitions:

Parang mas nakakalito siya (ang paggamit ng *mother tongue*) sa mga bata. Mas nahihirapan sila. Kasi ti'gnan mo, magtuturo ka ng Pangasinan mula *Grade 1* hanggang *Grade 3*... 'yung mga lalo na sa *Math*, 'yung mga *numbers*. Sa Pangasinan, *sakey* ta's pagdating mo ng *Grade 4*, *one*. Parang... kung ita-*translate* mo, ma-a-ano [*sic*] lang pero sana, ano [*sic*], sa umpisa pa lang, kung ano 'yung k'wan ('yung ginagamit sa *contest*), 'yun na lang. Kung sa *Math* – kasi sa *Math* kapag makikipag-*contest* ka, *English* naman. Anong mangyayari sa mga bata na naka-*mother tongue* siya [*sic*]? [Teaching using the mother

tongue confuses the learners. It makes it harder for them to learn. Look, you teach Pangasinan from Grade 1 to Grade 3... in Math especially. In Pangasinan, it is *sakey*, but in Grade 4, it is one. You are going to translate it. If only at the very beginning the language used in the contest is already taught. English is used when you join Math contests. What will happen to learners who are taught in the mother tongue?]

Likewise, they argued that it would make socializing with foreigners and other Filipinos easier when learners speak this language. Participant I noted, “Sa *English* po mas marami kang puwedeng makausap, Filipino man o ano mang lahi pa ‘yan. Mas malawak ‘yong ano [*sic*] *coverage* ng wikang ito.” [“You can communicate with a lot of people – with Filipinos or whatever race – using English. This language has a wider coverage.”]

Indicator of Intellect

Interestingly, English is also thought to be a sign of intelligence and perceived to deepen knowledge. It was mentioned earlier that some teachers lamented that not using English as much as using the mother tongue results in the poor performance of learners in competitions. This idea is related to learners not being able to understand the questions written in English. Some of the teachers also admitted that when the teacher speaks in English, learners are amazed, and they tend to look up to this person. For Participant B, English acts as a guiding tool as learners deepen their knowledge and said that “Yang *English* po, ‘pag alam na nila, alam na ng mga bata, mas malalim na ‘yong kaya nilang aralin at matutunan sa kanilang pag-aaral.” [“Once the learners already know the English language, they will have a deeper capacity to learn and understand in their studies.”] Accordingly, a learner who can use this language also understands things better.

Data from the class observations also highlighted the dominance of the official language English in early reading instruction. Phrases/statements such as “Very good!,” “Good job!,” “Let’s go!/Go,” “Five claps for [learner’s name],” and in English reading classes “Try to answer in English,” among others, were commonly used; these statements were used regardless of the language subject being taught. However, these phrases/statements were not enough to support *English as a highly valued language*. The Filipino language still dominated early reading classes in English. Aside from these aforementioned phrases/statements, the English language was used primarily when a teacher had to read something from a learning resource (such as book and/or television, among others) or say general statements (e.g., gist of the lesson) about the topic. Additional insights from the teacher were mostly given in Filipino. There seems to be a disconnect between the teachers’ language ideology and actual use of language in early reading classes in English. However, this does not prevent the teachers from idealizing the language because the majority of the learning materials in class were in English language, such as flash cards and charts showing basic sight words, list of CVC words, and English phrases and sentences.

English as a highly valued language alongside Filipino was further verified in the focus group discussions. The participants argued for the advantages of Filipino and English in the lives of their learners. Participant H talked about the importance of these languages in the lives of the learners: “Mas kagagamit-gamit kasi talaga ‘yang dalawang ‘yan, ‘di ba? Mas maraming gumagamit, mas kagamit-gamit.” [“Those two are more useful, right? The more people use them, the more useful they become.”]. Repeating what she shared in the interviews, Participant C further clarified that the Filipino and English languages would help learners as they ascend their academic ladder, especially after the first three grade levels: “Kasi po, *Sir*, pagkatapos naman

po ng *Grade 3*, more on Filipino o 'di kaya'y *English* na po ang kailangan gamitin at basahin ng mga bata. So dapat po, *prepared* na sila at the *very start pa lang*.” [Because, Sir, after Grade 3, children need to use and read more in Filipino or English. So, they should be prepared right from the very beginning.]

Phillipson (1992, 2013) pointed out that linguistic imperialism is ideological. In this sense, linguistic imperialism cultivates beliefs that glorify the dominant languages. This finding *English as a Highly Valued Language* reinforces the results of previous research on teachers' language ideologies, where ideologies that glorify more known languages such as English were identified. This finding of the study is also aligned with the argument that meaningful and powerful connections among languages are formed by language users (Cavanaugh, 2019).

The theme *English as a Highly Valued Language* is related to the study conducted by Phyak (2013) where one of the salient findings was that teachers are engaged with the idea of the English language making people's lives better, which directly affects the use of local languages in schools. The English language is still considered a dominant language in Nepalese communities. The extracted theme is also parallel with the local study of Parba (2018) in relation to placing the dominant languages, English and Filipino, at the top of the language hierarchy. This pushes the local languages towards more marginalization. Maseko's (2021) study on teachers' language ideologies in Zimbabwe, a multilingual country in Africa, also showed teachers' preference for the English language and explicitly shared their positive beliefs about it. In MTB-MLE, Cabansag (2016) and Medilo, Jr. (2016) also discovered teachers' preference for the English language. This is also echoed in Monje et al.'s (2021) study.

The English language is only the third language of the participants. However, the theme *English as a Highly Valued Language* and its sub-themes *Jobs and Internationalization*, *Academic Competitions and Social Integration*, and *Indicator of Intellect* highlight how teachers hold a special recognition towards the official language English, because of its perceived extensive use inside and outside of school, such as for economic, social, and academic purposes. This is supported by the greater resources and opportunities in this language. The teachers' language ideology that puts English language on a higher pedestal shows that glorifying a dominant language is reflected in the marginalization of the local languages. This also implies that the politics of language and of language learning are still present in the Philippine educational system despite the utilization of the local languages as medium of instruction. Therefore, *English as a Highly Valued Language* is a hegemonic language ideology.

Filipino as Preferred Language

The dominance of the Filipino language is also one of the most prominent patterns in the data analysis. The data indicated that the Filipino language holds a prominent position or its use is widely observed in the context examined. Reasons behind the theme *Filipino as Preferred Language* are shown in the thematic diagram in Figure 10.

Figure 10

Behind Filipino as Preferred Language

'Everyone understands it'

When it comes to the Filipino language, most of the teachers remarked that it is the common language everyone uses in the country because everyone understands it. Participant A claimed that Filipino is usually used because it is the national language, and learners understand it more than other languages. She also mentioned that more people are using it. She said, “Buong Pilipinas, *Sir*, *expected* na alam na nila ‘yang Filipino. Syempre ‘di ba *national language* natin ‘yan?” [“Throughout the Philippines, *Sir*, it is expected that they already know Filipino. Isn’t it our national language?”] This was also pointed out by all other participants. Participant C, who has the longest teaching experience among the teachers, pointed out that there are some words in the mother tongue that learners do not understand but they do when translated to the Filipino language. Translating these words to Filipino makes it easier for the learners to understand them. She shared, “Mahirap na din kasi, *Sir*, ‘yong ibang salita sa *mother tongue*, sa Ilokano. Parang mas mahirap na ‘yang maintindihan, *Sir*, para sa mga bata kasi Filipino na talaga (ang ginagamit). *Need mag-translate.*” [“It’s really difficult, *Sir*, to understand some words in the mother tongue, in Ilokano. It seems it’s harder to understand, *Sir*, especially for the children because Filipino is used more. There is really a need to translate.”] Participant J explicitly said that parents are also instrumental in the dominance of the Filipino language, especially at home:

Siguro, *Sir*, *ire-relate* ko sa ‘kin, *since* hindi naman lahat ng *parents* eh *from* Pangasinan, ‘yun siguro puwedeng Pangasinan sila. Eh pero ‘pag tulad ko na si Mama Tagalog siya, si Papa taga-Pangasinan, syempre gagamitin at ituturo ‘yung parehas nilang naiintindihan, sa Tagalog²³ tayo, sa Filipino. [*Sir*, maybe,

²³ Some of the participants seemed to think that Tagalog and Filipino are the same though they are not. Although the distinction between the two remains a subject of debate (Tantiangco, 2018), they are not used synonymously in this paper. Tagalog is used in mother tongue instruction as one of the 19 official languages in MTB-MLE, while Filipino is used in teaching the Filipino subject (DepEd, 2016d).

if I am going to relate it to myself, not all parents are from Pangasinan. If they were, they could speak Pangasinan. But if they are just like me, my mother is Tagalog, and my father is from Pangasinan, of course, the language that both of them understand is what they will use and teach to us, Tagalog or Filipino.]

The participants also mentioned how the Filipino language is commonly used in local television. Participant L stated that Philippine media is influential in making the Filipino language dominant when “Halos lahat na yata ng mapapanood sa *TV*, sa mga *channels* na mayroon dito sa atin, Filipino po ‘yung ano [*sic*] ‘yung wika na ginagamit.” [“Almost everything you can watch on TV, on the channels we have here, uses Filipino as the language.”] The participants claimed that most of what children watch on the television are in Filipino, so when you talk to them and their parents, they would use this language.

Fostering Inclusivity

When there are transferees whose first language is different from the school’s mother tongue, Filipino language is used to involve these learners. One of these cases is evident in Participant D’s class where she had a transferee from Manila whose first language is Filipino. She said, “*Need* magamit ‘yung salitang maiintindihan niya para naman, *Sir*, hindi ma-*outcast* ‘yung bata. Mahirap naman po ‘pag ganun.” [“It’s necessary to use a language that the child can understand, so that they won’t feel left out, *Sir*. It’s difficult when that happens.”] She used Filipino most of the time to cater to this particular learner. Echoing this, Participant B mentioned that this language serves as her connection to the learners regardless of the first language they speak. In

The two languages have common roots, but Filipino covers a wider scope than Tagalog (Tantiangco, 2018), because it borrows terms from the Spanish and English languages (Regalado, 2022). The Cornell University Department of Asian Studies (n.d.) states that substantial portion of Tagalog and Filipino vocabulary is common, and their grammatical structures are highly similar.

Filipino, she is understood by everyone and “Alam ni’yo po ‘yun? May *connection*, Sir, talaga sa bawat isa ‘pag mayroon pong *understanding through* ‘yong wika nga po na ginagamit. Nakikita po ito *through* Filipino.” [Do you know that? There is a connection, Sir, among each other when there is understanding through the language being used. This can be observed through Filipino.”]

During the class observations, it was observed how the teachers usually and mainly interacted with the class using the Filipino language while other languages complemented it. For example, in a Grade 2 English class during the reading of short e words in CVC (consonant-vowel-consonant) pattern, Filipino was mainly used in the teacher-learner interactions while English acted as a complement:

Participant D: CVC words *ang tawag natin sa mga salitang ito* (points to the list of words on the board: bet, fed, led ... peg). *Sabay-sabay tayo, basahin natin isa-isa ang mga salita rito. Repeat after me pala. Ako muna ang magbabasa, then kayo naman. Isa-isang word lang ha? Let’s read. Go!* [We call these words CVC (points to the list of words on the board: bet, fed, led ... peg). Let’s do it together and read one by one all the words here. Oh, you have to repeat after me. I will read first, then you read after me. Let’s do it one word at a time, okay? Let’s read. Go!]

May mga naiisip pa ba kayong mga examples ng CVC words na may vowel /e/ sound. Short e ‘yung vowel. [Can you think of other examples of CVC words with the vowel /e/ sound. The vowel is short e.]

Learner: Madam, *p'wede po ba 'yung net?* [Madam, is net, correct?]

Participant D: Oo! Very good! *Tama 'yun. Net. Ano pa?* Let's practice our English. *Kaya ni'yo 'yan! Maliban sa net, ano pa?* [Yes! Very good! It's correct! What else? Let's practice our English. You can do it. Net. Aside from net, what else?]

Similar to the English language, most of the educational resources used in the classroom were presented in the Filipino language such as syllabicated Filipino words. The participants' lesson plans in Mother Tongue subject were also in Filipino instead of the local language. Most of the classroom decorations mounted on walls were either in English or Filipino as well.

In the focus group discussions, the participants further supported the theme *Filipino as Preferred Language*. Participant L mentioned that if they had a choice, they would use this language as the major language of instruction: "Kung mayroong *choice* [*sic*] lang, *Sir*, Filipino na lang ang gagamitin. Mas madali, mas maiintindihan ng lahat." ["If only there were choices, Sir, we will use Filipino instead. It's easier, and everyone will understand it."] This was seconded by Participant M. She revealed that using this language as medium of instruction would unburden them: "Gagaan ang buhay, *Sir*, sa pagtuturo. Kasi ito naman ang magagamit ng mga bata eh. Ba't sa *Grade 4*, wala naman ng *mother tongue* na 'yan." ["Life will become easier, Sir, in teaching. Because this is what the children will use. Why in Grade 4, there's no longer any mother tongue."]

Language users create significant and potent links between languages (Cavanaugh, 2019). This is also true in the theme *Filipino as Preferred Language*, as supported by its sub-themes *'Everyone understands it'* and *Fostering Inclusivity*. These links between languages do not always promote positive relationship among

languages when some languages, for instance, are considered more important than others. Teachers who push for the use of Filipino as the preferred medium of instruction is not new in MTB-MLE. In the study of Cabansag (2016), teachers turned to employing Filipino as the medium of communication in the classroom, particularly when they themselves lacked sufficient proficiency in the learners' primary language. Although numerous studies have indicated a decline in opposition to Filipino being considered the national language, the same cannot be asserted regarding the use of Filipino as the medium of instruction (Tupas & Martin, 2017). This could also be related to it being expanded extensively throughout the archipelago and firmly established itself in the daily lives of numerous Filipinos, particularly because of media and popular culture. Filipino language has also functioned as a common means of communication among Filipino laborers dispersed across the globe (Tupas & Lorente, 2014).

Filipino language is considered the second language of most of the participants (85%). Nonetheless, the theme *Filipino as Preferred Language* also underscores that teachers accord distinct acknowledgment to this official language because of its perceived widespread utilization both within and beyond the educational setting. This covers various intentions, including both social and academic reasons. This is also reinforced by the increased availability of learning resources in this language. Hence, the theme *Filipino as Preferred language* is considered a hegemonic language ideology.

Challenges in MTB-MLE Implementation

Various reasons have been found that hinder the successful implementation of MTB-MLE as a language-in-education policy. These include challenges with multilingualism and language varieties, resistance towards the mother tongue in

particular and MTB-MLE in general, and the prevalence of language hierarchy. Figure 11 shows the thematic diagram of the theme *Challenges in MTB-MLE Implementation*.

Figure 11

Implementational Challenges in MTB-MLE

Challenges with Multilingualism and Language Varieties

This sub-theme covers the complications perceived to be brought by multilingualism and language varieties. Aside from wanting to focus on the use of the official languages (Filipino and English), some teachers seemed to have difficulty in the differences of languages in early reading instruction. Drawing from their personal experiences, they shared that using several languages creates divisions or factions. They can relate to speakers of their own language, but they cannot do the same in other language groups. Participant E, for instance, used the Province of Pangasinan as an example of a linguistically diverse context:

Kung minsan, *Sir*, sa mga Ilokano, hindi ako maka-*relate* sa kanila. Kasi hindi po ako nakakaintindi ng Ilokano. Kasi Bolinao ako. At minsan din nung una ko sa diyan [*sic*] po diyan sa Lingayen kung saan ginagamit po nila ay Pangasinan. So, ‘pag may pinag-uusapan sila... ah ‘pag halimbawa may gusto silang hindi ako ma-*disappoint* [*sic*] ganun nag-uusap po sila ng *language* nila. Yong salita nila. Para hindi ko ma-*gets*. [Sometimes, *Sir*, with Ilokanos, I can't really relate

to them. Because I don't understand Ilokano. I am from Bolinao. And there was also a time when I went to Lingayen, where they use Pangasinan. So, when they're talking about something... like if they want something and they don't want to hurt/offend me, they talk in their own language. Their words. So that I don't understand.]

Participant H also shared:

'Di ba ang *father* ko taga Dagupan, *Sir*. Ngayon kapag pumupunta kami sa Dagupan, mayroon kasing *gap* 'yong *family* namin kaya minsan 'yong mga tita ko doon, mga tita at tito, alam nila na hindi na kami, ako, nakakaintindi ng Panggalatot²⁴ [*sic*]. 'Yon nagsasalita sila ng Panggalatot [*sic*] para hindi ko malaman kung ano 'yong pinag-uusapan nila. Nakaka-bwisit. Kasi, *Sir*, andun ako dapat alam ko kung ano 'yong pinag-uusapan nila kasi *feeling* mo kasi 'pag ganyan na gumamit sila ng wika na nandun ka, parang ano, *Sir*, 'di ba nakakabwisit, nakakainsulto naman. 'Yon lang po. [My father is from Dagupan, *Sir*. Now, when we go to Dagupan, there's a sort of gap in our family, so sometimes my aunts and uncles there, they know that we, including me, don't understand Panggalatot [*sic*] anymore. So, they speak Panggalatot [*sic*] so that I won't know what they're talking about. It's annoying. Because, *Sir*, I'm supposed to be there, and I should know what they're discussing because it feels frustrating and kind of insulting when they use a language that even if you're there still you can't understand. That's it.]

Language variation is also a problem. In the research locale, language variation of the Iloko language, a majority local language, and Bolinao, a minority local

²⁴ Panggalatot or Panggalatok, a colloquial term which is used in lieu of Pangasinan (people/language), is considered offensive and derogatory. In Pangasinan language, "akatok" literally means *crazy* in English.

language, is also a challenge. The Iloko textbook (Alcayaga et al., 2017; Bamba et al., 2017a; Macob et al., 2016) provided by the government uses words that are quite different from the words used in the community, showing actual social and contextual differences. Examples of this are *ikur-it* [draw] instead of *igurit*; *agkaykay* [sweep] instead of *agwalis*; *agbasa* [study] instead of *agadal*; and *kawes* [clothing] instead of *bado*.

Pangasinan language is also a majority local language in the research locale. The participants from the Pangasinan group shared how the vowel “e” is differently pronounced in the Pangasinan language, compared to the Filipino language. This fact is perceived to make teaching and using different languages an obstacle. In Pangasinan language, e is written as *ë* to mean the /ə/ sound. They provided examples of this such as *imanuën* [pay attention]; *dëngëlën* [listen]; *ambëtël* [cold]; *‘ëlëk* [laugh]; and *agëw* [day]. In Grade 1 and Grade 3 Pangasinan textbooks, this vowel is also used (Alcantara et al., 2021; Bamba et al., 2017b). Examples of this are *basaën* [read]; *kuwanën* [said]; and *akanëngnëng* [saw] (Alcantara et al., 2021; Bamba et al., 2017b). However, the Grade 2 Pangasinan Mother Tongue Learners’ Material (Magtang et al., 2013), the vowel *é* is used to indicate the /ə/ sound. Examples of this are *pilién* [choose]; *kansiyunén* [sing]; and *usarén* [use].

During the classroom observations, this language variation was observed in the teachers’ language use and reading materials prepared for early reading instruction topics. For example, in Pangasinan, teachers used/wrote the *ë* letter all the time to indicate the /ə/ sound of the words. When Participant K taught the Letter Mm in the Mother Tongue subject, the *ë* letter was used. In one of the activities, Participant K wrote on the board “Isulat ëd kahon so nababalang iran letra.” [“Write the missing letter in the box.”]. The letter *ë* was particularly emphasized when the Letter Ee in the Mother

Tongue subject was taught by Participant K. The given examples were a combination of letter *ë* and letter *e*: *ëyag* [scream]; *ëgës* [tiyan]; *ë/ëk* [laugh]; *elisi* [fan blade]; *elepante* [elephant]. This was to make sure that the learners read the words accurately. During a poem recitation, a performance task in the Mother Tongue subject, Participant L reviewed the poem first to the learners:

The Poem in Pangasinan	The Poem's English Translation
<p style="text-align: center;">Si Bimbo Walay alagak ya aso Say ngaran to ët Bimbo Mapino so bago to Kiwël-kiwël so ikol to</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Bimbo I have a pet dog Its name is Bimbo It has fine fur It has a curly tail</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Sikato ët masiba-siba Papakanën koy baaw tan sira Agëw tan labi Babantayan toy abung mi</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">It has a big appetite I give it rice and fish Day and night It guards our house</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Sikato ët aamisën ko Litdan koy dukulan to Untan so iitër kon panangaro Ëd alagak ya aso</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">I bathe my dog I give it a soft bed I give it so much love My pet dog</p>

In the Bolinao language, teachers make the learning materials such as short stories themselves amidst the language variation among communities. Examples are presented in Figure 12 below.

Figure 12

Learning Materials in Bolinao - Examples

Note. Here are the translations of the titles: *Salamat sa Kalisa* [Thank you for the horse-drawn carriage]; *Ambale' Nanguman si Jose* [Why did Jose change].

Participant F, who lives in another community village, compared how Bolinao language is spoken and used in the communities:

Kasi doon sa amin sa bahay namin iba 'yong pagsasalita namin na Bolinao. Iba din dito (sa barangay na ito). Hindi ko alam kung ano kasi ay [sic] iba't-iba sila dito na salita na hindi ko maintindihan. Pero *paryas* [sic] do'n sa bahay namin na parang *garay* sabi nila. Eh, doon sa bahay namin buo talaga na *garay na'en* ganu'n. Bolinao talaga doon. [In our house we have a different way of speaking the Bolinao language. It is different here (in this barangay) as well. I don't know which is which. They have words here that I don't understand. Just like in our house, we say what seems to be the complete one *garay na'en* [oh, wow!], and here they say it's *garay* [oh, wow!]. We really use Bolinao in our community.]

When asked about multilingualism, one pattern that encompassed their statements is the negative beliefs about it. To them, multilingualism is confusing and can lead to language mixing or interference, making it difficult to communicate effectively. Using multiple languages in class is also seen to be difficult and time-consuming.

Participant F reported:

Sa *mother tongue* mayroon din ‘yong hiram, hiram [sic] sa Tagalog [sic]. Tapos ‘yon. ‘Yong sa Tagalog [sic] parang na-a-ano (nalilito) ‘yong mga bata. Kung Tagalog [sic] ba o ano. Kung minsan talaga ‘pag Filipino na ‘yong *examples* nila nagiging Bolinao na ‘yong mga *examples* nila ‘pag nasa Filipino na kami. [In the mother tongue there are borrowed (words) from Tagalog [sic]. In Tagalog [sic] it seems that the learners are confused if it’s a Filipino word or a Bolinao word. So sometimes, if the learners are asked to provide examples in Filipino, they would give Bolinao words even if the subject is Filipino.

Participant K noted that the three languages are too heavy for the learners to learn: “So, malilito sila – parang mas naaano [sic] ‘yong utak ng bata. Walang ano [sic], walang *clarification* ba, gano’n. Walang... ‘yun parang mas lalo silang naguguluhan ba, parang masyadong mabigat na tatlong *languages* ang pinag-aaralan nila. [“So, it will confuse them - making their brain addled. There’s no clarification. It would be too complicated for them. It seems that learning three languages is quite a heavy burden for the learners.”]

Participant J stated:

Parang ngayon kasi, *Sir*, dahil nga sa *technology* ‘di ba, ‘yung mga bata mas nag-aaral na sila sa *videos* na *English*. So parang ‘yong *last (school year)*, may mga *English* [sic] na kami na *students*, *English-speaking* na *students*. Kaya

lang, 'yun na naman ulit kasi 'yung *mostly* nga, Tagalog [*sic*] sila, Pangasinan, ano na naman ulit parang ang hirap na naman mag-adjust kasi may nag-i-*English*, may nagfi-Filipino, ta's may nagpa-Pangasinan. Eh Pangasinan 'yong *books*, parang mas dagdag trabaho. [At this time, Sir, because of technology, learners are able to study through videos in English. Last school year, we had English-speaking learners. Most of the learners speak Filipino and Pangasinan. It was a difficult adjustment because there were learners who spoke English, some spoke Filipino, and others communicated in Pangasinan. Eh, our books are in Pangasinan; it seemed like added work to the teacher.]

The data from the focus group discussions further reinforced the teachers' hegemonic language ideologies on *Multilingualism and Language Variation*. Common responses in the FGDs were *nakakalito* [*sic*] [confusing], *ubos ang oras sa pagtuturo* [time consuming], and *masyadong marami (na wika) for the learners* [too many languages for the learners]. Moreover, the extracted theme is also consistent with the earlier investigations on teachers' language ideologies. The study of Daugaard (2020) highlighted teachers' challenges when faced with language variation, which is exemplified in the case of the variations of 'old Pashto' and 'modern Pashto.' The local study of Parba (2018) also described language variations as challenges to the implementation of MTB-MLE in the Philippines, especially in the confusion in the textbooks due to the diversity of the Cebuano language variations. Related to the negative beliefs about multilingualism, the findings of Ganuza and Hedman (2015) and Daugaard (2020) showed that monoglossic language ideologies also emphasize the utilization of normative language use. Dubeck et al. (2012) also found that Kenyan teachers held negative beliefs on multilingualism.

The sub-theme *Challenges with Multilingualism and Language Variation* primarily implies that teachers held negative beliefs about multilingualism and language variations because of their monoglossic language ideology. This monoglossic language ideology could be related to the standardization of languages (what is accepted and what is not) and the promotion of dominant languages. The teachers also held negative beliefs on language variation because of the additional burden in teaching the discrepancies of the sounds and letters among the languages. They find these language variations difficult to navigate and see them as confusing and complex. Another interpretation of this sub-theme is the existence of teachers' language deficit perspective which made them unable to harness multilingualism as a potential source of a rich foundation of linguistic resources, leading them to consider it as problematic and worrying. Supported by this interpretation, the beliefs of the teachers on multilingualism and language variations are generally hegemonic in nature.

Resistance towards MTB-MLE

As previously presented, the official languages Filipino and English are considered dominant, and there is an apparent difficulty among teachers dealing with the differences between/among languages in early reading instruction. Another sub-theme that is linked to teachers' hegemonic language ideologies under the challenges in MTB-MLE implementation is the teachers' obvious *Resistance towards MTB-MLE*, especially towards the local language. Accordingly, using mother tongue alongside Filipino and English is seen as a barrier in teaching learners how to read. Teachers also viewed the mother tongue as unnecessary in teaching learners how to read. It is also seen as inferior compared to the other languages used in the classroom. In relation to the perceived complexities of multilingualism and language variations as

discussed above, Participant A reported that just like the Pangasinan language, Iloko as a mother tongue is confusing especially in teaching learners how to read. There are words that use the vowel sound /e/ in Filipino that when read in Iloko, the vowel sound /ə/ is used. In English, the vowel e is sometimes read as /ē/. Examples of these given by Participant A are *lames* [fish], *nagbukel* [circle], *kameng* [member], *innem* [six], and *aweng* [sound]. Participant C noted that learners mixing the three languages together results in hindrance in developing proficiency in the target languages. It could also interfere with how a learner uses a specific language fluently, accurately, and consistently. Participant C asked, “Paano po, Sir, matututo ang *learners* natin kung halo-halo na po ‘yung sobrang dami nilang inaaral na wika? Kailangan nilang basahin; kailangan pa nilang isalita.” [How can our learners learn, Sir, if they have to study a mix of so many languages? They need to read them; they need to use them in speaking.”]

Learners’ diminishing proficiency in using the mother tongue makes the MTB-MLE language policy even harder. Teachers believed that learners seemed to have adopted Filipino as their primary means of communication. The mother tongue is rarely used even inside the classroom. Some of the teachers also stated that there has been such a language shift in the community that even at home, the mother tongue is rarely used, with household members favoring the Filipino language. Participant C provided an example on this:

May mga halimbawa d’yan. Halimbawa, Sir, ‘*agburburek*.’ ‘*Agburburek adiaj danum*.’ Hindi na maintindihan ng bata ‘yan, Sir. Eh di i-*translate* mo na naman sa Filipino ‘yan para maintindihan. [There are examples of that. For example, Sir, ‘*agburburek*’ [boiling]. ‘*Agburburek adiaj danum*.’ [‘The water is boiling.’]

Learners can no longer understand that, Sir. So, you have to translate it into Filipino for them to understand it.]

Participant I admitted that MTB-MLE is a good language policy: “Maganda naman po ‘yung *goals* niyan, especially para hindi po natin malimutan ‘yung sariling wika natin dito.” [“It has good goals, especially to ensure we don’t forget our own language here.”] However, the problem comes with its implementation. She stated that majority of her learners are quite fluent with the Filipino language already. When she has to teach them, she would always resort to translating what had been said in Iloko to Filipino. This is similar to Participant J’s experience. She claimed that the first language of some, if not majority, of the learners in her class is not Pangasinan but Filipino and said “Napansin ko po na Filipino na po ang ginagamit nila as *their first language*” [“I noticed that Filipino is what they use as their first language”]. It makes teaching more tiring and requires more time to cover topics when teaching the learners always involves translating unfamiliar words or phrases.

Most of the teachers or about 85% of them shared unfavorable opinions on the use of the local language and MTB-MLE in general, ranging from utilizing the mother tongue not as MOI in most learning areas but in only one learning area (MT) to totally removing it from the curriculum. Participant A stated, “Puwedeng tanggalin na lang?” [“Can it just be taken out of the curriculum?”] Participant E also exclaimed, “Para sa akin *least priority* po siya sa *K to 12 curriculum*.” [“For me, the mother tongue is the least priority in the K to 12 curriculum.”]

Participant G said:

Okay lang na gamitin ang Bolinao sa pagtuturo pero sa *Mother Tongue* na lang dapat sana kasi *at least* parang ma-*refresh* ‘yong salitang Bolinao nga kasi ‘yong ibang mga bata nga hindi na nila alam, pero dapat sa Bolinao lang. [It is

okay to use Bolinao in teaching, but only in the Mother Tongue subject. It would help the learners remember and re-familiarize themselves with the Bolinao language's lexicon.]

Participant H shared:

Kahit sa MTB [*sic*] na *subject* ‘yon na lang ‘yong Ilokano dapat sana. ‘Yong iba, halimbawa sa *Math*, di ba ini-Ilokano rin ‘yong *Math*, *Sir*, ano? Mahirap kasi minsan i-*translate* lahat sa Ilokano ‘yong mga *mathematical terms* at saka dapat kasi ‘pag Ilokano na ang gagamitin doon, eh, hindi naman Ilokano lahat kapag lalabas na sila sa *outside Pangasinan*. Halimbawa, pumunta sila sa Manila. ‘Pag nag-aral sila doon, wala na. Hirap na sila kasi Ilokano. Puwede rin siguro sa MTB [*sic*], MTB [*sic*] lang siguro, *Sir*. ‘Yon na lang. [Ilokano should be taught only in the MTB [*sic*] subject. In other subjects, like Math, the concepts are also in Ilokano, right? Sometimes it's difficult to translate all the mathematical terms to Ilokano, and if they will use Ilokano in that subject, it will be difficult for them when they go outside of Pangasinan and encounter people who don't speak Ilokano. For example, if they go to Manila to study, it will be hard for them because they only know Ilokano. Maybe it's better to use Ilokano only in the MTB [*sic*] subject. That's enough.]

Participant K reported:

Sana ‘yong *mother tongue* hindi na ginagamit as *medium of instruction* sa mga ibang *subject*. Sana sa ano na lang, as a *subject*, ‘yong iisa. Kasi sa panahon ngayon, hindi na ‘yan masyado naririnig. Ang wikang Pangasinan, maganda siya. Pero ‘yon nga sana, meron [*sic*] lang siyang *focus* na sa isa lang, oo. [I hope that mother tongue is no longer used as the medium of instruction in other subjects. It would be better if it is only used in one subject. Nowadays, it's not

used as much anymore. The Pangasinan language is beautiful, but I hope its use is focused only on one subject.]

Teachers' proficiency in the mother tongue and the limited availability of learning resources in it also contribute to teachers' resistance towards MTB-MLE and the mother tongue in particular. The participants believed, however, that teachers' competence in teaching the mother tongue ensures that learners understand the concepts being taught, and it equips the teachers with knowledge to develop appropriate instructional strategies and materials that meet the students' learning needs. All of the teachers' first language is the community's local language, with the exception of Participants B and C who grew up in the local community but claimed that their native tongue has always been Filipino. However, despite this fact, some teachers found teaching in the local language challenging to do and expressed their concerns. Participant E, for example, commented that she was more comfortable teaching in Filipino than in Bolinao, because there are words that she no longer understands in Bolinao: "Ako mismo, *Sir*, *ket* [*sic*] nahihirapan sa ibang salitang Bolinao. Ano [*sic*] may mga salitang hindi ko na alam ang ibig sabihin, sa *true* lang." ["Even I, Sir, have difficulty with certain words in Bolinao. There are words whose meanings I don't know, to be honest."] This is the same case with Participant L. She said, "Parang parehas na natuto [*sic*] 'yong *teacher* at *students*." [It seems like both the teacher and students are learning."] Teaching in Pangasinan proves to be a mutually beneficial experience for her and her learners, as it not only enables them to learn but also helps her improve her command over the language as she is not fluent in it yet. Teachers also found it burdensome to provide learners with learning materials that are tailored to the local context and delivered in the mother tongue. Participant I argued that employing the local language alone is insufficient and stressed the need

for instructional materials to be available in the mother tongue as well: “Hindi puwedeng ginagamit lang siya (*mother tongue*); dapat ay may mga *instructional materials* din syempre ah.” [It is not enough that it (mother tongue) is being used; there should be instructional materials as well.”]

The teachers participated in the classroom observations in the MT subject using the mother tongue as the main medium of instruction. However, they were not purist, or they did not employ a pure language. In the MT subject, the required medium was used, but Filipino was also and mostly added to complement the local language. As previously mentioned in Chapter III, it is important to note that the teachers from the Pangasinan group wanted to use the Filipino language as the MOI in the Mother Tongue subject. The school head supported this idea, but the district supervisor did not allow this and reiterated the use of the required medium. Participant M even taught figures of speech, one of the topics in the MT subject, using the Filipino language. In addition, the Bolinao group’s supposed mother tongue in school – Bolinao – was changed in the middle of data gathering, and the teacher participants in the group did not push through with the agreed observations.

The data from the focus group discussions further verified the stand of teachers regarding their obvious resistance towards MTB-MLE. Participant H maintained her stand on MTB-MLE, “Kung hindi tatanggalin ay sa ano [*sic*] na lang sana, *Sir*, isang *subject* na lang gamitin ‘yung *mother tongue* na ‘yan.” [“If it will not be removed, Sir, then mother tongue should be used in only one subject.”] Participant L further shared, “Hindi masyadong magagamit talaga, ‘yan, *Sir*.” [It’s not going to be really useful, Sir.]

Resistance towards MTB-MLE provides additional evidence to support the findings of the study spearheaded by Philippine Institute for Development Studies (PIDS) (Monje et al., 2021). Teachers not supporting the school’s chosen medium of

instruction was one of the reasons impeding the successful implementation of MTB-MLE. However, the sub-theme is in contrast with the findings of Ganuza and Hedman (2015) where teachers were found to be supportive of bilingualism and/or multilingualism among learners. The study of Daugaard (2020), also in contrast with the theme, found teachers were supportive of the use of mother tongue, because the mother tongue (along with the Danish language) allows the development of linguistic skills and international understanding, among others. Likewise, Parba's (2018) study also contradicts the theme; teachers initially resisted the use of mother tongue as the language of instruction but eventually embraced it. T

Bodies of research and various theoretical discussions have shown support for MTB-MLE as a language policy. However, the results of this study showed otherwise. Teachers are still resistant to it and continue to oppose it because the use of mother tongue alongside the two official languages is seen as a barrier to learning. In addition, the use of three languages in the classroom is perceived to be confusing. This clearly contradicts the BESRA 2015 Report on 'KRT 3: Formulation of the National Learning Strategies for the Filipino and English Languages' (Ocampo, 2006); recommending the use of mother tongues in schools was a product of consultations with different stakeholders including teachers themselves. The problem also lies as well in the linguistic proficiency of both the teachers and the learners of the mother tongue. The findings mainly imply that MTB-MLE continues to be misconstrued. This could be related to the limited trainings of the participants on MTB-MLE. Hence, negative perceptions about it continue to proliferate. The teachers also seem to be lacking in awareness of important concepts in language acquisition/learning and cross-linguistic transfer such as the relationship of L1 to stronger literacy abilities in L2 and/or L3. This has led to the negative perception of multilingualism, mother tongue, and MTB-MLE.

It is also implied that the teachers' stereotypes of the local languages are strong and persistent. Hence, teachers' resistance towards the mother tongue in particular and MTB-MLE in general is a hegemonic language ideology and contributes to the challenges in MTB-MLE implementation.

Language Hierarchy

Despite not openly expressing their views on language hierarchy, some participants' remarks and attitudes suggested that they subscribed to it. This was evident among the teachers. Their feeling of inferiority towards their local language is the initial manifestation of this phenomenon. Participant E remarked that using the local language often triggers memories of negative perceptions towards Bolinao speakers, who are sometimes ridiculed for sounding like birds and struggling to pronounce Filipino and English words accurately, "Tunog ibon po, Sir, 'yan talaga 'yung kadalasang sinasabi nila 'pag nagsasalita 'yung mga taga dito po sa Bolinao. May ano [sic] may parang *something* daw po sa dila na parang ang bibilis magsalita ganun." ["Bird-like sound, Sir, that's what they usually say when people from Bolinao speak. There is something, like a quality in their tongue that makes them speak quickly like that."]

The perception of language hierarchy is widespread, extending from the workplace and local community to the national and global level. Teachers held diverse views on the ranking of languages in the language pyramid, despite their shared belief in the dominance of English and Filipino languages. At the national level for example, Participant B assigned the English language to a lower position in the language hierarchy, with Filipino occupying the apex of the pyramid: "Pinaka-importante po ang Filipino syempre. Wikang pambasa po 'yan eh. Susunod po na mahalaga, *Sir*, ang *English. International language* po 'yan." ["Filipino is the most important, of course. It

is our national language. The next important language, Sir, is English. It is an international language."] In contrast, Participant E situated English at the pinnacle of the pyramid, with the mother tongue occupying the lowest rung and shared "*English ang nasa tuktok niyang ano pyramid na 'yan. Mother tongue naman nasa last – pinakababa – kasi sabi ko nga sa isang subject na lang siya sana gamitin. Kung puwede lang ah?*" ["English is at the top of that pyramid. Mother tongue is at the bottom – the lowest level – because just like what I already mentioned, it should only be used in one subject. If only that's allowed, right?"] This was the prevailing notion of the language hierarchy.

The local study of Parba (2018) supported this particular finding of this study. English and Filipino are put at the top of the language pyramid, negatively affecting the local languages. In Nepal, this is the same case. English is placed above other languages (Phyak, 2013). This finding also supports the themes *English as a Highly Valued Language* and *Filipino as Preferred Language*. Hence, the presence of language hierarchy contributes to the challenges in MTB-MLE implementation, making it a hegemonic language ideology.

Use of Translations

Although they expressed negative beliefs on teaching multiple languages, all the teachers agreed to have done translations in early reading instruction in class, usually for clarifications, putting the language in cultural context, and mediating academic content. Translations are subsumed under translanguaging (De Los Reyes, 2018). Translations are used in language learning and teaching of reading to facilitate learners' comprehension of what is being taught to them. By providing translations of words, phrases, and sentences, teachers could clarify the meaning of the word or set of words. Despite the perceived dominance of the official languages and the continued

resistance towards the mother tongue, the teachers resort to translation to bridge a language to another language. However, they claimed that in translations, they translate the words from the mother tongue usually to the Filipino language, which is perceived to be understood more by the learners. Participant G, for example, used translations of the mother tongue to the Filipino for the sake of the transferees “Para hindi naman ma-*left out* (‘yung learners) o para po ma-*ka-join* pa din po sa klase ‘yung *learners* po, Sir.” [“So that the learners will not be left out or they can still participate in class, Sir.”] She claimed that transferees could not understand the mother tongue used in school, so she resorts to using another language that is understood by everyone. The need for translations of mother tongue to Filipino could be related to the local language variations. Hence, the Filipino terms for these words could be perceived as more familiar to both the teacher and the learners. For example, in Iloko language some Iloko words used in the textbooks are not really used in the community as previously mentioned.

Regarding the English subject of the first graders which only starts at the third quarter of every school year (DepEd, 2016a), Participant F shared:

Sa wikang *English*, ano madalang naming [*sic*], madalang na-ano [*sic*] tawag dun? Madalang naming naituturo kasi nasa *third quarter* na tapos minsan hindi naiintindihan. *English* ka nang *English* sa harapan parang nakatanga lang ‘yong mga ano [*sic*] bata kaya minsan tina-Tagalog [*sic*] mo na din, Bino-Bolinao mo na din. [The English language is rarely taught because it only starts at the third quarter of the school year, and sometimes learners can’t understand it. When you’re speaking too much English in front of them, they just stare blankly. That’s why I translate it into Filipino. I also translate it into Bolinao.]

Data from the class observations showed that teachers did translations in their reading lessons. For example, the following translations were noted in Participant H when she taught the letters of the English alphabet and their sounds:

(1) Are you ready to listen to our new lesson? *Handa na ba kayong makinig o mag-listen sa ating bagong lesson?* [Are you ready to listen to our new lesson?]

(2) There are 26 letters in the English alphabet. *Ilang letters mayroon po sa English alphabet?* [How many letters are there in the English alphabet?]

(3) Each of these letters have [*sic*] a sound. *May katumbas po na tunog ang bawat letra. Okay po?* [Each of these letters has a corresponding sound. Okay?]

During Participant M's teaching of characters and setting in a story, she also used translations to bridge the language to what the learners could understand better.

Examples of these translations are:

(1) Remember, *'di ba?* A story has important elements. These elements are characters and setting. *Ito 'yung tauhan at lugar at oras ng k'wento.* [These are the characters, place, and time of the story.] They keep the story together.

(2) The title of the short paragraph is "A Little Hero." *Ang pamagat ng paragraph na ito ay "A Little Hero" o munting bayani.* [The title of this paragraph is "A Little Hero" or a little hero.]

The importance of this language ideology was further verified by the data through the focus group discussions in which the participants claimed translations are helpful in navigating the complex system of three languages used in class. Participant J shared, "Nakakatulong talaga po 'yan (*translations*), Sir, kasi mas napapaintindi sa bata 'yong kailangan po nilang basahin or aralin po." [Those (*translations*) really help,

Sir, because they make it easier for the learners to understand what they need to read or study.” Participant M agreed and commented that:

Sa MTB-MLE, Sir, ‘di ba nga tatlong wika agad ‘yang ipapabasa mo sa mga bata o ituturo mo sa kanila, ‘pag naghalo-halo na ‘yan, wala na. Kaya maganda ‘yang *translations*. Mag-*translate* po dapat ‘pag talagang kailangan. Nakakatulong po ‘yan nang malaki lalo sa mga bata. [In MTB-MLE, Sir, aren't you supposed to introduce three languages to the children or teach them all at once²⁵? But when they mix together, it becomes confusing. That's why translations are beneficial. Translation should be done when necessary. It is a big help, especially to the children.

These findings corroborate earlier research by demonstrating similar outcomes. The study of Ganuza and Hedman (2015) found that translanguaging is one of the teaching practices in the classroom where spontaneous interactions in three languages among the learners were observed. Moreover, it was identified in Parba's (2018) study that translanguaging is an indicator of heteroglossic approach to language policy and use. Translanguaging also negotiates the use of more than one language in Zimbabwean classrooms (Maseko, 2021).

The theme *Use of Translations* strongly implies that using translations as part of translanguaging in class bridges the languages used in class, facilitating communication and understanding of classroom discourse. Through the use of translations, communication barriers are broken down and cross-cultural communication is given space to grow and prosper. Languages are acknowledged and valued. Translations also promote inclusion and participation. However, teachers

²⁵ In Grade 1, beginning reading is first taught in the mother tongue. The teaching of Filipino only starts in the second quarter of the school year. The teaching of English only starts in the third quarter of the school year.

use translations for the benefit of the dominant languages. Despite the rationale behind the use of translations and/or translanguaging as a language tool, using it to promote language exposure in the dominant languages could discourage the use and development of local languages as legitimate languages in early reading instruction. Doing so could further reinforce and strengthen the presence of language hierarchy. Translations could be used as a form of resistance against linguistic imperialism. But in the case of the language ideology of the teachers, the *Use of Translations* (especially from MT to Filipino) is a hegemonic language ideology.

Counter-Hegemonic Language Ideology

Language Preservation and Fostering Identity

Despite the oppositions and criticisms received by the mother tongue, most teachers (70%) agreed that MTB-MLE is also being implemented for language preservation and fostering one's identity, history, and heritage. According to Participant B, using the mother tongue in education should feel natural and should be fostered through the learners' lives because "Yang *mother tongue* bahagi 'yan ng buhay po ng mga bata, ng kanilang pamilya, ng lugar po nila." ["Mother tongue is part of the learners' lives, their families, and their community."] She felt that using the mother tongue in early reading instruction would teach learners their community roots through the language. The mother tongue is a vital part of one's identity and culture, and its use in reading instruction can help promote greater linguistic diversity and inclusivity. Participant G also mourned that the Bolinao language is losing its hold in the community, "Parang nawawala na po ang *language* ng Bolinao dito mismo sa amin. Nakakalungkot [*sic*] po." [It seems like Bolinao language is dying here. It's sad."] More and more people no longer speak the language. She claimed that MTB-MLE aids in restoring the language of the community. Participant E reported that Bolinao is known

for its language. Through MTB-MLE, learners can maintain their cultural connection to their heritage, “Dito sa amin kilala kami nga [*sic*] na may sarili kaming salita. ‘Yung Bolinao. Bolinao ‘yung lugar, ta’s Bolinao ‘yung salita. Dun pa lang makikita mo na kung anong *connection* dapat mayroon ang bawat isa sa Bolinao.” [“Here in our town, we are known for our language. That’s Bolinao. The town is called Bolinao, and the language is also Bolinao. You can already see from there what kind of connection each person should have with Bolinao.”]

The participants also placed importance in the role of the home in the use and development of mother tongue. Participant A for example shared, “Maganda sigurong ituro sa bahay na lang. Kasi sa bahay naman nagsisimula yan eh. Kumbaga dito i-parang, enhance na lang dito sa school.” [“It might be better to teach it at home. Because it actually starts at home. Here, we should just enhance it here in school.”]

The data from the class observations showed that the teachers decided to use the mother tongue in the MT subject. This was a clear evidence of a counter-hegemonic language ideology, despite their negative beliefs on mother tongue and MTB-MLE. Since teachers are required to use the mother tongue in their classes, language identity was highlighted. In Participant B’s MT class, she primarily used the Iloko language in teaching, for example:

Mabalin nga usaren ti *context clues* tapno maala iti usto a kayat a sawen ti balikas. *Kasi ‘di ba po* adda dagiti dabduma nga balikas nga sabali ti kayat na nga sawen ken abali met lang ti pannakausar na. *Gets po natin?* [Context clues can be used so that we can understand the meaning of a word. Because, right, the meanings of some words change depending on the use. Do we understand it?].

As mentioned earlier, however, the teachers' lesson plans in the MT subject were in Filipino. There were also available learners' materials/textbooks from DepEd in the Pangasinan and Iloko languages, but not in Bolinao. The focus group discussions conducted further verified the theme *Language Preservation and Fostering Identity*. Participant D further explained why MTB-MLE is being implemented, so that "Hindi malimutan ang pinanggalingan nila" ["They (the learners) won't forget where they came from."]. Moreover, Participant K did mention that "Yang wika na 'yan, 'yang *local language* o *mother tongue*, parte po 'yan, Sir, sa pagkatao na rin nila." [That language, that local language or mother tongue, it's part, Sir, of their (learners') identity."]

In the sociocognitive model of meaning-construction (Ruddell et al., 2019), it is asserted that literacy and languages have no meaning outside their particular cultural world. Languages will always be part of one's culture. The theme *Language Preservation and Fostering Identity* is parallel with the studies of other scholars such as Maseko's (2021) and Wawire and Barnes-Story's (2023). Indigenous languages are viewed by teachers as important and are generally appreciated only when it comes to cultural concepts. Translanguaging could further support the use of mother tongue and other languages, allows learners to express and embrace their unique identities.

The theme *Language Preservation and Fostering Identity* primarily implies that teachers believe that the mother tongue is used to promote and protect the language of the people. It resonates with people's cultural traditions, personal heritage, values, and social connections. The mother tongue allows the teachers and the learners to connect to their cultural roots. Therefore, the theme *Language Preservation and Fostering Identity* is clearly a counter-hegemonic language ideology.

Research Question 2:

What are the teachers' early reading instruction practices in the local language, Filipino, and English?

The second semi-structured interview was designed to gather information from teachers regarding their early reading instruction practices, with a particular focus on language use. The data obtained from individual interviews with teachers offered in-depth and detailed descriptions, making it highly relevant to address the second research question in a contextual manner. To validate the early reading instruction practices, teacher class observations and documents review were also utilized. FGDs were also used to validate the findings of the study. Similar to the first research question's discussion and analysis, identified assertions from the participant interviews were also included, as other data sources were used in the triangulation. Out of 448 codes derived from the semi-structured interviews (i.e., frequency of codes including the co-occurrence) for research question two, five relevant major themes emerged from the data: *Big Six of Reading with a Focus on Phonics Instruction*, *Learners' Experiences*, *Medium of Instruction and/or Learning Area*, *Translanguaging*, and *Learning Environment and Resources*. These themes were also delineated in terms of practices in each of the three languages (local language, Filipino, and English). Practices in the three languages were summarized to identify the similarities and differences among them. Figure 13, the extracted themes from RQ2 codes, graphically presents the dominant extracted themes.

Figure 13

Extracted Themes from RQ2 Codes

Figure 13 shows that the *Big Six of Reading with a Focus on Phonics Instruction* is the most dominant theme extracted from the codes. This is followed by *Filipino*, *Learning Environment and Resources*, *English*, *Mother Tongue*, *Translanguaging*, *Learners' Experiences*, and *Technology*. Other codes comprise about 8% of the total codes; these codes include *Teaching Activities* and *Teaching Expectations*, among others. These initial themes presented in Figure 11 were summarized further into five major themes for refinement, which were mentioned earlier: *Big Six of Reading with a Focus on Phonics Instruction*, *Learners' Experiences*, *Medium of Instruction and/or Learning Area*, *Translanguaging*, and *Learning Environment and Resources*. Summarizing and/or refining the initial themes was carried out to determine the particular data aspect each theme captured and to guarantee their alignment with the research question.

The idea of oral and written language development having an impact on thinking processes and directly contributing to the development of reading ability supports Ruddell et al.'s (2019) sociocognitive model of meaning-construction. Reading (or teaching reading for this matter) in the instructional context of the classroom is conceptualized as a meaning-construction process where teachers and learners build understanding through meaning negotiation. The sociocognitive model of meaning-construction also highlights the cognitive conditions of the reading teacher, which include their knowledge of the reader's meaning-construction process, literature and content areas, teaching strategies, metacognitive strategies, and personal and world knowledge. In line with this, the teachers' early reading instruction practices are discussed below and summarized in Figure 14, thematic diagram of teachers' early reading instruction practices.

Figure 14

Thematic Diagram of Teachers' Early Reading Instruction Practices

Big Six of Reading with a Focus on Phonics Instruction

The theme *Big Six of Reading with a Focus on Phonics Instruction* related to early reading instruction surfaced from all data sources. This could be related to teachers' teaching initiatives which refer to instructional decision-making processes of the reading teacher and could also refer to attempts "exerted to learn new pedagogical ideas, make use of some teaching aids to facilitate and accelerate students' learning, enhance student literacy and create a positive and inclusive learning environment" (Mohamed Mohamed Ali El Deen, 2023, p. 6). Teacher agency also plays a role in the *Big Six of Reading with a Focus on Phonics Instruction* because it encompasses making instructional decisions, exercising professional judgment, and taking initiatives in their teaching practice in early reading instruction. Under this particular theme, phonics-based instruction as an approach in teaching early reading is portrayed in the three languages (local language, Filipino, and English) and across languages.

Big Six of Reading in Early Reading Instruction

Although the participants ranked the big six of reading according to importance differently, they all ranked phonics as the starting point of reading and comprehension as the most important. Participant C commented that the big six of reading are all important in early reading instruction, regardless of the language:

Kahit anong *language* pa 'yan, itong *phonics*, *Sir*, ang *number one*. Then 'yong sa *comprehension*, *Sir*. Lahat po naman 'yan (*big six of reading*), mahalaga po. Kung isa lang pipiliin mo, lalong hindi nila (*students*) naintindihan na, kaya lahat andyan. Sa pagtuturo ng *reading*, lahat andyan para lalo nilang maintindihan kung ano 'yong ina-ano (tinuturo) mo sa kanila. Kung pipili lang tayo ng isa lang or dalawa diyan, paano na? [No matter what language it is, phonics is number one, *Sir*. And then, *comprehension*, *Sir*. All of those (*big six in reading*) are

important. If you choose just one, they (students) won't fully understand, that's why everything is included. In teaching reading, everything is there to help them better understand what you're teaching them. If we were to choose just one or two, what would happen?]

Different reading resources are being utilized in the teaching of the big six of reading in early grades classrooms. The language curriculum (MT, Filipino, and English) is followed by the teachers in teaching language and reading-related topics. This is the teacher's primary reference. The curriculum guides were cited in the teachers' lesson plans as reference materials. More so, the MT, Filipino, and English curricula (i.e., integrated language arts curriculum), have fourteen domains:

(1) Oral Language, (2) Phonological Awareness, (3) Book and Print Knowledge, (4) Alphabet Knowledge, (5) Phonics and Word Recognition, (6) Fluency, (7) Spelling, (8) Writing and Composition, (9) Grammar Awareness and Structure, (10) Vocabulary Development, (11) Reading Comprehension, (12) Listening Comprehension, (13) Attitudes towards Language, Literacy, and Literature, [and] (14) Study Strategies (DepEd, 2016a, p. 11; DepEd, 2016b, p. 5; DepEd, 2016c, p. 11).

The big six of reading are part of the integrated language arts curriculum, and teachers are expected to be able to teach them.

Although the participants were leaning towards phonics-based instruction, they were still able to integrate the big six of reading in early reading instruction as a support to phonics-based instruction. The development of oral language was primarily observed through recitations in the reading classes involving the three languages (MT, Filipino, and English). Phonological awareness was integrated through the use of nursery rhymes which were usually recited/sung at the start of the lesson, for example,

“Leron, Leron Sinta” in Filipino and “Row, Row, Row your Boat” and the “Alphabet song” in English. However, songs or nursery rhymes in the local language were not observed. Poems such as “Si Bimbo” [Bimbo] and “Siyak si Kutingting” [I am Kitten] were used in MT reading classes. Teaching vocabulary often involved translations, and teachers highlighted key words in their lessons. Word cards were also used. Fluency was integrated by having learners repeat/reread/resay the words, phrases, and/or sentences with appropriate speed and accuracy; this was done in three languages as well. Texts from the textbooks were utilized for reading comprehension, with comprehension questions asked after reading. Some teachers used stopping points in stories read to the class to also aid in reading comprehension.

Various activities involving the big six of reading that support early reading instruction were also noted in the teachers’ lesson plans such as singing of nursery rhymes, solving of word puzzles, reading of texts found in the textbooks, and reading of letter sounds, words, phrases, and sentences, among others.

Phonics-based Instruction in Early Reading

The use of phonics-based instruction is not limited to teaching reading in one language. It is used in teaching beginning reading in the local language, Filipino, and English. Phonics-based instruction is further discussed below and summarized in Figure 15.

Figure 15

Focusing on Phonics Instruction

When learners had a difficulty reading a particular word, phonics-based instruction was used. For example, one teacher had to sound out the word *mountain* and started doing it by emphasizing the sound of /m/ to guide the learner in reading the remaining part of the word. This was also observed when a teacher emphasized the /s/ in the words *sapa* [creek] and *batis* [stream]. Data collected from the lesson plans, which were computer-encoded and not manually written, provided by the participants were also consistent with the classroom observations with regards to the topics and/or competencies related to teaching phonics and word recognition, as guided by the prescribed curriculum. However, the participants did not religiously follow the teaching procedures and activities. For instance, group activities were included in the lesson plans, but these were not done in actual teaching. Differentiated instruction (e.g., group activities) in the lesson plans were also not conducted. Pulling out a learner to read beside the teacher was also not part of the lesson plans provided to the researcher. Also, the lesson plans used by the teachers were not detailed and explicit enough. The sub-theme phonics-based instruction and its prominence in early

reading instruction were further verified by the focus group discussions conducted. The participants claimed that the phonics-based approach follows basic steps, starting from simple to complex, which help beginning readers tackle the printed text. Participant E further claimed that phonics-based instruction in the three subjects, MT, Filipino, and English, helps slow readers: “Nag-uumpisa kami sa *sounds*, *Sir*, sa *phonics* para hindi masyadong mabigat ‘yung pag-atake mo (sa pagtuturo sa kanilang bumasa),” [“We start with sounds, Sir, in phonics so that the approach²⁶ (in teaching them how to read) is not too overwhelming for them.”] Participant F encouraged the other participants to know these sounds themselves as teachers: “Dapat alam mo ‘yung pa’no ‘yung *style* ng pagtuturo ng pagbabasa sa mga bata. Dapat alam mo po ‘yong mga *sounds* ng mga *letters* bilang teacher. Kahit pa talaga paulit-ulit ‘yan.” [“You should know the teaching style on how to teach reading to children. As a teacher, you should be familiar with the sounds of the letters, even if it requires repetition.”] The teachers were able to explain in detail how phonics instruction was done in their early reading classes (which they were not able to do with the other domains of the Big Six of Reading).

It is important to mention the noticeable differences on the use of phonics-based instruction in the three grade levels across the three languages. For instance, basic letter-sound correspondence and basic phonemic awareness were taught in the first grade. This is further expanded in Grade 2 where learners were exposed to larger units of sounds and reading and/or decoding multisyllabic words. In Grade 3, learners were exposed to complex phonics patterns, such as diphthongs and advanced

²⁶ When it comes to teaching beginning reading, the teacher-participants tended to use the words *approach*, *method*, *strategy*, and *technique* synonymously.

consonant blends, and spelling. However, teachers also went back to letter-sound correspondence to help struggling readers decode words.

Phonics-based Instruction in the Local Language

Not much was said about a specific approach or method to teaching reading in the local language. However, the teachers repeatedly mentioned the use of sounds in teaching early reading in the mother tongue. Participant A shared, “Sa *sounds* po talaga magsisimula. *Basic* po ‘yun.” [“It really starts with sounds. That’s the basic idea.”]. Participant H commented that she uses a YouTube video that teaches the sounds of Iloko letters, “May *video* po sa *YouTube* na nagdi-discuss na po ng mga Ilokano *letters and sounds*. Pinapanood ko na lang po ito sa mga bata, *Sir*.” [“There’s a video on YouTube that discusses Ilokano letters and sounds. I just let the children watch it, Sir.”].

The participants from the Pangasinan group contextualized the Marungko approach in teaching reading in the mother tongue, a sample of which is seen in Figure 16. The participants from the Bolinao group translated the learners’ material provided by the government from Filipino to Bolinao. The participants from the Iloko group said repeatedly that they teach the sounds of the most used letters first before others. For example, Participant A said, “Magsisimula ka sa *Letter Aa* kasi ‘yan ang ano pinakanagagamit na *letter* sa lahat.” [“You start with the Letter Aa because that’s the most used letter of all.”]

Figure 16

Contextualized Material Based on Marungko Approach - Example

Note: Here are the translations of the texts in the pictures: *Panagbasa ed Pangasinan* [Reading in Pangasinan]; *masamit* [Delicious]; *so* [the]; *dila* [tongue]; *ya* [of]; *baboy* [pig]; *Masamit so dila ya baboy*. [The tongue of the pig is delicious.]

Teaching of letters and sounds is part of the Mother Tongue curriculum, particularly in Grade 1 and Grade 2. Data from the class observations highlighted the phonics-based instruction even when the topic was not specifically about letters and sounds. When Participant A taught the letter Tt and its sound, she made use of missing letters in the words to discuss the topic. Examples of these words are: ___ian (*tian* [stomach]); ___asa (*tasa* [cup]); ___ambor (*tambor* [drums]); and ___ali (*tali* [rope]). Meanwhile, when Participant I read a poem to the learners entitled “Ti Bassit a Pusa” or “A Small Cat”, she made sure to read the multi-syllabic words such as *maragsakan* [made happy] and *kinaliday* [sadness] with an emphasis on sounding out the letters

and putting them together through the syllables. She allowed the learners to repeat the words as well.

Some competencies in the Grade 1 Mother Tongue curriculum related to phonics include:

(1) Naming and sounding out of letters... (2) Naming and sounding out the beginning letter of the name of a picture... (3) Blending specific letters to form syllables and words... (4) Saying spoken words when two or more sounds are put together... (5) Isolating the beginning and ending sounds of the given words... and (6) Sequencing of letters (DepEd, 2020b, pp. 487-489).

Out of the 48 identified Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs)²⁷, only six directly fall under the domain of phonics and word recognition. Phonics and word recognition is one of the domains of the Grade 1 MT curriculum where learners are expected to “demonstrate understanding that words are made up of sounds and syllables [and] use knowledge of phonological skills to discriminate and manipulate sound patterns” (DepEd, 2016b, p. 11). Although only 13% of the MELCs cover competencies related to phonics-based instruction, teachers are still expected to unpack the MELCs. For instance, naming and sounding out of letters is unpacked to teach each of the letters individually.

In the Grade 2 MT curriculum, some competencies related to phonics include: “(1) reading a large number of regularly spelled multi-syllabic words... [and] (2) reading with understanding words with consonant blends, clusters, and digraphs when applicable” (DepEd, 2020b, p. 491-492). Out of 29 MELCs²⁸, only two or about 7% of the MELCs explicitly cover phonics-based instruction. Phonics and word recognition

²⁷ First Quarter and Second Quarter

²⁸ First Quarter and Second Quarter

is also one of the components of the MT curriculum in Grade 2. Learners are expected to “demonstrate knowledge of and skills in word analysis to read, write in cursive and spell grade level words [and] apply word analysis skills in reading, writing in cursive and spelling words independently” (DepEd, 2016b, p. 82).

In the Grade 3 MT curriculum, phonics and word recognition is no longer one of the domains (DepEd, 2016b). However, one competency related to phonics out of 15 MELCs²⁹ is “correctly spelling the words in the list of vocabulary words and the words in the selections read” (DepEd, 2020b, p 494). This comprises about 7% of the MELCs.

Phonics-based Instruction in Filipino

Teachers mentioned different approaches on how the phonics-based approach is done in teaching early reading in Filipino, such as using the Marungko approach and the Claveria approach. Participant E shared that using the Marungko approach sets the reading pace for the learners, “Sa pagbabasa po, gumagamit po kami ng Marungko *approach* o kung minsan pinapadalhan ko po sila ng mga Abakada³⁰ (*booklet*). ‘Yon po muna ‘yong ginagamit po namin sa pagbabasa para hindi po sila mabigla.” [“When it comes to reading, we use the Marungko approach, or sometimes I provide them with *Abakada* (booklet). That’s what we currently use in reading, so that they won’t be overwhelmed.”]

Participant M also shared that using phonics-based approach is effective when it comes to teaching beginning reading in Filipino, “Oo. Best³¹ – ‘yon talaga. Kahit

²⁹ First Quarter and Second Quarter

³⁰Abakada is commonly referred to as the first step in reading in Filipino (Orpilla, n.d.). This booklet contains about 30 lessons that will guide the learners in reading Filipino sounds, vowels, clusters, and blending (Creative Guro, 2022).

³¹Although phonics-based instruction is considered an effective approach in teaching beginning reading, especially in word recognition and fluency, assuming that it is the best approach in teaching beginning reading is misleading. To make sure that learners make progress in other aspects of

nagtu-*tutor* ako, *Sir*, na talagang hindi makabasa, ‘yon ang ginagamit ko talagang masasabi kong *effective* ‘yon.” [“Yes. It’s really the best. Even when I tutor a struggling reader, *Sir*, I use it, and I can vouch for its effectiveness.”] The progression from basic to complex is how Participant K described the importance of phonics-based approach as the basis for teaching early reading in Filipino. This is important before learners engage in more complex reading activities such as reading of sentences and stories:

Ang paborito ko ‘yong kapag nakaka-pantig na sila, tapos nakakabuo na sila ng isang salita, tapos dadagdagan mo ng ‘yung mga ano ba ‘yong tawag do’n – mga “ang” or “ng,” nakakabuo na sila ng pangungusap, tapos unti-unti nakakabasa na sila ng simpleng talata, tapos buong kuwento na. [My favorite part is when they can already identify syllables and form a complete word, then you add "ang" or "ng" to make it a sentence. They can already read sentences, and gradually they can read simple paragraphs, until they can read a whole story.]

Participant I added:

Okay, specific ba ‘yan? Okay sa Tagalog [*sic*] kasi ginagamit ko na nga – dati [*sic*] – dati kasi nu’ng una una [*sic*] ko, ginagamitan ko sila ng... uhm Abakada. Bumibili pa ako noon nu’ng *booklet* na Abakada kasi doon rin naman ako natuto. Maganda naman ‘yong *purpose* nu’n. *And then recently* ko lang na-realize ‘yong kagandahan ng paggamit ng Marungko. Kasi sa Marungko, hindi lang basta-basta mine-*memorize* ng bata. Dapat alam niya ‘yung *sound*, *memorized* niya kung anong pangalan ng *letter* na ‘yon, alam niya ‘yung *sounds* nung *letters* na ‘yon. At mas madali kasi sa kanilang uhm intindihin ‘yong *word*.

reading, most especially in relation to reading comprehension, phonics-based instruction should be acknowledged only as one essential part of a balanced literacy approach (Goldberg, 2022).

Kahit na magkakaiba or hindi sunod-sunod ‘yong pantig. Halimbawa sa *m*, sa *letter m*. ‘Yong *sounds* [sic] alam nila – dadagdagan mo siya ng *letter* ulit na makakasama niya: ‘yong *vowels*, pero hindi sunod-sunod. Magkaka – naka-*shuffle* s’ya, kumbaga. [Okay, is that specific? In [Tagalog] because I used to use... uhmm Abakada before. I used to buy Abakada booklets back then because that's how I learned. Its purpose was good. And then recently, I realized the beauty of using Marungko. Because in Marungko, it's not just about the child memorizing things easily. They should know the sound, memorize the name of that letter, know the sounds of those letters. And it's easier for them to understand the word. Even if the syllables are different or not in order. For example, in *m*, in the letter *m*. They know the sounds [sic]: you add another letter like the vowels. Even if they're not in order. It's like they're shuffled.

According to the teachers, pictures also help in teaching beginning reading, and this is why the Claveria technique also works for them. Participant G shared, “Yung *pictures* sa Claveria technique maganda siya ta [sic] para mas ma-*guide* ‘yung bata ‘pag tinuturuan mo siya. ‘Yung *picture* ‘yung *guide* sa *sounding* ng salita.” [“The pictures in the Claveria technique are great because they help guide the child when you're teaching them. The picture serves as a guide for the pronunciation of the word.”]

Data from class observations during the teaching of beginning reading in Filipino support phonics-based instruction. In Participant B's Filipino class, for example, she started one of her lessons with choral reading of syllabicated words such as *si-lid* [room], *na-li-li-go* [taking a bath], *na-ki-ta* [saw], *pu-mun-ta* [went], *dal-hin* [bring], among others. Syllabication is closely related to phonics because of the breaking up of individual words in order to successfully read them. In the middle of the independent activity, she called one of the learners, presumably a struggling reader,

and asked this learner to come beside her to read. Participant B brought out her big book on the Marungko approach and guided the reader in reading several syllabicated words such as *i-sa* [one], *i-i-sa* [only one], *mi-sa* [mass], *ma-mi* [noodle soup], and *si-si* [blame]. Figure 17 shows an example of a reading material based on the Marungko approach.

Figure 17

Reading Material based on Marungko Approach - Example

In the Grade 1 Filipino curriculum which is used at the start of the second quarter of the school year, *palabigkasan at pagkilala sa salita* [phonics and word recognition] is also one of the domains. Learners are expected to “maipamalas ang iba’t ibang kasanayan upang makilala at mabasa ang mga pamilyar at di-pamilyar na

salita” [“demonstrate various skills to recognize and read familiar and unfamiliar words”] (DepEd, 2016c, p. 5). Competencies related to phonics include “(1) *Nabibigkas nang wasto ang tunog ng bawat letra ng alpabetong Filipino* [Pronounce correctly the sound of each letter of the Filipino alphabet] [and] (2) *Napapalitan at nadadagdagan ang mga tunog upang makabuo ng bagong salita* [Replace and add sounds to create new words]” (DepEd, 2020b, pp. 196-197). Two out of 16 MELCs³² or about 13% fall under the domain of phonics and word recognition. In addition, the competency *pronounce correctly the sound of each letter of the Filipino alphabet* is unpacked to teach the letters of the Filipino alphabet individually.

Palabigkasan at pagkilala sa salita [phonics and word recognition] is also included in the domains of the Grade 2 Filipino curriculum. Learners are also expected to “maipamamalas ang iba’t ibang kasanayan upang makilala at mabasa ang mga pamilyar at di-pamilyar na salita” [“demonstrate various skills to recognize and read familiar and unfamiliar words”] (DepEd, 2016c, p. 22). Competencies related to phonics include “(1) *nabibigkas nang wasto ang tunog ng patinig, katinig, kambal-katinig, diptonggo at klaster* [pronounce correctly the sounds of vowels, consonants, consonant clusters, diphthongs, and clusters] [and] (2) *nababaybay nang wasto ang mga salita tatlo o apat na pantig, batayang talasalitaang pampaningin, at natutunang salita mula sa mga aralin* [correctly spell words with three or four syllables based on the basic sight words and words learned from lessons] (DepEd, 2020b, p. 200-201). Two out of 16 MELCs³³ are explicitly related to phonics and word recognition. However, these MELCs could also be further unpacked.

³² Second Quarter

³³ First Quarter and Second Quarter

Similar to the Filipino curriculum for Grade 1 and Grade 2, under *palabigkasan at pagkilala sa salita* [phonics and word recognition], Grade 3 learners are also expected to “maipamamalas ang iba’t ibang kasanayan upang makilala at mabasa ang mga pamilyar at di-pamilyar na salita” [“demonstrate various skills to recognize and read familiar and unfamiliar words”] (DepEd, 2016c, p. 45). Some of the competencies related to phonics are:

(1) *nababasa ang mga salitang may tatlong pantig pataas, klaster, salitang iisa ang baybay ngunit magkaiba ang bigkas at salitang hiram* [read words with three syllables or more, word clusters, words with the same spelling but different pronunciation, and borrowed words]... (2) *nababaybay nang wasto ang mga salitang natutunan sa aralin, salita di-kilala batay sa bigkas, tatlo o apat na pantig, batayang talasalitaan, mga salitang hiram at salitang dinaglat* [accurately spell words learned from the lesson, unfamiliar words based on pronunciation, words with three or four syllables, basic vocabulary, borrowed words, and abbreviated words]... (3) *nababaybay nang wasto ang mga salitang natutunan sa aralin/batayang talasalitaang pampaningin* [accurately spell words learned from the lesson or based on basic sight words] (DepEd, 2020b, pp. 203-206).

Two out of 28 MELCs³⁴ fall under the domain of phonics and word recognition, and these could still be unpacked into several learning objectives. This covers about 7% of the MELCs.

³⁴ First and Second Quarter

Phonics-based Instruction in English

Phonics-based instruction also plays an important role in teaching beginning reading in English. For instance, teaching CVC words such as *dog*, *cat*, *sit*, *man*, and *run*, is being done in teaching beginning reading in English. CVC stands for Consonant-Vowel-Consonant, and a CVC word is a three-letter word that follows this specific pattern. In a CVC word, the first letter is a consonant, the second letter is a short vowel, and the third letter is again a consonant. Phonics-based instruction is also used in teaching beginning reading in English. Participant F said, “Mag-sa-sounds po kami ng letters katulad nga po, *Sir*, ng sa CVC para maka-*create* po sila ng *words* na puwede po nilang basahin.” [We will practice letter sounds, just like in CVC, so they can create words that they can read, Sir.”]

It is also important to note that only two teachers, Participant A and Participant J mentioned the use of Fuller method in teaching reading in English. According to Participant A, “May ginagamit kami sa *English*, ‘yung *Fuller method* po. Parang ‘*Look and Say*’³⁵ ‘yung tawag doon.” [“We use something in English, the Fuller method. It’s like ‘Look and Say’, that’s what it’s called.”]

Participant J shared:

Sa English naman po, Sir, ‘yung k’wan [*sic*] ang ginagamit natin siyang *approach*, ‘yung *Fuller*. Ginagamit po ito para ma-*introduce* ang *reading* sa *English* lalo na po sa mga bata, syempre medyo mahirap ang *English* eh. Napansin ko po, Sir, na parang napapabilis niya ‘yong *process* ay *progress* ng mga bata sa pagbabasa sa mga *English* na salita po. [In English, Sir, we use the so-called approach, specifically the Fuller method. This approach is utilized

³⁵ Look and Say in teaching reading is not synonymous to Fuller method. Look and Say is an approach that teaches children to read and recognize whole words (Grugan, 2016).

to introduce reading in English, especially to children, considering that English can be quite challenging. I've observed, Sir, that this method seems to expedite the progress of children in reading English words.]

During the class observations of English reading lessons, it was observed that phonics-based approach was also utilized. In the English subject of Grade 2 learners, the alphabet was always recited. In Participant M's English class, before they proceeded to the actual lesson, the teacher initiated first a sort of spelling bee contest among the learners, which was a battle between the boys and the girls. Some of the words spelled were *soup*, *choice*, *mother*, *father*, *water*, *arrow*, *happy*, *angry*, and *summer*. When a learner misspelled the word, the teacher would ask the other members of the class to help the learner spell the word accurately, saying "Who wants to help (insert learner's name), *para ma-spell na niya nang tama 'yung word?*" ["Who wants to help (insert learner's name), so that he can finally spell the word correctly?"]

Before Participant B taught possessive pronouns, she led the review of the digraphs /ch/ and /sh/. Each of the learners was asked to provide a word starting with /ch/. Some of the words given were *church*, *cheese*, *charger*, *chalk*, and *chicks*. One of the learners even said, "*Katulad ng* [just like], 'It's so cheap!'" Several learners were not able to provide examples though. After /ch/, Participant B asked the learners to give examples of words with /sh/ sound at the beginning. Some of the words provided were *ship*, *sheep*, *shiny*, *sharpener*, *Shopee*³⁶, *show*, *sharp*, and *share*. Again, several learners were not able to provide their own examples. Later on, Participant B wrote words on the board with missing digraphs and let the learners complete the words.

Another example of the utilization of phonics-based approach in teaching beginning reading in English was when Participant I taught CVC words. Participant I

³⁶Shopee is an online shopping platform.

showed /a/, /e/, /i/, /o/, and /u/ to the class. However, she read the short vowel sounds using their letter names (e.g., /a/ was read as /ā/; /e/ was read as /ē/; /i/ was read as /ī/). After the choral reading of the list of CVC words, the teacher proceeded to read a short story entitled “My fat cat.”

In Participant C’s class, a part of her chalkboard was utilized for posters of each letter of the English alphabet with mouth shapes, indicating how each letter is sounded out. Figure 18 shows these posters.

Figure 18

Posters of the English Alphabet with Mouth Shapes

Phonics and word recognition is not in the Grade 1 English curriculum³⁷; the curriculum focuses on oracy/oral language development and not yet on reading/

³⁷ Grade 1 English curriculum is only used in the second half of the school year.

literacy instruction. In the Grade 2 English curriculum, however, the phonics and word recognition domain is already included, and learners are expected to:

demonstrate understanding of the relationship of phonetic principles of Mother Tongue and English to decode unknown words in English... analyze the pattern of sounds in words for meaning and accuracy... [and] ably read and spell out grade appropriate regular and irregular words in English (DepEd, 2016a, p. 27).

Grade 2 English competencies related to phonics include:

(1) reading the alphabets³⁸ [*sic*] of English and associate to phonemes... (2) giving the beginning letter of the name of each picture... [and] spelling high-frequency words with short a, e, i, o and u sound in CVC (DepEd, 2020b, pp. 178-179).

Three out of the 16 MELCs³⁹ are related to phonics. This comprises 19% of the MELCs.

Learners are expected in the Grade 3 English curriculum to:

demonstrate understanding of processes in sight word recognition or phonic analysis to read and understand words... demonstrate understanding of familiar sight and irregularly spelled words for automatic recognition... use word recognition techniques to read and understand words that contain complex letter combinations, affixes and contractions through theme-based activities and use familiar sight and irregularly-spelled words in meaningful oral and written tasks pattern (DepEd, 2016a, p. 53).

Some of the competencies related to phonics include:

³⁸ This could refer to the 26 letters of the English alphabet, which are associated to phonemes.

³⁹ First Quarter and Second Quarter

³² First Quarter and Second Quarter

(1) reviewing reading and writing short e, a, i, o, and u words in CVC pattern...
(2) reading phrases, sentences and short stories consisting of 2-syllable words... [and] (3) reading words, phrases, sentences and short stories consisting of words with consonant digraphs *ch* and *sh* and other words previously studied (DepEd, 2020b, p. 182-183).

Thirteen (13) percent (three out of 24) of the MELCs³² are about phonics and word recognition.

The data collected in this study corroborate those in other scholarly works. The teacher's knowledge of reader's meaning-construction process is important to instruction and instructional decision making, which is related to the Big Six of Reading (Konza, 2014). The big six of reading are part of the integrated language arts curriculum (DepEd, 2016a; DepEd, 2016b; DepEd, 2016c). Their inclusion implies that they are supposed to support or enrich early reading instruction. Desta (2020) discovered that teachers use traditional approaches in teaching reading which include the teaching of letters and sounds. The result is also consistent with the findings of Lewis-Fokum and Thomas (2018) who argued that teachers' preference for a skills-based approach in teaching reading was evident through the classroom instruction focused on phonics. Employing the Marungko approach is also common in Philippine early reading classrooms (Boltron & Ramos, 2021; Laurente, 2021; Santos & De Vera, 2020; Vales, 2019). However, effective comprehension instruction, which is the ultimate goal of reading, is supported by the knowledge and ability to employ a range of strategies (Ruddell et al., 2019) extending beyond a phonics-based approach, in teaching beginning reading. The teachers failed to harness the full capabilities of and opportunities provided by the big six of reading by focusing more on phonics instruction. Despite the importance of phonological awareness (Brown, 2014; DepEd,

2012b; Konza, 2014) and oral language (Brown, n.d.; Byrnes & Wasik, 2019; Carter & Hopkins, 2022; Chang et al., 2020; Konza, 2014; Shanahan & Lonigan, 2013) in the development of learners' reading skills, their importance in early reading instruction is often overlooked or inadequately addressed. The finding is also inconsistent with Suarez et al. (2020) where teachers follow an eclectic approach in teaching reading.

The finding indicates that the big six of reading are expected to be taught by the teachers as prescribed by the integrated language arts curriculum. These enrich or support the delivery of early reading instruction. Through the big six of reading, not only are more opportunities in teaching beginning reading enhanced, but they are also generated (Konza, 2014). Teachers employ phonics-based instruction for early reading instruction due to its perceived advantages in the development of reading skills among learners (Desta, 2020; Lewis-Fokum, 2018). This supports the importance of decoding as learners' foundation in reading.

The finding indicates that teachers' use of the phonics-based approach is supported by a misconception that it is the best approach in teaching early reading. Although phonics-related competencies are only a small percentage of the competencies in the languages curricula (DepEd, 2020b), the dominance of phonics-based instruction was still evident. Teachers included phonics skills in early reading instruction because they believed that these skills form the basis for learners before they approach more challenging reading tasks. It is also implied that learners who are struggling in reading have not developed their phonics skills yet, which impacts their reading of words, sentences, and longer texts. Teachers also believed that by learning the relationship between letters and their corresponding sounds, learners could decode unfamiliar words, which is crucial for fluent reading and comprehension. Hence, there was an apparent need to utilize and/or integrate phonics-based

instruction even if the competency that needed to be taught was not a phonics-related competency. This is further supported by Phajane's (2014) argument that the traditional approach to teaching beginning reading often heavily depended on reinforcing learners' phonics abilities. Likewise, the principle of basic to complex or reading from parts to whole, which clearly indicates a bottom-up approach to reading, is what is being followed by the teachers when it comes to phonics instruction, because it is believed to develop strong foundational reading skills.

The finding also implies that proficiency in teaching strategies is vital for teachers' instructional decision-making process and aids in working towards the achievement of the chosen instructional objectives. This also implies that teaching-strategy knowledge encompasses a comprehensive understanding that enables general problem solving, as well as specific strategies that can be employed to achieve reading-related instructional goals. Ontario – Ministry of Education (2003) also mentioned that phonics-based instruction must be complemented with other reading strategies to create a more comprehensive and balanced literacy approach.

Learners' Experiences

Another theme that emerged from the data is teachers' utilization of learners' experiences in early reading instruction. Crosby (1959) postulated that experiences serve as a compass for young readers in the process of creating meaning. Moreover, utilizing learners' experiences contribute to bridging the gap in reading instruction.

Utilizing Learners' Experiences Across Languages

The use of learners' prior experiences is deemed important in early reading instruction in the three languages (local language, Filipino, and English). The languages curricula also promote the importance of these experiences (DepEd,

2016a; DepEd, 2016b; DepEd, 2016c). Utilizing learners' prior experiences across languages is summarized in Figure 19.

Figure 19

Utilizing Learners' Prior Experiences

Aside from the *Big Six of Reading with a Focus on Phonics Instruction*, the participants shared that early reading instruction is not complete without utilizing the learners' prior knowledge. Participant A, for example, stated that these experiences could be harnessed to teach learners how to read: "Hindi lahat manggagaling sa'yo. Sila mismo magko-*contribute* sa kanilang pababasa, base sa alam na nila." ["Not everything will come from you. They themselves will contribute to their own reading based on what they already know."]

Participant G shared:

Ano, *Sir*, 'pag may dala-dala na sila, *Sir*, hindi ka na mahihirapan kasi doon ka na ano [*sic*] kung ano 'yong kailangan mong ituro. 'Pag wala pa silang *knowledge* halimbawa, katulad nga nu'ng *pandemic*, napagi-iwanan na sila, parang 'yong *Grade 3*. Parang napag-iwanan na sila. 'Yong mga *topic* mo sa *Grade 3*, mula sa pinaka *beginning*, babalikan. [If learners already have prior

knowledge, Sir, you won't have a hard time because that's where you'll teach what needs to be taught. If they don't have any knowledge yet, for instance during the pandemic, they were left behind, like the Grade 3. It's like they were left behind. The topics in Grade 3, from the very beginning, need to be revisited.]

Similarly, Participant I shared:

Uhm, mas ah-nadadagdagan 'yong kanilang natutunan *plus*, nare-*relate* kasi nila or mas nai-*improve* kasi 'yung kanilang pagbabasa. Uhm, gamit 'yung dati [*sic*] 'yung dating natutunan nila *plus* dadagdagan mo pa ngayon kapag uhm nag-*level up* na sila – lumipat na sila ng ibang *grade level* kasi pahirap – hindi naman siya pahirap nang pahirap kung hindi padami nang padami 'yung kailangang matutunan ng bata. Hindi na lang siya dapat nai-*stick* sa kung ano'ng natutunan niya – nung *previous grade* niya. [Uhm, their learning is enhanced, and they can also relate or improve their reading skills. Using what they already learned, and you add more to it since they have leveled up – they moved to another grade level where the amount (not difficulty) of knowledge that they need to learn increases. Learners should not be stuck with what they learned in their previous grade.]

Participant J added:

Malaking bagay 'yon (*prior experiences*), Sir. Lalo na kapag 'yun nga may *prior experiences* na sila sa pagbabasa. Hindi na ganun kahirap – *although* mahirap, pero *at least* kahit papano makatulong [*sic*] 'yung mga 'yon para mas maging mabilis sila sa pagbabasa. [Those (*prior experiences*) are a significant advantage, Sir. Especially when they already have prior experiences in reading. It is not as difficult anymore – although still challenging, but at least those experiences can to some extent help them be faster in reading.]

All teacher participants agreed on the importance of learners' prior experiences. Teachers shared that these experiences serve as the learners' foundation in acquiring more complex reading skills. They can also relate new lessons to the learners' existing knowledge and experiences. Using learners' prior experiences allows teachers to make connections and apply comprehension strategies effectively. Data gathered from the class observations and review of teachers' lesson plans revealed that teachers draw on the prior experiences of the learners usually through the use of questions at the start of the lesson, mid-discussion, and in the wrap up. The researcher also observed that the learners' prior experiences were used as scaffold to bridge the new reading lesson to what the learners already knew. These are exemplified below in how the learners' prior experiences are utilized in the local language, Filipino, and English. Across the languages, teachers utilized their learners' prior experiences through questioning to introduce a text to be read, make connections between the text/topic and the learners' experiences or between the old and the new lessons, and to let learners provide examples of what was asked of them. This was also a similar observation across grade levels.

Utilizing Learners' Prior Experiences in MT Reading Classes

Data from the class observations showed how teachers specifically utilized their learners' prior experiences in the Mother Tongue reading classes. During the class observations, Participant A utilized the learners' prior experiences during their MT class through questions. In the beginning part of the lesson when she taught the Letter li, she asked the learners, "Anya ti itsura it igges? Nakakita kayon *po ba* ti kastoy?" ["How does a worm look like? Have you seen a worm before?"]. Learners responded and shared their experiences with worms. One of the learners said, "Wen, *madam! Medyo nakakadiri po! Gumagaraw po siya! Kasla bulate po.*" ["Yes, Ma'am. It's kind of

disgusting! It moves! Like an earthworm.”] In the middle of the lesson, Participant B said, “*Sige nga. Kitaen tayo man nu malagip yo pay dagiti nagan ng mga ito (pictures).*” [Okay. Let’s see if you still remember the names of these (pictures).] In the latter part, Participant B reinforced the lesson by asking the learners more examples of words beginning with *letter i*.

When Participant D taught classifying naming words into categories⁴⁰, she asked questions as well, utilizing the learners’ prior experiences to connect it to the new lesson. In the beginning part of the lesson, she showed a picture of a doctor and asked, “Sinno atoy nadtoy *picture*?” [Who is in the picture]. When the learners said, “Doktor!” [“Doctor!”], Participant B proceeded to ask the supporting questions, “Nakakita kayon ba ti doktor? Anya man ngarud ti kulay ti bado na ti maysa nga doktor? *Sino na ang nasubukang mai-confine* diay ospital?” [“Have you seen a doctor? What is the color of a doctor’s attire? Who among you here have been confined in a hospital before?”] In the middle of the lesson, Participant B asked the learners, “Mabalin ba nga mangted kayo ti *more examples* nga nagan ti tao? Dagidiay kilala ‘yon. *P’wede na ‘yon.*” [“Can you give more examples of people’s names? The ones you already know. That’s okay.”]. In the independent activity at the latter part of the lesson, a table was drawn on the board that asked learners to supply the missing information, and this information was found in the learners’ community, such as names of people, names of places, names of things, and names of animals.

In one of the MT reading lessons in Participant M’s class, she showed pictures at the beginning of the class to activate prior knowledge of the learners. She showed a picture of people cleaning in the community and children playing in the park. She

⁴⁰ The teacher used an integrated language arts curriculum, and the topic involved reading activities (e.g., reading of words and phrases).

then asked the learners, “Ano so nagagawa ed kada litrato? Wala ira so agawa ed bilay mo ya naikonektam ed nagagawa ed kada litrato?” [“What are they doing in the pictures? Do you also do these things like what they’re doing in the pictures?”]. Before the class read sentences with rising and falling intonations like “A, siguradon ansakit lamët si ngipën mo!” [Surely, your teeth hurt!] and “Ina, panangasi yo, awit yo ak ëd dentista natan.” [Mother, please bring me to the dentist now.], Participant M asked the class questions related to these sentences, “*Nakakita na kayo ng dentist? Syupa so unsasakit so ngipen ton siya?*” [“Have you seen a dentist before? Have your teeth hurt before?”].

Although there were questions tapping on the learners’ prior experiences in the teachers’ lesson plans, these were in the Filipino language. The lessons are not in the mother tongue. Moreover, the MTB-MLE framework which is included and discussed in the MT curriculum also supports the use of prior knowledge in engaging learners in discussions where this prior knowledge could be seamlessly integrated and applied into the current knowledge schemes (DepEd, 2016b).

Utilizing Learners’ Prior Experiences in Filipino Reading Classes

Teachers also utilized their learners’ prior experiences in Filipino reading classes. Participant C utilized the learners’ prior experiences when she taught *salitang kilos* [action words]⁴¹ to her Grade 1 class. She asked the learners, “Ano-ano ang mga binili ni’yo sa *canteen* kanina? *Sige man ngarud*, ano naman ang ginawa ni’yo sa mga pinagkainan ni’yo? Naglilinis ba kayo (ng paligid)? *Good!*” “[What are the things you bought at the canteen a while ago? Let’s see, what did you do with the food wrappers? Do you clean our surroundings? Good!]. When she was discussing the topic, she was

⁴¹ The teacher used an integrated language arts curriculum, and the topic involved reading activities (e.g., reading of words, phrases, and sentences).

also able to relate it to the learners: “Basahin natin ang mga pangungusap. *Number one*, ‘Dala-dala ni Leron ang buslo ng papaya.’ Ano ang ginagawa ni Leron sa buslo o *basket* ng papaya? Nasubukan ni’yo na rin ba’ng magdala ng buslo ng papaya?” [“Let’s read the sentences. Number one, ‘Leron carries the basket of papaya.’ What does Leron do with the *buslo* or basket of papaya? Have you tried carrying a basket of papaya?”] She also asked the learners action words of that they do at home and in school. Afterwards, these were read by the learners.

In Participant F’s Filipino class, questions were also utilized to tap on learners’ prior experiences. Before they read a short story, “Ang Bilin ni Ina” [“Mom’s Reminder”], Participant F asked the class, “Ano ang ginagawa ni’yo tuwing Sabado?” [What do you do every Saturday?]. One of the questions asked after the story was related to the learners’ experiences: “Tutularan mo ba si Kris? Bakit? O bakit hindi?” [“Will you emulate Kris? Why? Or why not?”]. At the end of the lesson, Participant B said: “Ang pagsunod sa bilin ng magulang ay dapat ugaliin. Pagiging masunurin ay laging isipin. Sumusunod naman ba kayo sa mga magulang ni’yo? Ba’t ako minsan hindi ni’yo sinusunod?” [“Obeying the instructions of parents should be practiced. Being obedient should always be considered. Do you even obey your parents? Why do you sometimes not obey me?”]

The lesson plans of the participants also included questions that drew upon the learners' prior experiences. Examples of these are (1) “Maaari ninyo bang ilarawan ang iyong [*sic*] lolo at lola at ibahagi ang iyong karanasan tungkol sa kanila?” [“Can you describe your grandparents? Share your experiences about them.”]; and (2) “Maaari bang magbahagi ng iyong karanasan kung saan ipinakita mo ang iyong paggalang?” [“Can you share an experience where you demonstrated your respect?”]

Utilizing Learners' Prior Experiences in English Reading Classes

Similar to MT and Filipino reading classes, teachers also leveraged learners' prior experiences in English reading classes, primarily by utilizing questions. In Participant B's class, for example, while teaching about characters and setting, she engaged the learners by asking them about the stories they had read previously and encouraged them to share their thoughts and experiences related to those stories: "Was there a story *na* you read before? *Puwedeng* your favorite story. Tell something about it. *I-share ni'yo sa akin.*" ["Was there a story that you have read before? It could be your favorite story. Tell something about it. Share something about it with me."]. Participant B read the story "The Ant and the Grasshopper" which could also be found in the textbook. She stopped several times to ask questions such as, "*Kayo ba*, what do you do *tuwing* summer? Do you also chirp or *nagsi-sing ba kayo tulad ni* grasshopper?" [How about you, what do you do every summer? Do you also chirp or sing like the grasshopper?"]. Participant B also requested the learners to share something about their activities in summertime and on rainy days.

Another instance of utilizing the learners' prior experiences was observed in Participant F's English class during a lesson on sequencing events. Prior to reading a short story titled "Grandmother's Cooking" from the textbook, she posed several questions to the learners: "Raise your hand *lahat ng may lola!* What is the name of your grandmother? How old is she? *Ilang taon na siya?* Do [*sic*] your lola cook?" ["Raise your hand if you have a grandmother! What is the name of your grandmother? How old is she? How old is she? Does your grandmother cook?"]. During the read-aloud session of the story by the teacher, she continued to engage the learners by asking them questions such as "'*Yong lola ni Gab* is the best cook daw! *Nakatikim na rin ba kayo ng* lumpiang shanghai, fried chicken, and sinigang? What's your favorite?"

[Gab's grandmother is supposedly the best cook! Have you eaten lumpiang shanghai, fried chicken, and sinigang? What's your favorite?]. Relevant questions that allowed the learners to connect with the story were also posed: "Why do you think *importante ang pagsasabi* ng 'Thank you.'? If you are [*sic*] Gab, *kung kayo si Gab*, how will you show *na* thankful ka o *nagpapasalamat ka* to Grandma?" ["Why do you think it's important to say 'Thank you.'? If you are [*sic*] Gab, if you were Gab, how will you show that you're thankful or *nagpapasalamat* to Grandma?"]

In the English curriculum, one of the principles of the language learning process is contextualization. Through this principle, lessons are designed to align with specific learning outcomes, themes, or types of texts, aiming to assist learners in effectively utilizing relevant language skills, grammatical items or structures, and vocabulary in both spoken and written language. The goal is to adapt language usage appropriately to suit the purpose, audience, context, and cultural considerations (DepEd, 2016a). This implies that relating the learning content to real-life situations, familiar contexts, and the learners' existing knowledge and experiences enhances learners' understanding and engagement. This facilitates meaningful connections between new information and what learners already know, making the learning process more relevant, meaningful, and effective.

The participants' lesson plans also incorporated questions that tapped into the learners' previous experiences. Some of these questions include (1) WH questions about a picture (e.g., grasshopper) before a story is read; and (2) What are the parts of a book that you've learned from your previous grade? Some of the questions in the review part of the lessons plans include (1) What are the different sounds of animals that you've learned before? and (2) What can you recall from the stories "Belling the Cat" and the "Crow and the Pitcher?" In establishing the background for the lesson

(i.e., motivation), questions are also used, such as (1) Have you seen a school of fish swimming in the river/aquarium/pond? and (2) For you, what makes stories interesting?

Utilizing learners' prior experiences is practiced in all three reading classes (MT, Filipino, and English) and across grade levels. The data from the focus group discussions further validated this finding. Participant F further said that without these experiences, grade level standards will not be met:

'Di ba, *Sir*, in every grade level may standards 'yan. Paano 'pag walang *stock knowledge* pa 'yang bata sa bagong *grade level* niya for example, tapos medyo mahirap na 'yong mga *competencies*, ano mangyayari sa *standard [sic]* ng *grade* na 'yon? [Isn't it, Sir, that there are standards for every grade level? What happens if a child doesn't have sufficient prior knowledge in their new grade level, for example, and the competencies are somewhat challenging? What will happen to the standard *[sic]* in that grade?].

Moreso, Participant L mentioned that learners' readiness to read is affected by their prior experiences: "K'wan, *Sir*, para bang *foundation* 'yan para makabasa 'yong bata. Nai-enhance din ang kanilang *understanding* din *[sic]* at magkakaroon ng *recognition* sa *topic* ganun. Apektado niyan ang *learners' readiness*." ["Sir, it's like a foundation for the child to be able to read. It also enhances their understanding and enables them to recognize the topic. Learners' readiness is affected by it."] This implies that from these prior experiences new knowledge and skills are built accordingly. Utilizing these experiences makes reading instruction more relevant, meaningful, and effective. It can also personalize learning experiences.

The sociocognitive model of meaning-construction also draws on the reader's pool of prior beliefs and knowledge, which is a huge part of the knowledge-construction

process (Ruddell et al., 2019). The finding is also supportive of McGlynn-Stewart's (2012) study on how teachers' literacy experiences affect their practices in teaching literacy. Teachers highly value learners' prior experiences as these help address the individual literacy needs of the learners in the classroom.

The finding primarily implies that teachers utilize the learners' prior experiences since these serve as the foundation for the learners as they earn more complex reading experiences. Making use of the learners' prior experiences in teaching them how to read helps both the teacher and the learners create associations between the learners' existing knowledge and the new knowledge to be learned (Ruddell et al., 2019). This indicates that the retrieval of information as the learners' prior experiences are activated prepares the learners' minds to integrate the newly learned knowledge. In this way, the learners' prior experiences work as scaffold. Moreover, teachers highly value the literacy experiences, skills, and knowledge of their learners when it comes to reading instruction (McGlynn-Stewart, 2012), implying that incorporating these in early reading instruction acknowledges the importance of individual backgrounds. Hence, the theme *Learners' Experiences* relates to the teachers' early reading instruction practices.

Medium of Instruction and/or Learning Area

Since this study deals with multilingual reading instruction, one prominent theme that emerged from the data is *Medium of Instruction and/or Learning Area* (in connection to the local language, Filipino, and English). MTB-MLE uses the local language as a learning area and medium of instruction (DepEd, 2016d). Likewise, Filipino and English are also taught as separate subjects and used as medium of instruction as well. The theme *Medium of Instruction and/or Learning Area* represents the use of languages as medium of instruction and/or subject areas. *This* theme

primarily refers to the teacher's deliberate and purposeful use of language(s) when teaching learners how to read in different language contexts. These three languages are used in early reading instruction, and the participants agreed that these languages are influential in teaching learners how to read. Languages play a significant role in early reading instruction because of their importance in aspects such as development of phonological awareness and vocabulary, form of communication, and social interactions (Brown, 2014). They also encompass the collective ideas, beliefs, and opinions expressed by individuals and entities across the world (Tupas, 2009). Hence, it is crucial for teachers to employ language(s) in the classroom that acknowledge(s) the diverse backgrounds of the learners, taking into account the broader society, as well as their unique culture and linguistic heritage (Fillmore & Snow, 2000).

When asked about the extent of how language/s influence/s learners how to read, Participant B shared, “Yang *language* po, napakaimportante po niyan. Lalo sa mga bata. Kahit anong gawin nila kailangan nila ‘yan. Bibili sa tindahan? Gagamit ng wika. Gan’un din kapag makikipag-usap sa ibang tao.” [“Language? That is very important. Especially to children. Whatever they do, they need it. Need to buy something from a store? They’ll use a language. The same thing with conversing with other people.”] Because languages are primarily used in communication, teachers recognize their role in teaching early reading to learners.

As discussed earlier in the section on teachers’ language ideologies, teachers have different opinions on the languages used in the classroom. When it comes to teaching early reading, they consistently supported their statements regarding these three languages (local language, Filipino, and English): the local language is less important than the official languages; the official languages, Filipino and English, are more useful in terms of academic, economic, and social aspects of learners’ lives.

Local Language as MOI and/or Learning Area

The participants maintained their opinions that learners are not proficient in this language (in connection to its use as MOI and as a learning area) and using it in teaching reading is confusing to the learners. Participant C shared:

Medyo mahirap na pong ituro ang Iloko sa pagbabasa. Dapat alisin na 'yang (paggamit ng) *mother tongue* kasi *mostly* talaga ang mga bata ngayon hindi na sila nag-i-Iloko. Maski pansinin ninyo, Sir. Sa bahay ninyo hindi na sila nag-i-Iloko. Maski dito sa komunidad natin, bibihira na ang nagsasalita na [*sic*] ng Iloko. [It is somehow challenging to teach reading in Iloko. The (use of) mother tongue should be removed (from the curriculum) because most children nowadays are no longer proficient in Ilokano. Take note of it, Sir. Even in your home, they no longer speak Iloko. Even here in our community, very few still speak the language.]

Participant E added, "Mas nahihirapan po sila, Sir, sa (paggamit ng) mother tongue. Kasi kahit ako mismo medyo nahihirapan (laughs). Pagdating po kasi sa *mother tongue* hindi naman sa tinatamad 'yong bata, parang nalilito po sila lalo." ["They are actually having a harder time, Sir, with the mother tongue. Even I myself somewhat find it challenging (laughs). When it comes to the mother tongue, it's not that the children are lazy; it seems that they get more confused."]

In addition, Participant J shared:

Mahirap talagang ituro, Sir, ang *mother tongue* (bilang wika). Parang hindi na siya *first language* ng mga bata. Ta's may *confusion* na sa /e/ ta's /ə/, /əy/, 'yung mga ganon, Sir. Imbes na basahin nila ng pa-Filipino biglang, 'Ay, hindi dapat Pangasinan nga [*sic*] /ə/ dapat,' parang gan'on, Sir. Nakakalito. [It is indeed difficult to teach mother tongue, Sir. It seems it is no longer the first language

of the children. There is confusion between the sounds /e/ and /ə/, /əy/, and similar ones, Sir. Instead of reading it in Filipino, they suddenly say, 'Oh, it shouldn't be /e/, it should be Pangasinan /ə/, ' something like that, Sir. It's confusing.

The researcher noted that during the observations of the MT reading classes, it seemed automatic for the learners and teachers to use Filipino instead of mother tongue, especially in interacting with each other. Here is an example:

Teacher: Ano na naman 'yan ginagawa mo? [What are you doing again?]

Learner: Wala po, madam. [Nothing, madam.]

This was also done in the teaching of a reading skill. Here is an example when Participant A taught the name and sound of letter Bb:

Teacher: Ibuka ang bibig. Sabihin /b/. /b/. Sige, *uliten* yo. [Open your mouth.

Say /b/. /b/. Okay, please repeat it.]

Learners: /b/. /b/.

Teacher: Kayang-kaya ni'yo naman na pala. [You can definitely do it.]

However, it was also observed that both teachers and learners were also capable of communicating in the local language. Here are examples:

Iloko Student: Madam, mabalin umisbo? [Teacher, may I pee?]

Iloko Teacher: Aguray ka lang biit. Gan-gani tayo malpasen. [Just wait a little.

We're almost done.]

Pangasinan Teacher: Alam may libro. [Get the book.]

Pangasinan Student: Iner, *madam*? [Where, Ma'am?]

Moreover, the MT curriculum guide that is originally in English is intended to be translated into the local language to make it more contextually relevant. However, teachers still use the MT curriculum written in English.

Filipino as MOI and/or Learning Area

Filipino language was identified in the interviews as the language teachers usually use in the three subjects (MT, Filipino, and English), specifically in explaining concepts explicitly, giving instructions for tasks, answering questions, making clarifications, and providing feedback in the context of teaching beginning reading. When asked why, all the participants remarked: “Naiintindihan ng lahat ito.” [“Everyone understands it.”] Likewise, the teachers shared that the learners primarily make use of this language in answering questions, asking questions and making clarifications, and sharing of own knowledge and experiences related to the task or activity in reading classes. When asked why, all of the teachers said: “Naiintindihan ng lahat ito.” [“Everyone understands it.”] Moreover, it was argued that this language is what learners use in interacting with each other. Participant D shared:

Filipino po, *Sir*, ang kadalasang ginagamit sa pagtatanong (sa tatlong *subjects*). Kasi po ‘pag ang *subject* po namin ay MTB [*sic*], talagang kailangan mag-Ilokano po ‘yan. Pero may mga estudyante nga po akong hindi siya marunong mag-Ilokano kaya trina-*translate* ko po ‘yan sa Filipino. ‘Yon po. So pati sila naka-Filipino na rin. [Filipino, *Sir*, is commonly used in asking questions. When our subject is MTB [*sic*], it really needs to be in Iloko. But I have students who don’t know how to speak in Iloko, so I translate it into Filipino. So even they also speak/use Filipino.

Participant C added,

Kasi po nakasanayan na po natin ‘yan at saka pag nanunuod po sila, wala naman pong Ilokano na mapanood sa *TV*. Maski ‘yong mga *cartoons*, kung hindi *English* eh Tagalog [*sic*] na siya. At saka pag kinakausap na rin ng guro at kasama sa bahay nila, Filipino na rin ang ginagamit, *Sir*. [Because they have

gotten used to it, and when they watch TV, there are no Iloko shows available.

Even the cartoons, if they're not in English, they're already in Tagalog. And when teachers and family members talk to them, they also use Filipino, Sir.

All the participants claimed both in the interviews and FGDs that the Filipino language is the language mostly used in early reading instruction because it is the national language, and both teachers and learners are proficient in it. It was also claimed that is easily understood regardless of where one came from. The participants also specified that learners should be reading more in this language, because this language is what they are going to use even up to the last of their days. Participant F explained that “[Ang] wikang Filipino po ay ginagamit sa pakikipag-usap kahit nasaan ka sa bansa, at nakakatulong kung magbabasa pa sa Filipino ang mga bata.” [“Filipino language is used for oral communication regardless of where you are in the country, and it will be useful for learners to read it more.”]. Participant C quipped, “Filipino po madalas ang ginagamit kasi ‘yung mga Ilokano naman pong mga bata, nakakaintindi naman po sila ng Filipino. Kumbaga gine-*general* ko na ‘yung pag-i-*explain* sa kanila gamit ‘yong Filipino.” [“Filipino is often used because the Ilokano children, for example, understand Filipino. It's like I'm generalizing the explanation to them using Filipino.”] Participant G said, “Kahit hanggang paglaki nila, dadalhin nila ‘yang wikang Filipino.” [“Even when they grow up, they will carry the Filipino language with them.”]

Despite the claim that Filipino is mostly used in reading instruction, some participants from the Iloko group of teachers and Bolinao group of teachers also acknowledged the use of the local language and Filipino together in early reading instruction, especially in answering questions, asking questions, making clarifications, and sharing of own knowledge and experiences related to the task and activity. According to them, doing this helps both the native speakers and the non-native

speakers of the local language. Participant D explained, “Kasi may mga *words* din po sa Filipino na medyo malalim na, so kailangan ko siyang *i-translate* sa *mother tongue* para mas lubos nilang maintindihan.” [“Because there are also words in Filipino that are somewhat deep, so I need to translate them into the mother tongue for them to understand more deeply.”] Participant E said that there are learners who use Filipino in the three reading subjects, and there are learners who use their mother tongue; learners who are not proficient in Filipino use their mother tongue, “Syempre, *Sir*, ‘pag Filipino nga [*sic*] mas naiintindihan ng lahat. Kasi nga may hindi naman nagma-*mother tongue*. ‘Yong marunong talaga, ‘yun (‘yung mga gumagamit ng *mother tongue*).” [“Of course, *Sir*, everyone understands Filipino. Because not everyone speaks the required mother tongue. Those who are really proficient (are the ones who use their mother tongue.)”] This helps learners communicate with a wider range of audience (see the discussion on translanguaging, p. 193).

English as MOI and/or Learning Area

The English language, on the other hand, is still considered an important language in early reading instruction. English has been an official language in the Philippines since the American colonial period, and it has played a significant role in shaping the country’s history and culture (Martin, 2008).

Most of the participants (about 77% of them) shared that learners are encouraged to read in and speak this language because it would allow them to communicate and connect with different people across the globe. The English language would also allow them to participate in the global economy, access information, and engage in international collaborations. Participant F reported, “Ako po, *I encourage them to read in English* at gamitin ito kasi nga po maiintindihan sila ng mga *foreigners*. So, kailangan nila mag-*practice*.” [“I encourage my learners to read

in English and speak this language because it would allow them to be understood by foreigners. So, they need to practice.”]

Participant L noted:

Kasi ‘di ba ano, lahat ng *rules* ngayon na nababasa mo, lahat ng mayro’n sa ano *instruction* [sic], *directions*, ‘yang mga ganiyan, ‘di ba ano [sic] puro *English* na. So, ‘pag nakapagbasa na sila ng *English*, parang marami na silang malalaman sa ano [sic], mundo. Kasi ‘yan ang pinaka-importante at pinakamagagamit nila talaga. [Because you see, all the rules that you read nowadays, all the instructions, directions, and things like that, they are all in English, right? So, when they can read English, it’s like they already know a lot about the world. Because that is the most important and most useful language for them.]

Participant M shared that she even practices an English-only policy in her classroom, “Ah, ako din sa klasrum, may ano kami, may *time* kami na, ganito lang ang salita namin. ‘Pag *English subject*, *English* lang din ang salita dapat namin – para mahikayat pa sila – hindi lang nasa iisang *language*.” [“Ah, we have this time in the classroom where we only speak the English language. If it’s our English subject, we should only be speaking English – to encourage them – not just in one language.”]

Despite their expressed respect towards the English language as a superior language, all the participants also accepted the fact that some learners find it difficult to speak and read in this language, and they themselves find it hard to teach it. Participant H said that learners find it difficult to understand the language: “Nahirapan sila... sa pag-ano (pag-inintindi) nila sa mga ano (salita), kasi nahihirapan silang magbasa lalo na sa pagsasalita (sa English). Hirap sila na ibigay ‘yong *words* na kailangan sa *English*. Nahirapan sila doon. [They also have difficulty

(understanding) certain (words), especially when it comes to reading and speaking (in English) They find it challenging to provide the necessary English words. They struggle with that.]

Participant B commented that many learners do not know this language yet, and there is a need to strengthen the way it is taught to them, especially when it comes to reading in this language. Participant B shared, “Dahil hindi pa nila alam itong *language* na ito na kahit sa *Grade 3*, ganito din, kailangan puspusan po ‘yong pagtuturo sa kanila. Sa *Grade 3 last year* pa naman ‘yun ng (paggamit ng) *mother tongue* (bilang MOI).” [“Because they are not yet familiar with this language, even in Grade 3, thorough teaching is necessary for them. Grade 3 is the last year of (using) the mother tongue (as the MOI).”]

The Grade 1 teachers also wanted to push for using this language at the beginning of the school year. Participant A shared, “Habulan ang mangyayari kasi nga *late* na na nagi-*start* (‘yong pagtuturo ng *English*).” [“There will be a need to catch up because it (teaching of English) starts late.”] Participant J also said, “Medyo nahihirapan ‘yong mga bata (sa English) tapos mabibigla na ay may *English* na sa *third quarter*. Para sana hindi mabigla, start na sa *first quarter* pa lang, kahit sa *sounds* lang muna at *basic word recognition*.” [“The children are having some difficulty (with English), and then they are suddenly surprised that English is introduced in the third quarter. To prevent any surprises, it would be better to start as early as the first quarter, focusing on sounds and basic word recognition first.”] At present, the English subject for the first graders is taught starting in the third quarter of the school year. Grade 2 teachers also lamented that the English subject of the first graders is taught at the later part of the year, and they claimed that it affects how they learn this language in the second grade, because at Grade 2 learners are still beginners in reading in English.

Participant D shared, “Mas maganda talaga kung magsisimula ang *English* nila (*Grade 1*) sa simula pa lang, parehas sa simula ng Filipino at MTB [*sic*]. Para hindi naman (sila) kawawa pag dating dito sa *Grade 2*.” [“It’s really better if their (*Grade 1*) English subject starts at the beginning of the school year, just like when they begin with Filipino and MTB [*sic*]. So, they won’t struggle when they reach *Grade 2*.”] Moreover, this learners’ difficulty in the English language is also observed by *Grade 3* teachers. Participant I mentioned, “Ti’gnan mo, *Sir*, ah, kahit *Grade 3* na sobrang nahihirapan pa rin sila. “[Look, *Sir*, even though they’re already in *Grade 3*, they’re still having a really hard time.”]

Data collected from the classroom observations also showed this *Medium of Instruction* (in connection to MT, Filipino, and English). Although the main medium used by the teacher in teaching explicitly, asking questions, making clarifications, among others was said to be Filipino, and that using English was encouraged, there seemed to be a discrepancy with their actual teaching practices. All of the participants were observed to be using different patterns in their language use when teaching reading. For instance, the local language and the English language are used along with the Filipino language even in a Filipino class. In her Filipino class, it was noted when Participant B said during class recitation, “Magbigay pa ng mga salitang nagsisimula sa letrang b. Magaling! *Asino pay? Very good!*” [“Give more examples of words starting with the letter b. Very good! Who else? Very good!”] After watching a short clip, Participant G asked her class, “Nag-*enjoy* ba kayo sa pakikinig sa *video? Natarusan yo?*” [“Did you enjoy listening to the video? Did you understand?”] When teaching figures of speech (a topic supposed to be taught in the mother tongue), Participant M provided examples of metaphors, “Halimbawa nito ay ‘Dragon kung magalit ang aking ina.’ ‘Si Marga ay isang magandang bulaklak.’ Ano ‘yong ginagawa

rito? Nagko-*compare* ka rito. Kawangis. *Atalusan n'yo?* ["Example of this is 'My mother is a dragon.' 'Marga is a beautiful flower.' What are you doing here? You are actually comparing. Similar. Did you understand?"]

As expected, less English was used in Grade 1 reading classes, whereas Filipino dominated the Grade 2 and Grade 3 reading classes. Mother tongue was used more often though compared to the English language. However, learners were encouraged to use Filipino and English. Learners were also exposed to reading materials in the Filipino and English languages. Remedial instruction also focused on reading in Filipino and/or English, regardless of the grade level.

During the focus group discussions, the teachers still placed importance towards using Filipino and English as MOI in early reading. Participant A asked, "Bakit hindi gamitin 'yong mas magagamit nila *over time*? Lahat ngayon nasa Filipino at English na." ["Why not use the languages that will be more useful to them over time? Almost everything now is in languages Filipino and English." Participant H said, "Babalik ulit tayo, *Sir*, sa anong ginagamit sa mga *contest*. 'Yon lang po." ["Let's go back, *Sir*, what is being used in contests. That's all, *Sir*."]

The theme *Medium of Instruction and/or Learning Area* as a teachers' early reading instruction practice is consistent with the sociocognitive model of meaning-construction (Ruddell et al., 2019). The teacher plays a crucial role in orchestrating instruction and facilitating the process of meaning-construction, which was observed in their automatic and/or facilitating the use of language/s in early reading instruction. The impact of various languages on multilingual classrooms was also investigated by Kartika-Ningsih and Rose (2018), and they discovered that interactions between the teacher and the learner are summarized using four patterns: interacting with the MT only, interacting with the second language only, interacting with both the MT and the

second language, and the mixing of the three languages (L1, L2, L3). These patterns are related to elaborating meanings in instruction. Similar to the findings of Djorbua et al. (2021), teachers determine the language of instruction to effectively deliver the lesson, backed by the reasoning that that language is used as the common ground for every learner, despite the existing language policy mandated by law and implemented by DepEd.

The theme *Medium of Instruction and/or Learning Area* strongly implies the presence of language bias in the teachers' use of language/s in early reading instruction. The mother tongue is seen as a barrier, Filipino is recognized as the language of all, and the use of English is encouraged because of its perceived benefits. However, the teachers also make use of these languages together and mix them as they and the learners take part in the meaning-making negotiation process. This implies that hegemonic teachers' language ideologies on multilingualism is quite different from their actual teaching practices. This disconnect refers to the gap between the affective conditions and cognitive conditions of the teachers, which is somehow inconsistent with the sociocognitive model of meaning-construction, where the former and the latter are highly dependent on each other (Ruddell et al., 2019). This further implies that this could also be related to the complex language classroom realities (e.g., Dubeck et al., 2012) and students' needs (Mokhtari et al., 2010), resulting in the teachers' beliefs being overpowered by the complexities of the factors inside the classroom (such as conducive learning environment and diversity of learners [e.g., Dubeck et al., 2012]) pressure brought by the workplace, among others).

Different patterns of language use are used in multilingual classrooms (Kartika-Ningsih & Rose, 2018). The theme implies that teachers should be aware of the

inherent power of each language and be mindful of their usage in the classroom (Brevik & Rindal, 2020). Moreover, teachers have the agency to choose what language is aptly appropriate as language of instruction (Djorbu et al., 2021). It is also crucial to ensure that learning takes place when teachers interact with learners using the target language, while also considering the learners' level of understanding (Crichton, 2009). According to Kemsley (2015), while teachers can significantly influence the language used by learners, it is also vital for them to actively encourage and embrace the learners' comfortable language, which could be their mother tongue, instead of simply tolerating it or, worse, prohibiting it. Hence, the theme *Medium of Instruction* is related to the teachers' early reading instruction practices in Philippine multilingual classrooms.

Translanguaging

The theme *Translanguaging* revealed that participants employed this language practice in early reading instruction across the three language subjects (MT, Filipino, and English). Translanguaging is the use of multiple languages fluidly and flexibly in the classroom context to leverage the student's existing linguistic resources and bridge the gap between their native language and the language of instruction (España & Herrera, n.d.). Although some of the participants thought of multilingualism and language varieties as confusing when learning how to read (see previous discussion on hegemonic language ideologies, p. 113), teachers were found to be frequently practicing translanguaging, which is actually common in multilingual educational settings (De Los Reyes & Bagona, 2022). All the participants mentioned code-switching and translations as translanguaging practices that happen in an early reading classroom, specifically in MT reading class, Filipino reading class, and English reading class. Participant I shared:

Kasi ang bata, kahit nagtuturo ka diyan ng *lesson* mo at ginamit mong *language* ay hindi nila naiintindihan, walang kuwenta ‘yang *lesson* mo. Kahit mag-*assessment* ka diyan, hindi nila ‘yan naiintindihan; magtanong ka sa kanila hindi nila naintindihan kasi in the *first place* hindi nila naiintindihan ‘yong ginamit mong salita, eh. Kahit daldal ka diyan nang daldal ng *English*, halimbawa, - *try* mo sa kanila. Ako – ito na-*discover* ko. Kapag nagtuturo ako ng *English*, ‘pag nagtuturo ako ng *English* [*sic*] at wala ng sumasagot sa akin, ibig sabihin no’n wala na silang naiintindihan. Pero ‘pag *translate* ko na ‘yan sa Tagalog [*sic*] o kaya’y Ilokano, andami na diyang magre-*recite*. Naiintindihan na nila. [Because even if you teach your lesson but use a language that the children don’t understand, your lesson becomes useless. Even if you give them assessments, they won’t understand these. If you ask them questions, they won’t understand because, in the first place, they don’t understand the language you used. Even if you keep speaking in English, for example, try it with them. As for me, this is what I have discovered. When I teach in English and nobody responds to me, it means they don’t understand anymore. But when I translate it into Tagalog [*sic*] or Ilokano, there are so many who participate and recite. They already understand.]

Participant B shared, “Mayroon pong *instances* ng *translanguaging*. Hindi ko po namamalayan syempre Ilokano ka po *then* kapag ano na hindi ko po namamalayan na naka-Tagalog [*sic*] na *then* bumabalik po ako sa Ilokano. *Then*, nag-*translate* na din po ako sa kanila.” [“There are instances of translanguaging. I may not realize it, but when you speak in Ilokano, for example, I may unconsciously switch to Tagalog [*sic*], and then I switch back to Ilokano. Then, I also translate for them.”]

Participant E shared that translanguaging aids in comprehension:

'Pag may *words* po na mahirap, kailangan mo talagang mag-*translate* o mag-*code-switch*. Halimbawa nasa *English* kami, i-Filipino ko siya. 'Pag hindi pa rin naiintindihan, mina-*mother tongue* ko, Bolinao. *More on stories, Sir*, lalo na sa *English*. Hindi naman po nila maiintindihan pag dire-diretsong *English*, so, itra-*translate* ko po 'yon. Ta's 'pag halimbawang Filipino ta's may *word* doon na hindi maintindihan, itra-*translate* ko po siya sa Bolinao. [When there are difficult words, you really need to translate or code-switch. For example, if we're in English, I translate it into Filipino. If it's still not understood, I switch to the mother tongue, Bolinao. Especially when it comes to stories, Sir, particularly in English. They won't understand it if it's in straight English, so I translate it. And if, for instance, it's in Filipino and there's a word there that they don't understand, I translate it into Bolinao.]

Participant J believed that translanguaging works in reading instruction involving all three languages, especially in English:

'Pag Filipino po na *subject* namin, *majority* talaga ng ginagamit na salita ay Filipino. So, Filipino talaga kami. 'Pag sa *English* po, ginagamitan ko po siya ng tatlo. Una muna 'di ba English, tapos hindi nila naiintindihan i-*translate* ko sa Filipino, 'pag hindi pa rin nila maintindihan, i-*translate* ko sa *mother tongue*. O puwede ring *mother tongue to Filipino*. O *mother tongue to English*. [When we have a Filipino subject, majority of the words we use are really in Filipino. So, we are really in Filipino mode. But when it comes to English, I use three languages. First, of course, English, then if they don't understand, I translate it into Filipino. And if they still don't understand, I translate it into their mother tongue. Or it can be from their mother tongue to Filipino. Or from their mother tongue to English.]

Participant B further added that translanguaging happens naturally to both the teachers and learners in early reading instruction, “Hindi lang po ako ang ang nagko-*code-switch* at *translate*, maski mga bata po, *Sir*; parang natural na, lalo sa pag-i-*explain*.” [“I’m not the only one who code-switches and translates, even the learners, *Sir*; it seems natural, especially when explaining.”] Participant D mentioned that in early reading instruction, the switching of languages still results in comprehension or understanding when learners interact with each other, “Syempre, *Sir*, nagagamit nila (‘yung mga wika) sa gusto nilang paggamitan depende na, *Sir*, sa *purposes* nila. ‘Pag may *interaction* ganun.” [“Of course, *Sir*, they use the languages based on their desired purposes, *Sir*. When there’s an interaction, like that.”]. In early reading instruction, translating words from one language to another, according to Participant A, expands the vocabulary of the learners, “Mas dumarami ‘yung mga salitang nalalaman nila (mga bata), *Sir*, kasi hindi lang sa isang wika mo minsan itra-*translate* eh”. [They (children) are learning more words, *Sir*, because sometimes you translate not just into one language.”] However, Participant L commented that translanguaging in early reading instruction is also time-consuming:

Ano, mahirap din kasi syempre ang mas nag-napapatagal ‘yung *time* kasi kailangan mo ring i-*translate*, pagkatapos itra-*translate* mo na naman, so parang dagdag na namang *work* kasi nakakapagod magsalita nang buong araw puro ka lang *translate* nang *translate*. [Well, it’s also challenging because it takes more time since you need to translate, and then translate again, so it is added work. It’s tiring to speak all day, constantly translating one thing after another.]

Teachers across grade levels employed translanguaging similarly. It was used mostly in early reading instruction during teacher-directed instruction, guided activities,

explanation and/or clarification of difficult concepts, and asking questions to check learners' comprehension.

Translanguaging in MT Reading Classes

The data collected from the classroom observations of MT reading classes revealed that translanguaging occurs in the multilingual early reading classroom. Some of the observed instances included code-switching and translations, which are subsumed under translanguaging (De Los Reyes, 2018). Below, sample instances of these observed phenomena for further examination and understanding are presented and discussed.

In Participant J's MT class when she taught pronouns⁴² *siyak* [I], *sika* [you], and *sikami* [we], Participant J read a short paragraph and asked several questions after, "Sangkaiba ed grupo si Rea, Edith, siyak tan sika. Sikami so sakey na manggawa ya alolong.' *Basahin nga po natin ito. Sino gustong mag-volunteer po para magbasa?*" ["Rea, Edith, you, and I are in one group. We are among those who will build the hut.' Let's read these sentences. Who wants to volunteer to read?"]. When giving out the directions, Participant J code-switched to Filipino. When she asked who wanted to volunteer to read, she actually translanguaged by using features of English and Filipino.

Another translanguaging instance was noted in Participant C's reading class. She asked the learners, "Nakakita kayon 'ti balay 'ti ansisit? 'Yong bahay ng duwende?" ["Have you seen a dwarf's house? The house of a dwarf?"] Participant B translated from the mother tongue, Iloko, to Filipino.

⁴² The teacher used an integrated language arts curriculum, and the topic involved reading activities (e.g., reading of words and phrases).

After letting the learners read several Iloko words such as *uliteg* [sibling], *lames* [fish], and *manong* [older brother], Participant D reminded the learners, “Adalen yo dagitoy nga balikas ken patang, *mga salita at phrases*, tapno ammo yon to nga basaen nu agpa-*spelling* ngak kada kayo. Okay, naturusan?” [Study these *balikas ken patang*, words and phrases, so that you will know how to read them when I ask you to spell them. Okay, (did you) understand?]. Participant D translanguaged as part of the discussion of the lesson, utilizing the mother tongue alongside Filipino and English. It could be noted that perhaps, *salita* [word] and *phrases* are more familiar to the learners than *balikas ken patang* [words and phrases]. Spelling could also be a more familiar term to the learners than its mother tongue word counterpart *panangibalikas ti letra*.

In the MT textbooks or learner’s material, translanguaging was also noted. In the Iloko Grade 1 MT textbook (Alcayaga et al., 2017), sentences such as the following are utilized: “Adalen ti *pictograph*” (p. 134) [“Study the pictograph.”]; “Agsursurat ni Alma iti *assignment* na.” (p. 142) [“Anna is writing her assignment”]; and “*Synonyms* wenno kapada – awag kadagiti balikas nga agpada ti kaipapananda.” (p. 147) [“Words that have the same meaning are called synonyms or *kapada*.”] The Pangasinan Grade 1 MT textbook, however, serves as a Pangasinan primer. Hence, the content focuses on the letters of the alphabet and examples of words and phrases in Pangasinan language.

In the Iloko Grade 2 MT textbook, one of the directions says, “Kumpletuen ti *rhyme* ken usaren dagiti sumaganad a balikas. Isurat ti sungbat iti papel.” (Macob et al., 2016, p. 4). [“Complete the rhyme and use the following words. Write your answer on your paper.”] Another one says, “Kitaen dagiti baro nga *electric gadgets*.” (Macob et al., 2016, p. 68). [“Check out these new electric gadgets.”]. In the Pangasinan Grade 2 MT textbook (Magtang et al., 2013), stories included in the textbook also used words

other than the local language. Here is an excerpt of the story “Say Nurse mi éd Eskuwelaan” [“Our Nurse in School”]: “Nansumpal iya éd elementarya tan *high school* ya walay nawat a dayéw... Natan, sakéy lan *nurse* éd nanurungan ton *high school* si Roda.” (p. 9) [“She finished elementary and high school and received awards... Roda is now a nurse at her high school alma mater.”] Directions also use words other than the local language. Here are examples: “Limpékan so dugan *spelling* éd kada bilang.” (p. 55) [“Encircle the correct spelling in every number.”]; and “Basaén irayan balikas tan isulat éd dilin papel iray *consonant cluster*.” (p. 64) [“Read the following words and write the consonant cluster on the paper.”]

Several stories in the Iloko and Pangasinan Grade 3 MT textbook included words from English. Here is an excerpt of one of the Iloko stories: “Nagluto ni Athena ti pammigat da. Nag-*bake* ni Bridgette ti *cookies* para ken lolong na.” (Bamba et al., 2017a, p. 81) [“Athena cooked their breakfast. Bridgette baked cookies for her grandfather.”] Also, here is an excerpt of one of the Pangasinan stories: “‘Pasensya kayo la ta andukëy so *traffic*,’ kuwanën Sally... ‘Ben, insaliwan ta ka na taluran balon kamiseta tan *backpack*.’” (Bamba et al., 2017b, p. 8). [“‘Sorry, traffic is long,’ said Sally... ‘Ben, I bought you three new shirts and a backpack.’”] One of directions of an activity in the Pangasinan MT textbook states, “Iyaliling yo ya unla kayon man-*camping* ëd luob na limaran agëw. Manilisa na 20 tutuo, pasën, tan agagamil a labay yon nanëngnëng diya ëd *camping* yo.” (Bamba et al., 2017b, p. 35). [“Imagine you are going camping for five days. List down 20 people, places, and things you want to see in your camp.”] In one of the reading activities, translations were also used in some words such as *talagnaw* [excitement] and *sësëg* [enthusiasm] (Bamba et al., 2017b, p. 51).

In MT reading classes across grade levels, translanguaging was seamlessly integrated into all aspects of the lesson, with careful consideration of the teacher's language use. In addition, translanguaging was mostly used to aid the teacher and the learners when they encountered unfamiliar words in the local language, to check learners' understanding of the lesson, to give directions, and to utilize words not in the local language but are familiar to the learners.

Translanguaging in Filipino Reading Classes

The data gathered from classroom observations of Filipino reading classes demonstrated the occurrence of translanguaging in the multilingual early reading classroom. The observations revealed various instances, such as code-switching and translations, which can be categorized as forms of translanguaging. Sample instances of these are presented and discussed below.

In teaching *sanhi at bunga* [cause and effect] to Grade 3 learners, Participant I said during the discussion, "(Insert learner's name), ano ang pumapasok sa iyong isipan (kapag ilog ang pinag-uusapan)? Okay. May mga isda. *Adda dagita lames.* Isda. Ano ang sabi ni *teacher*?" ["(Insert learner's name), what comes to mind (when we talk about rivers)? Okay. There is fish. There is fish. Fish. What did teacher say?"]. Participant B translanguaged to connect the Filipino language to the mother tongue. Interestingly, learners also translanguaged during the discussion. One of the learners even answered Participant B's question on what comes to mind when rivers are talked about, "May mga *bisukol* po!" *Bisukol* is an Iloko term for *snail*. The learner used both Filipino and Iloko. When Participant B told the learners to bring out their textbook, she also reminded them, "Ilapag nang ganito (maayos) ang libro sa inyong *desk*. Okay, handa na ba kayong makinig. *Let's see nga* if handa na makinig?" [Place the book like this (properly) on your desk. Okay, are you ready to listen? Let's see if you're really

ready to listen?"] The reminder and the question after it also showed an instance of translanguaging.

During the discussion of *pagsunod sa panuto*⁴³ [following directions], Participant B also employed translanguaging in Grade 1 reading class: “Ang panuto ay nagsasagawa ng mga tagubilin ng mga gawain. Okay. ‘Yun ‘yung mga *directions*, kung paano mo gagawin. Maaaring pabigkas o pasulat ang panuto. So, ano ‘yung dapat nating tandaan?” When learners were doing the activity, Participant B said, “Partakan yo nga isurat ‘yang pangalan ni’yo sa papel. Number one na po tayo. Unang panuto.” [“Write your name fast on your paper. We are already in number one. First directions.”] Participant B was able to utilize the three languages, the local language (e.g., *partakan* [be fast]), Filipino (i.e., medium of instruction), and English (e.g., *number one*), in the discussion and activities.

When Participant D taught *pangunahing ideya* [main idea], she also utilized translanguaging with her Grade 2 class. She asked her class, “Tumutulong ka ba sa mga gawain sa ating kapaligiran? *Kasanum ar-aramiden atoy ngay? Ano-ano ang mga ginagawa ni’yo? Okay. Mayroon akong picture dito sa blackboard. Ano ang makikita rito? Maruming kapaligiran. Very good! Okay. Kayat yo ba ti kastoy?*” [“Do you help with activities for our environment? How do you help? What do you do? Okay. I have a picture here on the blackboard. What can you see here? Dirty environment. Very good! Okay. Do you want this?"]. Participant D was also able to utilize three languages.

During the reading of the story “Ang Kaarawan” [“The Birthday”], instances of translanguaging were also observed in Participant M’s Grade 3 class. Participant M stopped at a certain point in the story and asked the learners, “Alam ni’yo ba ang

⁴³ The teacher used an integrated language arts curriculum, and the topic involved reading activities (e.g., reading of words and phrases).

kaarawan? Sino ang magbi-*birthday* dito? May plano din ba kayo sa *birthday* ni'yo?" ["Do you know what a birthday is? Who will be celebrating a birthday here? Do you also have a plan for your birthday?"]. Participant M also said after learners had responded to the stopping point questions, "*Wow naman! Sosyal naman 'pag ang theme ng birthday mo ay may maraming balloons at may clown pa.*" ["Wow! It's fancy when your birthday theme has lots of balloons and even a clown."]. It could be surmised that the English words *birthday*, *theme*, *balloons*, and *clowns* are more familiar to the learners, and their utilization along with the Filipino language shows familiarization with words are considered in the Participant M's language use.

In the Grade 1 Filipino textbook, the word *canteen* is used instead of *kantina* in a map (Calatrava et al., 2017, p. 12). In addition, words like *broccoli*, *zucchini*, *potassium*, and *calcium*, which do not have direct translations in the Filipino language, are also utilized (Calatrava et al., 2017, pp. 20-21). These words are highlighted in bold in the book, signaling that they are not Filipino words. This is similar to the Grade 2 Filipino textbook where the words *dengue*, *junk food*, *desk*, and *internet* are also in bold to indicate that these are not Filipino words (Garcia et al., 2013, p. 12). In one of the texts in the Grade 3 Filipino textbook, the following was also noted: "Anong laro ang alam mo? Siguradong tulad ko, ang naisip mo agad ay *online games* na nilalaro sa *computer*. Tama ba?... Kung marami lamang goma o *rubber band*, pagdugtung-dugtungin lamang ang mga ito." (Amaflor et al., 2017). "[What game do you know? Surely just like me, the first thing that comes to mind are online games which are played in a computer. Am I right?... If there was enough *goma* or rubber band, just connect them together.]" Words not in the Filipino are also highlighted in bold.

In Filipino reading classes across different grade levels, translanguaging was employed to establish connections between the Filipino language and other languages

to supplement it, to pose questions to learners, and to assess their comprehension. Additionally, translanguaging was utilized to give directions and reminders. Words not in Filipino were incorporated as well, taking into account learners' familiarity and linguistic background. Translanguaging occurred throughout all aspects of the lesson, considering the teacher's language use.

Translanguaging in English Reading Classes

Instances of translanguaging were more obvious in English reading classes. Both the teachers and the learners seemed to be more comfortable in speaking in Filipino and the mother tongue. This was expected because the participants' third language is English. The data collected from the classroom observations of English classes revealed how these translanguaging instances occurred. These observed instances encompassed code-switching and translations, both of which fall under the umbrella of translanguaging. Below, sample instances of these observed phenomena are presented and discussed, to facilitate further examination and enhance understanding of translanguaging.

During the discussion of the elements of a story to Grade 2 learners, Participant H translanguaged when she said, "A character or characters are persons or animals in the story. *Sila 'yong mga tao o hayop sa kuwento*. The characters have actions and dialogues. *May buhay sila. Nagsasalita sila.*" ["A character or characters are persons or animals in the story. They are the people or animals in the story. The characters have actions and dialogues. They are alive. They speak."] Participant A translated the English words into Filipino to make sure that they are understood by the learners.

Participant L did the same thing when she also discussed the elements of a story to her Grade 2 learners: "So, *mayroong iba't-ibang elemento ang kuwento*. 'Yan *din 'yong tinatawag nating* elements of the [*sic*] story. *Sa English, ano ang tauhan?*"

[“So, we have different elements of the story. That’s what we call elements of the story. In English, what is a character?”] Participant L tried to connect the discussion to the previously taught topic *sangkap ng maikling kuwento* or elements of a story in Filipino.

When Participant D showed the parts of a book to her Grade 2 learners, she also did translanguaging: “These are the parts of the book. *Kumuha ng isang libro at ituro ang part ng libro na sasabihin ko.*” “[These are the parts of the book. Get one book and point to the specific part of the book that I will tell you.”].

Participant B taught words ending with *-ight* to her Grade 3 class. She did it by translanguaging as well:

Okay. I-G-H-T. *Kadalasan (ang mga salitang ito ay) mayroon silang i-g-h-t.* The sound *po niyan ay parang layt/*. Okay, *dito muna po kayo tumingin sa may board natin.* Okay *na po? Anya atoy ngata? At night. One more. At night. At night. When we say, at night ibig sabihin sa gabi.* Okay, next. *Ano ba ang ibig sabihin ng bright? Maliwanag.* Okay, *parang ‘yung ilaw natin.* [Okay. I-G-H-T. Usually (these words), they have i-g-h-t. The sound is /ayt/. Okay, look at our board. Okay? What do you think this is? At night. One more. At night. At night. When we say, at night that means *gabi* [night]. Okay, next. What does the word bright mean? Bright. Okay, just like our lights.]

Participant B frequently translanguaged using features of English, Filipino, and Iloko in discussing the lessons. When she asked what the phrase *at night* and the word *bright* mean, she already expected her learners to give the translations of the two.

Regarding the Grade 1 English textbook, not many instances of translanguaging were noted. In one of the texts, the words *biodegradable* and *non-biodegradable* are translated into Filipino, *nabubulok* and *di-nabubulok*, respectively (Estuye et al., 2018, p. 96). This implies that these two English words are still not

understood by the learners. This is similar to Grade 2 English textbook. Not so many instances of translanguaging were noted. Names of food such as *pansit* [noodles] and *ensaymada* [brioche bread], which are also their names in Filipino and in the mother tongue, are used in the book (Pado et al., 2013, p. 5). The Grade 3 English textbook does not promote translanguaging (Ponciano et al., 2015). However, in one of the stories in the book, the word *bantay* [guard] was used as a name for a dog and the word *tagpi* [patch] was used to name a teddy bear (pp. 121-130). The lack of instances of translanguaging in the textbooks could be related to how English is considered as the language and symbol of intellectual and material dominance (Medilo, Jr., 2016).

In English reading classes across grade levels (Grade 2 and Grade 3), translanguaging was utilized to ensure that the lesson was comprehended by the learners, taking into account their proficiency in the English language. There was also a need to utilize this practice in all aspects of an English reading lesson.

In the review of lesson plans in the three early reading subjects, however, only one language was typically used in each of the three subjects, which was different compared to when the lessons were delivered and to the textbooks (most especially Mother Tongue and Filipino) primarily used in class. The lesson plans in the mother tongue subject are written in Filipino instead of the local language. The collected data from the focus group discussions further verified the results that translanguaging was utilized in meaning-making and was proven to be a useful tool in early reading instruction. The teachers sustained their opinion on translanguaging – that although it is time-consuming, it really helps the learners tread upon the intricacies of the three languages used in early reading instruction. Participant G claimed, “Parang *strategy* mo na rin ‘yan, *Sir*, para mas mai-*deliver* mo nang maayos ‘yung *lesson* at para mas intindihan na rin ng mga bata, *Sir*.” [“It’s like a strategy, Sir, so you can deliver your

lesson well, and so that learners can understand better, Sir.”] Participant J said, “Parang nakakaubos talaga, *Sir*, ng oras, syempre *one language* lang dapat, di ba? Pero kailangan mo eh (na mag-*translanguage*). Kailangan din ng bata.” [It is like time consuming, Sir, of course it should only be one language, right? But you need to do it (*translanguaging*). Learners need it, too.”]

Moreover, the teachers also clarified in the focus group discussions that mixing of languages (a pattern of language use) happens automatically to them when teaching reading in each of the three languages (MT, Filipino, and English). Participant H explained, “Hindi mo na nga yata namamalayan eh. Kasi ang *goal* mo is mapaintindi sa bata ‘yung kailangan niyang basahin.” [“It seems like you're not realizing it. Because your goal is to make the child understand what they need to read.”] Participant L mentioned that “*Automatic* talaga, *Sir*, (ang paghahalo-halo ng wika) siguro kasi may *exposure* na tayo sa tatlong wika na ‘to.” [“It's really automatic, Sir, (the mixing of languages), maybe because we have exposure to these three languages.”]. Participant K said that teachers had the autonomy to use the language appropriate in teaching learners how to read. She said, “Bilang *teacher*, alam mo na dapat kung anong wika ang dapat mong gamitin sa klase o dapat basahin ng mga bata. O dapat mong ipabasa, ipaintindi sa kanila. Na sa'yo ‘yun.” [“As a teacher, you should already know which language you should use in class or which language the children should read. Or you should let them read and understand it. It's up to you.”]

The theme *Translanguaging* is supported by the sociocognitive model of meaning-construction (Ruddell et al., 2019). The teacher needs to be attentive to instances of communication breakdowns and should possess knowledge of effective communication strategies to clarify meaning. Being able to adapt instructional strategies accordingly is crucial in enhancing the process of meaning-negotiation, and

being able to do so shows the teacher's resource of metacognitive strategies. The finding also reflects the results of the study conducted by Cenoz and Gorter (2017) where they claimed the existence of both pedagogical translanguaging and spontaneous translanguaging in schools. This implies that translanguaging is a natural phenomenon in multilingual contexts. Makalela's study (2019) also had the same result. The strategic use of translanguaging supports multilingual learners. Translanguaging happens frequently in Philippine multilingual classrooms (De Los Reyes & Bagona, 2022; Monje et al., 2021). In classrooms where another language is taught aside from the home language, code-switching is predominantly employed for a variety of purposes such as interpreting complex concepts, assessing learners' comprehension (Kumar et al., 2021), and providing clarifications (Zhang, 2023).

The theme *Translanguaging* primarily implies that translanguaging (code-switching and translating) is a natural occurrence in multilingual classrooms. More so, in reading instruction, translanguaging acts as a tool in sewing the languages together to deepen understanding. Pedagogical and spontaneous translanguaging (Cenoz & Gorter, 2017) is one way of understanding how translanguaging transpires in multilingual classrooms. Teachers utilize this practice to serve a specific and strategic purpose, as seen in pedagogical translanguaging (e.g., translanguaging practices to gain a deeper understanding of the information and/or texts) and spontaneous translanguaging (e.g., translanguaging practices initiated by the learners). Since the focus of this study was on teachers' early reading instruction practices and not specifically on the learners', emphasis was given to pedagogical translanguaging. The finding implies that intentional use of translanguaging in early reading instruction allows teachers to easily make connections between concepts through the seamless use of multiple languages. Through this practice, the diverse linguistic needs of the

learners are met. Moreover, translanguaging opens up possibilities for a broader multilingual language utilization (Makalela, 2019).

There may be some inconsistency on the translanguaging practices across the lesson plans, textbooks, and the actual delivery of lessons, however, it is important to note that the content of textbooks did not come from teachers. The lesson plans were also prepared beforehand. In the actual delivery of lessons, translanguaging practices were needed to mitigate and/or prevent communication breakdowns and sustain learners' understanding of the content/topic. In addition, translanguaging faces challenges from the politics of language and language learning, primarily due to the status and perceived influence of major languages (Cenoz & Gorter, 2017). Given these findings, the theme *Translanguaging* is considered as a teachers' early reading instruction practice in multilingual classrooms.

Learning Environment and Resources

Regarding early reading instruction support, the participants acknowledged the importance of print-rich classrooms and the use of technology in early reading instruction.

Print-rich Environments

When it comes to print-rich environments in early reading instruction, the participants all stated that these promote literacy development and even enhance learning outcomes. Participant B shared:

Ang kagandahan po ng isang *print-rich* na *classroom* ay kahit saan ka lumington ay marami kang babasahin. *Then* 'yong mga babasahin ay hindi po siya mahihirap lang. Ang kagandahan po ng ganu'n ay 'yong bata syempre ay susubukan niya pantigin 'yong mga *words* o 'yong *words* na nakikita niya. [The

beauty of a print-rich classroom is that wherever you look, there are many things to read. And the reading materials are not just difficult ones. The good thing about it is that children naturally try to syllabicate the words they see.]

Participant I added:

Kasi ang mga *prints* [sic] natin sa classroom natin, *related* din naman ‘yan sa mga *lessons* natin. So ‘yung mga bata ‘pag uhm lalo na ‘pag marunong na siyang [sic] magbasa, pagpasok pa lang niya [sic] at mahilig talaga siyang [sic] magbasa, nakasulat d'yan sa pader tapos nag-*lesson* kayo, ‘Ay, *Ma’am!* ‘Yan po ‘yong nabasa ko!’ *Exposure with* [sic] *words* kasi. ‘Yung bata itra-try niyang basahin, kahit minsan ‘yung mga bata naglalaro-laro lang sila diyan. Tapos magbabasa-basa lang sila ng kung ano-ano d’yan. Kahit ‘yung bata hindi masyadong marunong ‘pag ‘yung kaibigan niya ‘yung, ‘Halika, turuan kita; basahin natin ‘yan.’ Matututo ‘yong bata. [Because the prints [sic] in our classroom are also related to our lessons. So, when the children, especially when they already know how to read, enter the classroom, they are really eager to read. When you have a lesson and there's something written on the wall, they would say, ‘Oh, Ma'am! That's what I read!’ It's all about exposure to words. The child will try to read them, even sometimes when the children are just playing around. Then they read various things. Even if a child is not very skilled, when their friend says, ‘Come, let me teach you how to read that,’ the child learns.]

A print-rich environment gives a teacher extra time do other tasks while the learners are reading, like what Participant M commented:

Malaki ang *effect* ng *print-rich classroom* sa bata kasi, *Sir*, kasi kasi [sic] kahit *busy* ka, andiyan ‘yung time na magbabasa lang sila. Oo. May mga *reports*,

nandiyan naggagawa ka, oh i-a-ano mo sila, igo-*group by group* mo sila, kunin n'yo 'yung ganito ganiyan, gagawin nila—gagamitin nila, nagagamit nila lalo sa pagbabasa, *Sir*. [The effect of a print-rich classroom on children is considerable because, *Sir*, even when you're busy, there's time for them to read. Yes. When there are reports that you are working on, you can assign them in groups. You can ask them to work on certain tasks—they will use and apply what they have learned, especially in reading, *Sir*.]

It was also observed during class observations that the classrooms of participants have a reading corner. The reading charts, flash cards, self-learning modules, and textbooks are displayed here. However, it was observed that there is a dearth of reading materials in the mother tongue. The participants said that the existing charts and flash cards in Filipino and English are usually used in remedial reading instruction. Filipino and English are primarily used in remedial reading instruction. See Figure 20 for the samples of charts and flash cards in Filipino and English.

Figure 20

Charts and Flash Cards in Filipino and English – Examples

In Bolinao, there are no readily available reading materials in the mother tongue. Bolinao teachers said they were tasked to make the reading materials themselves and use them even if these had not undergone quality control yet. Participant E shared, “Wala kaming ginagamit na LM (MT *textbook*) na galing sa DepEd. Nagta-*translate* kami. Ta’s kailangan na gamitin ‘yon kahit hindi na dumaan sa *quality assurance*. Kasi wala kaming gagamitin.” [We don't use any MT textbooks

from DepEd. We translate instead. Then, we have to use those materials even if they haven't gone through quality assurance yet. Because we have nothing else to use."] However, as of September 2022, their MOI in Grade 1 to Grade 3 was changed to Filipino (R. Caalaman, personal communication, September 16, 2022). Language mapping was done, where learners were asked to respond to questions in Bolinao. The teachers argued that based on the result of the language mapping, Bolinao was no longer the learners' mother tongue.

Technology in Early Reading Instruction

Teachers also use non-print reading materials through information and communications technology (ICT) equipment such as audio-visual devices as early reading instruction support. One example of a non-print material used in reading instruction is videos. Participant A believed that using videos aids retention among learners, "Syempre nagbibigay ako ng maraming babasahin. Pero maliban doon, mas maganda na napapanood na ng mga bata kasi halos lahat naman na ng mga bahay dito may TV na. Napansin ko na mas madali 'yong *retention* sa mga bata." ["Of course, I provide a lot of reading materials. However, aside from that, it's better if the children can also watch because almost every household here already has a TV. I noticed that retention is easier for children that way."]

Participant E commented:

Mayroon na po kaming mga TV dito, Sir. Gumagamit din po kami ng mga *videos* na pinapanood sa [*sic*] mga bata, mga *videos* na nada-*download* na puwede nila gayahin. Minsan [*sic*] gumagamit po kami ng *laptop* tapos kino-*connect* po namin sa *speaker*. [We already have TVs here, Sir. We also use videos that the children watch; downloadable videos that they can imitate. Sometimes we use a laptop and connect it to a speaker.]

Participant M shared:

Sa ngayon, sa *generation* ngayon, maganda na panoorin [*sic*] natin (sa) 'yung [*sic*] mga bata ng mga *videos etcetera* para habang nakikita nila, nagagaya din nila. Kasi ang mga bata ngayon, mas sanay na sila sa *gadget*. Kaya *helpful* ang *videos* para sa panonood sa *reading*. [In today's generation, it is beneficial to let children watch videos, etcetera, because as they see them, they also imitate them. Because children nowadays are more accustomed to gadgets, videos are helpful for enhancing reading through visual engagement.]

Data collected from the classroom observations showed that teachers utilized videos in early reading instruction. Videos included nursery rhymes, alphabet songs, and DepEd video lessons⁴⁴. These were in Filipino and/or English. They also utilized powerpoint presentations in their lessons; the topics and pictures were included here. Figure 21 shows a screenshot of an example of a DepEd video lesson.

⁴⁴During the COVID-19 pandemic, different learning modalities were adopted. Most public schools in the country adopted modular distance learning. Because of this, both DepEd and teachers initiated the development of video lessons that learners could watch even in the confines of their homes. Most of these videos can be accessed on youtube.com.

Figure 21

DepEd Video Lesson – Example

Grade 2 Filipino Q1 Ep1: Pag unawa sa Teksto Gamit ang Karanasan

DepEd TV - Offi...
692K subscribers

Subscribe

725

Share

Note. Here is the link of the video 'Grade 2 Filipino Q1 Ep1: Pag-unawa sa Teksto Gamit ang Karanasan' [Grade 2 Filipino Quarter 1 Episode 1: Understanding Text Through Experience]

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xvYTwIbFTU&ab_channel=DepEdTV-Official

Moreover, materials not limited to videos were also listed in their lesson plans such as songs and audio-speaker. The focus group discussions further verified the theme *Learning Environment and Resources*. Participant H commented that technology is essential in teaching beginning reading, "Parang *requirement* na, *Sir*, ano na mayroon ng mga [*sic*] *technology* sa classroom. Maghahanap na rin minsan, *Sir*, ang mga bata. Kasi *exposed* na rin sila sa *technology* ngayon eh. Tulad ng sa *YouTube*." ["It's like a requirement already, Sir, to have technology in the classroom.

Sometimes, the children themselves will also look for it, Sir, because they are already exposed to technology nowadays. Just like YouTube.”]

The use of technology to support early reading instruction also eases the delivery of the reading lesson, according to Participant G: “Mas madali na magturo, Sir, naman ah ‘pag may *TV* na ganyan, *projector*. Hindi mo na kailangan *print* nang *print* ng kung ano-ano. Mas mabilis na. Mas maganda ang *delivery ng lessons*.” [“It’s easier to teach, Sir, when there’s a TV like that, a projector. You don’t need to keep printing various materials. It’s faster. The delivery of lessons is better.”] The teachers consistently agreed that technology aids the teaching profession. They also noted that digital materials such as YouTube videos are easily accessible now.

The theme *Learning Environment and Resources* is also reinforced by the sociocognitive model of meaning-construction (Ruddell et al., 2019). The learning environment is an essential component of the meaning-negotiation process. When a teacher creates a learning environment (e.g., print-rich classroom that supports a reader [Rehman, 2019]), this environment strongly influences the reader’s purpose, because the physical and social aspects of the classroom should promote reading and provide the necessary resources and support for learners (Ibrahim et al., 2022). This implies that this environment plays a crucial role in shaping the reader’s purpose or their motivation and intention behind reading. The finding *Learning Environment and Resources* also corroborates the implementational challenges of MTB-MLE found by Monje et al. (2021). One of the activities required for the successful implementation of the program is writing big books. There was a dearth of big books and other reading materials in the mother tongue in the classrooms. Monje et al. (2021) found that lack of relevant teaching materials challenges MTB-MLE. It was the top reason why schools are not fully implementing the program. The USAID (2014) study also found

this lack of learning materials when it comes to the mother tongue. Regarding the importance of a print-rich classroom, Prosper and Nomlomo (2016) found that multilingual reading resources contribute to literacy development. The finding is also congruent with the study of Castillo (2017). He remarked that digital materials support development of early reading skills and cross-language transfer from mother tongue to English, for example. Moreover, the findings of the studies of Alcott (2021) and Samat and Aziz (2020) mentioned that digital technology has the ability to engage and interest learners, and technology and the integration of multimedia materials demonstrate advantageous outcomes.

The finding indicates that the unavailability of print-rich environments cannot sustain nor support the literacy development of the learners. A print-rich multilingual classroom can support learners in developing their reading skills across languages and creating engaging learning spaces, because print-rich classrooms provide opportunities for learners to practice reading and develop a genuine love for it. A print-rich classroom environment has proven to be highly effective in assisting and motivating learners to improve their literacy skills (Ibrahim et al., 2022). The result also primarily implies that the use of technology in early reading instruction helps the teachers deliver the content of their lessons. Technology includes digital equipment and digital reading materials. The use of these materials supplements and supports the traditional print materials in reading and promotes multimodal learning (Alcott, 2021). This further implies fast-paced spread of technology gives teachers access to a wide range of digital resources which can also be used as print resources. *Learning Environment and Resources* as a theme through the print-rich classrooms and use of technology, therefore, is included in the teachers' early reading instruction practices.

Research Question 3:

Are the teachers' language ideologies reflected in their use of language/s in early reading instruction?

The results of the first two research questions were utilized to answer the third research question. Whether or not these language ideologies are reflected in the teachers' use of language in early reading instruction is summarized in Figure 22, the thematic diagram of teachers' language ideologies and use of language/s in early reading instruction. Figure 23 specifically shows how these language ideologies are matched and/or interrelated with the teachers' early reading instruction practices (as representatives of early reading instruction).

Figure 22

Thematic Diagram of Teachers' Language Ideologies as Reflected in Early Reading Instruction

Figure 23

Matching Teachers' Language Ideologies and Early Reading Instruction Practices

The teacher's role is of utmost importance in actively negotiating and facilitating the construction of meaning in the text (or language/s) and social context of the classroom (Ruddell et al., 2019). The affective conditions and cognitive conditions of the sociocognitive model of meaning-construction (Ruddell et al., 2019) are highly interactive with one another. The teachers' language ideologies could be associated with the affective conditions of the sociocognitive model of meaning-construction, as these conditions involve teachers' beliefs (Ruddell et al., 2019). The teachers' early reading instruction practices could be related to the cognitive conditions of the said

reading model, as these conditions involve teachers' strategies in teaching reading (Ruddell et al., 2019).

English as a Highly Valued Language

Teachers held linguistic assumptions that glorify the English language. Various reasons were also cited to underscore the significance of this perceived dominant language, encompassing its economic, social, and academic importance (see p. 113). During the interviews, Participant I highlighted the prominence of the English language as the language of internationalization and stressed that DepEd is responsible for cultivating globally competitive learners through proficiency in this language, which could be refined in early reading instruction. Using English as the main language of competitions in and among schools also supports the theme *English as a Highly Valued Language*. Moreover, using English in early reading instruction was commonly associated with intelligence and believed to contribute to the expansion of knowledge. English phrases were also used to give positive feedback and encourage learners such as "Good!" and "Very good!"

The teachers' hegemonic language ideology *English as a Highly Valued Language* is reflected in at least three of the extracted themes in the teachers' early reading instruction practices: *Big Six of Reading with a Focus on Phonics Instruction*, *Medium of Instruction and/or Learning Area*, and *Learning Environment and Resources*. This is further discussed below and related to the teachers' use of language/s. Moreover, Figure 24 provides the diagram of the relationship of the said teachers' language ideology to the teachers' early reading instruction practices.

Figure 24

English as a Highly Valued Language in Early Reading Instruction

Teachers placed significant value on the use of the English language in early reading instruction. When it comes to the big six of reading, oral language in English was developed through instances of recitations. Various nursery rhymes such as the “Alphabet Song” promoted phonological awareness. Materials were used for vocabulary, and texts were read for fluency and reading comprehension. Teachers wanting to start teaching beginning reading in English to Grade 1 learners not later than the first quarter of the school year, focusing first on phonics and basic word recognition, also supports *English as a Highly Valued Language*.

The focus on phonics instruction shows how the hegemonic language ideology *English as a Highly Valued Language* persists, not only because reading in English is part of the curriculum. It is also because of the high regard of the teachers towards this language. Phonics instruction is an essential component of early reading development, focusing on the relationship between letters and the sounds they represent (National Reading Panel, 2000). Teachers' use of phonics instruction in English (see p. 159) is anchored on the belief that using this approach would benefit the learners in developing their reading skills in English. From simple to complex, learners are expected to ultimately read or confront more complex and/or challenging reading tasks.

Moreover, *English as a Highly Valued Language* is reflected in teachers' intentional and strategic utilization of the English language as medium of instruction in early reading instruction (see p. 187). Teachers also want English to be used as MOI not just for reading instruction but for other learning areas as well because English is the language of assessment, especially for Mathematics. Teachers considered English as a superior language. The problem lies however in the learners' and teachers' proficiency in the language. Hence, they argued for the need to enhance the manner in which it is imparted to learners or taught to them, particularly with regards to the skill of reading in this particular language. Teachers encouraged their learners to learn and speak in this language. Remedial instruction also focused on beginning reading in English.

Teachers' use of the English language in learning environment and resources was also evident (see p. 208). Reading materials and classroom displays were in this language. These materials were mostly used for remedial reading instruction, a

program which is given to struggling readers. Non-print materials such as videos were also developed using this language.

Therefore, it can be argued that the teachers' hegemonic language ideology *English as a Highly Valued Language*, although it is more on the aspirational aspect, was reflected in the teachers' use of language in early reading instruction as evidenced by teaching practices such as the *Big Six of Reading with a Focus on Phonics Instruction, Medium of Instruction and/or Learning Area, and Learning Environment and Resources*. The teachers during the focus group discussion only echoed what they initially shared in the semi-structured interviews. Participant D repeated how the English language would benefit learners later on, "Di ba nga, Sir, *English* ang gagamitin nila paglabas nila dito sa *school*? 'Pag mag-a-*apply* sila ng trabaho ganun." ["Isn't it true, Sir, that they will use English when they leave school? When they apply for jobs and such."] This language would also expand learners' communication networks and contribute to learners' success in various competitions. Participant K shared, "Kung hindi marunong magbasa ang bata sa *English*, mananalo kaya siya, Sir, sa mga *contest* na ganyan? Medyo tagilid. At mas marami silang magiging *opportunity* 'pag na-*develop* lalo nila ang *reading* nila dito." ["If a learner doesn't know how to read in English, Sir, do you think they will win in contests? It's a bit unlikely. And they will have more opportunities if they further develop their reading skills in English."]

Teachers tended to prioritize using and teaching the languages that they thought would be more beneficial for the learners, especially in terms of economic opportunities and academic successes. The prevailing beliefs that exalted English as an official language unconsciously influenced the delivery of early reading instruction in multilingual classrooms. This negates the premise of MTB-MLE that "learners begin their education in a language they understand best" (DepEd, 2016b, p. 2), which is

anchored on the fact that learners who have a strong foundation in their own language develop more solid literacy abilities (DepEd, 2016b). Cross-linguistic transfer of reading skills is also hampered. Because of the given focus on English, sufficient attention to the mother tongue is not provided.

The availability of reading materials mostly intended for learning the English language is also a clear manifestation of this hegemonic language ideology. Available materials that can be easily accessed through the internet are usually used in early reading classrooms. This further signifies the dominance of this language over the local language/s. This limits the opportunities for children who speak the local language to engage with literature and develop reading skills in their mother tongue. *English as a Highly Valued Language* implies that it can perpetuate the marginalization of the local language and reinforce the idea that it is inferior or less important compared to the major languages in early reading instruction. Also, the availability of reading materials in this language can create a barrier for children who are not yet proficient in English. Moreover, pushing the learners to speak in and read more frequently this language supports a hegemonic language ideology, thereby devaluing their own language (Wiley, 2000).

English as a Highly Valued Language as reflected in early reading instruction is further supported by the sociocognitive model of meaning-construction (Ruddell et al., 2019). A teacher's sociocultural values and beliefs have a tremendous effect on the relationships with the readers, instructional planning, and interpretation of texts. This indicates that teacher must be aware of and sensitive to the reader's understanding of the ways language can be used during classroom discussion and interaction. The theme is also parallel with the study of Norro (2022) where it was observed that English, a perceived dominant language, maintains its high status

compared to the local languages in Namibia. In Norro's (2022) study, it was also found that language hierarchy favoring the dominant language endures, especially for educational purposes.

This hegemonic language ideology mainly implies that teachers' linguistic biases are present in early reading instruction. The focus on teaching early reading using English could disregard the value of local languages, thereby marginalizing learners' voice and space. This ideology is somehow problematic. Focus on certain languages does not recognize and embrace linguistic diversity in the classroom. The MTB-MLE curriculum provides eight guiding principles for teaching and learning (DepEd, 2016c) (see p. 60). All these principles directly affect early reading instruction. This also implies that when dominant languages, such as English, take precedence in early reading instruction, it can result in limited exposure and resources for teaching the local language. When this happens, learners will receive little opportunities to learn to read in a language that they own and understand best.

Filipino as preferred language

Majority of the teachers preferred Filipino as the medium of instruction (see p. 119). They argued that its being an official and the national language of the Philippines makes it comprehensible to everyone. Hence, more people use this language compared to other Philippine languages. Teachers also argued for the dominance of this language, and they also believed that the influence of the local language is waning in the community. They also stated how the Philippine media is instrumental to this dominance. Using this language in class also allows learners who don't speak the school's mother tongue to participate, and the use of Filipino facilitates inclusion and involvement.

The teachers' hegemonic language ideology *Filipino as Preferred Language* is reflected in all the identified teachers' early reading instruction practices: *Big Six of Reading with a Focus on Phonics Instruction*, *Learners' Experiences*, *Medium of Instruction and/or Learning Area*, *Translanguaging*, and *Learning Environment and Resources*. This is elaborated upon in the subsequent discussion and interconnected with teachers' use of language/s in early reading instruction. Furthermore, Figure 25 illustrates the diagram of the hegemonic language ideology *Filipino as Preferred Language* and its relationship to early reading instruction practices.

Figure 25

Filipino as Preferred Language in Early Reading Instruction

Teachers favored the Filipino language as the primary means of communication in early reading instruction. The different components of the big six of reading are developed through this language: recitations for oral language; songs such as “Leron, Leron Sinta” for phonological awareness; and utilization of reading materials for vocabulary, fluency, and comprehension (see p. 151). The phonics instruction in Filipino is utilized to develop learners’ foundational skills in reading (i.e., decoding). Since the teachers repeatedly argued that learners are more proficient in this language than English and the school’s chosen mother tongue, teachers use this language as the major classroom language. Even when a reading lesson is in English such as *reading of short e words in CVC* (consonant-vowel-consonant) pattern (see p. 122), Participant D, for instance, employed Filipino to ensure learners grasp the lesson effectively. Teachers’ use of the Marungko approach and Claveria approach (see p. 160) is grounded in the teachers’ conviction that utilizing these is seen to enhance learners’ reading proficiency in Filipino. Doing syllabication in Filipino reading classes also ensures the development of learners’ phonics and word recognition skills.

Moreover, utilizing learners’ prior experience using the Filipino language in any learning area is a clear manifestation of the hegemonic language ideology *Filipino as Preferred Language*. Learners’ experiences were employed as a scaffold to connect the new reading lesson with their existing knowledge. The majority of questions posed by teachers to learners, aimed to access their prior experiences, were also presented in Filipino (see p. 171).

Filipino as Preferred Language is also witnessed on how teachers purposefully and deliberately use Filipino as medium of instruction in early reading instruction (see p. 185). Because *naiintindihan ng lahat ito* [everyone understands it], teachers use Filipino in explaining concepts explicitly, giving instructions for tasks, answering

questions, making clarifications, and providing feedback in the context of teaching beginning reading. Teachers also employ Filipino to supplement both the local language and the English language.

In translanguaging, Filipino language still asserts its dominance. In some MT reading lessons, mother tongue was translated to Filipino (see p. 197). In English reading lessons, teachers mostly translanguaged using the features of the Filipino language. Translanguaging was utilized to forge links between the Filipino language and other languages (local language and English), such as posing questions to learners and gauging their understanding.

Filipino as Preferred Language is also evident in learning environment and resources. The reading materials and classroom displays, if not in English, are in Filipino. These resources also primarily cater to remedial reading instruction program.

The teachers' hegemonic language ideology *Filipino as Preferred Language* is clearly reflected in the teachers' use of language/s in early reading instruction. In contrast to English, it does not just pertain to the aspirational aspect; rather, it represents a tangible concept. The teachers' early reading instruction practices *Big Six of Reading with a Focus on Phonics Instruction, Learners' Experiences, Medium of Instruction and/or Learning Area, Translanguaging, and Learning Environment and Resources* are a testament to that.

During the focus group discussions, Participant C said, "Mas nakakatipid ng oras, Sir, kapag Filipino 'yung gagamitin. Hindi na kailangan mag-*translate* kasi, Sir, *expected* na alam na ah [*sic*] naiintindihan na ito ng mga bata." ["It's more timesaving, Sir, when we use Filipino. There's no need to translate because, Sir, it's already expected that it's understood by the learners."] Also, Participant J commented, "Siguro sa *exposure* na rin, Sir, (sa wikang Filipino). Hindi mo naman 'yon mapipigilan. *Click*

click na lang ngayon eh.” [“Perhaps due to exposure as well, Sir, (in the Filipino language). You can't really prevent that. Everything is just a click away now.”]

Teachers often give preference to teaching and utilizing languages they believe will offer greater advantages to learners. The idea of Filipino being the national language is implied to have contributed largely to this preference (Tupas & Martin, 2017). Filipino preference may or may negate the premise of MTB-MLE that learners learn best in the language they understand (DepEd, 2016b). If learners' first language was truly Filipino, then teachers' use of Filipino most of the time would greatly benefit them. However, if learners' first language was the school's chosen mother tongue, they are put at a disadvantage. If due emphasis was given to Filipino, proper consideration for the mother tongue would be lacking.

Access to reading and teaching materials in Filipino also contributes to how the hegemonic language ideology *Filipino as Preferred Language* is reflected in the early reading instruction. This also constrains the chances for children who are already proficient in the local language to interact with local literature and cultivate reading abilities in their first language. Moreover, the presence of reading materials in this language can pose an obstacle for children who haven't yet acquired proficiency in Filipino yet. Wiley (2000) argued that the focus on the dominant languages strengthens language hegemony, especially when the local language is marginalized. This implies for the limited opportunity for learners who speak the local language to have their voice heard and their space seen and acknowledged.

Challenges in MTB-MLE Implementation

Challenges to MTB-MLE Implementation have been identified in this research. Teachers shared pervasive criticisms and arguments against MTB-MLE and the use of the mother tongue. These challenges include *challenges with multilingualism and*

language varieties (see p. 125), *resistance towards MTB-MLE* (see p. 132), and *language hierarchy* (see p. 140). Some of the teacher participants appeared to encounter challenges in managing the language differences during early reading instruction. According to their perspective, multilingualism can be perplexing and result in language mixing or interference, hindering effective communication. Incorporating multiple languages in the classroom is also perceived as intricate and demands so much time. Linguistic variations are also a concern. Teachers also argued that learning three languages could be overwhelming for learners.

Teachers also believed that the inclusion of the mother tongue alongside Filipino and English is perceived as a hindrance to effectively teaching learners how to read. Teacher and learner proficiency in the local language is also a factor in challenges in MTB-MLE implementation. Teachers also put the local language at the lowest level of the language hierarchy.

The teachers' hegemonic language ideology *Challenges in MTB-MLE Implementation* is reflected in three of the five identified early reading instruction practices: *Medium of Instruction and/or Learning Area*, *Translanguaging*, and *Learning Environment and Resources*. This is further discussed below and related to the teachers' use of language/s. Moreover, Figure 26 provides the diagram of the relationship of this hegemonic teachers' language ideology to the teachers' early reading instruction practices.

Figure 26

Challenges in MTB-MLE Implementation in Early Reading Instruction

Teachers consistently mentioned how the local language is less important than Filipino and English. In the theme *Medium of Instruction and/or Learning Area* (see p. 181) in teachers' early reading instruction practices, this is even clearly demonstrated. The teachers consistently upheld their view that learners lack proficiency in this language, and its utilization for teaching reading leads to confusion among the learners. They were pushing for its removal in the curriculum, and if that won't be possible, they argued that mother tongue should be used in one learning area only. It was also noted that both teachers and learners possessed the ability to communicate in the local language. However, using Filipino instead of the mother tongue, especially

in interactions between the teacher and the learners, appeared to be a natural tendency (see p. 181). The teachers also did not bother translating the Mother Tongue curriculum, which is in English, into the local language.

Teachers' hegemonic language ideology *Challenges in MTB-MLE Implementation* is also clearly reflected in early reading instruction through translanguaging. Teachers were observed engaging in frequent instances of translanguaging. It was predominantly employed during teacher-led discussion in early reading instruction, guided activities, simplification of complex concepts, and posing questions to assess learners' comprehension. Despite being a language tool to bridge languages and recognize linguistic diversity, however, translanguaging mostly promotes Filipino than the local language (see p. 197).

The dearth of teaching and reading materials in the mother tongue is also a clear evidence of how *Challenges in MTB-MLE Implementation* is reflected in early reading instruction. The materials and classroom displays which are mainly in English and Filipino are tangible proofs of language hierarchy and/or dominance of major languages. Remedial instruction for struggling readers focusing on using the Filipino and English materials implies that there is no need for struggling readers to be taught in the mother tongue anymore. The lack of big books in the mother tongue (Monje et al., 2021) is also evident. This supports Monje et al.'s (2021) finding that lack of big books and materials in Mother Tongue stood out as the primary factor behind schools' incomplete implementation of the MTB-MLE. If given the chance, the teachers would not even use the mother tongue as the medium of instruction. Practical reasons were repeatedly mentioned such as the lack of learning materials in the mother tongue and the language variations that even exist in the learners' materials provided by the government.

Participant C shared in the focus group discussion, “Kailan din kaya nila maiintindihan na mahirap na ring ituro talaga ‘yang Ilokano sa mga bata. Lalo sa pagbabasa. Nasabi ko na rin ito, *Sir*, maski sa bahay nila nagta-Tagalog [*sic*] na sila eh.” [“When will they understand that teaching Ilokano to children is also difficult? Especially in reading. I've mentioned this before, *Sir*, even at their homes, they're already speaking Tagalog [*sic*.”] Participant A said, “Ang gulo. May *confusion* talaga sa *vowels*.” [“It's confusing. There's really a confusion with vowels.”]

The challenges in MTB-MLE Implementation are rooted in unfavorable opinions towards multilingualism and language variation, especially in familiarity of words and diversity of letter-sounds. Parba (2018) found that language variation challenges MTB-MLE implementation. It is perceived to be additional work for teachers once they cater to these language variations. The teachers encounter difficulty in navigating these multilingualism and language variations and perceive them as perplexing and too complex, especially for the learners. When teachers do not support the school's chosen MOI, it also hinders the effective implementation of MTB-MLE (Monje et al., 2021).

Use of Translations

Teachers' hegemonic language ideology *Use of Translations* (see p. 140) is also reflected in their use of language/s in early reading instruction. Teachers practiced translanguaging, code-switching, and translating to bridge and/or clarify a concept from one language to another, thereby aiding comprehension in learning. The different patterns (mixing of languages) of translanguaging are integrated in early reading instruction. In this way, languages are given space for utilization in reading instruction. If translanguaging allows the simultaneous use of languages in multilingual contexts (España & Herrera, n.d.) such as an early reading instruction classroom in the

Philippines, translanguaging could challenge the dominant languages and promote inclusive language practices. Through translanguaging, the local languages which are often marginalized, can be provided with space in the linguistic landscape (Cenoz & Gorter, 2017). This would allow the local languages, along with the official languages Filipino and English, to be maintained and revitalized. This further indicates that teachers practicing translanguaging support the practical benefits of multilingualism. However, what makes the use of translations hegemonic is that translanguaging benefits more the Filipino language, a dominant language, more than the local language. Teachers practice translations and/or code-switching mostly from mother tongue to Filipino or English to Filipino. Utilizing it to enhance language exposure in dominant languages may discourage the utilization and growth of local languages as valid mediums in early reading instruction.

Use of Translations is clearly reflected in the teachers' use of language/s in early reading instruction. This was observed in the practices *Learners' Experiences*, *Medium of Instruction*, and *Translanguaging*. Further elaboration on this matter is presented below in connection with the teachers' use of language/s. Additionally, Figure 27 depicts the relationship between teachers' language ideology *Use of Translations* and their practices in early reading instruction.

Figure 27

Use of Translations in Early Reading Instruction

It seems automatic for teachers to use translations in early reading instruction. Translanguaging in early reading instruction as a pedagogical practice of leveraging learners' full linguistic repertoires could support learners' reading development (see p. 193). The curriculum clearly specifies the literacy support from L1 to L2 and L3 through cross-linguistic transfer, integration and application of prior knowledge, cognitive development and higher order thinking skills, bridging L1, L2, and L3 and scaffolding where L1 is used to support L2 learning, meaning and accuracy, and confidence building and proficiency development for two or more languages (DepEd, 2016a). When it comes to utilizing learners' experiences (see p. 171), teachers make use of

translations and translanguaging across the three subjects to establish connections. This is also true with regards to the medium of instruction and/or learning area (see p. 181) and translanguaging (see p. 193). Different patterns of language use were also observed.

In the interviews and focus group discussions, the participants admitted to using translations, code-switching, and translanguaging in supporting early reading instruction through its diverse applications, such as facilitating clarifications, contextualizing language within culture, and mediating academic content. By doing this, they were able to clarify meanings and bridge languages (Kumar et al., 2021; Zhang, 2023). Translanguaging is employed as a means of fostering inclusion and supporting learners' diverse languages and linguistic repertoire (Wawire and Barnes-Story, 2023). Because it happens naturally, it helps learners navigate the complexities of reading in three languages. The teachers also consider it as a strategy in delivering reading lessons well (Wawire and Barnes-Story, 2023).

During the class observations, translanguaging was noted to prepare learners for the lessons such as asking "Are you ready to listen to our new lesson? *Handa na ba kayong makinig* [are you ready to listen] o [or] *mag-listen sa ating bagong* [to our new] lesson?" When discussing concepts, translanguaging was used in questions to check learners' comprehension. Bridging the language of instruction to a language the learners understand better utilizes translanguaging as well (Cenoz & Gorter, 2017).

In MT reading classes, features of Filipino and English languages are used in translanguaging (see p. 197). Translations of the mother tongue to Filipino also happen, which makes these hegemonic in nature. Translanguaging is also present in the learners' textbooks.

In Filipino reading classes, teachers translanguage to connect the Filipino language to the mother tongue or to the English language. Fluid use of the three languages also happens (see p. 200). Commonly used and more familiar words in English are also used in Filipino such as *balloons*, *birthday*, and *clown*. These were probably incorporated in reading instruction because the learners' familiarity with the language was considered. This is also true with the Filipino textbooks where English words are also found.

Translanguaging in English reading classes is also a reality. Teachers translate the English language to Filipino, and sometimes to the mother tongue, to ensure learners' comprehension of the reading lesson or text read (see p. 203). Similar lessons across the three reading subjects are also related through translanguaging (e.g., teachers mentioned what the topic title was in Filipino and in mother tongue). The teachers expect that when the meanings/definitions of English words are asked, translations of these words are given by the learners. Not so much translanguaging has been noted in the English reading textbooks except when there are words commonly known and too difficult for learners to understand.

According to the sociocognitive model of meaning-construction (Ruddell et al., 2019), learners' sociocultural values and beliefs need to match those of the teacher, and the teacher should be responsive to cultural differences to prevent learners' breakdowns in communication. Furthermore, Ruddell et al. (2019) stated that by being attentive to learners' sociocultural backgrounds, teachers can adapt classroom instruction to accommodate diverse perspectives. This is likely to boost learners' motivation and involvement in their learning. Through the teachers' building of relationships, reflection, and self-exploration, teachers are able to positively affect learners whose culture they grew up in is different from the school culture (Ruddell et

al., 2019). Translanguaging was also found in the study conducted by Wawire and Barnes-Story (2023), in which translanguaging is considered a pedagogical strategy to promote literacy and/or develop multiliteracy. This implies that incorporating translanguaging pedagogies in early reading instruction in the context of multilingual classrooms promotes social and linguistic justice and inclusive learning, which in return may increase higher levels of learning outcomes. The finding also indicates that teachers purposefully employed translanguaging techniques to encourage the use of diverse languages, thereby creating opportunities for broader multilingual language use similar to Makalela's (2019) study.

The finding implies that translanguaging (translations and code-switching), when used strategically and purposively, aids teachers' delivery of instruction in teaching early reading. Translanguaging enables teachers to communicate more clearly and effectively, facilitate vocabulary development, and support cross-lingual transfer of reading skills, among others. This supports multilingual learners' development of essential literacy skills (Wawire and Barnes-Story, 2023). As repeatedly discussed, it is an important tool in multilingual educational contexts. However, translations, code-switching, translanguaging, and other related concepts should also promote the local languages and should not contribute to their marginalization. Hence, teachers should keep a positive view on its use, especially when it concerns multiple languages in early reading instruction.

Language Preservation and Fostering Identity

Language Preservation and Fostering Identity is the only teachers' counter-hegemonic language ideology in this study (see p. 144). This theme is also reflected in the teachers' use of language/s in early reading instruction. Majority of teachers concurred that MTB-MLE is being implemented to preserve local languages and

cultivate an individual's identity, history, and cultural heritage. Accordingly, the local language is an inherent part of learners' lives. MTB-MLE as the language-in-education policy also contributes to the revitalization of the community's language. The use of the mother tongue in schools, although sometimes seen as required or mandated, contributes greatly to this *Language Preservation and Fostering Identity*.

The teachers' counter-hegemonic language ideology *Language Preservation and Fostering Identity* is also reflected in the teachers' use of language/s in early reading instruction. This is manifested in the practices *Big Six of Reading with a Focus on Phonics Instruction, Learners' Experience, Medium of Instruction and/or Learning Area, and Translanguaging*. Further exploration of this topic is presented below in connection with teachers' language use. Additionally, Figure 28 illustrates the diagram depicting the relationship between the language ideology *Language Preservation and Fostering Identity* and teachers' early reading instruction practices.

Figure 28

Language Preservation and Fostering Identity in Early Reading Instruction

Language Preservation and Fostering Identity still has a long way to go in early reading instruction. As the only counter-hegemonic language ideology, its legitimacy remains challenged. However, the fact that it is still utilized as medium of instruction despite the teachers' negative attitudes towards the use of the local language in early reading instruction says a lot about its perceived importance. In the *Big Six of Reading with a Focus on Phonics Instruction*, teachers localized materials to teach phonics to learners in the mother tongue (see p. 157). Mother tongue is also used in utilizing *Learners' Experiences* through series of questions to establish connections and scaffold learning (see p. 174). Moreover, a little space is given to this counter-

hegemonic language ideology in *Medium of Instruction and/or Learning Area* (see p. 181) and *Translanguaging* (see p. 193) because the local language is still acknowledged.

The assertion is made that literacy and languages hold significance only within their specific cultural context (Ruddell et al., 2019). The value and meaning of literacy and languages are closely tied to the cultural environment in which they exist. The way people read, write, and communicate, as well as the significance they attribute this action, is deeply influenced by their cultural beliefs, practices, and traditions. Meaningful literacy practices cannot be divorced from the cultural norms and values that shape how language is used and understood.

Although the teachers' counter hegemonic language ideology *Language Preservation and Fostering Identity* is not reflected in the teachers' use of language/s in early reading instruction as much as the teachers' hegemonic language ideologies, it is implied that the use of the local language aligns with cultural traditions, individual heritage, values, and social bonds. The use of the mother tongue in early reading instruction enables both teachers and learners to establish a link to their cultural origins (Maseko, 2021; Wawire and Barnes-Story, 2023).

Chapter V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the summary, conclusions, and recommendations derived from the findings of the study.

Summary of Salient Findings

Based on the conducted semi-structured interviews, class observations, documents review, and focus group discussions analyzed qualitatively and thematically, the following salient findings are hereby presented:

Teachers' Language Ideologies

The language ideologies of the teachers on the use of the local language alongside Filipino and English in early reading instruction are identified as hegemonic language ideologies and counter-hegemonic language ideologies. Four research themes are related to teachers' hegemonic languages which promote linguistic inequalities. The first theme, *English as a Highly Valued Language*, is supported by the use of this language for a variety of purposes including economic, social, and academic purposes. The second theme, *Filipino as Preferred Language* shows how teachers favor this language as the common language for everyone, regardless of one's mother tongue. The third theme, *Challenges in MTB-MLE Implementation*, features the negative beliefs about multilingualism and language varieties because of the negative perceptions on language mixing and other mother tongue-related issues. It is also attributed to seeing mother tongue as a barrier to learning, the issue of teacher and learner proficiency in the mother tongue and in the three languages used in early reading instruction, the lack of learning resources (especially in the local language) for the proper implementation of the language policy, and the presence of

language hierarchy. The fourth theme, *Use of Translations*, is evidenced by the use of this tool to bridge a language to another language and to clarify meaning; however, this mostly promoted the Filipino language.

Only one theme emerged to describe the teachers' counter-hegemonic language ideologies which challenge the dominance of the official languages and in a way promote the value of the local language and not just the two official languages (Filipino and English). *Language Preservation and Fostering Identity* revolves around the implementation of MTB-MLE as a way to strengthen the local community's language and heritage.

Teachers' Early Reading Instruction Practices

Five major themes emerged to describe the teachers' early reading instruction practices in the local language, Filipino, and English or across languages. The first theme, *Big Six of Reading with a Focus on Phonics Instruction*, places the importance of teacher agency in the teachers' instructional orientation which is phonics-based and supported by the other components of the big six. The second theme, *Learners' Experiences*, shows how teachers utilize learners' prior experiences in teaching early reading to establish connections and promote engagement. The third theme, *Medium of Instruction and/or Learning Area*, describes how the three languages are used purposefully and deliberately used in early reading instruction. The fourth theme, *Translanguaging*, is related to the two specific tools used in bridging languages and clarifying meaning and content which are code-switching and translating. Finally, the last theme, *Learning Environment and Resources*, is reinforced by what print-rich classrooms are in theory and in reality, the teachers' classroom realities when it comes to reading resources, and the use of technology in early reading instruction.

Teachers' Language Ideologies Reflected in their Use of Language/s in Early Reading Instruction

The four teachers' hegemonic language ideologies (English as a Highly Valued Language, Filipino as Preferred Language, Challenges in MTB-MLE Implementation, and Use of Translations) and the one teachers' counter-hegemonic language ideology (Language Preservation and Fostering Identity) are clearly reflected in the teachers' use of language/s in early reading instruction. The teachers' early reading instruction practices (Big Six of Reading with a Focus on Phonics Instruction, Learners' Experiences, Medium of Instruction, Translanguaging, and Learning Environment and Resources) support how the teachers' language ideologies are manifested in early reading instruction.

Conclusions

Teachers' language ideologies are present in multilingual classrooms. These linguistic assumptions affect the way the teachers view the use and value of local languages. The dominance of official languages, especially the Filipino language, in early reading instruction further marginalizes the local languages. There is a need to value and acknowledge the local languages to promote and sustain linguistic and cultural diversity in school. If the imbalance of status and power (politics of language and language learning) among these languages which is being spearheaded by the teachers continues to persist, the limited space given to the local languages in the educational setting would shrink even smaller. The mixing of languages and language variation are seen to be a burden among teachers. Their resistance towards MTB-MLE indicates a strong need for teachers to revisit the theoretical and practical backgrounds on why MTB-MLE is being implemented. Learners having different mother tongue challenges how local languages are further developed and supported.

The bigger issue on the use of mother tongue is the loss of preservation or the weak efforts in revitalizing the local language in the bigger community. Teachers also need support as they face the challenges brought by the implementation of MTB-MLE, especially on the provisions of teaching and learning materials. Teachers' use of translations which are not intended for language separation but to scaffold learning supports the reading development of learners, but mostly in dominant languages. The presence of teachers' counter-hegemonic language ideologies, however, is a step towards a more inclusive literacy classroom. Although more space must be given to valuing and preserving local languages aimed for fostering identity, the use of translations as a language ideology should be used to challenge the dominant languages in early reading instruction and not to further promote them.

The concept of the big six of reading calls for a more balanced approach in teaching early reading. Giving more focus on phonics-based approach is essential in teaching learners how to decode words, but other teaching/learning strategies used should also further be strengthened. Learners' experiences and utilizing them well promote engagement and comprehension. The deliberate and purposeful use of the medium of instruction shows the teachers' bias against the mother tongue. In other words, it results in local languages being pushed to the sidelines or not given as much importance as the other 'dominant' languages. This also hinders the development of the learners' literacy skills in the mother tongue. This marginalization can also lead to a range of consequences, such as reduced usage and development of local languages and a potential loss of cultural identity and heritage associated with those local languages. Teachers' limited training on multilingual education and literacy instruction could have also contributed to this bias against the mother tongue. Translanguaging breaks down communication and comprehension barriers. As a pedagogical tool to

bridge languages and clarify content and meaning, it is supposed to be an empowering practice in teaching early reading as it enhances the colorful linguistic repertoire of both the teachers and the learners. However, it may also further marginalize the local languages if translanguaging is used to promote exposure of the dominant languages. Learning environment and resources show the dearth of materials in the mother tongue and the utilization of technology in early reading instruction.

The focus on teaching early reading through Filipino and English marginalizes the local language. The challenges in MTB-MLE implementation further emphasize the problems that are closely associated with the language-in-education policy. Translanguaging should allow the fluid use of languages most especially in utilizing the local language to help learners understand and connect with the reading lessons. Uncovering teachers' language ideologies and their early reading instruction practices is of utmost importance to better understand their relationship with each other, with respect to MTB-MLE as the current educational language policy of the country. This indicates that teachers bring to the classroom their experiences and beliefs, especially as they teach reading to young learners. This has serious implications in creating a more inclusive learning environment for the learners, in the marginalization and promotion of languages used in class, in using authentic and meaningful experiences for the learners, and in the learners' sense of identity following their community heritage and history. The impact of teachers' language use is crucial to the promotion of inclusive and empowering language practices in early reading instruction.

Recommendations

Based on the significance of the study, the findings, and the conclusions, the researcher recommends the following:

1. Thorough revisit and reexamination of RA 10533 and the MTB-MLE language-in-education policy, in connection with the newly launched MATATAG Curriculum. The results of this study show that this policy continues to be challenged and opposed. Considering the teachers' language ideologies and early reading instruction practices, the results of this study should assist educational administrators and/or stakeholders in making informed decisions and/or implementing policy modifications regarding MTB-MLE. Revisiting and reexamining thoroughly the implementation of MTB-MLE will monitor the effectiveness of this language-in-education policy and identify areas for improvement. It is also important that policymakers consider linguistic diversity, cultural sensitivities, research on harmful language ideologies and effective language/reading instruction methodologies/practices, and the needs of learners, teachers, and communities in the new MATATAG curriculum (especially in its implementation, as well as the removal of the Mother Tongue subject) and in implementing a language-in-education policy intended for a multilingual context. The abandonment of the Mother Tongue subject in the new MATATAG curriculum should also be clarified and further addressed, because it seems in contrast to the still unamended RA 10533 which indicates the use of the MTB-MLE framework.

2. Teacher Training, Teacher Support, and Curricular Modification/s: The results should also be used as a reference in crafting a professional development program on multilingual education and literacy instruction (in relation to the MATATAG Curriculum), not only for pre-service teachers but also for in-service early grades teachers. There is a need for teachers to be trained in literacy instruction and teaching ideology involving multilingualism to inform their instructional beliefs, which reflect their instructional planning. Quality support such as necessary tools, resources (e.g., funds

and instructional materials), and professional development opportunities to enhance their teaching skills should be provided to teachers, especially on the development and/or procurement of materials. Translanguaging involves how the local language alongside other languages is used in multilingual classrooms as a language and/or early reading instruction practice. Curriculum adjustments should be made to acknowledge and allow translanguaging as an authentic and legitimate tool in early reading instruction, not to further marginalize the Philippine languages but also to help promote them alongside Filipino and English.

3. Future Research: Since this is the first Philippine study to investigate teachers' language ideologies and early reading instruction practices in three languages (a Philippine local language, Filipino, and English), and whether or not these language ideologies are reflected in the teacher's use of language/s in early reading instruction, similar topics should be explored to enrich the research literature. This study acknowledges that one of the weaknesses of qualitative research such as this study is the low number of participants, making it insufficient to arrive at generalizations. The Philippines is a multilingual country (Lasco, 2017). The extent to which findings from the studied three local languages (Bolinao, Iloko, and Pangasinan) can be generalized to other local languages across the entire country is limited. Despite this limitation, this study featuring the aforementioned local languages provided rich data about these particular languages and the contexts where they are used. For future studies, it is recommended that more participants be involved, and the research be conducted in a wider research locale. It is recommended that a broader context be explored, to also encompass sociocultural, historical, and political aspects of the (future) research sites. A longer period of data gathering would also make results of this study more robust.

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Appendix A

Demographic Questionnaire

Name: _____

School: _____

Age: _____

Gender: _____

Years in Service: _____

Teaching Position: _____

Grade Level Being Taught: _____

Years Teaching in the Current Grade Level: _____

Subjects Being Taught in the Present School Year:

Highest Educational Attainment: _____ Major: _____

Number of Trainings Related to MTB-MLE: _____

Total Number of Days/Hours of Trainings Related to MTB-MLE: _____

Number of Trainings Related to Teaching Beginning Reading: _____

Total Number of Days/Hours of Trainings Related to Teaching Beginning Reading:

Language/s spoken: _____

Appendix B

Interview Schedule for Teachers' Language Ideologies

A. English Version

Introduction: *Thank you for agreeing to participate in this study on Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education in the Philippines. This interview will take about 30-45 minutes. Your answers will be used as part of a research study to learn about teachers' views on the language/s used in their classroom. I will be recording this interview, and your identity and all of your responses will be kept confidential.*

Note: The language the participant is comfortable of using will be utilized in the interview.

Types of Questions	Questions
Introductory question	Based on the information you provided in the questionnaire, you have been teaching for _____ years already. How does it feel to be a teacher all this time?
Transition Questions	In the questionnaire, you added that you speak and use these languages. Which one is your first language? Your second language? How will you describe your proficiency in these languages? Will you please rank them according to your proficiency?
Key Questions (other follow-up questions may be inserted depending on the answers of the interviewee)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. So, you teach grade ____ level. How does it feel to be teaching these learners? 2. What is your favorite subject to teach? Why? 3. Earlier, I asked you about the languages that you speak and use. Have you ever used a specific language in order to fit in more with a group? When and why? How did that make you feel? 4. Have you ever used a specific language to exclude someone from a conversation? When and how? How did that make you feel? 5. Have you ever felt excluded because of your language usage? When and how? How did that make you feel? 6. What are your opinions about MTB-MLE? 7. What are your thoughts on the use of the local language alongside Filipino and English in your classroom? What are your opinions about the local language? Filipino language? English language? 8. Why do you think this MTB-MLE policy is being implemented?

	<p>9. Do you believe there are language hierarchies? “Language hierarchies” refers to a language pyramid where a “high value language/s” is/are put at the top of the pyramid, and an/other language/s considered “low value” is/are located at the bottom of that pyramid. Are there any you can identify at your workplace? How does that make you feel? Are there any you can identify outside of your workplace? How does that make you feel?</p>
Closing Questions	<p>Before we conclude this interview, is there something in your experience as a teacher in a multilingual classroom that we haven’t had the chance to discuss?</p>

Guided by the Interview Protocol Refinement Framework (Castillo-Montoya, 2016)

Interview Schedule for Teachers' Language Ideologies

B. Filipino Version

Panimula: Maraming salamat sa iyong pagpayag na lumahok sa pananaliksik na ito patungkol sa *Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education* sa Pilipinas. Ang panayam na ito ay aabot mula 30-45 na minuto. Ang iyong mga tugon ay gagamitin sa isang pag-aaral tungkol sa mga ideolohiya ng mga guro sa mga wikang kanilang ginagamit sa pagtuturo tulad ng *mother tongue*, *Filipino*, at *English*. Irerekord ko ang panayam na ito. Aking sinisiguro ang pagiging kompidensiyal ng iyong mga sagot at ng iyong pangalan.

Types of Questions	Questions
Introductory question	Base sa mga impormasyon na isinulat mo sa <i>questionnaire</i> , ikaw ay nagtuturo na sa loob ng _____ na taon. Ano ang pakiramdam na maging guro sa loob ng panahong ito?
Transition Questions	Isinulat mo rin sa <i>questionnaire</i> na ito ang mga wikang ginagamit mo. Ano rito ang iyong <i>first language</i> ? Ang iyong <i>second language</i> ? Ano ang iyong antas ng kasanayan sa paggamit ng mga wikang ito? Sa anong wika ka pinakamagaling?
Key Questions (other follow-up questions may be inserted depending on the answers of the interviewee)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ikaw ay nagtuturo ng <i>Grade</i> _____. Ano ang pakiramdam na magturo ng ganitong <i>grade level</i>? 2. Ano ang pinaka-paborito mong ituro na <i>subject</i>? Bakit? 3. Kanina tinanong kita tungkol sa mga wikang ginagamit mo. May mga pagkakataong bang gumamit ka ng isang wika upang sumabay o makiyon sa isang grupo? Kailan at paano ito nangyari? Ano ang naramdaman mo noon? 4. May mga pagkakataon din bang gumamit ka ng isang wika upang ibukod o huwag isama sa isang pag-uusap ang isang tao? Kailan at paano ito nangyari? Ano ang naramdaman mo noon? 5. Naranasan mo na bang maibukod dahil sa wikang ginagamit mo? Ano ang pakiramdam? 6. Ano-ano ang mga opinyon mo tungkol sa MTB-MLE? 7. Ano naman ang masasabi po sa paggamit ng wikang Bolinao/Iloko/Pangasinan kung saan ginagamit din ang Filipino at <i>English</i> sa iyong klasrum? Ano-ano ang opinyon mo tungkol sa wikang Bolinao/Iloko/Pangasinan? Sa wikang Filipino? Sa wikang <i>English</i>? 8. Sa tingin mo, bakit ipinapatupad ang MTB-MLE? 9. Naniniwala ka bang mayroong <i>language hierarchies</i>? Ang <i>language hierarchies</i> ay tumutukoy sa isang <i>pyramid</i> ng mga

	wika kung saan inilalagay sa tuktok nito ang wika na sa tingin ng tao ay mahalagang wika o <i>“high-value”</i> , at inilalagay naman sa ilalim nito ang wikang mas mababa ang halaga o <i>“low-value”</i> . Mayroon bang ganito sa mismong trabaho o pinagtatrabahuhan mo? Ano ang opinyon mo tungkol dito? Mayroon din bang <i>language hierarchies</i> sa labas ng trabaho mo? Ano ang opinyon mo tungkol dito?
Closing Questions	Bago matapos ang panayam na ito, may mga gusto ka pa bang sabihin tungkol sa iyong karanasan bilang isang guro sa isang <i>multilingual</i> na klasrum na hindi natin napag-usapan?

Appendix C

Interview Schedule for Teachers' Early Reading Instruction Practices

A. English Version

Introduction: *Thank you for agreeing to participate in this study on Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education in the Philippines. This interview will take about 30-45 minutes. Your answers will be used as part of a research study to learn about teachers' early reading instruction practices in the local language, Filipino, and English. I will be recording this interview, and your identity and all of your responses will be kept confidential.*

Note: The language the participant is comfortable of using will be utilized in the interview.

Types of Questions	Questions
Introductory Question	How does it feel to teach reading?
Transition Question	What is your favorite part in teaching reading?
Key Questions (other follow-up questions may be inserted depending on the answers of the interviewee)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How do you teach reading? What process do you usually follow in teaching reading? What do you think is the most important part when teaching reading? What methods/strategies/activities do you usually implement in your class? 2. How important are the learners' prior experiences to reading instruction? 3. What can you say about the use of the local language in teaching your learners how to read? Filipino language? English language? Which is the most used in class? The least used? In what instances is each language used? 4. What is the most important language that learners should be reading? Why do you say so? 5. To what extent do you think that the language influences how students learn literacy? 6. Do your learners have the same mother tongue? If they don't, how do you address this? 7. Do your pupils hesitate using languages other than their mother tongue? If yes, how do you motivate them to speak their second and/or third language/s? 8. What language/s do you usually use to: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. explain/teach explicitly? Why?

	<p>b. give instruction for tasks? Why?</p> <p>c. answer questions? Why?</p> <p>d. make clarifications? Why?</p> <p>e. provide feedback? Why?</p> <p>9. What language/s do learners use to:</p> <p>a. answer questions? Why?</p> <p>b. ask questions/clarifications? Why?</p> <p>c. share own knowledge/experience related to task/activity/topic? Why? What language do they usually use when they interact with each other?</p> <p>10. What is your opinion on translanguaging or allowing yourself or your learners to use multiple languages in your classroom? What are the translanguaging practices that happen in your classroom? Do you and/or your learners code-switch or translate? When is this done?</p> <p>11. Rank the six domains in teaching beginning reading: oral language, phonological awareness, phonics, vocabulary, fluency, comprehension. Which of them is the most important in teaching learners how to read in the local language? Filipino language? English language?</p> <p>12. What are the kinds of texts you used in your class, if any? Cite examples and describe their content.</p> <p>13. What do you think children entering grade 1 from kindergarten or basic school should know or be able to do when it comes to reading? How do you address the individual language needs of the learners?</p> <p>14. To what extent do you think the grade 1/2/3 language arts curriculum in mother tongue/Filipino/English is too easy or too hard? Why do you say so?</p> <p>15. Do you think all of your students will have learned how to read by the end of the school year? How come? What is your role in this?</p> <p>16. How important is a print-rich environment in teaching beginning reading? How is this manifested in your own classroom?</p>
Closing Questions	Before we conclude this interview, is there something in your experience as a reading teacher in a multilingual classroom that we haven't had the chance to discuss?

Guided by the Interview Protocol Refinement Framework (Castillo-Montoya, 2016)

Interview Schedule for Teachers' Early Reading Instruction Practices

A. Filipino Version

Panimula: Maraming salamat sa iyong pagpayag na lumahok sa pananaliksik na ito patungkol sa *Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education* sa Pilipinas. Ang panayam na ito ay aabot mula 30-45 na minuto. Ang iyong mga tugon ay gagamitin sa isang pag-aaral tungkol sa mga pamamaraan ng mga guro sa pagtuturo ng pagbabasa sa mga bata gamit ang *mother tongue*, *Filipino*, at *English*. Irerekord ko ang panayam na ito. Aking sinisiguro ang pagiging kompidensiyal ng iyong pagkakakilanlan at ng iyong mga sagot.

Types of Questions	Questions
Introductory Question	Ano ang pakiramdam na magturo ng pagbabasa sa mga bata?
Transition Question	Ano ang gusto mo sa pagtuturo ng pagbabasa sa mga bata?
Key Questions (other follow-up questions may be inserted depending on the answers of the interviewee)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Paano mo itinuturo ang pagbabasa sa mga estudyante mo? Ano ang prosesong ginagamit mo sa pagtuturo? Ano sa tingin mo ang pinaka-importanteng parte sa pagtuturo ng pagbabasa? Ano-ano ang mga <i>method/strategy/activity</i> na ginagawa o ginagamit mo sa iyong klase? 2. Gaano kahalaga ang mga karanasan o <i>prior experiences</i> ng mga bata sa pagtuturo sa kanilang bumasa? 3. Ano ang masasabi mo patungkol sa paggamit ng wikang Bolinao/Iloko/Pangasinan sa pagtuturo ng pagbabasa sa mga estudyante mo? Ng wikang Filipino? Ng wikang <i>English</i>? Ano ang pinakamadalas ginagamit? Hindi madalas ginagamit? Sa anong mga pagkakataon ginagamit ang bawat wikang ito? 4. Ano sa tingin mo ang pinaka-importanteng wika na dapat binabasa ng mga bata? Paano mo nasabi? 5. Haggang saan naaapektuhan ng isang wikang ginagamit sa pagtuturo ang pagkatuto ng mga bata sa pagbabasa? 6. Pare-parehas ba ang <i>mother tongue</i> ng mga estudyante mo? Kung hindi, paano mo ito na-a-address o niresolba? 7. Nag-aalangan ba ang mga estudyante mong gamitin ang ibang mga wika maliban sa kanilang <i>mother tongue</i>? Kung oo, paano mo sila hinihikayat na gamitin ang kanilang <i>second/third language/s</i>? 8. Ano ang wikang kadalasang ginagamit mo upang:

	<p>a. ipaliwanag o tahasang ituro ang isang aralin o konsepto? Bakit?</p> <p>b. magbigay ng mga panuto? Bakit?</p> <p>c. magtanong? Bakit?</p> <p>d. magbigay? Bakit?</p> <p>e. magbigay ng <i>feedback</i>? Bakit?</p> <p>9. Ano namang wika ang ginagamit ng mga mag-aaral upang:</p> <p>a. sumagot sa tanong? Bakit?</p> <p>b. magtanong? Bakit?</p> <p>c. magbahagi ng karanasang may kinalaman sa aralin? Bakit?</p> <p>Ano ang wikang kadalasang ginagamit nila upang makipag-usap sa kapwa nila mag-aaral?</p> <p>10. Ano ang masasabi mo tungkol sa <i>translanguaging</i> o pagpapalit-palit mo o ng mga bata ng mga wikang ginagamit sa klase? Ano-ano ang mga gawain na may kinalaman sa <i>translanguaging</i> ang nangyayari sa klasrum mo? Mayroon bang <i>code-switching</i> o <i>translation</i> na nangyayari sa iyo o sa mga estudyante mo? Kailan ito ginagawa?</p> <p>11. I-rank ang <i>six domains</i> sa pagtuturo ng pagbabasa sa mga bata: <i>oral language, phonological awareness, phonics, vocabulary, fluency, comprehension</i>. Ano rito ang pinakamahalaga sa pagtuturo ng pagbabasa sa mga bata gamit ang kanilang mother tongue? Gamit ang wikang Filipino? Gamit ang wikang English?</p> <p>12 Anong klaseng mga teksto ang ginagamit mo sa klase? Magbigay ng halimbawa at ipaliwanag ang mga nilalaman ng mga ito.</p> <p>13. Ano sa tingin mo ang dapat alam na ng batang papasok sa Grade 1 mula sa kinder tungkol sa pagbabasa? Paano mo nasasagot o nasosolusyonan ang mga iba't-ibang pangangailangan ng mga mga bata tungkol sa <i>literacy</i>?</p> <p>14. Sa tingin mo, madali ba o mahirap ang language arts kurikyulum ng <i>Mother Tongue/Filipino/English</i> ng Grade 1/2/3? Bakit?</p> <p>15. Sa tingin mo, lahat ba ng mga estudyante mo ay matututong magbasa bago matapos ang school year na ito? Bakit? Ano ang nagagawa/magagawa mo rito?</p> <p>16. Gaano kahalaga ang isang <i>print-rich</i> na klasrum? Paano ito nakikita sa iyong sariling klasrum?</p>
Closing Question	Bago matapos ang panayam na ito, may mga gusto ka pa bang sabihin tungkol sa iyong karanasan bilang isang gurong nagtuturo ng pagbabasa sa isang <i>multilingual</i> na klasrum na hindi natin napag-usapan?

Appendix D

Classroom Observation Protocol

Teacher Observed: _____

Grade Level: _____

Number of Students in Class: _____

Teacher's MT/s: _____ Students' MT/s: _____

School: _____

Subject: _____

Date: _____

Time began: _____ Time ended: _____

Reading Instruction Observables	Description/Comments
1. Provide a brief description of the class.	
2. What process does the teacher follow in teaching reading? What methods/strategies/activities are implemented? Explain.	
3. Describe the verbal and non-verbal interactions between the teacher and the learners: a. What language does the teacher use to explain/teach explicitly, give instruction for tasks, answer questions, make clarifications, and provide feedback? Discuss. b. What language do learners use to answer questions, ask questions/clarifications, share own knowledge/experience related to the task/activity/topic (unprompted), and share own knowledge/experience unrelated to the task/activity/topic (unprompted)? Discuss.	
4. Describe the verbal and non-verbal interactions between the learners, in terms of:	

<p>a. answering questions/making clarifications; b. asking questions/clarifications c. sharing own knowledge/experience related to the task/activity/topic (unprompted) d. sharing own knowledge/experience unrelated to the task/activity/topic (unprompted) e. providing feedback</p> <p>What language do they usually use when they interact with each other?</p>	
<p>5. What is/are the language/s used in the classroom? What is the most used? Least used? Are multiple languages used in the classroom? In what instances is each language used?</p>	
<p>6. How do learners practice reading? What is the role of the teacher in this?</p>	
<p>7. How does the teacher utilize the prior experiences of the learners and connect them to reading instruction?</p>	
<p>8. How does the teacher address the individual language needs of the learners?</p>	
<p>9. Is there a specific text used in reading instruction? Describe it, especially its content.</p>	

10. Other observations:

- a. Is the classroom considered a print-rich environment?
- b. Is there a reading corner? Describe it.
- c. Are there labels on the common objects? Cite examples.
- d. What are the kinds/types of print materials available in the classroom?

Appendix E

Focus Group Discussion Guide Questions

INTRODUCTION:

I am Jackson G. Orlanda, and I am conducting a study on teachers' language ideologies and early reading instruction practices in Philippine multilingual classrooms. I am from the University of the Philippines Open University. I will also be the moderator of this FGD. Thank you for participating in this discussion. We are here to talk about what has been found in your previous interviews and in the class observations conducted.

(Muli, ako si Jackson G. Orlanda. Ako ay nagsasagawa ng isang pag-aaral tungkol sa *teachers' language ideologies and early reading instruction practices in Philippine multilingual classrooms*. Ako ay nag-aaral sa University of the Philippines Open University. Ako ang magiging *moderator* ng ating magiging diskusyon. Nandito tayo para pag-usapan ang mga napansin at nakita sa mga isinagawang *interviews* sa inyo at *classroom observations*.)

Let's clarify that there are no right or wrong answers. You don't need to agree with others, but you must listen respectfully as others share their views. You can freely use the language you are most comfortable using. I will also be recording this discussion, so, we'll follow the one-person- speaking-at-a-time guideline.

(I-clarify lang natin na walang tama at maling sagot. Hindi mo kailangan sumang-ayon sa iba, pero kailangan mo rin namang makinig nang may paggalang habang nagbabahagi ng opinyon ang bawat isa.) Ire-record ko rin ang ating diskusyon, kaya kailangan na sundin natin ang *one-person-speaking-at-a-time-guideline*. Isa-isa lang po ang magsasalita.

My role as a moderator will be to guide the discussion.

(Ang role ko po ay i-guide ang ating diskusyon.)

Guide questions:

1. What you do think of the current issues on Mother Tongue Based Multilingual Education, especially on the use of the mother tongue?

(Ano ang masasabi niyo sa mga isyu ngayon tungkol sa *Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education* lalo na paggamit ng *mother tongue*?)

2. Let's talk about English and Filipino and their advantages and disadvantages.

(Pag-usapan natin ang *English* at *Filipino*, ang mga *advantages* nila at *disadvantages*.)

3. Tell me more about these three languages: mother tongue, Filipino, and English.

(Ano pa ang masasabi niyo tungkol sa tatlong wikang ginagamit sa klase – *mother tongue*, *Filipino*, at *English*?)

4. *Let's talk about language mixing, or use of more than one language, and the differences of vowel e in mother tongue and Filipino.*

(Pag-usapan natin ang paghahalo-halo ng mga wika at ang kaibahan ng pagbigkas sa letrang e sa Filipino at sa *mother tongue*.)

5. *How does the mother tongue become a barrier to learning?*

(Paano nagiging hadlang ang *mother tongue* sa pagkatuto ng mga bata?)

6. *What can you say about learners' and teachers' proficiency in the mother tongue?*

(Ano ang masasabi niyo sa kakayahan ninyo at ng mga bata sa paggamit ng *mother tongue* sa klase?)

7. *Tell me about the learning and teaching resources available for MTB-MLE.*

(I-share niyo ang tungkol sa mga learning and teaching resources na mayroon kayo para sa MTB-MLE.)

8. *How do translations work for you?*

(Paano nakatutulong ang *translations* sa inyo?)

9. *Think about your experiences teaching with MTB-MLE as a language policy. What went wrong? What went well? How does the use of mother tongue become an agent in language preservation and fostering identity?*

(Isipin ang inyong mga karanasan sa pagtuturo ng MTB-MLE bilang *language policy*. Ano ang naging mali? Ano ang naging maayos? Paano nakatutulong sa pagpapahalaga ng wika at pagpapaunlad ng sariling pagkakakilanlan ang paggamit ng *mother tongue* sa klase?)

10. *How does phonics-based instruction help you in teaching early reading?*

(Paano nakatutulong sa inyo ang *phonics-based instruction* sa pagtuturo ng pagbabasa?)

11. *Tell me about using the learners' prior experiences in teaching them how to read.*

(Ano ang tungkol sa paggamit ninyo ng mga *prior experiences* ng mga mag-aaral kapag tinuturuan silang bumasa?)

12. *What do you think of code-switching and translations?*

(Ano ang masasabi ninyo patungkol sa *code-switching* at *translations*?)

13. *Tell me about comprehension as the end goal of reading.*

(Sabihin sa akin ang tungkol sa *comprehension* bilang end goal ng reading.)

14. *What needs improvement in your teaching of early reading?*

(Ano ang nangangailangan ng pagpapabuti o *improvement* tungkol sa pagtuturo mo ng pagbabasa?)

15. *Tell me about the changes in your classroom when it comes to reading materials.*

(Sabihin sa akin ang mga tungkol sa *reading materials* sa loob ng inyong klasrum)

16. *How does technology help you teach reading? What are the materials related to technology that you use?*

(Paano nakatutulong ang *technology* sa pagtuturo mo ng pagbabasa? Ano ang mga *materials* na ginagamit mo?)

17. *Let's talk more about the need to teach learners how to read in the languages Filipino and English. Tell me about the reading materials in these languages.*

(Pag-usapan pa natin ang tungkol sa paggamit ng *Filipino* at *English* sa pagtuturo ng pagbabasa sa mga bata. Sabihin sa akin ang mga *materials* na ginagamit ninyo tuwing ininuturo ninyo ang pagbabasa sa *English* at *Filipino*.)

18. *Think back at the time you used code-switching and translation while teaching learners how to read. How did it work? How did it help learners in the reading process?*

(Isipin ang isang pangyayari na ginamit mo ang *code-switching* at *translation* habang nagtuturo ka sa mga batang bumasa. Paano ito nangyari? Paano ito nakatulong sa mga bata sa proseso ng pagbabasa?)

WRAP UP

Suppose you have a minute to talk to the DepEd Secretary about the teachers' language ideologies and early reading instruction practices which is the topic of today's discussion, what are you going to say?

(Kunwari may isang *minute* ka para makausap ang DepEd Secretary tungkol sa *teachers' language ideologies and early reading instruction practices* na *topic* natin ngayon sa ating *discussion*, ano ang sasabihin mo?)

We talked about your language ideologies and early reading instruction practices. Have we missed anything?

(May nakalimutan pa ba tayo?)

That ends our focus group discussion. Thank you very much!

(At diyan nagtatapos ang ating *focus group discussion*. Maraming salamat!)

Appendix F

Letter to the Schools Division Superintendent

May 16, 2022

ELY S. UBALDO, CESO VI

Assistant Schools Division Superintendent
Officer-in-Charge, Office of the Schools Division Superintendent
Schools Division Office I Pangasinan

Ma'am:

I am **Jackson G. Orlanda**, a Master of Arts in Language and Literacy Education student at the University of the Philippines Open University. I am also a public school teacher at Zaragoza Elementary School, Bolinao, Pangasinan. I am currently working on my thesis entitled "**Teachers' Language Ideologies and Early Reading Instruction Practices in Philippine Multilingual Classrooms.**" This study aims to revisit the decade-long implementation of the Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) and provide a fresh perspective on the reconceptualization of teacher education programs across the country. Likewise, this study will be the first to investigate whether the teachers' language ideologies are reflected in their use of language/s in early reading instruction in Philippine multilingual classrooms.

Hence, I would like to ask for your permission and recommendation to interview a number of primary grades teachers in our division, observe and/or record their reading classes next school year, subject them to focus group discussions, and analyze their relevant documents such as lesson plans used in reading instruction, for the gathering of data needed for the completion of my study. Rest assured that research ethics will be observed all throughout the study.

Thank you so much for your support!

Sincerely,

JACKSON G. ORLANDA

Researcher
0919 008 7153
jgorlanda@up.edu.ph

Noted:

PORTIA P. PADILLA, PhD

Research Adviser
pppadilla@up.edu.ph

Approved:

ELY S. UBALDO, CESO VI

OIC, Office of the Schools Division Superintendent
Schools Division Office I Pangasinan

Appendix G

Approval of the Schools Division Superintendent to Conduct the Study

Republic of the Philippines
Department of Education
Region I
SCHOOLS DIVISION OFFICE I PANGASINAN

May 30, 2022

Jackson G. Orlanda
Researcher

Sir:

This Office hereby approves the request to conduct study to the Primary grade teachers (MTB-MLE), Schools Division Office I Pangasinan, relative to your study entitled **“Teachers’ Language Ideologies and Early Reading Instruction Practices in Philippine Multilingual Classrooms”** subject to the following conditions:

1. Respondent’s consent must be secured first;
2. No government time/supplies/equipment and other resources shall be used;
3. Classes/Office work shall not be disrupted;
4. Performance of your official duties/responsibilities shall not be affected;
5. Copy of the result/findings of the study shall be furnished this Office;
6. The provisions of the Data Privacy Act of 2012 must be strictly complied with;

and

7. All prescribed health protocols are observed at all times.

Good Luck and more power!

ELY S. UBALDO, Ed. D., CESO VI
Assistant Schools Division Superintendent
Officer in Charge
Office of the Schools Division Superintendent

RELEASED
MAY 31 2022
SDO1-RECORDS ✓

 Address: Alvear St., East Capitol Ground
Lingayen, Pangasinan
Telephone No.: (075)-522-2202
Email: pangasinan1@deped.gov.ph

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Revision No.: 01
Page No.: Page 34 of 40
Effectivity Date: MM-DD-2020

Appendix H

Letter to the Public Schools District Supervisor

Date

Public Schools District Supervisor

District
Schools Division Office I Pangasinan

Sir/Ma'am:

I am **Jackson G. Orlanda**, a graduate student in language and literacy education at the University of the Philippines Open University. I am also a public school teacher at Zaragoza Elementary School, Bolinao, Pangasinan. I am currently working on my thesis entitled “**Teachers’ Language Ideologies and Early Reading Instruction Practices in Philippine Multilingual Classrooms.**” This study aims to revisit the decade-long implementation of the Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) and provide a fresh perspective on the reconceptualization of teacher education programs across the country. Likewise, this study will be the first to investigate whether the teachers’ language ideologies are reflected in their use of language/s in early reading instruction in Philippine multilingual classrooms.

Hence, I would like to ask for your permission to interview primary grades teachers, observe and/or record their reading classes, subject them to focus group discussions, and analyze their relevant documents such as lesson plans used in reading instruction, for the gathering of data needed for the completion of my study. I am also asking for permission to be allowed to discuss my study to the school heads and the research methods to be used. Rest assured that research ethics will be considered all throughout the study.

Thank you so much for your support!

Sincerely,

JACKSON G. ORLANDA

Researcher

0919 008 7153

jgorlanda@up.edu.ph

Noted:

Approved:

PORTIA P. PADILLA, PhD

Research Adviser

pppadilla@up.edu.ph

Public Schools District Supervisor

District

Appendix I

School Information Sheet

Name of School:

Address:

Language used in MTB-MLE:

Number of Grade 1 Teachers: _____

Number of Grade 2 Teachers: _____

Number of Grade 3 Teachers: _____

Appendix J

Consent Form for the School Head

Date

School Head

Elementary School

District

Schools Division Office I Pangasinan

Sir/Ma'am:

I am **Jackson G. Orlanda**, a graduate student in language and literacy education at the University of the Philippines Open University. I am also a public school teacher at Zaragoza Elementary School, Bolinao, Pangasinan. I am currently working on my thesis entitled **“Teachers’ Language Ideologies and Early Reading Instruction Practices in Philippine Multilingual Classrooms.”** This study aims to revisit the decade-long implementation of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) and provide a fresh perspective on the reconceptualization of teacher education programs across the country. Likewise, this study will be the first to investigate whether the teachers’ language ideologies are reflected in their use of language/s in early reading instruction in Philippine multilingual classrooms.

Hence, I would like to ask for your permission and recommendation in inviting your primary grades teachers to be part of my research study. I will interview them, observe and/or record their reading classes, subject them to focus group discussions, and analyze their relevant documents such as lesson plans used in reading instruction to gather the data needed in the completion of my study. Rest assured that research ethics will be considered all throughout the study.

Thank you so much for your support!

Sincerely,

JACKSON G. ORLANDA

Researcher

0919 008 7153/jgorlanda@up.edu.ph

Noted:

PORTIA P. PADILLA, PhD

Research Adviser

pppadilla@up.edu.ph

Approved:

School Head

Appendix K

Study Information and Consent Sheet (adapted from Burton, 2013)

You are invited to participate in a study on language and reading instruction. You were selected as a possible participant because you are currently a public elementary school teacher teaching primary grades in Pangasinan. Please read this form and ask any questions you may have before agreeing to be in the study. This study is being conducted by Jackson G. Orlanda, a graduate student at the University of Philippines Open University.

Background Information:

The purpose of this study is to investigate teachers' language ideologies and their early reading instruction practices in Philippine multilingual classrooms.

Procedure:

If you agree to be in this study, you will be asked to participate in completing a questionnaire, an interview, class observations, and a focus group discussion, conducted by the researcher. The documents that you use in your class such as your lesson plans will also be analyzed by the researcher. The questionnaire will take approximately 5 minutes to complete, the interviews will take about 30-45 minutes, your reading class will be observed for at nine times and video recorded if possible, and the focus group discussion will take about 30-45 minutes. The interview and focus group discussion will be audio recorded.

Risks and Benefits:

In your participation in the study, there might be statements that you may unintentionally utter, and there might be incidents in the reading class that are not intended to be observed by the researcher. Your identity and your learners' identities will be private, and pseudonyms will be used instead. Health protocols must still be observed considering the COVID-19 health risks. However, this study will lead to the revaluing of the local languages and to the evaluation of the language policy (MTB-MLE) currently in place. This study will also be the first to investigate whether teachers' language ideologies are reflected in their use of languages in early reading instruction in Philippine multilingual classrooms.

Confidentiality:

The records of this study will be kept private. Participants will not be identified in any presentations or publications that will result from this study. Research documents and audio and video recordings will be stored securely and will only be accessed by the researcher and his research adviser.

Voluntary Participation:

Participation in this study is voluntary. Your decision whether or not to participate will not affect your current or future relations with the University of the Philippines Open University (UPOU) or the Department of Education (DepEd). If you decide to participate, you are free not to answer any question or withdraw at any time without affecting those relationships.

Contact Information:

The researcher conducting this study is Jackson G. Orlanda. You may ask any questions you have now. If you have questions later, you are encouraged to contact him at 0919 008 7153 or email him at jgorlanda@up.edu.ph. Other questions may be directed to Dr. Portia P. Padilla at pppadilla@up.edu.ph, Jackson's thesis adviser.

You will be given a copy of this information to keep for your records.

<p>Name: _____ Signature:</p> <p>_____</p> <p>Date: _____</p> <p>_____ <i>I consent to be part of this research study.</i></p> <p>_____ <i>I do not consent to be part of this research study, because</i></p>

Appendix L

Learner's Assent Form

Ako si Jackson G. Orlanda. Ako ay isang guro at kasalukuyang nag-aaral sa University of the Philippines Open University. Samahan mo ako sa isang pag-aaral tungkol sa paggamit ng iba't-ibang wika sa iyong klase at kung paano ka turuan magbasa ng iyong guro. Ang mga impormasyon patungkol sa pag-aaral na ito ay alam na ng iyong guro at mga magulang.

Narito ang mga impormasyon tungkol sa iyong pagsama:

1. Oobserbahan ko ang iyong klase nang siyam na beses. Gagamit ako ng isang video camera upang mairekord ang pagtuturo ng iyong guro.
2. Libre at ligtas ang iyong pagsali rito.
3. Wala akong ibang pagsasabihan ng tungkol sa iyo at mga gagawin mo maliban sa aking adviser sa pag-aaral na ito.
4. Maari kang umayaw sa pagsali kahit kailan mo gusto.

Ang iyong paglagda o pagsulat ng pangalan dito ay nangangahulugan ng iyong pagsali sa pag-aaral na ito.

Pangalan: _____ Lagda:

Petsa: _____

Note: This was also read and explained to the learners.

Appendix M

Parent's Consent Form

MGA MAGULANG:

Magandang araw po sa inyo!

Ako po si Jackson G. Orlanda, kasalukuyang kumukuha ng *Master of Arts in Language and Literacy Education* sa *University of the Philippines Open University*. Ako ay isa ring guro sa Zaragoza Elementary School, Bolinao, Pangasinan. Ako ay kasalukuyang nagsasagawa ng isang pag-aaral tungkol sa mga ideolohiya o paniniwala ng mga guro tungkol sa iba't-ibang wika na ginagamit sa kanilang klase at ang kanilang mga iba't-ibang pamamaraan sa pagtuturo ng pagbabasa sa mga bata.

Dahil dito, aking hinihingi ang inyong permiso na obserbahan ang klase ng inyong anak nang hindi kukulang sa siyam (9) beses.. Ako ay gagamit din ng isang video camera upang mairekord ang pagtuturo ng kaniyang guro. Aking sinisiguro na walang peligro sa inyong anak kaugnay ng pag-aaral na ito. Ang mga talaan ng pananaliksik na ito ay mananatiling pribado. Ang mga sumali ay walang pagkakakilanlan at hindi mailalagay ang kanilang pangalan sa alinmang mga lathalain o presentasyon na magiging resulta ng pananaliksik na ito. Ang mga datos ay itatago sa isang pribadong lalagyan at maari lamang magamit ng mananaliksik at ng kaniyang tagapayo.

Maraming salamat po!

Lubos na sumasainyo,

JACKSON G. ORLANDA

0919 008 7153

jgorlanda@up.edu.ph

Gupitin ang CONFIRMATION SLIP na ito, at ibalik ito sa guro ng inyong anak.

Petsa: _____

_____ Ako ay pumapayag na maisama sa obserbasyon ang aking anak.

_____ Ako ay hindi pumapayag na maisama sa obserbasyon ang aking anak dahil

Pangalan ng Magulang: _____

Lagda: _____

Petsa: _____

Appendix N

List of RQ1 Codes and Sample Transcription

Code	Sample Transcription
Advantage of language groupings	Okay lang naman po. Masaya. Kasi kahit magkaiba-iba ang mga lengguahe, nagkakaintindihan pa rin po kami.
Challenges in MTB-MLE	Parang mas nakakalito siya sa mga bata. Mas nahihirapan sila. Kasi ti'gnan mo, magtuturo ka ng Pangasinan mula Grade 1 hanggang Grade 3... 'yung mga lalo na sa Math, 'yung mga numbers. Sa Pangasinan, sakey ta's pagdating mo ng Grade 4, one. Parang... kung ita-translate mo, ma-a-ano lang pero sana, ano, sa umpisa pa lang, kung ano 'yung k'wan 'yun na lang. Kung sa Math – kasi sa Math kapag makikipag-contest ka, English naman. Anong mangyayari sa mga bata na naka-mother tongue siya?
Code-switch	Okay. Sa English wala ay sa Tagalog, wala tayong problema d'yan kasi ang bata maiintindihan niya rin ang Tagalog. Kasi usually naman ang ginagamit talaga nila dito sa school at kahit sa bahay nila is Tagalog talaga. Sa English, 'pag nag-swish—nag-switch na ako sa English lalo na sa English Language- na topic namin, talagang 'yung vocabulary nila at 'pag-construct nila ng sentences in English talagang nahihirapan sila pati understanding nila sa English nahihirapan sila. Kasi mas sanay talaga silang gumamit ng tagalog at Ilokano.
Difficulty in differences of language	Kasi noon, nung ano namin... nung K to 12, hindi nila pinagsama-sama 'yong mga Iloko. Bale may kasama rin kaming Pangasinan kaya nahihirapan din 'yong iba. Pero mas nakaka—yong karamihan doon Iloko. Mas nakaka-relate kami sa isa't-isa. May naisasabi naming 'yong gusto naming sabihin. Ganun.
Dominance of a major language	Kasi diba kapag mga ano sa mga school di naman ginagamit 'yung mother tongue 'pag nag-uusap usap 'yung mga tao. 'Yung ano pa rin, 'yung kung ano talaga 'yung major na language lang talaga 'yung ginagamit. Masasabi ko... ah... okay lang din sa 'kin (laughing) kasi nasanay na din ako sa mga ganon, eh. Kaya siguro hindi ako masyadong natuto mag-Pangasinan.

Dominance of English	Oo, sir, naniniwala ako. Syempre kapag nag-aapply tayo ng trabaho ang nasa taas talaga yong English na. Yong sa baba hindi mo napapansin kung maski Pangasinense ka o Iloko ka, hindi ka tatanungin sa Iloko, sir. Pure English po kaya naniniwala ako diyan.
Dominance of Filipino	Ah... okay lang naman yon pero kasi ‘yung mga bata ngayon tulad ko, kahit lumaki ako dito sa Mabini di ako nasanay sa sa Pangasinan, so mas lalo ‘yung mga bata ngayon. Kasi syempre mas modern na ‘yung mga ano ngayon—puro Tagalog na.
Effects of Pandemic	Sa loob ng 14 years, hindi pa. Baka ngayon kasi may mga English speaking pupils ako, mga YouTube babies.
English as a Sign of Intelligence	Ano naman, positive na naa-amaze kasi ah feeling nila pag nag-English ang isang tao napakagalang.
English as bridge	English? Ito yong tulong ko sa kanila na – yong mga bata po kasi nahihya po silang mag-English. Pag nagenglish ka po parang “wooh!” iba yong feeling sa kanila. Kaya parang for me, yong English po ito po yong magiging hagdan pataas po nila sa paglalim pa ng knowledge nila.
English as top	Yes, sir. Dito sa community po, ay wala, sir. Sa bansa natin ay ganun pag nag-apply ka ng trabaho English din ang itatanong sa’yo. Sa world, ganun din, English din.
English deepens knowledge	English? Ito yong tulong ko sa kanila na – yong mga bata po kasi nahihya po silang mag-English. Pag nagenglish ka po parang “wooh!” iba yong feeling sa kanila. Kaya parang for me, yong English po ito po yong magiging hagdan pataas po nila sa paglalim pa ng knowledge nila
English for economic and social purposes	Wikang English? Para po sa akin dapat siya po ‘yong priority sa K to 12 curriculum natin para po ‘yong mga bata kaya po nilang makipag-compete or makisalamuha hindi lang po sa lugar natin pati sa ibang bansa o nation na lang din, Sir.
English for economic purposes	Mayroon po. Halimbawa na lang po sa pag-a-apply natin sa trabaho. ‘Di ba po nung first tayong ma-in, in-interview tayo hindi namarn po ginamit

	<p>'yong Iloko na salita, kun'di ang priority po is English? Ang masasabi ko po 'yong English po kahit saan ka man pumunta na mag-apply ng trabaho 'yon naman 'yong i-na-adopt nilang salita; hindi naman po puwedeng halimbawa in-interview ka, ang salita mo is Ilokano, 'di ba po hindi naman po pare-parehas 'yong salita natin, kaya ang ginagamit po natin is English.</p>
English for social purposes	<p>Paulit-ulit pero pahirap siya nang pahirap. Uhm ngayon, diba uhm ang priority natin kapag Grade 1, Grade 2, Grade 3, ang priority ng matutunan ng bata or gamitin ng teacher sa pagtuturo sa mga bata, syempre 'yung mother tongue. Pagdating nila ng 4, 5, and 6, tsaka lang pu- masu- m- malilipat sa Tagalog hanggang sa 'pag pataas din nang pataas 'yung grade nila, palipat din nang palip- nagiging English na siya hanggang sa English na siya. Kasi sa atin sa DepEd, ang gusto natin maging globally competitive ang ating mga napo-produce na estudyante. Therefore, syempre kung ano 'yung globally used na language, yun 'yung binibigyan natin ng halaga.</p>
Filipino as home language	<p>Yong MTB, sir? Kasi yong MTB, sir, medyo mahirap kasi i-ano kasi mostly sa mga bata natin lalo na sa bahay bibihira na yong nag-i-Ilokano na talaga. Katulad sa amin Ilokano nga kami pero nagta-Tagalog din sa pag-uusap.</p>
Filipino as medium of instruction	<p>Wikang Filipino... okay din (laughs) mas mas mas mas mas okay kasi 'yan eh ng medium instruction ko.</p>
Filipino as mother tongue	<p>Kasi parang nagbase sila sa ano eh, sa ibang bansa na ano, na... parang sa Japan, Nihonggo ganon, parang ganon. Pero ang point—ang ano ko dyan, kasi sa Japan isa lang, Nihonggo lang. Kung sana ang ginamit natin ay Tagalog, buong Pilipinas na 'yun, mas okay pa kesa 'yung iba-iba ang... bawat ano iba-iba. Parang ano pa siya, magastos- magastos pa. Kung sana Tagalog lang—Tagalog na lang, ano hindi mahihirapan siguro 'yung bata. Kasi kung Pangasinan, pupunta ka sa ano iba na naman. Kung Tagalog na lang sana, mas madali.</p>
Filipino is commonly used	<p>Mas maganda po. Mas madaling nakakaintindi yong bata kaysa yong ibabato mo sa kanya o kakausapin mo siya ng Iloko. Mas mahirap nilang</p>

	intindihin yon. Hamlibawa, sir, yong nagtuturo ka sa, sir, sa MTB-MLE mas maraming hindi nila alam yong vocabulary na gagamitin mo. I-translate mo pa sa Filipino mas naiintindihan nila, sir.
Filipino is home language	Siguro, Sir, ire-relate ko sa 'kin, since hindi naman lahat ng parents eh from Pangasinan, 'yun siguro puwedeng Pangasinan sila. Eh pero 'pag tulad ko na si Mama Tagalog siya, si Papa taga-Pangasinan, syempre gagamitin at ituturo 'yung parehas nilang naiintindihan, sa Tagalog tayo, sa Filipino.
Filipino is the bridge in learning	Wikang Filipino po? Uhm, sa wikang Filipino ito po 'yong nagiging tulay ng mga bata. Ito yong nagiging daan kung saan naiintindihan ako ng lahat.
Filipino promoted in the media	Kasi 'yung... feeling ko din sa mga pinapanood din nila, syempre Tagalog din, ta's kung pano sila kausapin diba mga magulang nila puro Tagalog pa din.
Fitting in through language	Anong grupo? Hindi naman po talagang gumamit pero nung college po kasi syempre mga friends ko mga taga Mangaldan. Ngayon ang medium po nila talaga ay kapag nag-uusap po kami ay Pangasinan. Ngayon po syempre hindi naman po puwedeng sa akin lang sila nag-aadjust. Nag-aadjust din po ako sa kanila. May konting alam din po akong Pangasinan. Then 'yong Iloko po syempre La Union po. Madami din po naming taga La Union kaya pag nakikipag-usap po ako sa iba naka-Iloko po ako. So may mga time na hindi naman po talagang ginamit ko siya pero in-adjust ko po 'yong sarili ko.
Giving Importance of Filipino	Mahalaga din na ituro ang Filipino kasi ito yong wika natin so kailangan pagtibayan natin para hindi rin mawala katulad ng kasi minsan English na yong nangingibabaw sa ibang ano diba so kailangan din 'yong Filipino na ano.
Iloko is less used	Maganda naman siya. Kaya lang sa sa panahon ngayon mas ginagamit na 'yong Filipino.
Importance of mother tongue	Sa mga bata? Sa school? Syempre yong kahalagahan po ng isang language ng bayan kumbaga sa atin dito sa atin Iloko po ang wika natin dito then dito naman po tayo pumapasok so

	<p>mahalaga po na alam natin kung paano gamitin ang wika natin.</p>
Lack of teacher proficiency in mother tongue	<p>Mahirap po kasing mag-Ilokano kaya may time -. Lalo na po kapag may word po ako na hindi ko maintindihan. Kaya bago po talaga ako magstart ng klase ko, nagtatanong po muna ako. Kung ano ang ibig sabihin ng ganito, kung ano ang tamang pronunciation ng ganito.</p>
Language choice	<p>Andon na 'yon, nakakalimutan na. Kasi kahit ako mismo, mapapatunayan ko 'yan kasi Iloko kami sa bahay, may baby ako, Tagalog talaga ang sinasalita ko na talaga sa kaniya.</p>
Language discrimination	<p>Ay hindi po, Sir. May discrimination na po sa ganun. Dapat wag mo ibukod isama mo pa rin at ipaintindi kung ano yong tinatalakayat pinag-uusapan.</p>
Language diversity	<p>Parang ngayon kasi, Sir, dahil nga sa technology 'di ba, 'yung mga bata mas nag-aaral na sila sa videos na English. So parang 'yong last (school year), may mga English na kami na students, English-speaking na students. Kaya lang, 'yun na naman ulit kasi 'yung mostly nga, Tagalog sila, Pangasinan, ano na naman ulit parang ang hirap na naman mag-adjust kasi may nag-i-English, may nagfi-Filipino, ta's may nagpa-Pangasinan. Eh Pangasinan 'yong books, parang mas dagdag trabaho.</p>
Language for exclusion	<p>Kung minsan, Sir, sa mga Ilokano, hindi ako maka-relate sa kanila. Kasi hindi po ako nakakaintindi ng Ilokano. Kasi Bolinao ako. At minsan din nung una ko sa diyan po diyan sa Lingayen kung saan ginagamit po nila ay Pangasinan. So, 'pag may pinag-uusapan sila... ah 'pag halimbawa may gusto silang hindi ako ma-disappoint ganun nag-uusap po sila ng language nila. Yong salita nila. Para hindi ko ma-gets.</p>
Language hesitancy	<p>Nung una po nahihiya. Syempre bago tsaka hindi naman ako ganun ka fluent pag dating sa Ilokano. Nakatulong din naman na hindi ako jinajudge ng iba kapag sinusubukan ko.</p>
Language hierarchy in the community	<p>Mayroon siguro. Mayroon. Kasi kung tutuusin sa bayan natin, mas marami ang Iloko kaysa sa</p>

	Bolinao. Doon sa bayan kasi isa lang yata ang Bolinao, tama? At sa isla.
Language hierarchy in the country	Sa bansa natin ay ganun pag nag-apply ka ng trabaho English din ang itatanong sa'yo. Sa world, ganun din, English din.
Language hierarchy in the workplace	Halimbawa kapag may meeting (dito sa school). Syempre po yong mga nanay po kapag may additional na mga tanong, mostly po ang ginagamit po nila ay Ilokano. Lalo na kapag galling po sila malayo tsaka yon po ginagamit nilang wika. So kapag nagtatanong po sila though naiintindihan po nila yong Filipino hindi po naiiwasan na kapag nagtanong sila naka Ilokano, syempre 'yon po 'yong ginagamit nila. Ngayon po kapag dayo po sila, Tagalog po. Sa kapwa ko guro, sabihin ko yong wika mismo?
Language of instruction	'Yong MTB, sir? Kasi yong MTB, sir, medyo mahirap kasi i-ano kasi mostly sa mga bata natin lalo na sa bahay bibihira na yong nag-i-Ilokano na talaga. Katulad sa amin Ilokano nga kami pero nagta-Tagalog din sa pag-uusap.
Language of the parents	Halimbawa kapag may meeting. Syempre po 'yong mga nanay po kapag may additional na mga tanong, mostly po ang ginagamit po nila ay Ilokano. Lalo na kapag galing po sila malayo tsaka 'yon po ginagamit nilang wika. So kapag nagtatanong po sila though naiintindihan po nila 'yong Filipino hindi po naiiwasan na kapag nagtanong sila naka Ilokano, syempre 'yon po 'yong ginagamit nila. Ngayon po kapag dayo po sila, Tagalog po.
Language preservation	Ang opinyon ko dyan, Sir, regarding po bas a mga subjects o yong pagkakagamit ng mother tongue? 'Yong pagkakagamit ng mother tongue okay lang din. Kasi nga ang sabi, sir, hindi makalimutan ng mga bata ang magsalita ng Ilokano kasi nga Ilokano tayo dito. Ayaw nilang mamatay yong pagsasalita ng Ilokano kaya okay lang din na mag-Ilokano sila.
Language utilization determined by majority	Oo. Naniniwala ako. Kasi syempre uhm nakadepende 'yon sa majority ng tao na gumagamit ng wika, eh. Syempre kung anong alam nila 'yon ang gagamitin nila sa pag-e-explain. Then kung ano ang hindi nila alam 'yon ang mas

	<p>hindi nila gagamitin. 'Yong wika na pinaka-alam nila, kumbaga 'yon na 'yong pinaka high sa kanila. Then yong hindi nila masyadong alam then yon 'yong at the bottom.</p>
Language variation	<p>Kasi doon sa amin sa bahay namin iba 'yong pagsasalita namin na Bolinao. Iba din dito (sa barangay na ito). Hindi ko alam kung ano kasi ay iba't-iba sila dito na salita na hindi ko maintindihan. Pero paryas do'n sa bahay namin na parang garay sabi nila. Eh, doon sa bahay namin buo talaga na garay na'en ganu'n. Bolinao talaga doon.</p>
Languages are equal	<p>Ah wala lahat pinapahalagan. Lahat ng wika.</p>
Learner proficiency in mother tongue	<p>Uhm, unique at malalim. Kasi po may words po talaga na Ilokano na malalalim na hindi ko na po maintindihan. Pero 'yong ibang mga bata naman po alam naman po nila ito. Ibig sabihin po siguro parang kahit sa bahay po siguro ginagamit po talaga nila yong medium na Ilokano. So parang nagshi-sharing po kami doon. Nagbibigay po sila ng knowledge sa akin, nagbibigay din po ako ng knowledge sa kanila, ganun.</p>
Learners understand Filipino better than MT	<p>Mas maganda po. Mas madaling nakakaintindi yong bata kaysa 'yong ibabato mo sa kanya o kakausapin mo siya ng Iloko. Mas mahirap nilang intindihin y'on. Hamlibawa, Sir, yong nagtuturo ka sa, Sir, sa MTB-MLE mas maraming hindi nila alam 'yong vocabulary na gagamitin mo. I-translate mo pa sa Filipino mas naiintindihan nila, Sir.</p>
Learners understand mother tongue better	<p>Pagdating po sa Bolinao hindi po masyado kasi nga minsan ah hindi po ako masyadong nag-stay dito. Mas preferred ko pong ginagamit ang Filipino pero pagdating po sa pagtuturo mas naiintindihan ng mga bata ang Bolinao. So mas ina-ano ko po ang Bolinao, mas ginagamit. Pagdating po sa bahay 'pag ang parents ko po ang kinakausap ko, Bolinao. Pero 'pag pamangkin ko is Filipino.</p>
Learners' difficulty understanding English	<p>Sa wikang English, ano madalang naming, madalang na-ano tawag dun? Madalang naming naituturo kasi nasa third quarter na tapos minsan hindi naiintindihan. English ka nang English sa harapan parang nakatanga lang 'yong mga ano</p>

	bata kaya minsan tina-Tagalog mo na din, Bino-Bolinao mo na din.
Learning English via exposure	Hay, wikang English. Okay. Ang wikang Ingles mahirap siya kung kulang ka ng exposure dito pero kung ikaw ay sanay or naririnig mo palagi ang wikang ito, madali lang itong gamitin, madali ka lang ding makapag-communicate sa ibang tao kung nai-expose ka palagi sa wikang ito.
Less allotted time for English	Sa wikang English, ano madalang naming, madalang na-ano tawag dun? Madalang naming naituturo kasi nasa third quarter na tapos minsan hindi naiintindihan. English ka nang English sa harapan parang nakatanga lang 'yong mga ano bata kaya minsan tina-Tagalog mo na din, Bino-Bolinao mo na din.
Less vocabulary in mother tongue	Mas maganda po. Mas madaling nakakaintindi yong bata kaysa yong ibabato mo sa kanya o kakausapin mo siya ng Iloko. Mas mahirap nilang intindihin 'yon. Hamlibawa, Sir, yong nagtuturo ka sa, Sir, sa MTB-MLE mas maraming hindi nila alam yong vocabulary na gagamitin mo. I-translate mo pa sa Filipino mas naiintindihan nila, Sir.
Medium of instruction	Eto na tayo. Okay... uhm Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education, MTB-MLE, uhm napaka—napakaganda nito kaso uhm ang implementation namin, eto na uhm ang kailangang gamitin ay Ilokano hanggang sa mga instructio- ins- uhm instructional materials Ilokano din. Ngayon ang problema, 'yung mga bata Tagalog sila. Ang mas naiintindihan nila ay Tagalog so kailangan ko ulit i-Tagalog 'yung naka Ilokano na learning materials nila para mas maintindihan din nila ulit. Though, 'pag dating sa akin sa Grade 3 ha, 'pag dating sa akin sa Grade 3, marami na ring mga bata ang nakakaintindi ng gamit ang wikang Ilokano kaso minsan kapag sumasagot din sila, nahihirapan silang sumagot sa Ilokano.
More people use English	Kasi halos pantay lang din naman sa ibang lugar. Maraming gumagamit ng English. Sa ibang lugar marami ring ano... hindi ko rin kasi sigurado.
More time is needed for English	Pwede bang i-start na lang sa first quarter yong subject na English?

More vocabulary in Filipino	Mas maganda po. Mas madaling nakakaintindi yong bata kaysa yong ibabato mo sa kanya o kakausapin mo siya ng Iloko. Mas mahirap nilang intindihin yon. Hamlibawa, Sir, yong nagtuturo ka sa, Sir, sa MTB-MLE mas maraming hindi nila alam yong vocabulary na gagamitin mo. I-translate mo pa sa Filipino mas naiintindihan nila, Sir.
Mother tongue for cultural preservation	Kasi nawawala na daw ‘yung kultura, ‘yung language—baka mawala na, baka hindi na alam ng mga susunod na mga ano mga bata. So ‘yung ‘yung... anong tawag do’n? Para hindi mawala ‘yon, kailangan nila ulit- kailangan i-ano sa kanila—kasi diba ‘yung ibang bansa nga, ‘yung ‘yung... Mother tongue nila ang ginagamit as a medium of instruction sa kanila. Kaya daw mas natututo ‘yung bata sa kanila so siguro ganon din sa ‘tin, para mas matuto daw ‘yung bata.
Mother tongue is least priority	Para sa akin least priority na po siya para sa K to 12 curriculum.
Mother tongue is hard	Yong MTB, Sir? Kasi yong MTB, Sir, medyo mahirap kasi i-ano kasi mostly sa mga bata natin lalo na sa bahay bibihira na yong nag-i-Ilokano na talaga. Katulad sa amin Ilokano nga kami pero nagta-Tagalog din sa pag-uusap.
Mother tongue is not helpful	‘Yan ang hindi ko rin maintindihan, Sir, kaya lang sumusunod tayo sa mga guidelines ng DepEd. Siguro, Sir, kaya binabato nila ‘yan para sa mga pure na Iloko na hindi rin nakakapagsalita ng wikang Filipino at wikang English katulad ng mga Aeta ata talagang sa salita nila dapat yong ipinpush na pagtuturo sa kanila.
Mother tongue is not used outside of school	‘Yon na nga po, sir, dapat hindi na masyadong ginagamit pagdating sa loob ng classroom. Kasi pag halimbawang mapunta naman po tayo sa ibang lugar so hindi po siya magagamit po ng mga bata pagdating sa kanilang learning. Para sa akin lang po ‘yon, sir, ah?
Mother tongue should be one subject not as medium	Kahit sa MTB na subject ‘yon na lang ‘yong Ilokano dapat sana. ‘Yong iba, halimbawa sa Math, di ba ini-Ilokano rin ‘yong Math, Sir, ano? Mahirap kasi minsan i-translate lahat sa Ilokano ‘yong mga mathematical terms at saka dapat kasi ‘pag Ilokano na ang gagamitin doon, eh, hindi naman Ilokano lahat kapag lalabas na sila sa

	outside Pangasinan. Halimbawa, pumunta sila sa Manila. 'Pag nag-aral sila doon, wala na. Hirap na sila kasi Ilokano. Puwede rin siguro sa MTB, MTB lang siguro, Sir. 'Yon na lang.
Mother tongue should be taught	Sa primary grade po pakiramdam ko naman po talaga uhm dapat din po talagang may mother tongue na subject po 'yong mga bata. Kasi syempre pinapakita rin po dito na at their young age kailangan na kung ano 'yong mismong language sa lugar nila, alam nila 'yon. Kumbaga hindi po sila foreigner. Kumbaga dapat kahit na bata pa lang sila 'yon na 'yong language nila hindi nila nakakalimutan hanggang pagtanda nila.
Mother tongue should not be taught	To be honest, Sir, para sa akin, dapat hindi po masyadong pinapag-aralan yong MTB-MLE sa subject po. Para sa akin po yon, Sir. Kasi kadalasan na po sa mga bata ngayon ang ginagamit na po nila is Filipino. Kung nagtuturo po kami MTB-MLE na subject, napaghahalo po nila 'yong ibang words tas nalilito sila halimbawa pag iba na yong ibig sabihin sa Bolinao, so nalilito po yong mga bata.
MTB-MLE difficulty	May mga halimbawa d'yan. Halimbawa, Sir, 'agburburek.' 'Agburburek adiyay danum.' Hindi na maintindihan ng bata 'yan, Sir. Eh di i-translate mo na naman sa Filipino 'yan para maintindihan.
MTB-MLE is required	'Yan ang hindi ko rin maintindihan, Sir, kaya lang sumusunod tayo sa mga guidelines ng DepEd. Siguro, sir, kaya binabato nila 'yan para sa mga pure na Iloko na hindi rin nakakapagsalita ng wikang Filipino at wikang English katulad ng mga aeta ata talagang sa salita nila dapat yong ipinpush na pagtuturo sa kanila.
Multilingualism	Sa mother tongue mayroon din 'yong hiram, hiram sa Tagalog. Tapos 'yon. 'Yong sa Tagalog parang na-a-ano 'yong mga bata. Kung Tagalog ba o ano. Kung minsan talaga 'pag Filipino na 'yong examples nila nagiging Bolinao na 'yong mga examples nila 'pag nasa Filipino na kami.
No Idea about language hierarchies	Kasi halos pantay lang din naman sa ibang lugar. Maraming gumagamit ng English. Sa ibang lugar marami ring ano... hindi ko rin kasi sigurado.

No idea why MTB-MLE is implemented	Yan ang hindi ko rin maintindihan, Sir, kaya lang sumusunod tayo sa mga guidelines ng DepEd. Siguro, Sir, kaya binabato nila yan para sa mga pure na Iloko na hindi rin nakakapagsalita ng wikang Filipino at wikang English katulad ng mga Aeta ata talagang sa salita nila dapat 'yong ipinpush na pagtuturo sa kanila.
No language hierarchy	Tingin ko naman, Sir, hindi ganyan siguro. Kasi halos lahat naman ng ginagamit nating salita is nagagamit naman natin pare-parehas kaya hindi dapat nagkakaroon ng ganyan. Kasi nga, Sir, nagagamit naman nating sila lahat kaya dapat hindi na mag-hierarchy ganun kasi nga depende din siguro sa as the need arises sab inga nila, o kaya nagagamit din siguro natin yan lahat-lahat at hindi na kailangan na magkaroon pa ng ganyan.
Speaking English means understanding better	Uhm, hindi naman sa magaling pero mas nakakaintindi.
Stereotypes	Okay naman po siya, Sir. Maayos po siya. Pero pagdating po kasi sa ibang lungsod 'yong parang nagsasalita tayo is sinasabi nilang matigas, parang ibon, pero pag nasalita na tayo ng Filipino o English minsan sabi nila matigas, so 'yon po, sir.
Stop MTB-MLE implementation	Pwedeng tanggalin na lang? Pwedeng ano na rin, gamitin na lang na parang medium na pagtuturo sa ibang subjects para ma-explain mong mabuti sa mga bata. Pero sana tanggalin na lang 'yong subject na MTB-MLE.
Teach mother tongue at home not in school	Maganda sigurong ituro sa bahay na lang. kasi sa bahay naman nagsisimula yan eh. Kumbaga dito i-parang, -enhance na lang dito sa school.
Teaching and learning reading in three languages is confusing	Nakakalito. Nakakalito lalo na sa reading. Kasi may mga /e/ sa Tagalog. Ay, mayroong /e/ sa Tagalog na ang basa sa Iloko ay /ee/. Ganun din sa English.
Translations	Mas maganda po (pag may translations). Mas madaling nakakaintindi yong bata kaysa 'yong ibabato mo sa kanya o kakausapin mo siya ng Iloko. Mas mahirap nilang intindihin 'yon. Hamlibawa, Sir, yong nagtuturo ka sa, Sir, sa MTB-MLE mas maraming hindi nila alam yong vocabulary na gagamitin mo. I-translate mo pa sa Filipino mas naiintindihan nila, sir.

Use mother tongue as an auxiliary language	Pwedeng tanggalin na lang? Pwedeng ano na rin, gamitin na lang na parang medium na pagtuturo sa ibang subjects para ma-explain mong mabuti sa mga bata. Pero sana tanggalin na lang 'yong subject na MTB-MLE.
Use of Filipino in modern times	Ah... okay lang naman yon pero kasi 'yung mga bata ngayon tulad ko, kahit lumaki ako dito sa Mabini di ako nasanay sa sa Pangasinan, so mas lalo 'yung mga bata ngayon. Kasi syempre mas modern na 'yung mga ano ngayon—puro Tagalog na.
Use of lingua franca	Naranasan ko na po yan, Sir. Halimbawa nung nag seminar ako doon po sa La Union, may ibatibang lengwahe po na ginagamit, halimbawa po may Pangasinan may mga Bolinao. Tapos po syempre po grinoup po kami pero hindi po pareparehas 'yong aming language at 'yong ginamit lang po naming is 'yong nagkakaintindihan po kaming lahat.
Use of mother tongue and Identity	Mother tongue po kasi aside from topic po nami, uhm, naiprapractice din po namin yong languages na ginagamit nila. Kumbaga kahit nasa school kami hindi naming nakakalimutan yong language nila.
Using the dominant language in class	Then of course, Grade 3 mayroon po kaming mother tongue. Bago po ako, bago po kami nagstart ng lesson tinatanung ko muna kung ano 'yong dominant na language po na ginagamit po ng mga bata. Then, kapag may nakita ako na magkaiba 'yong ginagamit o 'yong dominant ang ginagawa ko po dalawa po. Yon ginagamit ko pong medium pag nagtuturo po ako

Appendix O

List of RQ2 Codes and Sample Transcription

Code	Sample Transcription
Abakada	Sa pagbabasa po, gumagamit po kami ng Marungko approach o kung minsan pinapadalhan ko po sila ng mga Abakada. 'Yon po muna 'yong ginagamit po namin sa pagbabasa para hindi po sila mabigla.
Activity sheets	Strategy po, halimbawa po pagbibigay po sa kanila ng activity sheets. 'Yon nga po iba-iba po 'yong kanilang kakayahan kaya 'yong activity sheets na ibibigay ko po sa kanila, naklasi-classify po base po sa kakayahan nila ng bata.
All can be readers	Opo may possibility po. Kapag 'yong bata po mismo gusto po niyang bumasa. Kumbaga hindi po siya napipilitan. Kasi po nakaka apekto din po 'yon. Kapag nakatanim na po sa kanyang isipan syempre po wala po talagang learning pero kung 'yong bata eager matututo po siya.
Allowing mistakes and correcting them	Lagi ko pong sinasabi, -- pagbibigay po ng positive na feedback. May very good. May clap. Then aside po doon, hinahayan ko po silang magkamali sa English. Kumbaga sabihin lang po nila 'yong alam nila then i-ko-correct ko na lang po sila.
Application of reading	'Yong application na. 'Yong titingnan mo na sila kung nakakabasa na sila. Halimbawa tinuro mo tapos i-aaply din nila, sila naman kung natuto sila o hindi.
Assessment	Ah unang una, ina-assist muna kung ano 'yung level ng kakayahan niya. Kung halimbawa, hindi pa siya makabasa ng ng pantig, 'yung mga katinig, yun muna. Pero kung nakakabasa na siya ng mga pantig ah mga katinig ganon, ah ano na hinahaluan ko na ng mga ibang tunog. Halimbawa 'yung 'ma' dadagdagan mo ng 's', oh ima-master 'yon hanggang sa dagdagan mo uli ng ano ng katinig, oh mabu- mababasa na—mastery lang ang inaano ko, mastery.
Basic to complex	Ang paborito ko 'yong kapag nakaka-pantig na sila, tapos nakakabuo na sila ng isang salita, tapos dadagdagan mo ng 'yung mga ano ba 'yong tawag do'n – mga "ang" or "ng," nakakabuo na sila

	ng pangungusap, tapos unti-unti nakakabasa na sila ng simpleng talata, tapos buong kuwento na.
Big Six of Reading	Siguro, Sir, doon ako sa ano sa phonics, sounds 'yan Sir diba? Tapos sa oral, Pangatlo 'yong phonological. Tapos doon ako sa comprehension na, tapos sa vocabulary tapos fluency. Siguro comprehension.
Big Six of Reading is important in English	Lahat din po. Kasi po ginagamit po natin 'yang mga domain na 'yan sa pagtuturo.
Big Six of Reading Is important in Filipino	Lahat din po 'yan.
Big Six of Reading Is important	Kahit anong language pa 'yan, itong phonics, Sir, ang number one. Then 'yong sa comprehension, Sir. Lahat po naman 'yan, mahalaga po. Kung isa lang pipiliin mo, lalong hindi nila naintindihan na, kaya lahat andyan. Sa pagtuturo ng reading, lahat andiyan para lalo nilang maintindihan kung ano 'yong ina-ano mo sa kanila. Kung pipili lang tayo ng isa lang or dalawa diyan, paano na?
Blending	'Yung ano, favorite part? 'Yung... 'yung magbe-blend na ng le- 'yung mga letters kapag katapos mong patunugin, 'yung ibe-blend mo na 'yung mga pantig, ganon. Lalo na 'pag nage-gets nila agad.
Bolinao and Filipino for questions	Uhm minsan Bolinao, minsan Tagalog. Same reason talaga.
Bolinao for clarifications	Mothe tongue po, sir. Kasi may mga words din po sa Filipino na medyo malalim so kailangan ko siyang itranslate sa mother tongue para mas lubos po nilang maintindihan.
Bolinao for directions	Ano po, sir, Bolinao. Kasi pag sa instruction po mas naiintindihan nila.
Bolinao language	Uhm yon nga para mapreserve nga yong salita namin kaya naming ginagamit yong salitang Bolinao kasi mayroon din kasi trabaho na parang translator nga na sinasabi ko puwede din nilang gamitin 'yon para sa future nila.
Bolinao not used at home	Kung i-a-ano natin, Sir, yong mga bata parang medyo hindi na nga sila aware sa ano sa Bolinao kung paano magbasa sa Bolinao. Kumbaga napag-iwanan sila Tagalog na nga 'yong

	ginagamit nila sa bahay. Kaya kung minsan medyo nahihirapan sa una 'yon kung ginagamit mo 'yong Bolinao, pero at the end naman parang na-ano naman nila.
Bolinao variation	'Yong nga 'yong sinasabi ko. Kunwari sa Salud iba yong ano nila. Mayroong mga taga Salud dito na pumupunta pa rito para mag-aral minsan iba yong salita nila kaya minsan, ibang version ng Bolinao, oo, ibang version dito, ibang version din doon sa Lucero. Kaya ay sa amin kasi ganito yan kaya sinasabi namin sa syemore doon kinukuha ng yong pinakahead nila sa translator doon sila kumukuha sa Lucero ng Bolinao.
Bridging of a language	Lahat. Parang mas malinaw sa kanila 'yon. Bridging nga ang ginagamit namin eh. Bolinao muna tas Tagalog muna tas English. Parang ganun.
Children are taught in Filipino	'Yun, kasi 'yun nga 'yung nasabi ko kanina na, kami parang kami kapag kapanganak na, 'yung bata tinuturuan na namin sila sa hindi na Pangasinan na salita or Iloko. Nasa Tagalog na sila or Filipino, 'yun na ang ano.
Classroom not print-rich	Sa ngayon po, Sir, ang nakalagay na lang po sa aking kwarto ay bulletin. Wala na po yong mga reading materials sa ngayon po. Kasi po nawala na po. Natanggal na po. Kaya ang mayroon na lang sa akin ay konte na lang po hindi kagaya noon na sobrang dami po, andyan po 'yong mga flashcard na mga salita ngayon po kunti na lang po. Mayroon pero kukunti na lang po hindi po kagaya noon.
Claveria Technique	Ang maganda na po na experience ko, sir, yong Claveria technique. 'Yong picture na mayroong words, madali nilang magreading doon.
Cooperation among Learners	Uhm mas madami po akong time na binibigay sa mga hindi po masyadong makabasa. Then 'yong mga nakakabasa naman po eh hinahayaan ko na lang po silang magtulungan.
Curriculum guides	Depende sa subject 'yon, Sir. Depende sa sequence ng ano diba ng curriculum guide 'yong ano 'yong susundin mo.

CVC	Sa English naman po, may mga rules po kasi sa English di ba po? Kaya ganoon din po. Sounds, basic po then CVC. Inuuna ko po yong mga madadaling mga words.
Dedication in teaching	Paano? Siguro di gawin mo 'yong part mo as a teacher talaga, Sir. Kung hindi siya makabasa di tutukan mo siyang makabasa hanggang sa ano makabasa siya, Sir. Ganun lang naman 'yon.
Depends on the subject	Pag sa Bolinao, Bolinao, sa Filipino, Filipino, pag sa English, itra-translate ko talaga. English ka muna ksi yong ano hindi naiintindihan, ia-ano mo rin sa English tsaka sa Tagalog.
Developing readers in Filipino	Mismong pamagat po? Tagalog po 'yong mga ginagamit po. Doon ko po sila balak pagalingin kasi po nakakalimut na po sila, eh. 'Yong mga nilalaman niya po ket no mayroon po 'yong pagtungkol sa pananampalataya, pagrespeto lalo na kapag iba po ang kanilang paniniwala. Mayroon din po yong pananalig. Moral values.
Dominant language is used	Ano, syempre 'yong kung ano 'yong dominant 'yon 'yong ginagamit parang 'yon talaga 'yong tinuturo namin. Tapos 'yong mga ilan lang na ano parang in-explain lang naming sa kanila na. Kumbaga hindi nila maintindihan kasi nga iba yong ano nila, parang in-explain lang naming sa kanila kasi ilan-ilan lang naman.
Encourage learners to speak English	Hinihikayat ko silang mag-English lalo na kapag may kausap kayong foreigner sabi ko sa kanila hindi niyo maintindihan kaya practisin niyo rin mag ano sabi ko sa kanila.
Encourage learners to speak the languages	Kailangan ipaliwanag mo muna sa sa mga bata bakit kailangan nilang—kailangan nilang matutunan 'yon. 'Yon ang pinakamahalaga sa lahat. Kailangan mong sabihin sa kanila ano ba 'yung purpose bakit pa kailangan mong—kailangan nilang ma-expose do'n o kailangan nilang gamitin 'yon, kailangan pa nilang matutunan 'yon eh meron na nga silang ginagamit dito. Kailangang sabihin mo sa kanila ano 'yong importansya. "Kailangan mo 'yan kasi in case mapunta ka sa lugar na hindi hindi na hindi na 'yung mother tongue mo ang nagagamit, kailangan mong may alam kang ibang salita na alam din nila." 'Yon lagi ang sinasabi ko sa kanila.

English and Filipino for feedback	English at Filipino po. Nahihirapan po ako sa Iloko.
English as the most important language	Kasi 'di ba ano, lahat ng rules ngayon na nababasa mo, lahat ng mayro'n sa ano instruction, directions, 'yang mga ganiyan, 'di ba ano puro English na. So, 'pag nakapagbasa na sila ng English, parang marami na silang malalaman sa ano, mundo. Kasi 'yan ang pinaka-importante at pinakamagagamit nila talaga.
English curriculum is easy	Madali din. Halos pareho din sya sa Filipino. Kaya lang uhm late nan ga magstart kaya yong iba hindi na nae-explain ng mabuti kasi habulan na.
English curriculum is hard	Yon nga ang sabi ko kanina, medyo mahirap ang English, hindi naman natin araw-araw na ginagamit sa bahay o kaya dito rin sa school; pagdating natin dito sa school nasa third quarter lang ang Grade 1 na ituturo mo ng English po kaya medyo nahihirapan din sila.
English curriculum is similar to Filipino	Madali din. Halos pareho din sya sa Filipino. Kaya lang uhm late na nga magstart kaya 'yong iba hindi na nae-explain ng mabuti kasi habulan na.
English is hard to teach	Sa English 'yon 'yong mahirap talagang ituro sa kanila kasi lalo na pag tatlong letters na ganyan yong a nagiging a sa Tagalog na nalilitolito sila pero naiintindihan din nila kinalaunan
English most important to read	Para sa akin ano English.
English only policy	Ah, ako din sa klasrum, may ano kami, may time kami na, ganito lang ang salita namin. 'Pag English subject, English lang din ang salita dapat namin – para mahikayat pa sila – hindi lang nasa iisang language.
Enrichment	Ganun pa rin. Remedial, enrichment activities dito. Puwede rin siguro mag home visit ka kasama na rin 'yong nanay, pabasahin na rin 'yong nanay.
Entering Grade 1	Sounds. Sounds and syllables. Mas madali nang magbasa kapag alam mo na 'yong sounds ng letter.

Entering Grade 2	Dapat alam na po nila ‘yong mga sounds ng alphabet. ‘Yong mga at alam na rin nila mga words na basahin at kahit ‘yong simpleng short stories lang kaya’y sentence na kwan lang po.
Entering Grade 3	Kumbaga hindi na lang po sa pagpapantig at tsaka dapat mabilis na po sila magbasa syempre ‘yon na ‘yong huling lower level then magigrade 4 po na po sila. For me po kasi kung pagpapantig palang ‘yong bata ng grade 3 uhm marigatanen nu grade 4 syempre mas mahirap na po ‘yong lesson syempre more on knowledge na po. Hindi na po lang yong pagbi-build na lang po ng pagbabasa.
Evaluation	Sa reading sa strategies andun yong una, halimbawa andun yong i-ano mo yong predicting, predict may outcomes, questions, may evaluation para alam mo na natatarget nila yong ibinato mong reading sa kanila, Sir.
Filipino as the most important language to be read	Uhm siguro Tagalog kasi ‘yon ‘yong kahit saan ka pumunta uhm makikita na Filipino ka, Tagalog ‘yong ano mo makikita mo ‘yong pinag-uusapan ng ibang tao ‘yong ibang lengwahe.
Filipino curriculum and learner adjustment	Nasa kalagitnaan po. Kasi po may uhm may mga bata pong nag-a-adjust po sa wikang Filipino.
Filipino curriculum is easy	Okay lang, SIR. Average. Average, Sir, kasi madali na nilang maintindihan kasi nga pang-araw-araw na nilang ginagamit sa bahay, sa community, sa pakikipag-usap sa ibang tao kaya parang sanay na sila diyan sa Filipino.
Filipino for answering questions	Filipino po. Kasi po pag ang subject namin ay MTB talagang naka-Ilokano po ‘yan. Pero may mga estudyante nga po akong hindi siya marunong mag-Ilokano kaya trinatranslate ko po yan sa Filipino. ‘Yon po.
Filipino for clarifications	Filipino po. Sabi ko nga po may mga batang hindi po nakakaintindi nung Iloko sa akin kasi ay estudyante po akong galing Maynila kaya ang ginagawa ko po, trinatranslate – nagpi-Filipino na lang ako para po pantay po sila, nagkakaintindihan po at naiintindihan ‘yong mga hindi nakakaintindi nung Iloko po.

Filipino for conversations	Uhm syempre magagamit ng mga bata yan 'yang wikang Filipino kapag nasa ibang lugar na sila kasi kapag makikipagusap na sila kunware doon sa Dewey syempre hindi sila magkakaintindihan 'yong ano.
Filipino for explanation	Filipino po. Uhm kasi po 'yong Ilokano pong mga bata ko, nakakaintindi naman po sila ng Filipino kumbaga ginigeneral ko na po yong pag-e-explain sa kanila gamit' yong Filipino.
Filipino for feedback	Filipino din. Kasi mas naiintindihan talaga nila ang Filipino.
Filipino for giving directions	Uhm, Filipino din. Trinatranslate lang kung minsan. Mas naiintindihan nila ang Filipino kaysa sa mother tongue, ah Iloko, at English.
Filipino for learners' answers	Filipino. Mas na-express nila 'yong sagot nila pag Filipino.
Filipino for learners' experiences	Sa sharing naman, mostly, Sir, sa pagsharing dito sa classroom ko, Filipino talaga. Doon siguro sila naeexpress nilang mabuti ang sarili nila kaysa sa Iloko.
Filipino for learners' interaction	Filipino, Sir.
Filipino for learners' questions	Filipino po. Uhm, Filipino kasi mas madali po siyang gamitin sa pagtatanong.
Filipino for sharing experiences	May mga iba, Sir, na gumagamit ng Ilokano talaga tsaka 'yong iba din na Filipino din. Siguro may mga bata siguro na nag-i-Ilokano din sa bahay tsaka yong mga nakakasalamuha din nila araw-araw siguro, at 'yong iba kalimitan kinakausap sila ng mga magulang nila sa Filipino kaya po siguro ganun.
Filipino is easier to teach	Mas madali po. Kasi po 'yon na po yong gamit ko. Kumbaga alam na alam ko na po kung paano siya ituro sa mga bata.
Filipino is mostly used	Kasi po nakasanayan na po natin 'yan at saka pag nanunuod sila wala ng Iloko yan. Maski cartoon nasa Tagalog na siya. At saka pag kinakausap na rin ng guro at kasambahay nila, Filipino na rin, Sir.

Filipino is the most important to read	Hmm, tingin pa rin, sir, Filipino pa din pag ka ano kasi di ba kilala tayo – ang Pilipinas kilala sa paggamit ng Filipino as language natin ano, Sir. Kasi pag sinabi natin na Filipino, dyan tayo nakikilala at kahit na lalabas na tayo sa ibang bansa, diba, Sir, noong ano is hindi naman ang English kasi, di ba halimbawa sa beauty contest paglalabas sila na ano diba ang ginagamit naman nila noon is Filipino? Tapos mayroon lang interpreter. Kaya sa tingin mas importante pa rin na Filipino.
Flash cards	Ang ginagawa ko dyan, Sir, nagrepresent ako sa klase ko ng five words na nakasulat doon sa maliit na parang flash cards, binabasa nila bago magsimula ang lessons. Nakapaskil naman na doon at nakikita nila nang one week ‘yong words na ‘yon.
Fluency	Ah, ‘yung English din kaparehas lang din ng ng Filipino. Kasi ‘yung English, kapag mas kapag sa ano kasi, ‘pag Grade 1/Grade 2, focus sa Filipino. ‘Pag Grade 3 to Grade 6 na, more on English na dapat—English fluenc—fluent na s-sila sa pagbabasa so, mahalaga ‘yung English din.
Focus in teaching reading	Ay tutukan natin sila at kunting tiyaga sa pagtuturo sa kanila para maturuan po sila.
Friendship	In a way po kasi bukod po kasi sa – pag grupo po kasi bukod po doon sa sabay-sabay silang natututo ah yong pagiging palakaibigan, maintegrate din po doon.
Fuller Approach	Gumamagamit po kami ng Marungko, Fuller kapag English na o kaya’y sight words.
Gamified	Strategy ko? Minsan in a form of game ‘yong ginagawa ko pag hindi pa gumana hindi ko na alam kung ano dun. Pero ‘yon usually, Sir. Sa game siya o nagiging strict na ako sa behavior nila. Halimbawa, Sir, yong isang word, in-scramble scramble siya tapos aayusin nila ‘yon. Kung minsan may word akong sasabihin, game na rin ‘yon kasi sila yong maghahanap kung aling word doon ‘yong ginamit.
Getting the learners' attention	Siguro ano, Sir, ang pinaka-importante sa akin ay ‘yong sa attention ng bata dapat makuha ko ‘yong attention ng bata kasi pag hindi mo nakuha ‘yong

	attention ng bata hindi rin magsink in kahit anong ituro mo na pabasa pabasa na 'yan. Pag hindi mo nakuha ang attention niya, wala din.
Graphic organizers	Proseso, process? 'Yon nga po ano dapat may sinusundan tayo. Tulad ng graphic organizer para mas madali po nilang ma-ano mo na tama ba. Malaking tulong 'yon, sir, kasi 'yong graphic organizer nasusundan nila kung tama ba. Una halimbawa 'yong pinaka heading, tatanungin mo na sila, then bababa ka kung ano 'yong naintindihan nila, sino yong characters, then events. Para makompleto po.
Group activities	Mayroon 'yong one to one ako sa mga bata. Mayroon din 'yong ginu-group ko sila. Kumbaga pinagsasama ko na po 'yong mga magagaling then tulungan po sila. Then tinututukan ko po 'yong mga nahihirapan po.
Guide	Strategy yan, Sir? Ay dapat may mga strategy ka sa reading strategies, Sir, na sinusunod mo para madali yang pagtuturo ng reading.
Hesitation in using mother tongue	Mas nag-aalangan silang gamitin ang mother tongue. Mas marami 'yong Filipino kaysa sa Iloko.
Home visitation	Para maabot yan, sir, nagha-house visit ako doon sa mga bata na kailangan talaga at doon ko na nakikita yong sitwasyon nila na ganun. At doon ko na rin napagtatanto na minsan kailangan mo rin na intindihin yong bata na ganun talaga siya at hidi mo basta-basta maipapasok sa sistema ng bata na halimbawa gusto mo na matututo mo 'yong pagbabasa, hindi po kasi 'yon biglaan na proseso. Dahan-dahan po 'yon.
Importance of learners' prior experiences	Ano, Sir, 'pag may dala-dala na sila, Sir, hindi ka na mahihirapan kasi doon ka na ano kung ano 'yong kailangan mong ituro. 'Pag wala pa silang knowledge halimbawa, katulad nga nu'ng pandemic, napagi-iwanan na sila, parang 'yong Grade 3. Parang napag-iwanan na sila. 'Yong mga topic mo sa Grade 3, mula sa pinaka beginning, babalikan.
Individualized	Mayroon 'yong one to one ako sa mga bata. Mayroon din 'yong ginu-group ko sila. Kumbaga pinagsasama ko na po 'yong mga magagaling

	then tulungan po sila. Then tinututukan ko po 'yong mga nahihirapan po.
Language for communication	Malaki, Sir, ah. Kasi nga ito yong wika natin, paraan ng pakikipag-kumunikasyon natin sa mga tao. Kung alam nila 'yong ano, puwede silang kahit sino ang kaharap nila, hindi sila mahihiya. Parang nakaka-ano sila, anong tawag dun? Hindi ko maexpress yong sagot ko.
Language is influential in reading	'Yong impluwensya? Halimbawa sa Iloko, Sir, talagang maimpluwensya 'yang paggamit ng Iloko kasi po bihira na ang gumagamit ng Iloko ngayon kaya medyo nahihirapan ang teacher, nahihirapan din ang mga bata lalong lalo na ang mga nanay, nagchachat sila at nagtetest, tinatanong kung anong ibig sabihin nun sa Tagalog. Maski nga mga magulang natin hindi nila alam ang ibig sabihin nun. Medyo malalim yong pagka Iloko 'yong mga ginagamit natin.
Learner hesitation in using English	Opo, lalo na po kapag English. Una po, dahil nahihiya sila may feeling po sa kanila kapag may nag-i-English.
Learners are left behind in English	Parang napag-aano 'yong mga bata ngayon, napag-iwanan sa English. Para sa akin ah.
Learner connection	Ah, yong connection, Sir? Maganda na yong may connection, Sir. Halimbawa sa review sa story na ibabato mo sa kanila mayroong connection sa life nila mas maganda, nakakarelate sila, Sir. Kaya may connection dapat.
Learners' difficulty in English	'Yong English po medyo nahihirapan po sa panahon ngayon ng English pagdating po ng Grade 2 kasi po nung Grade 1 po ata sila andun pa lang po nag English ata sila ng third quarter na lang po ata. Kaya pagdating po ata nila dito sa Grade 2, nahihirapan na po sila.
Learners literacy levels	Proseso? Sa akin naman po, depende po 'yan sa bata. Ah kasi naklasi-classify naman po may slow ganun po. Halimbawa po 'yong slow po, mga sound 'yong binibigay tapos yong iba po may mga short stories na, 'yong medyo marunong marunong na rin.
Learners not aware of Bolinao	Kung i-a-ano natin, Sir, 'yong mga bata parang medyo hindi na nga sila aware sa ano sa Bolinao

	<p>kung paano magbasa sa Bolinao. Kumbaga napag-iiwanan sila Tagalog na nga 'yong ginagamit nila sa bahay. Kaya kung minsan medyo nahihirapan sa una 'yon kung ginagamit mo 'yong Bolinao, pero at the end naman parang na-ano naman nila.</p>
Learners' readiness	<p>Hindi po siya madali. Dahil 'yong mga bata ko po iba-iba po 'yong level nila, eh. 'Yong readiness nila sa pagbabasa. Kumbaga may nauuna may nahuhuli.</p>
Learners' literacy needs	<p>Syempre nagbibigay ka ng ano ng reading materials. Magbabasa ka din. Ano pa? Videos</p>
Learning Environment	<p>Mayroon po 'yong one time na-observe ko po noong college po ako, during PT days po. May pinuntahan po kami na school tapos isang room po 'yong reading corner niya hindi po siya 'yong nakakatense po na reading corner 'yong reading corner niya para lang pong isang small na kwarto tapos may upuan tas pwedeng tanggalin 'yong tsinelas tas pwede na silang magbasa doon. Ang kagandahan po ng kwartong 'yon ay kahit ka lumingon ay marami kang babasahin. Then 'yong mga babasahin na 'yon hindi po siya mahihirap lang. Ang kagandahan po ng ganun 'yong bata syempre ay susubukan niya pantigin 'yong mga words o 'yong mga nakikita niya.</p>
Learning styles	<p>Kanya-kanya kasing learning styles diba nga, Sir. Minsan itong method na 'to hindi naman magfi-fit do'n sa isa kaya ano din aanohin mo din eh i-evaluate mo din. Pero ang madalas ko kasing ginagamit, Sir, 'yung Marungko approach. 'Yung N tas S tas sa sounds, 'yun.</p>
Less reading materials are good	<p>Ah sa akin, Sir, ano, hindi naman sa maraming babasahin kasi mas mahihilo 'yong bata pag marami na siyang nakikita. Mayroon siguro pero minimal lang. Sa akin lang din 'yon.</p>
Letter to words	<p>Ang ginagawa ko naman uh mayroon kasi 'yong mga powerpoint ko na ano magkakasama na. Mayroon na doon 'yong by letter mayroon na' yong by syllable hanggang mabuo 'yong word. Halimbawa a-b-c tapos ginagawang a-ba-ca tapos ginagawang abaca.</p>

Letters	Ako kasi, umpisa pa lang tinuturan ko na sila ng ano sounds talaga paulit-ulit 'yan. Tas yong mga letters, paulit-ulit din.
Leveled activities	Ah di ano, mga ano ano tawag dito, iba-iba 'yong mga binibigay ko sa kanila na activities. Kasi nga diba iba-iba yong levels nila, nagbibigay ako ng mga babasahin nila na suited doon sa ano nila, level nila sa pagbabasa parang ganun.
Little teacher	Nung face to face, Sir, 'yon nga 'yong ano sila may groupings sila tapos may leader sila. Tas 'yong leader nila nagiging teacher sa group niya ganun. 'Yong isa naman gumagamit din kami minsan ng mga pelikula, videos.
Making connection	Una magpredict ka then mag visualize sa mga reading stories, mga gagamitin natin. May outcomes din tapos you are going to identify tapos iko-connect mo talaga doon sa story para lalo nilang maintindihan. Halimbawa nagbabasa, magstop ka then magtatanong. Halimbawa nagreading ka ng story, magstop ka, then magtatanong ka na doon. Then go on ulit. Tapos stop.
Marungko Approach	Sa pagbabasa po, gumagamit po kami ng Marungko <i>approach</i> o kung minsan pinapadalhan ko po sila ng mga Abakada (<i>booklet</i>). 'Yon po muna 'yong ginagamit po namin sa pagbabasa para hindi po sila mabigla."
Modeling English	Parang ano, Sir, how to motivate them sa wikang Filipino at English, pag sa English po, Sir, nagpapakita po ako ng mga pictures para hindi naman po para alam din po nila yong English ng isang bagay. So ang ginagawa ko po, nagpapakita po ako ng mga pictures, or nagsasalita din po ako sa English para magaya din po nila.
Modeling reading	'Yong gagamit ka ng mga materials tapos ipapakita mo sa kanila yong paraan ng pagbabasa 'yong modeling.
More time allotment	Uhm mas madami po akong time na binibigay sa mga hindi po masyadong makabasa. Then 'yong mga nakakabasa naman po eh hinahayaan ko na lang po silang magtulungan.

Mother Tongue curriculum is easy	Hindi ko sila hinihikayat (laughs) joke lang. Kasi... kami din ang mahihirapan kasi. Pero kung kinakailangan, gagamitin namin 'yon.
Mother Tongue curriculum is hard	Medyo mahirap na pong ituro ang Iloko sa pagbabasa. Dapat alisin na 'yang mother tongue kasi mostly talaga ang mga bata ngayon hindi na sila nag-i-Iloko. Maski pansinin ninyo, Sir. Sa bahay ninyo hindi na sila nag-i-Iloko. Maski dito sa komunidad natin, bibihira na ang nagsasalita na ng Iloko.
Mother Tongue curriculum is important	Hindi naman po. Kasi nakikita ko naman po yong importance nito.
Mother Tongue curriculum is similar to Filipino and English	Kasi 'yung mga laman doon, mga lessons sa Mother Tongue ay lessons din sa English at Filipino.
Mother Tongue is confusing	Ang hirap, Sir (laughs). Ano kasi yun nga hindi nga first language, Sir, tas may confusion na. Yun nga para sa Filipino, Sir. Sa /e/ tas /ə/, /əy/, 'yung mga ganon, Sir. Imbes na basahin nila ng pa-Filipino biglang, "Ay, hindi dapat dap—Pangasinan nga /ə/ dapat," parang ganon, Sir. Nakakalito (laughs).
Mother Tongue is rarely used	Medyo mahirap na pong ituro ang Iloko sa pagbabasa. Dapat alisin na 'yang mother tongue kasi mostly talaga ang mga bata ngayon hindi na sila nag-i-Iloko. Maski pansinin ninyo, Sir. Sa bahay ninyo hindi na sila nag-i-Iloko. Maski dito sa komunidad natin, bibihira na ang nagsasalita na ng Iloko.
Multilingualism	Sa akin sa totoo lang, hindi ko siya pinopokus diyan. Kasi kung nakakabasa sila ng Filipino, madali na rin namamasa nila 'yung Pangasinan. Ang kaibahan nga lang, 'yung /e/ namin, /ə/ ang basa.
No available materials	Medyo mahirap, Sir. Tulad ng sinabi ko medyo mahirap siya kasi wala po tayong available na materials na ginagamit lalo na po sa Bolinao kasi ang kilala nila is Ilokano. So kailangan kami pa ang magprovide na kung hindi pa nadaan sa quality control so hindi po natuturo nang maayos sa bata.
No books	Okay naman po, sir. May mga mayroon na po silang mga books na – sa Grade 2 po kasi, Sir,

	wala kaming books na ano binibigay, so ang ginagamit po namin is kami pa po ang nagproprovide. Hindi po namin nabibigyan ang mga bata nang isa-isa. Ng mga books. Wala po silang books.
No follow up at home	Hindi po. Hindi po lahat. Kasi mayroon ‘yong mga bata na pagdating dito okay naman sila pero pagdating sa bahay wala ng follow-up. So nakakalimutan nila ‘pag dating ulit dito wala na.
No letter v in bolinao	Minsan mahirap kasi more on Tagalog ‘yong curriculum tas ‘yong ano kunwari by letters kasi yon may mga letters na wala sa Bolinao na mayroon sa Tagalog. V parang wala.
No need for translation in Filipino	Mas... mas mabilis, Sir, tapos yun nga dahil first language nila mas madali din ituro kasi mas magkakaintindihan kami nang mas mabilis. Wala ng ano... translation.
Not all will be readers	Base sa aking experience, Sir, hindi lahat natututo. Siguro sa kakulangan ng guide o kaya’y ‘yong ibang bata wala ‘yong attention wala ‘yong ano siguro, Sir, kaya ang kailangan diyan dapat gabayan ng mga magulang natin sila.
Pagong at Tipaklong	Halimbawa po, uhm nilalaman po ng kuwento ganun po, Sir? Halimbawa po si ano po halimbawa po si pagong at saka si tipaklong at marami pa pong iba.
Pagong at Unggoy	‘Pag sa Bolinao po, si “Pagong at si Unggoy”. Kwentong bayan, mga alamat, minsan po mga tula.
Pangasinan accent	Para ano, Sir, kasi para maiwasan din minsan ‘yung... alam mo ‘yung parang may tono- may punto kasi ang bata kapag ka Pangasinan. ‘Yung pag nagta-Tagalog sila, parang nadadala nila ‘yung puntong ‘yon na ‘yung may /əy/, may ganon. Kaya pag nagta-Tagalog sila minsan, eh may kasama na din na “əy” “ngarod”, mga ganon (laughs).
Parents’ involvement	Dapat siguro, Sir, ang gusto ko lang sabihin ganito: Dapat mai-educate din ‘yong mga magulang sa paraan ng pagtuturo ng pagbabasa sa mga bata o mga anak nila. Kasi hindi naman lahta ‘yan dapat na pinapa-ako sa school kasi mga

	<p>ilang oras lang tayo dito, siguro matagal sila na magkakasama ng mga anak nila. 'Yon ang dapat nilang maintindihan. kaya dapat, siguro, may partnership siguro 'yong bond ng parents siguro, Sir, no dapat ma-emphasize 'yan sa mga magulang para maintindihan din nila 'yong mga obligasyon nila sa pag-aaral ng kanilang mga anak. 'Yon lang.</p>
Part of the lesson	<p>Lahat po. Lahat po dapat po ah 'yong pagtuturo po dapat andun na po lahat kasi po from the beginning po para maintindihan po ng mga bata yong ituturo mo po sa kanila</p>
Peer reading	<p>Ay very effective yan, Sir. Kasi in my experience talaga nung marami pa rito, sir, andyan 'yong mga library natin pag tuwing recess mapapansin ko 'yong mga bata pumupunta sila sa reading corner kung ano ano 'yong mga binabasa para bang may peer tutoring na nangyayari. Kung mayroon niyan.</p>
Phonics	<p>Syempre po, kapag alam na nila 'yong tunog ng bawat titik, kahit anong word o salita po 'yan malalaman po nila yong pagkaka-ayos ng mga ano.</p>
Phonics in English	<p>Sa English naman po, may mga rules po kasi sa English di ba po? Kaya ganoon din po. Sounds, basic po then CVC. Inuuna ko po yong mga madadaling mga words.</p>
Phonics in Filipino	<p>Phonics pa din po.</p>
Phonics in Mother Tongue	<p>Phonics po then phonological awareness next po ay oral next po ay vocab compre then fluency. Phonics po. Sound po, eh.</p>
Phrases	<p>Kuwento, mga salita, mga parilala.</p>
Picture reading in English	<p>Average lang. Parang okay lang din po. Kaya lang gaya nga ng sinabi ko kanina, third quarter na kasi kaya nahihirapan sila. Pero mas maganda doon yong pagpapakita ng picture. Picture reading na muna sa kanila pag English.</p>
Positive feedback as encouragement to use language	<p>Lagi ko pong sinasabi, -- pagbibigay po ng positive na feedback. May very good. May clap. Then aside po doon, hinahayan ko po silang magkamali sa English. Kumbaga sabihin lang po nila yong alam nila then i-ko-correct ko na lang po sila.</p>

PowerPoint	Ang ginagawa ko naman uh mayroon kasi yong mga powerpoint ko na ano magkakasama na. Mayroon na doon yong by letter mayroon na yong by syllable hanggang mabuo yong word. Halimbawa a-b-c tapos ginagawang a-ba-ca tapos ginagawang abaca.
Predicting	Una magpredict ka then mag visualize sa mga reading stories, mga gagamitin natin. May outcomes din tapos you are going to identify tapos iko-connect mo talaga doon sa story para lalo nilang maintindihan. Halimbawa nagbabasa, magstop ka then magtatanong. Halimbawa nagreading ka ng story, magstop ka, then magtatanong ka na doon. Then go on ulit. Tapos stop.
Preservation of language	Uhm 'yon nga para mapreserve nga 'yong salita namin kaya naming ginagamit 'yong salitang Bolinao kasi mayroon din kasi trabaho na parang translator nga na sinasabi ko puwede din nilang gamitin 'yon para sa future nila.
Print Rich is effective	Ay very effective yan, Sir. Kasi in my experience talaga nung marami pa rito, Sir, andyan 'yong mga library natin 'pag tuwing recess mapapansin ko 'yong mga bata pumupunta sila sa reading corner kung ano ano 'yong mga binabasa para bang may peer tutoring na nangyayari. Kung mayroon niyan.
Prior experiences	Syempre, Sir, sa bahay na nila 'yan nakukuha diba? O sa labas, o sa Grade 1 o bago maggrade 1. Pag nag Grade 2 na sila, ano na lang parang 'yong namiss nila sa Grade 1, i-ano mo na lang sa Grade 2. Karagdagan na lang para sa kanilang natutunan sa Kinder tsaka sa Grade 1.
Prior experiences deepen knowledge	For me 'yong mga prior knowledge po nila 'yon po 'yong mga tutulong po sa amin para mapalalim ko pa po 'yong kaalaman po nila. Kumbaga dahil may kaalaman na po sila, dadagdagan ko na lang po iyon.
Problem in comprehension	Depende na lang siguro, Sir, kung ano 'yong lesson. Halimbawa, 'yong mga madaling lesson may mga words kasi Sir na pagbabasa ng mga maiiksing mga salita, pagbabasa ng mga kuwento ganun na lang. Ang mahirap na lang sa kanila is

	yong sa comprehension. Doon sila madalas na nahihirapan.
Pronunciation	Kasi 'yung Pangasinan, mas iba 'yung pagbabasa do'n kasi diba, kunware 'yung /e/, /ə/ ang pronunciation. Mas maraming- mas hindi nila kayang basahin nang maayos 'yung Pangasinan. So kailangan mo talagang i-ano 'yung mga letters na iba, 'yung pronunciations sa kanila. Mahirap din.
Push learner to speak English	Ibang wika gaya ng English? Kapag nagtuturo na ako ng English, Sir, talagang ina-ano pinupush talaga sila maski na hirap na hirap na sila talagang yong ang sundin natin sa curriculum natin.
Reading comprehension	Dun sa ano, Sir, dapat may comprehension po talaga para naiintindihan nila, Sir. Maski reading ka nang reading kung hindi nila naiintindihan, kaya dapat i-ano mo yong comprehension talaga, Sir.
Reading corner	Ay very effective yan, Sir. Kasi in my experience talaga nung marami pa rito, Sir, andyan 'yong mga library natin pag tuwing recess mapapansin ko 'yong mga bata pumupunta sila sa reading corner kung ano ano 'yong mga binabasa para bang may peer tutoring na nangyayari. Kung mayroon niyan.
Reading for independence	Okay. Napakaganda ng... uhm napakaganda ng ah purpose natin kung bakit tayo nagtuturong magbasa sa mga bata. Kasi ang mga bata kapag alam nilang magbasa, kahit ako mismo dahil natuto ako magbasa gusto ko rin sila matuto magbasa, kasi once na marunong kang magbasa, ang bata once na naging reader na siya kahit pabayaang mo siya d'yan at naiintindihan n'ya ang binabasa n'ya, kayang kaya n'yang mag-isang mag-aral. Kahit wala ka as a teacher. Guide ka na lang. 'Y-Yon ang ah pakiramdam ko 'pag nagtuturo ako. Napaka... ano... napakasaya kong magturo kasi minsan kasi, gusto ko matuto talaga sila – 'Yung purpose nung bakit mo sila tinuturuang magbasa, specifically kailangang sabihin mo sa mga bata 'yan. "Bakit ba tinuturuan ka ni teacher?", "Bakit ka ba pinipilit ni teacher?", "Bakit kahit umiiyak ka na d'yan kailangan marunong kang magbasa, kailangan mong matutong magbasa?" Kailangang sabihin mo 'yon sa kanila.

Reading in Bolinao is confusing	Pagdating po kasi sa mother tongue hindi naman sa tinatamad 'yong bata, parang nalilito po sila lalo.
Reading in English	Ah sa English naman po 'yong iba kaya nga po iba-iba nga po 'yong kakayahan nila po. 'Yong iba po marunong na silang magbasa ng English 'yong iba hindi pa po. Uh tsaka po, 'pag English na po 'yong mga salita may mga hindi po sila naiintindihan.
Reading in English is hard	<p>Kasi hindi nila alam 'yung salita unless sa Taga—maliban sa Tagalog at saka sa Ilocano—alam kasi nila 'yung mga salitang binabasa nila. Haliwbawa nagbasa sila, “ba-ba-e,” ulitin lang ulit nila 'yon, “ba-ba-e”.</p> <p>Sabihin ko lang, “bilisan mo” “babae” (binilisan) “Oh, ano 'yung nabuo mong salita?” “babae”</p> <p>Alam na agad nilang basahin – natatandaan na nila. Kapag sa English kasi halimbawa, nag nag nagpabasa kanila ng ng ah uhm basic sight words na “see”. See—'pag nagbasa sila ng see “s-e-e”, “se-e” — sasabihin nila se-e kasi hindi naman nila alam 'yung word na see; hindi pa nila 'yon masyadong alam, eh. Unless—maliban sa uhm unlike sa Tagalog na alam na nila kaya kapag nakita na nila 'yan, binasa nila, “Ah, alam ko na 'to, 'babae’.” Hindi katulad nung, “Ma'am, ma'am, madam, madam, 'se-e', se-e 'yan, se-e.” Ganon sila. Kaya mas mahirap magturo ng English kasi 'di nila alam 'yung mga salita.</p>
Reading in Filipino	<p>Ang napansin ko po, Sir, mas madali po nilang maintindihan po yong Filipino po, Sir. Kasi nga po, Sir, yon nga nakagisnang na nila. Maski Iloko pero ang ginagamit nila Filipino. Kagaya ko sa apo ko, Iloko tayo, pero siya nagta-Tagalog di ko alam kung bakit saan niya natutunan hindi ko naman itinuturo. Siguro sa napapanood na nila po.</p>
Reading in Filipino is easy	<p>Kasi 'yun 'yong pinakaginagamit namin. Andami naming subjects na 'yon ang ginagamit kaya kailangan matatas sila do'n, alam nila 'yon, naiintindihan nila 'yon.</p>
Reading in Iloko is confusing	<p>Iloko? Ang hirap ituro ng Iloko. Kasi nga gaya ng sabi ko kanina iba yong way ng pagbabasa ng mga syllables at mga letters, 'yong sounds nila.</p>

	Kumbaga doon sa Filipino na usual na ginagamit natin. Nalilito sila.
Reading in Iloko is easier	Masasabi ko, uhm, minsan sa pagtuturo ng pagbabasa ng Ilokano sa mga bata, parang mas madali nilang nababasa kapag sa Ilokano no. Minsan nagkakalituhan na lang sa spelling. Kasi nga sa Ilokano, sir, letter c yong letter k. Yon lang pero sa pagbabasa, okay naman.
Reading materials	Halimbawa ‘yong mga slow readers, bigyan natin ng activity sila o kaya’y reading materials, o kaya’y puwede nating i-suggest sa mga magulang na gabayan o kaya’y kumuha sila ng tutor sa anak nila para makasunod sila sa susunod na grado nila.
Reading motivation	Opo may possibility po. Kapag ‘yong bata po mismo gusto po niyang bumasa. Kumbaga hindi po siya napipilitan. Kasi po nakaka apekto din po ‘yon. Kapag nakatanim na po sa kanyang isipan syempre po wala po talagang learning pero kung yong bata eager matututo po siya.
Reading strategies	Strategy ‘yan, Sir? Ay dapat may mga strategy ka sa reading strategies, Sir, na sinusunod mo para madali yang pagtuturo ng reading.
Recognition of letters	Yong pinakauna po yong tunog kasi doon po magsisimula lahat, eh. Yong recognition of letters din.
Relating Iloko to English	Ah, dun muna tayo sa mga batang hindi masyado pang marunong magbasa. Dun muna tayo sa— hindi pa sila masyadong nakakaintindi—dun pa lang sila sa words or mga pantig pa lang sila marunong magbasa. Kasi, kap—ang napansin ko lang nung nagtuturo ako ng Ilong Iloko, marami din kasi dong mga... salita na hindi lang siya uhm by pantig. Meron siyang 3 letters, 5 letters, na ma mga salita wherein ‘yung bata, ‘pag nag nagbabasa na kami ng Ilok Iloko, mas uhm matututo na siyang magbasa na parang doon sa sa English. Kasi halimbawa ‘yung word na kal’leb. Sa Tagalog, minsan uhm pantig lang; kapag doon sa Ilocano kasi kal’leb – andon na siya sa English na families ng ang ending—words ending with b, gano’n.

Remedial	K'wan po gagawin ko po ang aking magagawa para pagdating po ng end ng school year eh medyo may maiwan o medyo marunong na rin silang kahit magbasa lang ng word ng mga salita na English, matuto po sila. Bibigyan ko po sila ng mga remedial, ganun po.
Remove Mother Tongue	Medyo mahirap na pong ituro ang Iloko sa pagbabasa. Dapat alisin na 'yang mother tongue kasi mostly talaga ang mga bata ngayon hindi na sila nag-i-loko. Maski pansinin ninyo, Sir. Sa bahay ninyo hindi na sila nag-i-loko. Maski dito sa komunidad natin, bibihira na ang nagsasalita na ng Iloko.
Role of media	Kasi po nakasanayan na po natin 'yan at saka 'pag nanunuod sila wala ng Iloko 'yan. Maski cartoon nasa Tagalog na siya. At saka 'pag kinakausap na rin ng guro at kasambahay nila, Filipino na rin, Sir.
Sharing experiences	Halimbawa po 'yan 'yong halimbawa po doon sa kumbaga experience po na dadalhin nila sa school parang 'yan po, shinesshare po nila 'yang kakayahan sa loob po ng kanilang sa aming classroom po. 'Yon po.
Short stories	Uhm.. tungkol sa ano sa kasi sa ano namin ano bang tawag dun? 'Di ba every grading period namin mayroong "Me" "My Family" and community ganun?
Sight words	Gumamagamit po kami ng Marungko, Fuller kapag English na o kaya'y sight words.
Slow readers	Halimbawa 'yong mga slow readers, bigyan natin ng activity sila o kaya'y reading materials, o kaya'y pwede nating i-suggest sa mga magulang na gabayan o kaya'y kumuha sila ng tutor sa anak nila para makasunod sila sa susunod na grado nila.
Sounds	Dapat alam mo 'yung pa'no 'yung style ng pagtuturo ng pagbabasa sa mga bata. Dapat alam mo po 'yong mga sounds ng mga letters bilang teacher. Kahit pa talaga paulit-ulit 'yan.
Start with the basic	'Pag sa pagbabasa po, Sir, 'yong mga slow learners ko po, Sir, ginagamitan ko po sila ng mga salita na madadali. 'Yong mag-uumpisa kami sa

	<p>basic pero sa mga fast learners ko naman, Sir, ah, anong tawag dito, ginagamitan ko po sila ng medyo mas machallenge po 'yong mind nila sa pagbabasa.</p>
Step by step process	<p>Ah by ano po 'yong kumbaga hindi ka po masyadong mabigat yong pag-atake mo po. Kumbaga eh pinapakita mo na okay lang na andyan ka lang tinutulungan mo sila ganun. Pakiramdam ko naman po ano 100 percent.</p>
Stock knowledge	<p>Mas ano, Sir, mas maganda kung mayroon na silang parang stock knowledge na sinasabi natin. Para po pagpasok po nila dito hindi po tayo babalik sa pinaka basic na talaga especially nasa Grade 2 na po sila at least mas marami na po kaming mga words na mababasa na so maganda pa rin po 'yong mayroong prior knowledge po ang mga bata.</p>
Stopping points	<p>Una magpredict ka then mag visualize sa mga reading stories, mga gagamitin natin. May outcomes din tapos you are going to identify tapos iko-connect mo talaga doon sa story para lalo nilang maintindihan. Halimbawa nagbabasa, magstop ka then magtatanong. Halimbawa nagreading ka ng story, magstop ka, then magtatanong ka na doon. Then go on ulit. Tapos stop.</p>
Syllabication	<p>Kumbaga hindi na lang po sa pagpapantig at tsaka dapat mabilis na po sila magbasa syempre 'yon na 'yong huling lower level then magigrade 4 po na po sila. For me po kasi kung pagpapantig palang 'yong bata ng grade 3 uhm marigatanen nu grade 4 syempre mas mahirap na po 'yong lesson syempre more on knowledge na po. Hindi na po lang yong pagbi-build na lang po ng pagbabasa.</p>
Teacher collaboration	<p>Nagagawan ko po ng paraan minsan po sa paggamit ng dictionary at co-teacher po natin na magaling at bihasa sa Iloko, nagtatanong po ako, Sir, sa kanila.</p>
Teacher proficiency in language	<p>Syempre, Sir, sa pagtuturo ng wika siguro kapag master mo 'yong wika na ituturo mo, mas madali siyang maka-catch up ng mga bata. Whereas pag in-ano ko hindi naman sa ina-ano 'yong English ano 'pag magi-English ka, di ba nga-nga sila</p>

	minsang at kailangan mo pang i-translate sa Filipino or sa Ilokano.
Teaching English must be moved to Q1	'Yon nga ang sabi ko kanina, medyo mahirap ang English, hindi naman natin araw-araw na ginagamit sa bahay o kaya dito rin sa school; pagdating natin dito sa school nasa third quarter lang ang Grade 1 na ituturo mo ng English po kaya medyo nahihirapan din sila.
Teaching Iloko is hard	Iloko? Ang hirap ituro ng Iloko. Kasi nga gaya ng sabi ko kanina iba 'yong way ng pagbabasa ng mga syllables at mga letters, 'yong sounds nila. Kumbaga doon sa Filipino na usual na ginagamit natin. Nalilito sila.
Teaching in English is sort of easy	Average lang. Parang okay lang din po. Kaya lang gaya nga ng sinabi ko kanina, third quarter na kasi kaya nahihirapan sila. Pero mas maganda doon yong pagpapakita ng picture. Picture reading na muna sa kanila pag English.
Teaching reading	Sa realidad po tayo, hindi. Kasi may mga bata po tayo na kasi pag sinabi ko na 100% na matututo sila, sasabihin ko siguro na napakagaling ko na teacher, no? Kasi may instances na kahit napakagaling na ng teacher, may mga depende rin sa environment na kinabibilangan ng bata, eh. Kahit na gaano mo siya kagustong makabasa, kung doon sa bahay nila, walang follow-up tsaka may mga factors din dyan na nakaka-apekto sa bata. Halimbawa yong bata kailangan niya munang magtrabaho bago pumasok, mali-late na yan syempre, Sir. Ang reading namin, Sir, sa akin, ah, bago magsimula ang klase ko. At mag-uwian. Ngayon paano mo pa matuturuan ang bata kung late na siya papasok? Tapos pag uwian naman na nagmamadali na siyang umuwi kasi may gagawin pa siyang kung ano-ano.
Teaching reading is fulfilling	Pakiramdam sa pagtuturo sa mga bata, medyo masaya na mahirap na malungkot kasi yong iba dyan talaga hindi pa sila ready sa pagbabasa.
Teaching reading is the hard	'Yan ang may kahirapan, Sir. Kasi may mga bata kasi na hindi na napa-follow up sa bahay tsaka yong ibang mga cases din yong sa attitude ng bata kung paano siya matututong bumasa. Minsan kasi, ah hindi lang minsan pala, 'yan ang

	pinakamahirap ituro sa mga bata eh 'yong pagbabasa talaga. O 'yon lang.
Teaching reading is tiring	Pakiramdam? As in pakiramdam? Nakaka-stress. Nakakapagod. Ngayong taon na kasi as in pati letter hindi nila alam – sound ng letters.
Teaching reading is unfortunate	Pakiramdam? Medyo malungkot po, Sir. Kasi marami po sa ting mga learners, slow learners po sila. So nakakalungkot isipin na sa panahon natin ngayon is may mga Grade 2 pa po na hindi marunong magbasa.
Technology	Ay wala na, Sir. Kagaya ngayon ta nag-i-interview kayo dito sa classroom ko wala na kayong makikita. Yan na lang mga bulletin boards at saka yong TV kung nagflash ka lang diyan hindi kagaya nun sa sinasabi niyo na printed na materials andyan na naka-display. 'Yong mga bata kung minsan pumupunta na dyan. 'Yon bang parang naglalaro na teacher-teacher-an. Ganun may peer tutoring na nangyayari dyan maski hindi mo sabihin.
Three languages for asking questions	English po, Ilokano tsaka Filipino. Kasi po Filipino given po na alam na nila yon. Kapag ginagamit ko po yong English at Ilokano, kahit pinapakinggan lang po nila malalaman po nila yong katumbas sa ibang wika.
Translanguaging	Kasi ang bata, kahit nagtuturo ka diyan ng lesson mo at ginamit mong language ay hindi nila naiintindihan, walang kuwenta 'yang lesson mo. Kahit mag-assessment ka diyan, hindi nila 'yan naiintindihan; magtanong ka sa kanila hindi nila naintindihan kasi in the first place hindi nila naiintindihan 'yong ginamit mong salita, eh. Kahit daldal ka diyan nang daldal ng English, halimbawa, - try mo sa kanila. Ako – ito na-discover ko. Kapag nagtuturo ako ng English, 'pag nagtuturo ako ng English at wala ng sumasagot sa akin, ibig sabihin no'n wala na silang naiintindihan. Pero 'pag trinanslate ko na 'yan sa Tagalog o kaya'y Ilokano, andami na diyang magre-recite. Naiintindihan na nila.
Translanguaging confuses	Nalilito po sila, Sir. Kasi may mga words silang alam sa Bolinao, may words din silang alam sa Filipino. Minsan nahahalo-halo po nila.

Translanguaging instance	Pag halimbawa pag nagtuturo ka na, Sir, doon sa activity nila, gagabayan mo rin sila, 'yon nga i-explain mo na sa Filipino para mas lalo nila maintindihan. Pag hindi naman nila naintindihan sa Filipino, i-Iloko natin.
Translanguaging is good	Yong pagpapalit-palit po, halimbawa Iloko Tagalog magpapalit po? Mas maganda 'yong ganun, Sir, kasi 'yong mga pupil ko nga po, sir, may Iloko may Tagalog kaya kung minsan talagang pinapagpapalit palit ko, Sir.
Translanguaging is natural	Feeling ko po ano na po 'yon, eh. Hindi mo na namamalayan, eh. Na yon na 'yong nagagamit mo. Okay na po 'pag ganun kasi 'yon na po 'yong nagagamit po, eh. Pero feeling ko po unaware po 'yong mga bata. Unaware na rin po 'yong teacher as long as may sense.
Translanguaging sounds off	Ang pangit pakinggan kasi (laughs). Ang pangit niyang pakinggan kapag pinaghalo. Minsan naghahalo ang Ilocano at saka Tagalog.
Translate to Filipino	Bolinao. Kasi 'yon 'yong naintindihan nila kasi 'yon 'yong Bolinao. Ganun kasi sa bahay nila. Pero minsan may Tagalog nga trinatranslate ko din sa Tagalog kaya medyo matagal 'yong pagtuturo talaga.
Translation	Uhm, Filipino din. Trinatranslate lang kung minsan. Mas naintindihan nila ang Filipino kaysa sa mother tongue, ah Iloko, at English.
Translator	Tapos sa Filipino, syemp—Tagalog. Filipino sa Filipino Language, English 'pag English language na nahahaluan pa minsan ng Tagalog at Ilokano—Tagalog nga, eh. English to Tagalog to Ilokano kasi kailangan ipaintindi mo sa kanila 'yung words na na na pag-aaralan nila sa English. Halimbawa, magtuturo ako sa kanila ng pronouns, ita-Tagalog ko pa 'yon, after ko i-Tagalog 'yon, "Maalala ko, oh pinag-aralan din natin ito sa Ilokano, oh ito 'yung ganito sa Ilokano," 'yan. Kai—kailangan i-translate translate mo pa s'ya.
Use Filipino in teaching	Gagamit na lang po ako ng Filipino kasi po 'yon po lahat sila naintindihan o nauunawaan ang mga sinasabi ko o tinuturo ko sa kanila.

Using learners' prior experience

Ah, 'pag tinuturuan ko silang bumasa, kasi may time na kine-kwentuhan din nila ako based from their experience, nakikinig lang din ako. Tapos 'yung experience nila na 'yon, sina-sample ko na lang din sa parang inaano ko na rin sa pagtuturo sa kanila.

Videos

Maraming babasahin? Ah, pag print-rich? Sa ngayon ah mas maganda kasi na videos na, 'yong napapanood na. Mas madali 'yong retention.

Visualization

Una magpredict ka then mag visualize sa mga reading stories, mga gagamitin natin. May outcomes din tapos you are going to identify tapos iko-connect mo talaga doon sa story para lalo nilang maintindihan. Halimbawa, nagbabasa, magstop ka then magtatanong. Halimbawa nagreading ka ng story, magstop ka, then magtatanong ka na doon. Then go on ulit. Tapos stop.

Appendix P

RQ1: Groupings of Codes and Final Research Themes

Code	Category	Theme
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dominance of English • English as a sign of intelligence • English as bridge • English as top • English deepens knowledge • English for economic and social purposes • English for economic purposes • English for social purposes • Learners' difficulty understanding English • Learning English via exposure • Less allotted time for English • More people use English • More time is needed for English • Speaking English means understanding better 	<p>Dominance of English</p>	<p>English as a highly-valued language</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dominance of Filipino • Filipino as home language • Filipino as medium of instruction • Filipino as mother tongue • Filipino is commonly used • Filipino is home language • Filipino is the bridge in learning • Filipino promoted in the media • Learners understand Filipino better than MT • More vocabulary in Filipino 	<p>Dominance of Filipino</p>	<p>Filipino as preferred language</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulty in differences of language • Language of instruction • Language of the parents • Language utilization determined by majority 	<p>Multilingualism and language varieties</p>	<p>Challenges in MTB-MLE implementation</p>

- Language variation
- Medium of instruction
- Multilingualism
- Stereotypes
- Teaching and learning reading in three languages is confusing

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|--|--------------------|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Language hierarchy in the community • Language hierarchy in the country • Language hierarchy in the workplace • No idea about language hierarchies • No language hierarchy • Using the dominant language in class | Language Hierarchy |
|--|--------------------|

- | | |
|--|--------------------------------------|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Challenges in MTB-MLE • Dominance of a major language • Iloko is less used • Lack of teacher proficiency in mt • Language choice • Language discrimination • Language diversity • Language for exclusion • Language hesitancy • Learner proficiency in mother tongue • Less vocabulary in mother tongue • Mother tongue is least priority • Mother tongue is hard • Mother tongue is not helpful • Mother tongue is not used outside of school • Mother Tongue should be one subject not as medium • Mother tongue should not be taught • MTB-MLE difficulty • MTB-MLE is required • No idea why MTB-MLE is implemented | Resistance towards the mother tongue |
|--|--------------------------------------|

- Stop MTB-MLE implementation
 - Teach mother tongue at home not in school
 - Use mother tongue as an auxiliary language
- | | | |
|--|-------------------|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Code-switch | Code-switching | Use of translations |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Translations | Translations | |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Importance of mother tongue • Language preservation • Languages are equal • Learners understand mother tongue better than other languages • Mother tongue for cultural preservation • Mother tongue should be taught • Use of mother tongue and identity | Language Identity | Language preservation and fostering identity |
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Appendix Q

RQ2: Groupings of Codes and Final Research Themes

Code	Category	Theme
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Big Six of Reading • Big Six of Reading is important in English • Big Six of Reading Is important in Filipino • Big Six of Reading Is important In MT • Fluency • Problem in comprehension • Reading comprehension • Stopping points 	Big Six of Reading	Big Six of Reading with a focus on phonics instruction
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Abakada • Basic to complex • Blending • Claveria Technique • CVC • Fuller Approach • Letter to words • Letters • Marungko approach • Phonics • Phonics in English • Phonics in Filipino • Phonics in Mother Tongue • Pronunciation • Sounds • Start with the basic • Step by step process • Syllabication • Recognition of letters • Learners' readiness • Learners' literacy needs 	Phonics-based instruction	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Importance of learners' prior experiences • Making connection • Prior experiences • Prior experiences deepen knowledge • Sharing experiences • Stopping points 	Utilizing learners' prior experiences	Learners' Experiences

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|--|----------------------|---|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using learners' prior experience | | |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bolinao and Filipino for questions • Bolinao for clarifications • Bolinao for directions • Bolinao language • Bolinao not used at home • Bolinao variation • Mother Tongue curriculum is easy • Mother Tongue curriculum is hard • Mother Tongue curriculum is important • Mother Tongue curriculum is similar to Filipino and English • Mother Tongue is confusing • Mother Tongue is rarely used • Preservation of language • Reading in Iloko is confusing • Reading in Iloko is easier • Remove Mother Tongue • Teaching Iloko is hard | <p>Mother Tongue</p> | <p>Medium of Instruction and/or Learning Area</p> |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Children are taught in Filipino • Developing readers in Filipino • Filipino as the most important language to be read • Filipino curriculum and learner adjustment • Filipino curriculum is easy • Filipino for answering questions • Filipino for clarifications • Filipino for conversations • Filipino for explanation • Filipino for feedback • Filipino for giving directions • Filipino for learners' answers • Filipino for learners' experiences • Filipino for learners' interaction • Filipino for learners' questions | <p>Filipino</p> | |

- Filipino for sharing experiences
- Filipino is easier to teach
- Filipino is mostly used
- Filipino is the most important to read
- Reading in Filipino
- Reading in Filipino is easy
- Use Filipino in teaching

- Encourage learners to speak English
- English As the most important language
- English curriculum is easy
- English curriculum is hard
- English curriculum is similar to Filipino
- English is hard to teach
- English most important to read
- English only policy
- Enrichment
- Learner hesitation in using english
- Learners are left behind in english
- Modeling English
- Modeling reading
- More time allotment
- Push learner to speak English
- Reading in English
- Reading in English is hard
- Teaching English must be moved to Q1
- Teaching in English is sort of easy

- Encourage learners to speak the languages
- English and Filipino for feedback
- Multilingualism
- Three languages for asking questions

- Bridging a language

- No need for translation in Filipino
- Translanguaging
- Translanguaging confuses
- Translanguaging instance
- Translanguaging is good
- Translanguaging is natural
- Translanguaging sounds off
- Translate to Filipino
- Translation
- Translator

- Classroom not print-rich
- Flashcards
- Learning environment
- Less reading materials are good
- No available materials
- No books
- Pagong at Tipaklong
- Pagong at Unggoy
- Print-rich is effective
- Reading corner
- Reading materials
- Remedial
- Short stories
- Sight words

Print-rich
Classrooms

Learning
Environment and
Resources

- PowerPoint
- Role of media
- Technology
- Videos

Technology